

Multiple Choice Patterns in Selfie Numbers - II

Inder J. Taneja¹

Abstract

Numbers represented by their own digits by certain operations are considered as **selfie numbers**. There are many ways of representing **selfie numbers**. It can be represented in digit's order, reverse order of digits, increasing and/or decreasing order of digits, etc. These can be obtained by use of basis operations along with **factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence, Triangular numbers**, etc. Also we can use **binomial coefficients, quadratic (square), cubic functions**, etc. In the past author worked with these functions separately. For more details see the author's works [5]-[37]. Also refer [38], where the the author worked with selfie numbers having together these functions. These work brings patterns in selfie numbers derived from the recent work of author [38]. This is the extension of the first part. The first part is up to numbers 3000 [48]. This part is from 3001 to 10000.

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¹Formerly, Professor of Mathematics, Federal University of Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, SC, Brazil (1978-2012).
E-mail: ijtaneja@gmail.com; Twitter: @IJTANEJA;
Web-sites: <https://numbers-magic.com>; <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com>;

1 Different Types of Number Patterns

In this section, we shall give examples of some different kinds of patterns in numbers studied by author. For details refer [39]-[48]

1.1 Historical Patterns

Below are few examples of **number patterns** in different situations. For details are given in [39].

$16^2 := 256$	$34^2 := 1156$
$166^2 := 27556$	$334^2 := 111556$
$1666^2 := 2775556$	$3334^2 := 11115556$
$16666^2 := 277755556$	$33334^2 := 1111155556$
$166666^2 := 27777555556$	$333334^2 := 111111555556$
$1666666^2 := 2777775555556$	$3333334^2 := 11111115555556$
$16666666^2 := 277777755555556$	$33333334^2 := 1111111155555556$
$43^2 = 1849$	$67^2 := 4489$
$433^2 = 187489$	$667^2 := 444889$
$4333^2 = 18774889$	$6667^2 := 44448889$
$43333^2 = 1877748889$	$66667^2 := 4444488889$
$433333^2 = 187777488889$	$666667^2 := 444444888889$
$4333333^2 = 18777774888889$	$6666667^2 := 44444448888889$
$43333333^2 = 1877777748888889$	$66666667^2 := 4444444488888889$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7623 &:= 11 \times 9 \times 77 & 99 &= 98 + 1 \\
 776223 &:= 111 \times 9 \times 777 & 999 &= 987 + 12 \\
 77762223 &:= 1111 \times 9 \times 7777 & 9999 &= 9876 + 123 \\
 7777622223 &:= 11111 \times 9 \times 77777 & 99999 &= 98765 + 1234 \\
 777776222223 &:= 111111 \times 9 \times 777777 & 999999 &= 987654 + 12345 \\
 77777762222223 &:= 1111111 \times 9 \times 7777777 & 9999999 &= 9876543 + 123456 \\
 7777777622222223 &:= 11111111 \times 9 \times 77777777 & 99999999 &= 98765432 + 1234567 \\
 777777776222222223 &:= 111111111 \times 9 \times 777777777 & 999999999 &= 987654321 + 12345678 \\
 7777777776222222223 &:= 1111111111 \times 9 \times 7777777777 & 9999999999 &= 9876543210 + 123456789
 \end{aligned}$$

1.2 Patterns with Single Letters

Below are examples of number patterns written in terms of single letter "a":

$$\begin{aligned}
 121 &= 11 \times 11 & & := (aa \times aa) / (a \times a) \\
 12321 &= 111 \times 111 & & := (aaa \times aaa) / (a \times a) \\
 1234321 &= 1111 \times 1111 & & := (aaaa \times aaaa) / (a \times a) \\
 123454321 &= 11111 \times 11111 & & := (aaaaa \times aaaaa) / (a \times a) \\
 12345654321 &= 111111 \times 111111 & & := (aaaaaa \times aaaaaa) / (a \times a) \\
 1234567654321 &= 1111111 \times 1111111 & & := (aaaaaaa \times aaaaaaa) / (a \times a) \\
 123456787654321 &= 11111111 \times 11111111 & & := (aaaaaaaa \times aaaaaaaa) / (a \times a) \\
 12345678987654321 &= 111111111 \times 111111111 & & := (aaaaaaaaa \times aaaaaaaaa) / (a \times a).
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1331 &= 11 \times 11 \times 11 & & := aa \times aa \times aa / (a \times a \times a) \\
 13431 &= 11 \times 11 \times 111 & & := aa \times aa \times aaa / (a \times a \times a) \\
 134431 &= 11 \times 11 \times 1111 & & := aa \times aa \times aaaa / (a \times a \times a) \\
 1344431 &= 11 \times 11 \times 11111 & & := aa \times aa \times aaaaa / (a \times a \times a) \\
 13444431 &= 11 \times 11 \times 111111 & & := aa \times aa \times aaaaaa / (a \times a \times a) \\
 134444431 &= 11 \times 11 \times 1111111 & & := aa \times aa \times aaaaaaa / (a \times a \times a) \\
 1344444431 &= 11 \times 11 \times 11111111 & & := aa \times aa \times aaaaaaaa / (a \times a \times a) \\
 13444444431 &= 11 \times 11 \times 111111111 & & := aa \times aa \times aaaaaaaaa / (a \times a \times a).
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1001 &= 13 \times 77 & := aa \times (aaaa - aaa + a) / (aa \times a) \\
 10101 &= 13 \times 777 & := aaa \times (aaaa - aaa + a) / (aa \times a) \\
 101101 &= 13 \times 7777 & := aaaa \times (aaaa - aaa + a) / (aa \times a) \\
 1011101 &= 13 \times 77777 & := aaaaa \times (aaaa - aaa + a) / (aa \times a) \\
 10111101 &= 13 \times 777777 & := aaaaaa \times (aaaa - aaa + a) / (aa \times a) \\
 101111101 &= 13 \times 7777777 & := aaaaaaa \times (aaaa - aaa + a) / (aa \times a) \\
 1011111101 &= 13 \times 77777777 & := aaaaaaaaa \times (aaaa - aaa + a) / (aa \times a) \\
 10111111101 &= 13 \times 777777777 & := aaaaaaaaaa \times (aaaa - aaa + a) / (aa \times a).
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 83 &:= \frac{(aa - a - a) \times (aa - a - a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 983 &:= \frac{(aa - a - a) \times (aaa - a - a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 9983 &:= \frac{(aa - a - a) \times (aaaa - a - a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 99983 &:= \frac{(aa - a - a) \times (aaaaa - a - a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 123 &:= \frac{aaa + aa + a}{a} & 276 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a} \\
 1123 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa + a}{a} & 2576 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times (aaa + a)}{a \times a} \\
 11123 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa + a}{a} & 25576 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times (aaaa + a)}{a \times a} \\
 111123 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aa + a}{a} & 255576 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times (aaaaa + a)}{a \times a}
 \end{aligned}$$

The letter "a" appearing in above three examples is such that $a \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9\}$, i.e., for any value of "a" from 1 to 9, the results remains the same. Also,

$$aaa = 10^2 \times a + 10 \times a + a, \quad a \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9\} \text{ etc.}$$

A general study of numbers in terms of letter "a" is given in [39, 44].

1.3 Patterns in Pair of Amicable Numbers

$$\begin{aligned}
 264 &:= 5 \times 8 + 28 \times 8 & \Leftrightarrow & 528 := 2 \times 8 + 64 \times 8 \\
 2664 &:= 5 \times 8 + 328 \times 8 & \Leftrightarrow & 5328 := 2 \times 8 + 664 \times 8 \\
 26664 &:= 5 \times 8 + 3328 \times 8 & \Leftrightarrow & 53328 := 2 \times 8 + 6664 \times 8 \\
 266664 &:= 5 \times 8 + 33328 \times 8 & \Leftrightarrow & 533328 := 2 \times 8 + 66664 \times 8 \\
 2666664 &:= 5 \times 8 + 333328 \times 8 & \Leftrightarrow & 5333328 := 2 \times 8 + 666664 \times 8 \\
 \\
 1650 &:= 325 \times 5 + 5 \times 5 & \Leftrightarrow & 3255 := 1 \times 5 + 650 \times 5 \\
 16650 &:= 3325 \times 5 + 5 \times 5 & \Leftrightarrow & 33255 := 1 \times 5 + 6650 \times 5 \\
 166650 &:= 33325 \times 5 + 5 \times 5 & \Leftrightarrow & 333255 := 1 \times 5 + 66650 \times 5 \\
 1666650 &:= 333325 \times 5 + 5 \times 5 & \Leftrightarrow & 3333255 := 1 \times 5 + 666650 \times 5 \\
 \\
 3544 &:= 437 \times 8 + 6 \times 8 & \Leftrightarrow & 4376 := 3 \times 8 + 544 \times 8 \\
 35544 &:= 4437 \times 8 + 6 \times 8 & \Leftrightarrow & 44376 := 3 \times 8 + 5544 \times 8 \\
 355544 &:= 44437 \times 8 + 6 \times 8 & \Leftrightarrow & 444376 := 3 \times 8 + 55544 \times 8 \\
 3555544 &:= 444437 \times 8 + 6 \times 8 & \Leftrightarrow & 4444376 := 3 \times 8 + 555544 \times 8
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [41]

1.4 Patterns in Selfie Fractions

Below are few examples of patterns in **selfie fractions**. For details refer author's work [42, 48]

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 \frac{42}{231} := \frac{4+2}{2+31} & \frac{108}{1188} := \frac{1+08}{11+88} & \frac{266}{627} := \frac{2+6+6}{6+27} \\
 \frac{42}{2331} := \frac{4+2}{2+331} & \frac{108}{11988} := \frac{1+08}{11+988} & \frac{266}{6327} := \frac{2+6+6}{6+327} \\
 \frac{42}{23331} := \frac{4+2}{2+3331} & \frac{108}{119988} := \frac{1+08}{11+9988} & \frac{266}{63327} := \frac{2+6+6}{6+3327} \\
 \frac{42}{233331} := \frac{4+2}{2+33331} & \frac{108}{1199988} := \frac{1+08}{11+99988} & \frac{266}{633327} := \frac{2+6+6}{6+33327}
 \end{array}$$

1.5 Pythagorean Triples Patterns

$$\begin{aligned}
 124^2 + 3843^2 &:= 3845^2 \\
 1240^2 + 384399^2 &:= 384401^2 \\
 12400^2 + 38439999^2 &:= 38440001^2 \\
 124000^2 + 3843999999^2 &:= 3844000001^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 8844^2 + 133^2 & := 8845^2 \\
 888444^2 + 1333^2 & := 888445^2 \\
 88884444^2 + 13333^2 & := 88884445^2 \\
 8888844444^2 + 133333^2 & := 8888844445^2 \\
 39600^2 + 398^2 & := 39602^2 \\
 3996000^2 + 3998^2 & := 3996002^2 \\
 399960000^2 + 39998^2 & := 399960002^2 \\
 39999600000^2 + 399998^2 & := 39999600002^2
 \end{array}$$

For more studies refer author's work [45].

1.6 Pandigital-Type Pythagorean Triples Patterns

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 096^2 + 40^2 & := 104^2 \\
 12\ 096^2 + 440^2 & := 12\ 104^2 \\
 1232\ 096^2 + 4440^2 & := 1232\ 104^2 \\
 123432\ 096^2 + 44440^2 & := 123432\ 104^2 \\
 12345432\ 096^2 + 444440^2 & := 12345432\ 104^2 \\
 1234565432\ 096^2 + 4444440^2 & := 1234565432\ 104^2 \\
 123456765432\ 096^2 + 44444440^2 & := 123456765432\ 104^2 \\
 12345678765432\ 096^2 + 444444440^2 & := 12345678765432\ 104^2 \\
 1234567898765432\ 096^2 + 4444444440^2 & := 1234567898765432\ 104^2 \\
 \\
 091^2 + 60^2 & := 109^2 \\
 12\ 091^2 + 660^2 & := 12\ 109^2 \\
 1232\ 091^2 + 6660^2 & := 1232\ 109^2 \\
 123432\ 091^2 + 66660^2 & := 123432\ 109^2 \\
 12345432\ 091^2 + 666660^2 & := 12345432\ 109^2 \\
 1234565432\ 091^2 + 6666660^2 & := 1234565432\ 109^2 \\
 123456765432\ 091^2 + 66666660^2 & := 123456765432\ 109^2 \\
 12345678765432\ 091^2 + 666666660^2 & := 12345678765432\ 109^2 \\
 1234567898765432\ 091^2 + 6666666660^2 & := 1234567898765432\ 109^2
 \end{array}$$

For more details refer author's work [46]

2 Selfie Numbers and Patterns

Recently, the author studied different ways of expressing numbers in such a way that both sides are with same digits. One side is with number, and another side is an expression formed by same digits with some operations. These types of numbers we call **selfie numbers**. Some times they are called as **wild narcissistic numbers**. These numbers are represented by their own digits by use of certain operations. Subsections below give different ways of writing **selfie numbers**. See below some examples:

$$\begin{aligned}
 936 &:= (\sqrt{9})!^3 + 6! &= 6! + (3!)^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 1296 &:= \sqrt{(1+2)!^9/6} &= 6^{(\sqrt{9}+2-1)} \\
 2896 &:= 2 \times (8 + (\sqrt{9})!! + 6!) &= (6! + (\sqrt{9})!! + 8) \times 2 \\
 331779 &:= 3 + (31 - 7)^{\sqrt{7+9}} &= \sqrt{9} + (7 \times 7 - 1)^3 \times 3 \\
 342995 &:= (3^4 - 2 - 9)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5 &= -5 + (-9 + 9^2 - \sqrt{4})^3 \\
 759375 &:= (-7 + 59 - 37)^5 &= (5 + 7 + 3)^{\sqrt{9}-5+7} \\
 759381 &:= 7 + (5 \times \sqrt{9})^{-3+8} - 1 &= -1 + (8 \times 3 - 9)^5 + 7
 \end{aligned}$$

More studies on **selfie numbers** can be seen in author's work [5]-[37]. In [40], the author worked with **patterns in selfie numbers**, but for four digits and more. See below two examples.

$$\begin{aligned}
 1285 &:= (1 + 2^8) \times 5 & 3645 &:= 3^{\sqrt{\sqrt{6^4}}} \times 5 & 72688 &:= 7 \times (2 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times 8 \\
 12850 &:= (1 + 2^8) \times 50 & 36450 &:= 3^{\sqrt{\sqrt{6^4}}} \times 50 & 726880 &:= 7 \times (2 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times 80 \\
 128500 &:= (1 + 2^8) \times 500 & 364500 &:= 3^{\sqrt{\sqrt{6^4}}} \times 500 & 7268800 &:= 7 \times (2 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times 800
 \end{aligned}$$

The above patterns are only with **square-root**. For more examples of similar kind refer author's work [40].

The subsections below give **patterns in selfie numbers**. The total work is up to 3000 numbers. The sequential functions such as, **quadratic (square), cubic, triangular, Fibonacci**, etc. are also considered.

3 Multiple Choice Patterns in Selfie Numbers

The examples below are referring letters **Q, C, T** and **F** respectively sequential functions as **square, cubic, triangular** and **Fibonacci**. Still **factorial** and **square-root** are also used. This is the extension of the first part. The first part is up to numbers 3000 [48]. This part is from 3001 to 10000.

1.

$$\begin{aligned}3003 &:= (C(Q(3) + 0!) + 0!) \times 3 \\30030 &:= (C(Q(3) + 0!) + 0!) \times 30 \\300300 &:= (C(Q(3) + 0!) + 0!) \times 300 \\3003000 &:= (C(Q(3) + 0!) + 0!) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

2.

$$\begin{aligned}3008 &:= (T(C(3)) - (0! + 0!)) \times 8 \\30080 &:= (T(C(3)) - (0! + 0!)) \times 80 \\300800 &:= (T(C(3)) - (0! + 0!)) \times 800 \\3008000 &:= (T(C(3)) - (0! + 0!)) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

3.

$$\begin{aligned}3015 &:= (C(3) + Q(Q(0! + 1!))) \times 5 \\30150 &:= (C(3) + Q(Q(0! + 1!))) \times 50 \\301500 &:= (C(3) + Q(Q(0! + 1!))) \times 500 \\3015000 &:= (C(3) + Q(Q(0! + 1!))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

4.

$$\begin{aligned}3017 &:= (-Q(Q(3)) + C(C(0! + 1))) \times 7 \\30170 &:= (-Q(Q(3)) + C(C(0! + 1))) \times 70 \\301700 &:= (-Q(Q(3)) + C(C(0! + 1))) \times 700 \\3017000 &:= (-Q(Q(3)) + C(C(0! + 1))) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

5.

$$\begin{aligned}3024 &:= (C(3) + C(0! + C(2))) \times 4 \\30240 &:= (C(3) + C(0! + C(2))) \times 40 \\302400 &:= (C(3) + C(0! + C(2))) \times 400 \\3024000 &:= (C(3) + C(0! + C(2))) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

6.

$$\begin{aligned}3036 &:= (C(C(3 - 0!)) - 3!) \times 6 \\30360 &:= (C(C(3 - 0!)) - 3!) \times 60 \\303600 &:= (C(C(3 - 0!)) - 3!) \times 600 \\3036000 &:= (C(C(3 - 0!)) - 3!) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

7.

$$\begin{aligned}3036 &:= T(T(T(3)) + 0!) \times F(3) \times 6 \\30360 &:= T(T(T(3)) + 0!) \times F(3) \times 60 \\303600 &:= T(T(T(3)) + 0!) \times F(3) \times 600 \\3036000 &:= T(T(T(3)) + 0!) \times F(3) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

8.

$$\begin{aligned}3042 &:= Q(Q(3!) + 0! + \sqrt{4}) \times 2 \\30420 &:= Q(Q(3!) + 0! + \sqrt{4}) \times 20 \\304200 &:= Q(Q(3!) + 0! + \sqrt{4}) \times 200 \\3042000 &:= Q(Q(3!) + 0! + \sqrt{4}) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

9.

$$\begin{aligned}3042 &:= Q(Q(3!) - 0! + 4) \times 2 \\30420 &:= Q(Q(3!) - 0! + 4) \times 20 \\304200 &:= Q(Q(3!) - 0! + 4) \times 200 \\3042000 &:= Q(Q(3!) - 0! + 4) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

10.

$$\begin{aligned}3045 &:= (C(Q(3)) - (0! + 4!)) \times 5 \\30450 &:= (C(Q(3)) - (0! + 4!)) \times 50 \\304500 &:= (C(Q(3)) - (0! + 4!)) \times 500 \\3045000 &:= (C(Q(3)) - (0! + 4!)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

11.

$$\begin{aligned}3045 &:= (F(Q(3)) - 0! + Q(4!)) \times 5 \\30450 &:= (F(Q(3)) - 0! + Q(4!)) \times 50 \\304500 &:= (F(Q(3)) - 0! + Q(4!)) \times 500 \\3045000 &:= (F(Q(3)) - 0! + Q(4!)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

12.

$$\begin{aligned}3048 &:= (Q(Q(3)) + T(4!)) \times 8 \\30480 &:= (Q(Q(3)) + T(4!)) \times 80 \\304800 &:= (Q(Q(3)) + T(4!)) \times 800 \\3048000 &:= (Q(Q(3)) + T(4!)) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

13.

$$\begin{aligned}3064 &:= (C(Q(3)) + 0! + Q(6)) \times 4 \\30640 &:= (C(Q(3)) + 0! + Q(6)) \times 40 \\306400 &:= (C(Q(3)) + 0! + Q(6)) \times 400 \\3064000 &:= (C(Q(3)) + 0! + Q(6)) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

14.

$$\begin{aligned}3064 &:= (T(Q(3)) + 0! + 6!) \times 4 \\30640 &:= (T(Q(3)) + 0! + 6!) \times 40 \\306400 &:= (T(Q(3)) + 0! + 6!) \times 400 \\3064000 &:= (T(Q(3)) + 0! + 6!) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

15.

$$\begin{aligned}3065 &:= (3 + F(T(-0! + 6))) \times 5 \\30650 &:= (3 + F(T(-0! + 6))) \times 50 \\306500 &:= (3 + F(T(-0! + 6))) \times 500 \\3065000 &:= (3 + F(T(-0! + 6))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

16.

$$\begin{aligned}3069 &:= (C(3! - 0!) + C(6)) \times 9 \\30690 &:= (C(3! - 0!) + C(6)) \times 90 \\306900 &:= (C(3! - 0!) + C(6)) \times 900 \\3069000 &:= (C(3! - 0!) + C(6)) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

17.

$$\begin{aligned}3069 &:= (C(T(3) - 0!) + C(6)) \times 9 \\30690 &:= (C(T(3) - 0!) + C(6)) \times 90 \\306900 &:= (C(T(3) - 0!) + C(6)) \times 900 \\3069000 &:= (C(T(3) - 0!) + C(6)) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

18.

$$\begin{aligned}3069 &:= (-F(3) + C(0! + 6)) \times 9 \\30690 &:= (-F(3) + C(0! + 6)) \times 90 \\306900 &:= (-F(3) + C(0! + 6)) \times 900 \\3069000 &:= (-F(3) + C(0! + 6)) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

19.

$$\begin{aligned}3087 &:= F(F(3!)) \times F(08) \times 7 \\30870 &:= F(F(3!)) \times F(08) \times 70 \\308700 &:= F(F(3!)) \times F(08) \times 700 \\3087000 &:= F(F(3!)) \times F(08) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

20.

$$\begin{aligned}3087 &:= T(T(3)) \times F(08) \times 7 \\30870 &:= T(T(3)) \times F(08) \times 70 \\308700 &:= T(T(3)) \times F(08) \times 700 \\3087000 &:= T(T(3)) \times F(08) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

21.

$$\begin{aligned} 3087 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(\sqrt{T(08)}) \times 7 \\ 30870 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(\sqrt{T(08)}) \times 70 \\ 308700 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(\sqrt{T(08)}) \times 700 \\ 3087000 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(\sqrt{T(08)}) \times 7000 \end{aligned}$$

22.

$$\begin{aligned} 3088 &:= (T(C(3)) + 8) \times 8 \\ 30880 &:= (T(C(3)) + 8) \times 80 \\ 308800 &:= (T(C(3)) + 8) \times 800 \\ 3088000 &:= (T(C(3)) + 8) \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

23.

$$\begin{aligned} 3092 &:= (T(3) + T(T(0! + 9))) \times 2 \\ 30920 &:= (T(3) + T(T(0! + 9))) \times 20 \\ 309200 &:= (T(3) + T(T(0! + 9))) \times 200 \\ 3092000 &:= (T(3) + T(T(0! + 9))) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

24.

$$\begin{aligned} 3122 &:= (-Q(3!) + F(1 + Q(Q(2)))) \times 2 \\ 31220 &:= (-Q(3!) + F(1 + Q(Q(2)))) \times 20 \\ 312200 &:= (-Q(3!) + F(1 + Q(Q(2)))) \times 200 \\ 3122000 &:= (-Q(3!) + F(1 + Q(Q(2)))) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

25.

$$\begin{aligned} 3122 &:= (T(F(T(3 + 1))) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 2 \\ 31220 &:= (T(F(T(3 + 1))) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 20 \\ 312200 &:= (T(F(T(3 + 1))) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 200 \\ 3122000 &:= (T(F(T(3 + 1))) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

26.

$$\begin{aligned} 3122 &:= (T(T(T(3 + 1))) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 2 \\ 31220 &:= (T(T(T(3 + 1))) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 20 \\ 312200 &:= (T(T(T(3 + 1))) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 200 \\ 3122000 &:= (T(T(T(3 + 1))) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

27.

$$\begin{aligned} 3126 &:= (C(F(3)) + 1 + C(C(2))) \times 6 \\ 31260 &:= (C(F(3)) + 1 + C(C(2))) \times 60 \\ 312600 &:= (C(F(3)) + 1 + C(C(2))) \times 600 \\ 3126000 &:= (C(F(3)) + 1 + C(C(2))) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

28.

$$\begin{aligned} 3126 &:= (-F(3!) + Q(-1 + Q(2)!)) \times 6 \\ 31260 &:= (-F(3!) + Q(-1 + Q(2)!)) \times 60 \\ 312600 &:= (-F(3!) + Q(-1 + Q(2)!)) \times 600 \\ 3126000 &:= (-F(3!) + Q(-1 + Q(2)!)) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

29.

$$\begin{aligned} 3126 &:= (Q(3) + C(C(2))) \times 6 \\ 31260 &:= (Q(3) + C(C(2))) \times 60 \\ 312600 &:= (Q(3) + C(C(2))) \times 600 \\ 3126000 &:= (Q(3) + C(C(2))) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

30.

$$\begin{aligned} 3144 &:= (T(3)! + T(1 + T(4))) \times 4 \\ 31440 &:= (T(3)! + T(1 + T(4))) \times 40 \\ 314400 &:= (T(3)! + T(1 + T(4))) \times 400 \\ 3144000 &:= (T(3)! + T(1 + T(4))) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

31.

$$\begin{aligned}3145 &:= (Q(F(3)) + Q(Q(1 + 4))) \times 5 \\31450 &:= (Q(F(3)) + Q(Q(1 + 4))) \times 50 \\314500 &:= (Q(F(3)) + Q(Q(1 + 4))) \times 500 \\3145000 &:= (Q(F(3)) + Q(Q(1 + 4))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

32.

$$\begin{aligned}3150 &:= F(C(F(3))) \times 150 \\31500 &:= F(C(F(3))) \times 1500 \\315000 &:= F(C(F(3))) \times 15000 \\3150000 &:= F(C(F(3))) \times 150000\end{aligned}$$

33.

$$\begin{aligned}3150 &:= F(F(3!)) \times 150 \\31500 &:= F(F(3!)) \times 1500 \\315000 &:= F(F(3!)) \times 15000 \\3150000 &:= F(F(3!)) \times 150000\end{aligned}$$

34.

$$\begin{aligned}3150 &:= T(T(3)) \times 150 \\31500 &:= T(T(3)) \times 1500 \\315000 &:= T(T(3)) \times 15000 \\3150000 &:= T(T(3)) \times 150000\end{aligned}$$

35.

$$\begin{aligned}3155 &:= (3!! - F(\sqrt{1 + 5!})) \times 5 \\31550 &:= (3!! - F(\sqrt{1 + 5!})) \times 50 \\315500 &:= (3!! - F(\sqrt{1 + 5!})) \times 500 \\3155000 &:= (3!! - F(\sqrt{1 + 5!})) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

36.

$$\begin{aligned}3155 &:= (3! + Q(Q(5))) \times 5 \\31550 &:= (3! + Q(Q(5))) \times 50 \\315500 &:= (3! + Q(Q(5))) \times 500 \\3155000 &:= (3! + Q(Q(5))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

37.

$$\begin{aligned}3155 &:= (C(C(F(3))) - 1 + 5!) \times 5 \\31550 &:= (C(C(F(3))) - 1 + 5!) \times 50 \\315500 &:= (C(C(F(3))) - 1 + 5!) \times 500 \\3155000 &:= (C(C(F(3))) - 1 + 5!) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

38.

$$\begin{aligned}3155 &:= (F(F(3!)) + F(15)) \times 5 \\31550 &:= (F(F(3!)) + F(15)) \times 50 \\315500 &:= (F(F(3!)) + F(15)) \times 500 \\3155000 &:= (F(F(3!)) + F(15)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

39.

$$\begin{aligned}3155 &:= (T(3) + Q(Q(5))) \times 5 \\31550 &:= (T(3) + Q(Q(5))) \times 50 \\315500 &:= (T(3) + Q(Q(5))) \times 500 \\3155000 &:= (T(3) + Q(Q(5))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

40.

$$\begin{aligned}3155 &:= (T(T(3)) + F(15)) \times 5 \\31550 &:= (T(T(3)) + F(15)) \times 50 \\315500 &:= (T(T(3)) + F(15)) \times 500 \\3155000 &:= (T(T(3)) + F(15)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

41.

$$3159 := T(31 - 5) \times 9$$

$$31590 := T(31 - 5) \times 90$$

$$315900 := T(31 - 5) \times 900$$

$$3159000 := T(31 - 5) \times 9000$$

42.

$$3165 := (3 + T(Q(6) - 1)) \times 5$$

$$31650 := (3 + T(Q(6) - 1)) \times 50$$

$$316500 := (3 + T(Q(6) - 1)) \times 500$$

$$3165000 := (3 + T(Q(6) - 1)) \times 5000$$

43.

$$3185 := (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(-1 + 8))) \times 5$$

$$31850 := (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(-1 + 8))) \times 50$$

$$318500 := (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(-1 + 8))) \times 500$$

$$3185000 := (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(-1 + 8))) \times 5000$$

44.

$$3186 := (T((3 + 1)!) + T(F(8))) \times 6$$

$$31860 := (T((3 + 1)!) + T(F(8))) \times 60$$

$$318600 := (T((3 + 1)!) + T(F(8))) \times 600$$

$$3186000 := (T((3 + 1)!) + T(F(8))) \times 6000$$

45.

$$3186 := (T((3 + 1)!) + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times 6$$

$$31860 := (T((3 + 1)!) + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times 60$$

$$318600 := (T((3 + 1)!) + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times 600$$

$$3186000 := (T((3 + 1)!) + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times 6000$$

46.

$$3195 := (T(T(F(T(3))) - 1) + 9) \times 5$$

$$31950 := (T(T(F(T(3))) - 1) + 9) \times 50$$

$$319500 := (T(T(F(T(3))) - 1) + 9) \times 500$$

$$3195000 := (T(T(F(T(3))) - 1) + 9) \times 5000$$

47.

$$3202 := (Q(Q(3!) + Q(2)) + 0!) \times 2$$

$$32020 := (Q(Q(3!) + Q(2)) + 0!) \times 20$$

$$320200 := (Q(Q(3!) + Q(2)) + 0!) \times 200$$

$$3202000 := (Q(Q(3!) + Q(2)) + 0!) \times 2000$$

48.

$$3204 := (3!! + Q(0! + C(2))) \times 4$$

$$32040 := (3!! + Q(0! + C(2))) \times 40$$

$$320400 := (3!! + Q(0! + C(2))) \times 400$$

$$3204000 := (3!! + Q(0! + C(2))) \times 4000$$

49.

$$3204 := (3!! + Q(Q(2 + 0!))) \times 4$$

$$32040 := (3!! + Q(Q(2 + 0!))) \times 40$$

$$320400 := (3!! + Q(Q(2 + 0!))) \times 400$$

$$3204000 := (3!! + Q(Q(2 + 0!))) \times 4000$$

50.

$$3208 := (Q(Q(3!) - Q(Q(2))) + 0!) \times 8$$

$$32080 := (Q(Q(3!) - Q(Q(2))) + 0!) \times 80$$

$$320800 := (Q(Q(3!) - Q(Q(2))) + 0!) \times 800$$

$$3208000 := (Q(Q(3!) - Q(Q(2))) + 0!) \times 8000$$

51.

$$3210 := (T(T(3)) + T(Q(2)!)) \times 10$$

$$32100 := (T(T(3)) + T(Q(2)!)) \times 100$$

$$321000 := (T(T(3)) + T(Q(2)!)) \times 1000$$

$$3210000 := (T(T(3)) + T(Q(2)!)) \times 10000$$

52.

$$3224 := (Q(Q(3)) \times T(Q(2)) - Q(2)) \times 4$$

$$32240 := (Q(Q(3)) \times T(Q(2)) - Q(2)) \times 40$$

$$322400 := (Q(Q(3)) \times T(Q(2)) - Q(2)) \times 400$$

$$3224000 := (Q(Q(3)) \times T(Q(2)) - Q(2)) \times 4000$$

53.

$$3240 := C(3) \times T(2) \times 40$$

$$32400 := C(3) \times T(2) \times 400$$

$$324000 := C(3) \times T(2) \times 4000$$

$$3240000 := C(3) \times T(2) \times 40000$$

54.

$$3240 := Q(3^2) \times 40$$

$$32400 := Q(3^2) \times 400$$

$$324000 := Q(3^2) \times 4000$$

$$3240000 := Q(3^2) \times 40000$$

55.

$$3240 := \sqrt{3^{C(2)}} \times 40$$

$$32400 := \sqrt{3^{C(2)}} \times 400$$

$$324000 := \sqrt{3^{C(2)}} \times 4000$$

$$3240000 := \sqrt{3^{C(2)}} \times 40000$$

56.

$$3242 := (C(Q(2) + Q(3)) - Q(4!)) \times 2$$

$$32420 := (C(Q(2) + Q(3)) - Q(4!)) \times 20$$

$$324200 := (C(Q(2) + Q(3)) - Q(4!)) \times 200$$

$$3242000 := (C(Q(2) + Q(3)) - Q(4!)) \times 2000$$

57.

$$3242 := (T(T(3)) + Q(Q(2) \times T(4))) \times 2$$

$$32420 := (T(T(3)) + Q(Q(2) \times T(4))) \times 20$$

$$324200 := (T(T(3)) + Q(Q(2) \times T(4))) \times 200$$

$$3242000 := (T(T(3)) + Q(Q(2) \times T(4))) \times 2000$$

58.

$$3244 := (Q(Q(2) + 4!) + C(3)) \times 4$$

$$32440 := (Q(Q(2) + 4!) + C(3)) \times 40$$

$$324400 := (Q(Q(2) + 4!) + C(3)) \times 400$$

$$3244000 := (Q(Q(2) + 4!) + C(3)) \times 4000$$

59.

$$3245 := (Q(Q(3 + 2)) + 4!) \times 5$$

$$32450 := (Q(Q(3 + 2)) + 4!) \times 50$$

$$324500 := (Q(Q(3 + 2)) + 4!) \times 500$$

$$3245000 := (Q(Q(3 + 2)) + 4!) \times 5000$$

60.

$$3246 := (C(3) + C(C(2)) + \sqrt{4}) \times 6$$

$$32460 := (C(3) + C(C(2)) + \sqrt{4}) \times 60$$

$$324600 := (C(3) + C(C(2)) + \sqrt{4}) \times 600$$

$$3246000 := (C(3) + C(C(2)) + \sqrt{4}) \times 6000$$

61.

$$3246 := (F(3) + C(C(2)) + C(F(4))) \times 6$$

$$32460 := (F(3) + C(C(2)) + C(F(4))) \times 60$$

$$324600 := (F(3) + C(C(2)) + C(F(4))) \times 600$$

$$3246000 := (F(3) + C(C(2)) + C(F(4))) \times 6000$$

62.

$$3248 := (3! + Q(Q(2) + Q(4))) \times 8$$

$$32480 := (3! + Q(Q(2) + Q(4))) \times 80$$

$$324800 := (3! + Q(Q(2) + Q(4))) \times 800$$

$$3248000 := (3! + Q(Q(2) + Q(4))) \times 8000$$

63.

$$3248 := T(32 - 4) \times 8$$

$$32480 := T(32 - 4) \times 80$$

$$324800 := T(32 - 4) \times 800$$

$$3248000 := T(32 - 4) \times 8000$$

64.

$$3249 := (3!! + 2) / F(F(4)) \times 9$$

$$32490 := (3!! + 2) / F(F(4)) \times 90$$

$$324900 := (3!! + 2) / F(F(4)) \times 900$$

$$3249000 := (3!! + 2) / F(F(4)) \times 9000$$

65.

$$3249 := (3!! + 2) / \sqrt{4} \times 9$$

$$32490 := (3!! + 2) / \sqrt{4} \times 90$$

$$324900 := (3!! + 2) / \sqrt{4} \times 900$$

$$3249000 := (3!! + 2) / \sqrt{4} \times 9000$$

66.

$$3249 := (C(3) - C(2))^{\sqrt{4}} \times 9$$

$$32490 := (C(3) - C(2))^{\sqrt{4}} \times 90$$

$$324900 := (C(3) - C(2))^{\sqrt{4}} \times 900$$

$$3249000 := (C(3) - C(2))^{\sqrt{4}} \times 9000$$

67.

$$3250 := (Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(2))) \times 50$$

$$32500 := (Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(2))) \times 500$$

$$325000 := (Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(2))) \times 5000$$

$$3250000 := (Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(2))) \times 50000$$

68.

$$3264 := T(3) \times T(2 \times F(6)) \times 4$$

$$32640 := T(3) \times T(2 \times F(6)) \times 40$$

$$326400 := T(3) \times T(2 \times F(6)) \times 400$$

$$3264000 := T(3) \times T(2 \times F(6)) \times 4000$$

69.

$$3265 := (-F(T(3) + F(2)) + T(T(F(6)))) \times 5$$

$$32650 := (-F(T(3) + F(2)) + T(T(F(6)))) \times 50$$

$$326500 := (-F(T(3) + F(2)) + T(T(F(6)))) \times 500$$

$$3265000 := (-F(T(3) + F(2)) + T(T(F(6)))) \times 5000$$

70.

$$3265 := (-Q(3) - Q(2) + T(Q(6))) \times 5$$

$$32650 := (-Q(3) - Q(2) + T(Q(6))) \times 50$$

$$326500 := (-Q(3) - Q(2) + T(Q(6))) \times 500$$

$$3265000 := (-Q(3) - Q(2) + T(Q(6))) \times 5000$$

71.

$$3275 := (T(T(F(T(3)))) + (2 - F(7))) \times 5$$

$$32750 := (T(T(F(T(3)))) + (2 - F(7))) \times 50$$

$$327500 := (T(T(F(T(3)))) + (2 - F(7))) \times 500$$

$$3275000 := (T(T(F(T(3)))) + (2 - F(7))) \times 5000$$

72.

$$3285 := (-3^2 + T(T(8))) \times 5$$

$$32850 := (-3^2 + T(T(8))) \times 50$$

$$328500 := (-3^2 + T(T(8))) \times 500$$

$$3285000 := (-3^2 + T(T(8))) \times 5000$$

73.

$$3285 := (Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 8)) \times 5$$

$$32850 := (Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 8)) \times 50$$

$$328500 := (Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 8)) \times 500$$

$$3285000 := (Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 8)) \times 5000$$

74.

$$3288 := (T(Q(3)) \times Q(T(2)) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 8$$

$$32880 := (T(Q(3)) \times Q(T(2)) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 80$$

$$328800 := (T(Q(3)) \times Q(T(2)) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 800$$

$$3288000 := (T(Q(3)) \times Q(T(2)) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 8000$$

75.

$$3295 := (3!! - Q(C(2)) + \sqrt{9}) \times 5$$

$$32950 := (3!! - Q(C(2)) + \sqrt{9}) \times 50$$

$$329500 := (3!! - Q(C(2)) + \sqrt{9}) \times 500$$

$$3295000 := (3!! - Q(C(2)) + \sqrt{9}) \times 5000$$

76.

$$3295 := (F(3)^{T(T(2))} + T(F(9))) \times 5$$

$$32950 := (F(3)^{T(T(2))} + T(F(9))) \times 50$$

$$329500 := (F(3)^{T(T(2))} + T(F(9))) \times 500$$

$$3295000 := (F(3)^{T(T(2))} + T(F(9))) \times 5000$$

77.

$$3295 := (F(T(3))^2 + T(F(9))) \times 5$$

$$32950 := (F(T(3))^2 + T(F(9))) \times 50$$

$$329500 := (F(T(3))^2 + T(F(9))) \times 500$$

$$3295000 := (F(T(3))^2 + T(F(9))) \times 5000$$

78.

$$3295 := (Q(Q(3+2)) + F(9)) \times 5$$

$$32950 := (Q(Q(3+2)) + F(9)) \times 50$$

$$329500 := (Q(Q(3+2)) + F(9)) \times 500$$

$$3295000 := (Q(Q(3+2)) + F(9)) \times 5000$$

79.

$$3305 := (Q(3!) + Q(Q(3! - 0!))) \times 5$$

$$33050 := (Q(3!) + Q(Q(3! - 0!))) \times 50$$

$$330500 := (Q(3!) + Q(Q(3! - 0!))) \times 500$$

$$3305000 := (Q(3!) + Q(Q(3! - 0!))) \times 5000$$

80.

$$3305 := (T(T(F(T(3)))) - T(3) + 0!) \times 5$$

$$33050 := (T(T(F(T(3)))) - T(3) + 0!) \times 50$$

$$330500 := (T(T(F(T(3)))) - T(3) + 0!) \times 500$$

$$3305000 := (T(T(F(T(3)))) - T(3) + 0!) \times 5000$$

81.

$$\begin{aligned}3306 &:= (3!! - Q(F(3! + 0!))) \times 6 \\33060 &:= (3!! - Q(F(3! + 0!))) \times 60 \\330600 &:= (3!! - Q(F(3! + 0!))) \times 600 \\3306000 &:= (3!! - Q(F(3! + 0!))) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

82.

$$\begin{aligned}3325 &:= (3!! - F(F(3!) + 2)) \times 5 \\33250 &:= (3!! - F(F(3!) + 2)) \times 50 \\332500 &:= (3!! - F(F(3!) + 2)) \times 500 \\3325000 &:= (3!! - F(F(3!) + 2)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

83.

$$\begin{aligned}3325 &:= (T(3)! - T(T(T(3) - 2))) \times 5 \\33250 &:= (T(3)! - T(T(T(3) - 2))) \times 50 \\332500 &:= (T(3)! - T(T(T(3) - 2))) \times 500 \\3325000 &:= (T(3)! - T(T(T(3) - 2))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

84.

$$\begin{aligned}3325 &:= (T(T(3)^{F(3)}) - F(2)) \times 5 \\33250 &:= (T(T(3)^{F(3)}) - F(2)) \times 50 \\332500 &:= (T(T(3)^{F(3)}) - F(2)) \times 500 \\3325000 &:= (T(T(3)^{F(3)}) - F(2)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

85.

$$\begin{aligned}3335 &:= (F(F(3)) + T(T(3)^{F(3)})) \times 5 \\33350 &:= (F(F(3)) + T(T(3)^{F(3)})) \times 50 \\333500 &:= (F(F(3)) + T(T(3)^{F(3)})) \times 500 \\3335000 &:= (F(F(3)) + T(T(3)^{F(3)})) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

86.

$$\begin{aligned}3339 &:= (-3! + F(3! + F(3!))) \times 9 \\33390 &:= (-3! + F(3! + F(3!))) \times 90 \\333900 &:= (-3! + F(3! + F(3!))) \times 900 \\3339000 &:= (-3! + F(3! + F(3!))) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

87.

$$\begin{aligned}3342 &:= (3!! - Q(3!) + F(Q(4))) \times 2 \\33420 &:= (3!! - Q(3!) + F(Q(4))) \times 20 \\334200 &:= (3!! - Q(3!) + F(Q(4))) \times 200 \\3342000 &:= (3!! - Q(3!) + F(Q(4))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

88.

$$\begin{aligned}3345 &:= (3 + T(T(3)^{\sqrt{4}})) \times 5 \\33450 &:= (3 + T(T(3)^{\sqrt{4}})) \times 50 \\334500 &:= (3 + T(T(3)^{\sqrt{4}})) \times 500 \\3345000 &:= (3 + T(T(3)^{\sqrt{4}})) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

89.

$$\begin{aligned}3350 &:= (3 + Q(F(3!))) \times 50 \\33500 &:= (3 + Q(F(3!))) \times 500 \\335000 &:= (3 + Q(F(3!))) \times 5000 \\3350000 &:= (3 + Q(F(3!))) \times 50000\end{aligned}$$

90.

$$\begin{aligned}3352 &:= (Q(Q(3)) \times T(T(3)) - Q(5)) \times 2 \\33520 &:= (Q(Q(3)) \times T(T(3)) - Q(5)) \times 20 \\335200 &:= (Q(Q(3)) \times T(T(3)) - Q(5)) \times 200 \\3352000 &:= (Q(Q(3)) \times T(T(3)) - Q(5)) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

91.

$$\begin{aligned} 3355 &:= (T(T(3) \times T(3)) + 5) \times 5 \\ 33550 &:= (T(T(3) \times T(3)) + 5) \times 50 \\ 335500 &:= (T(T(3) \times T(3)) + 5) \times 500 \\ 3355000 &:= (T(T(3) \times T(3)) + 5) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

92.

$$\begin{aligned} 3355 &:= (T(T(3)^{F(3)}) + 5) \times 5 \\ 33550 &:= (T(T(3)^{F(3)}) + 5) \times 50 \\ 335500 &:= (T(T(3)^{F(3)}) + 5) \times 500 \\ 3355000 &:= (T(T(3)^{F(3)}) + 5) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

93.

$$\begin{aligned} 3365 &:= (F(F(3)) + T(3) + T(T(F(6)))) \times 5 \\ 33650 &:= (F(F(3)) + T(3) + T(T(F(6)))) \times 50 \\ 336500 &:= (F(F(3)) + T(3) + T(T(F(6)))) \times 500 \\ 3365000 &:= (F(F(3)) + T(3) + T(T(F(6)))) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

94.

$$\begin{aligned} 3365 &:= (T(T(3))/3 + T(Q(6))) \times 5 \\ 33650 &:= (T(T(3))/3 + T(Q(6))) \times 50 \\ 336500 &:= (T(T(3))/3 + T(Q(6))) \times 500 \\ 3365000 &:= (T(T(3))/3 + T(Q(6))) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

95.

$$\begin{aligned} 3366 &:= T(3^3 + 6) \times 6 \\ 33660 &:= T(3^3 + 6) \times 60 \\ 336600 &:= T(3^3 + 6) \times 600 \\ 3366000 &:= T(3^3 + 6) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

96.

$$\begin{aligned} 3368 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + T(-F(3) + T(6))) \times 8 \\ 33680 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + T(-F(3) + T(6))) \times 80 \\ 336800 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + T(-F(3) + T(6))) \times 800 \\ 3368000 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + T(-F(3) + T(6))) \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

97.

$$\begin{aligned} 3375 &:= T(3 \times 3) \times 75 \\ 33750 &:= T(3 \times 3) \times 750 \\ 337500 &:= T(3 \times 3) \times 7500 \\ 3375000 &:= T(3 \times 3) \times 75000 \end{aligned}$$

98.

$$\begin{aligned} 3385 &:= (3 + F(T(3)) + T(T(8))) \times 5 \\ 33850 &:= (3 + F(T(3)) + T(T(8))) \times 50 \\ 338500 &:= (3 + F(T(3)) + T(T(8))) \times 500 \\ 3385000 &:= (3 + F(T(3)) + T(T(8))) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

99.

$$\begin{aligned} 3385 &:= (T(T(T(3)))/(T(T(3))) + T(T(8))) \times 5 \\ 33850 &:= (T(T(T(3)))/(T(T(3))) + T(T(8))) \times 50 \\ 338500 &:= (T(T(T(3)))/(T(T(3))) + T(T(8))) \times 500 \\ 3385000 &:= (T(T(T(3)))/(T(T(3))) + T(T(8))) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

100.

$$\begin{aligned} 3385 &:= (T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3)) + T(T(8))) \times 5 \\ 33850 &:= (T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3)) + T(T(8))) \times 50 \\ 338500 &:= (T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3)) + T(T(8))) \times 500 \\ 3385000 &:= (T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3)) + T(T(8))) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

101.

$$\begin{aligned}3393 &:= (3 + T(F(3) + T(9))) \times 3 \\33930 &:= (3 + T(F(3) + T(9))) \times 30 \\339300 &:= (3 + T(F(3) + T(9))) \times 300 \\3393000 &:= (3 + T(F(3) + T(9))) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

102.

$$\begin{aligned}3410 &:= (Q(T(T(3))) - Q(T(4))) \times 10 \\34100 &:= (Q(T(T(3))) - Q(T(4))) \times 100 \\341000 &:= (Q(T(T(3))) - Q(T(4))) \times 1000 \\3410000 &:= (Q(T(T(3))) - Q(T(4))) \times 10000\end{aligned}$$

103.

$$\begin{aligned}3412 &:= (3!! + F(Q(4)) - 1) \times 2 \\34120 &:= (3!! + F(Q(4)) - 1) \times 20 \\341200 &:= (3!! + F(Q(4)) - 1) \times 200 \\3412000 &:= (3!! + F(Q(4)) - 1) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

104.

$$\begin{aligned}3415 &:= (3!! - Q(F(4)!) - 1) \times 5 \\34150 &:= (3!! - Q(F(4)!) - 1) \times 50 \\341500 &:= (3!! - Q(F(4)!) - 1) \times 500 \\3415000 &:= (3!! - Q(F(4)!) - 1) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

105.

$$\begin{aligned}3415 &:= (-T(F(T(3))) + T(F(4)!) + 1) \times 5 \\34150 &:= (-T(F(T(3))) + T(F(4)!) + 1) \times 50 \\341500 &:= (-T(F(T(3))) + T(F(4)!) + 1) \times 500 \\3415000 &:= (-T(F(T(3))) + T(F(4)!) + 1) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

106.

$$\begin{aligned}3422 &:= (3!! + F(Q(4)) + Q(2)) \times 2 \\34220 &:= (3!! + F(Q(4)) + Q(2)) \times 20 \\342200 &:= (3!! + F(Q(4)) + Q(2)) \times 200 \\3422000 &:= (3!! + F(Q(4)) + Q(2)) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

107.

$$\begin{aligned}3422 &:= T((C(3) + \sqrt{4}) \times 2) \times 2 \\34220 &:= T((C(3) + \sqrt{4}) \times 2) \times 20 \\342200 &:= T((C(3) + \sqrt{4}) \times 2) \times 200 \\3422000 &:= T((C(3) + \sqrt{4}) \times 2) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

108.

$$\begin{aligned}3422 &:= T(T(3) \times T(4) - 2) \times 2 \\34220 &:= T(T(3) \times T(4) - 2) \times 20 \\342200 &:= T(T(3) \times T(4) - 2) \times 200 \\3422000 &:= T(T(3) \times T(4) - 2) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

109.

$$\begin{aligned}3424 &:= (C(3!) \times 4 - C(2)) \times 4 \\34240 &:= (C(3!) \times 4 - C(2)) \times 40 \\342400 &:= (C(3!) \times 4 - C(2)) \times 400 \\3424000 &:= (C(3!) \times 4 - C(2)) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

110.

$$\begin{aligned}3425 &:= (3!! - C(F(4)) - C(2)) \times 5 \\34250 &:= (3!! - C(F(4)) - C(2)) \times 50 \\342500 &:= (3!! - C(F(4)) - C(2)) \times 500 \\3425000 &:= (3!! - C(F(4)) - C(2)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

111.

$$3425 := (T(3)! - \sqrt{T(T(T(4)) - T(T(2)))) \times 5$$

$$34250 := (T(3)! - \sqrt{T(T(T(4)) - T(T(2)))) \times 50$$

$$342500 := (T(3)! - \sqrt{T(T(T(4)) - T(T(2)))) \times 500$$

$$3425000 := (T(3)! - \sqrt{T(T(T(4)) - T(T(2)))) \times 5000$$

112.

$$3426 := (-3 + Q(4!) - 2) \times 6$$

$$34260 := (-3 + Q(4!) - 2) \times 60$$

$$342600 := (-3 + Q(4!) - 2) \times 600$$

$$3426000 := (-3 + Q(4!) - 2) \times 6000$$

113.

$$3429 := (3 + T(4! + T(2))) \times 9$$

$$34290 := (3 + T(4! + T(2))) \times 90$$

$$342900 := (3 + T(4! + T(2))) \times 900$$

$$3429000 := (3 + T(4! + T(2))) \times 9000$$

114.

$$3429 := (3 + T(F(4)^{T(2)})) \times 9$$

$$34290 := (3 + T(F(4)^{T(2)})) \times 90$$

$$342900 := (3 + T(F(4)^{T(2)})) \times 900$$

$$3429000 := (3 + T(F(4)^{T(2)})) \times 9000$$

115.

$$3429 := (F(F(3!)) + F(4)!!/2) \times 9$$

$$34290 := (F(F(3!)) + F(4)!!/2) \times 90$$

$$342900 := (F(F(3!)) + F(4)!!/2) \times 900$$

$$3429000 := (F(F(3!)) + F(4)!!/2) \times 9000$$

116.

$$3429 := (Q(F(3)) + F(Q(4) - 2)) \times 9$$

$$34290 := (Q(F(3)) + F(Q(4) - 2)) \times 90$$

$$342900 := (Q(F(3)) + F(Q(4) - 2)) \times 900$$

$$3429000 := (Q(F(3)) + F(Q(4) - 2)) \times 9000$$

117.

$$3429 := (T(3) \times C(4) - T(2)) \times 9$$

$$34290 := (T(3) \times C(4) - T(2)) \times 90$$

$$342900 := (T(3) \times C(4) - T(2)) \times 900$$

$$3429000 := (T(3) \times C(4) - T(2)) \times 9000$$

118.

$$3429 := (T(3^{F(4)}) + T(2)) \times 9$$

$$34290 := (T(3^{F(4)}) + T(2)) \times 90$$

$$342900 := (T(3^{F(4)}) + T(2)) \times 900$$

$$3429000 := (T(3^{F(4)}) + T(2)) \times 9000$$

119.

$$3432 := (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) \times T(3) \times 2$$

$$34320 := (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) \times T(3) \times 20$$

$$343200 := (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) \times T(3) \times 200$$

$$3432000 := (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) \times T(3) \times 2000$$

120.

$$3435 := (3!! - 4! - Q(3)) \times 5$$

$$34350 := (3!! - 4! - Q(3)) \times 50$$

$$343500 := (3!! - 4! - Q(3)) \times 500$$

$$3435000 := (3!! - 4! - Q(3)) \times 5000$$

121.

$$\begin{aligned} 3435 &:= (3!! - C(F(4)) - 3!) \times 5 \\ 34350 &:= (3!! - C(F(4)) - 3!) \times 50 \\ 343500 &:= (3!! - C(F(4)) - 3!) \times 500 \\ 3435000 &:= (3!! - C(F(4)) - 3!) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

122.

$$\begin{aligned} 3435 &:= (3 \times Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(3))) \times 5 \\ 34350 &:= (3 \times Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(3))) \times 50 \\ 343500 &:= (3 \times Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(3))) \times 500 \\ 3435000 &:= (3 \times Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(3))) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

123.

$$\begin{aligned} 3435 &:= (T(T(3)^{\sqrt{4}}) + T(T(3))) \times 5 \\ 34350 &:= (T(T(3)^{\sqrt{4}}) + T(T(3))) \times 50 \\ 343500 &:= (T(T(3)^{\sqrt{4}}) + T(T(3))) \times 500 \\ 3435000 &:= (T(T(3)^{\sqrt{4}}) + T(T(3))) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

124.

$$\begin{aligned} 3437 &:= (-C(3) + \sqrt{C(C(4))} + 3!) \times 7 \\ 34370 &:= (-C(3) + \sqrt{C(C(4))} + 3!) \times 70 \\ 343700 &:= (-C(3) + \sqrt{C(C(4))} + 3!) \times 700 \\ 3437000 &:= (-C(3) + \sqrt{C(C(4))} + 3!) \times 7000 \end{aligned}$$

125.

$$\begin{aligned} 3437 &:= (C(T(3) + \sqrt{4}) - T(T(3))) \times 7 \\ 34370 &:= (C(T(3) + \sqrt{4}) - T(T(3))) \times 70 \\ 343700 &:= (C(T(3) + \sqrt{4}) - T(T(3))) \times 700 \\ 3437000 &:= (C(T(3) + \sqrt{4}) - T(T(3))) \times 7000 \end{aligned}$$

126.

$$\begin{aligned} 3437 &:= (F(T(3))^{F(4)} - T(T(3))) \times 7 \\ 34370 &:= (F(T(3))^{F(4)} - T(T(3))) \times 70 \\ 343700 &:= (F(T(3))^{F(4)} - T(T(3))) \times 700 \\ 3437000 &:= (F(T(3))^{F(4)} - T(T(3))) \times 7000 \end{aligned}$$

127.

$$\begin{aligned} 3442 &:= (T(3 + F(T(4))) + T(4)) \times 2 \\ 34420 &:= (T(3 + F(T(4))) + T(4)) \times 20 \\ 344200 &:= (T(3 + F(T(4))) + T(4)) \times 200 \\ 3442000 &:= (T(3 + F(T(4))) + T(4)) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

128.

$$\begin{aligned} 3442 &:= (T(3 + T(T(4))) + T(4)) \times 2 \\ 34420 &:= (T(3 + T(T(4))) + T(4)) \times 20 \\ 344200 &:= (T(3 + T(T(4))) + T(4)) \times 200 \\ 3442000 &:= (T(3 + T(T(4))) + T(4)) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

129.

$$\begin{aligned} 3444 &:= T(-3 + 44) \times 4 \\ 34440 &:= T(-3 + 44) \times 40 \\ 344400 &:= T(-3 + 44) \times 400 \\ 3444000 &:= T(-3 + 44) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

130.

$$\begin{aligned} 3448 &:= (-Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 8 \\ 34480 &:= (-Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 80 \\ 344800 &:= (-Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 800 \\ 3448000 &:= (-Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

131.

$$\begin{aligned}3448 &:= (T(T(3))^{F(F(4))} - T(4)) \times 8 \\34480 &:= (T(T(3))^{F(F(4))} - T(4)) \times 80 \\344800 &:= (T(T(3))^{F(F(4))} - T(4)) \times 800 \\3448000 &:= (T(T(3))^{F(F(4))} - T(4)) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

132.

$$\begin{aligned}3448 &:= (T(T(3))^{\sqrt{4}} - T(4)) \times 8 \\34480 &:= (T(T(3))^{\sqrt{4}} - T(4)) \times 80 \\344800 &:= (T(T(3))^{\sqrt{4}} - T(4)) \times 800 \\3448000 &:= (T(T(3))^{\sqrt{4}} - T(4)) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

133.

$$\begin{aligned}3450 &:= (T(Q(3)) + 4!) \times 50 \\34500 &:= (T(Q(3)) + 4!) \times 500 \\345000 &:= (T(Q(3)) + 4!) \times 5000 \\3450000 &:= (T(Q(3)) + 4!) \times 50000\end{aligned}$$

134.

$$\begin{aligned}3452 &:= (-F(3) + C(\sqrt{4! + 5!})) \times 2 \\34520 &:= (-F(3) + C(\sqrt{4! + 5!})) \times 20 \\345200 &:= (-F(3) + C(\sqrt{4! + 5!})) \times 200 \\3452000 &:= (-F(3) + C(\sqrt{4! + 5!})) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

135.

$$\begin{aligned}3453 &:= (Q(34) - 5) \times 3 \\34530 &:= (Q(34) - 5) \times 30 \\345300 &:= (Q(34) - 5) \times 300 \\3453000 &:= (Q(34) - 5) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

136.

$$\begin{aligned}3455 &:= (3!! - 4! - 5) \times 5 \\34550 &:= (3!! - 4! - 5) \times 50 \\345500 &:= (3!! - 4! - 5) \times 500 \\3455000 &:= (3!! - 4! - 5) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

137.

$$\begin{aligned}3464 &:= (F(3) + 4! \times Q(6)) \times 4 \\34640 &:= (F(3) + 4! \times Q(6)) \times 40 \\346400 &:= (F(3) + 4! \times Q(6)) \times 400 \\3464000 &:= (F(3) + 4! \times Q(6)) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

138.

$$\begin{aligned}3464 &:= (F(3) + 4 \times C(6)) \times 4 \\34640 &:= (F(3) + 4 \times C(6)) \times 40 \\346400 &:= (F(3) + 4 \times C(6)) \times 400 \\3464000 &:= (F(3) + 4 \times C(6)) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

139.

$$\begin{aligned}3465 &:= (-3 - 4! + 6!) \times 5 \\34650 &:= (-3 - 4! + 6!) \times 50 \\346500 &:= (-3 - 4! + 6!) \times 500 \\3465000 &:= (-3 - 4! + 6!) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

140.

$$\begin{aligned}3465 &:= (C(3)^{\sqrt{4}} - Q(6)) \times 5 \\34650 &:= (C(3)^{\sqrt{4}} - Q(6)) \times 50 \\346500 &:= (C(3)^{\sqrt{4}} - Q(6)) \times 500 \\3465000 &:= (C(3)^{\sqrt{4}} - Q(6)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

141.

$$\begin{aligned}3465 &:= (Q(3)^{F(4)} - Q(6)) \times 5 \\34650 &:= (Q(3)^{F(4)} - Q(6)) \times 50 \\346500 &:= (Q(3)^{F(4)} - Q(6)) \times 500 \\3465000 &:= (Q(3)^{F(4)} - Q(6)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

142.

$$\begin{aligned}3468 &:= (C(3) + 4!) \times 68 \\34680 &:= (C(3) + 4!) \times 680 \\346800 &:= (C(3) + 4!) \times 6800 \\3468000 &:= (C(3) + 4!) \times 68000\end{aligned}$$

143.

$$\begin{aligned}3475 &:= (T(3)! + F(4) - T(7)) \times 5 \\34750 &:= (T(3)! + F(4) - T(7)) \times 50 \\347500 &:= (T(3)! + F(4) - T(7)) \times 500 \\3475000 &:= (T(3)! + F(4) - T(7)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

144.

$$\begin{aligned}3475 &:= (T(3)! + T(\sqrt{4}) - T(7)) \times 5 \\34750 &:= (T(3)! + T(\sqrt{4}) - T(7)) \times 50 \\347500 &:= (T(3)! + T(\sqrt{4}) - T(7)) \times 500 \\3475000 &:= (T(3)! + T(\sqrt{4}) - T(7)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

145.

$$\begin{aligned}3484 &:= (-3 + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(8))) \times 4 \\34840 &:= (-3 + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(8))) \times 40 \\348400 &:= (-3 + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(8))) \times 400 \\3484000 &:= (-3 + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(8))) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

146.

$$\begin{aligned}3485 &:= (3!! - F(F(4)) - F(8)) \times 5 \\34850 &:= (3!! - F(F(4)) - F(8)) \times 50 \\348500 &:= (3!! - F(F(4)) - F(8)) \times 500 \\3485000 &:= (3!! - F(F(4)) - F(8)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

147.

$$\begin{aligned}3485 &:= (3!! - \sqrt{4} - F(8)) \times 5 \\34850 &:= (3!! - \sqrt{4} - F(8)) \times 50 \\348500 &:= (3!! - \sqrt{4} - F(8)) \times 500 \\3485000 &:= (3!! - \sqrt{4} - F(8)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

148.

$$\begin{aligned}3485 &:= (T(3)! - \sqrt{4} - F(8)) \times 5 \\34850 &:= (T(3)! - \sqrt{4} - F(8)) \times 50 \\348500 &:= (T(3)! - \sqrt{4} - F(8)) \times 500 \\3485000 &:= (T(3)! - \sqrt{4} - F(8)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

149.

$$\begin{aligned}3485 &:= (T(T(3)) + T(4) + T(T(8))) \times 5 \\34850 &:= (T(T(3)) + T(4) + T(T(8))) \times 50 \\348500 &:= (T(T(3)) + T(4) + T(T(8))) \times 500 \\3485000 &:= (T(T(3)) + T(4) + T(T(8))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

150.

$$\begin{aligned}3486 &:= (-3 + Q(4!) + 8) \times 6 \\34860 &:= (-3 + Q(4!) + 8) \times 60 \\348600 &:= (-3 + Q(4!) + 8) \times 600 \\3486000 &:= (-3 + Q(4!) + 8) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

151.

$$\begin{aligned}3495 &:= (3!! - 4! + \sqrt{9}) \times 5 \\34950 &:= (3!! - 4! + \sqrt{9}) \times 50 \\349500 &:= (3!! - 4! + \sqrt{9}) \times 500 \\3495000 &:= (3!! - 4! + \sqrt{9}) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

152.

$$\begin{aligned}3495 &:= (-3 \times T(4) + C(9)) \times 5 \\34950 &:= (-3 \times T(4) + C(9)) \times 50 \\349500 &:= (-3 \times T(4) + C(9)) \times 500 \\3495000 &:= (-3 \times T(4) + C(9)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

153.

$$\begin{aligned}3495 &:= 3 \times F(4 + 9) \times 5 \\34950 &:= 3 \times F(4 + 9) \times 50 \\349500 &:= 3 \times F(4 + 9) \times 500 \\3495000 &:= 3 \times F(4 + 9) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

154.

$$\begin{aligned}3505 &:= (C(3)!/Q(5)! - 0!) \times 5 \\35050 &:= (C(3)!/Q(5)! - 0!) \times 50 \\350500 &:= (C(3)!/Q(5)! - 0!) \times 500 \\3505000 &:= (C(3)!/Q(5)! - 0!) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

155.

$$\begin{aligned}3507 &:= (C(C(F(3))) - \sqrt{5! + 0!}) \times 7 \\35070 &:= (C(C(F(3))) - \sqrt{5! + 0!}) \times 70 \\350700 &:= (C(C(F(3))) - \sqrt{5! + 0!}) \times 700 \\3507000 &:= (C(C(F(3))) - \sqrt{5! + 0!}) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

156.

$$\begin{aligned}3510 &:= T(T(T(3)) + 5) \times 10 \\35100 &:= T(T(T(3)) + 5) \times 100 \\351000 &:= T(T(T(3)) + 5) \times 1000 \\3510000 &:= T(T(T(3)) + 5) \times 10000\end{aligned}$$

157.

$$\begin{aligned}3513 &:= (Q(Q(3!)) - C(5)) \times 3 \\35130 &:= (Q(Q(3!)) - C(5)) \times 30 \\351300 &:= (Q(Q(3!)) - C(5)) \times 300 \\3513000 &:= (Q(Q(3!)) - C(5)) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

158.

$$\begin{aligned}3515 &:= (C(Q(3)) - Q(5) - 1) \times 5 \\35150 &:= (C(Q(3)) - Q(5) - 1) \times 50 \\351500 &:= (C(Q(3)) - Q(5) - 1) \times 500 \\3515000 &:= (C(Q(3)) - Q(5) - 1) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

159.

$$\begin{aligned}3515 &:= T(T(3 + 5) + 1) \times 5 \\35150 &:= T(T(3 + 5) + 1) \times 50 \\351500 &:= T(T(3 + 5) + 1) \times 500 \\3515000 &:= T(T(3 + 5) + 1) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

160.

$$\begin{aligned}3519 &:= (C(C(F(3))) - 5! - 1) \times 9 \\35190 &:= (C(C(F(3))) - 5! - 1) \times 90 \\351900 &:= (C(C(F(3))) - 5! - 1) \times 900 \\3519000 &:= (C(C(F(3))) - 5! - 1) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

161.

$$\begin{aligned}3525 &:= (3!! - 5!/C(2)) \times 5 \\35250 &:= (3!! - 5!/C(2)) \times 50 \\352500 &:= (3!! - 5!/C(2)) \times 500 \\3525000 &:= (3!! - 5!/C(2)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

162.

$$\begin{aligned}3525 &:= (F(F(3!)) + 5!) \times 25 \\35250 &:= (F(F(3!)) + 5!) \times 250 \\352500 &:= (F(F(3!)) + 5!) \times 2500 \\3525000 &:= (F(F(3!)) + 5!) \times 25000\end{aligned}$$

163.

$$\begin{aligned}3525 &:= (T(T(3)) + 5!) \times 25 \\35250 &:= (T(T(3)) + 5!) \times 250 \\352500 &:= (T(T(3)) + 5!) \times 2500 \\3525000 &:= (T(T(3)) + 5!) \times 25000\end{aligned}$$

164.

$$\begin{aligned}3525 &:= (T(T(3)) + T(T(5))) \times 25 \\35250 &:= (T(T(3)) + T(T(5))) \times 250 \\352500 &:= (T(T(3)) + T(T(5))) \times 2500 \\3525000 &:= (T(T(3)) + T(T(5))) \times 25000\end{aligned}$$

165.

$$\begin{aligned}3528 &:= (3! + 5!) \times 28 \\35280 &:= (3! + 5!) \times 280 \\352800 &:= (3! + 5!) \times 2800 \\3528000 &:= (3! + 5!) \times 28000\end{aligned}$$

166.

$$\begin{aligned}3528 &:= (T(3) + 5!) \times 28 \\35280 &:= (T(3) + 5!) \times 280 \\352800 &:= (T(3) + 5!) \times 2800 \\3528000 &:= (T(3) + 5!) \times 28000\end{aligned}$$

167.

$$\begin{aligned}3528 &:= (T(3) + T(5))^2 \times 8 \\35280 &:= (T(3) + T(5))^2 \times 80 \\352800 &:= (T(3) + T(5))^2 \times 800 \\3528000 &:= (T(3) + T(5))^2 \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

168.

$$\begin{aligned}3528 &:= F(3 + 5)^2 \times 8 \\35280 &:= F(3 + 5)^2 \times 80 \\352800 &:= F(3 + 5)^2 \times 800 \\3528000 &:= F(3 + 5)^2 \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

169.

$$\begin{aligned}3528 &:= Q(3 \times (5 + 2)) \times 8 \\35280 &:= Q(3 \times (5 + 2)) \times 80 \\352800 &:= Q(3 \times (5 + 2)) \times 800 \\3528000 &:= Q(3 \times (5 + 2)) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

170.

$$\begin{aligned}3535 &:= (3!! - F(F(3) + 5)) \times 5 \\35350 &:= (3!! - F(F(3) + 5)) \times 50 \\353500 &:= (3!! - F(F(3) + 5)) \times 500 \\3535000 &:= (3!! - F(F(3) + 5)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

171.

$$\begin{aligned}3535 &:= (C(Q(3)) - Q(5) + 3) \times 5 \\35350 &:= (C(Q(3)) - Q(5) + 3) \times 50 \\353500 &:= (C(Q(3)) - Q(5) + 3) \times 500 \\3535000 &:= (C(Q(3)) - Q(5) + 3) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

172.

$$\begin{aligned}3535 &:= (Q(Q(3!)) - Q(Q(5)) + (Q(3!))) \times 5 \\35350 &:= (Q(Q(3!)) - Q(Q(5)) + (Q(3!))) \times 50 \\353500 &:= (Q(Q(3!)) - Q(Q(5)) + (Q(3!))) \times 500 \\3535000 &:= (Q(Q(3!)) - Q(Q(5)) + (Q(3!))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

173.

$$\begin{aligned}3535 &:= (T(3)! - T(5) + F(3)) \times 5 \\35350 &:= (T(3)! - T(5) + F(3)) \times 50 \\353500 &:= (T(3)! - T(5) + F(3)) \times 500 \\3535000 &:= (T(3)! - T(5) + F(3)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

174.

$$\begin{aligned}3542 &:= (T(F(3+5)) + T(F(T(4)))) \times 2 \\35420 &:= (T(F(3+5)) + T(F(T(4)))) \times 20 \\354200 &:= (T(F(3+5)) + T(F(T(4)))) \times 200 \\3542000 &:= (T(F(3+5)) + T(F(T(4)))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

175.

$$\begin{aligned}3542 &:= (T(T(3) + T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 2 \\35420 &:= (T(T(3) + T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 20 \\354200 &:= (T(T(3) + T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 200 \\3542000 &:= (T(T(3) + T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

176.

$$\begin{aligned}3542 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + T(F(5 \times \sqrt{4}))) \times 2 \\35420 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + T(F(5 \times \sqrt{4}))) \times 20 \\354200 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + T(F(5 \times \sqrt{4}))) \times 200 \\3542000 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + T(F(5 \times \sqrt{4}))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

177.

$$\begin{aligned}3542 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(5 \times \sqrt{4}))) \times 2 \\35420 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(5 \times \sqrt{4}))) \times 20 \\354200 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(5 \times \sqrt{4}))) \times 200 \\3542000 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(5 \times \sqrt{4}))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

178.

$$\begin{aligned}3543 &:= (T(3)! + T(Q(5)) + T(Q(4))) \times 3 \\35430 &:= (T(3)! + T(Q(5)) + T(Q(4))) \times 30 \\354300 &:= (T(3)! + T(Q(5)) + T(Q(4))) \times 300 \\3543000 &:= (T(3)! + T(Q(5)) + T(Q(4))) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

179.

$$\begin{aligned}3545 &:= (3!! + 5 - Q(4)) \times 5 \\35450 &:= (3!! + 5 - Q(4)) \times 50 \\354500 &:= (3!! + 5 - Q(4)) \times 500 \\3545000 &:= (3!! + 5 - Q(4)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

180.

$$\begin{aligned}3545 &:= (3!! - 5 - F(4)!) \times 5 \\35450 &:= (3!! - 5 - F(4)!) \times 50 \\354500 &:= (3!! - 5 - F(4)!) \times 500 \\3545000 &:= (3!! - 5 - F(4)!) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

181.

$$\begin{aligned} 3545 &:= (3!! - \sqrt{C(5) - 4}) \times 5 \\ 35450 &:= (3!! - \sqrt{C(5) - 4}) \times 50 \\ 354500 &:= (3!! - \sqrt{C(5) - 4}) \times 500 \\ 3545000 &:= (3!! - \sqrt{C(5) - 4}) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

182.

$$\begin{aligned} 3545 &:= (T(3)! - T(5) + 4) \times 5 \\ 35450 &:= (T(3)! - T(5) + 4) \times 50 \\ 354500 &:= (T(3)! - T(5) + 4) \times 500 \\ 3545000 &:= (T(3)! - T(5) + 4) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

183.

$$\begin{aligned} 3555 &:= (Q(Q(3)) + 5 + Q(Q(5))) \times 5 \\ 35550 &:= (Q(Q(3)) + 5 + Q(Q(5))) \times 50 \\ 355500 &:= (Q(Q(3)) + 5 + Q(Q(5))) \times 500 \\ 3555000 &:= (Q(Q(3)) + 5 + Q(Q(5))) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

184.

$$\begin{aligned} 3564 &:= (C(3) \times Q(5) + C(6)) \times 4 \\ 35640 &:= (C(3) \times Q(5) + C(6)) \times 40 \\ 356400 &:= (C(3) \times Q(5) + C(6)) \times 400 \\ 3564000 &:= (C(3) \times Q(5) + C(6)) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

185.

$$\begin{aligned} 3575 &:= F(F(3) \times 5) \times F(7) \times 5 \\ 35750 &:= F(F(3) \times 5) \times F(7) \times 50 \\ 357500 &:= F(F(3) \times 5) \times F(7) \times 500 \\ 3575000 &:= F(F(3) \times 5) \times F(7) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

186.

$$\begin{aligned} 3575 &:= T(F(3) \times 5) \times F(7) \times 5 \\ 35750 &:= T(F(3) \times 5) \times F(7) \times 50 \\ 357500 &:= T(F(3) \times 5) \times F(7) \times 500 \\ 3575000 &:= T(F(3) \times 5) \times F(7) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

187.

$$\begin{aligned} 3576 &:= (-Q(3!) + Q(Q(5)) + 7) \times 6 \\ 35760 &:= (-Q(3!) + Q(Q(5)) + 7) \times 60 \\ 357600 &:= (-Q(3!) + Q(Q(5)) + 7) \times 600 \\ 3576000 &:= (-Q(3!) + Q(Q(5)) + 7) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

188.

$$\begin{aligned} 3585 &:= (3!! + 5 - 8) \times 5 \\ 35850 &:= (3!! + 5 - 8) \times 50 \\ 358500 &:= (3!! + 5 - 8) \times 500 \\ 3585000 &:= (3!! + 5 - 8) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

189.

$$\begin{aligned} 3595 &:= (3!! + 5 - (\sqrt{9})!) \times 5 \\ 35950 &:= (3!! + 5 - (\sqrt{9})!) \times 50 \\ 359500 &:= (3!! + 5 - (\sqrt{9})!) \times 500 \\ 3595000 &:= (3!! + 5 - (\sqrt{9})!) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

190.

$$\begin{aligned} 3595 &:= (3!! - F(5 - \sqrt{9})) \times 5 \\ 35950 &:= (3!! - F(5 - \sqrt{9})) \times 50 \\ 359500 &:= (3!! - F(5 - \sqrt{9})) \times 500 \\ 3595000 &:= (3!! - F(5 - \sqrt{9})) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

191.

$$\begin{aligned}3595 &:= (3!! - F(F(F(-(5-9)))) \times 5 \\35950 &:= (3!! - F(F(F(-(5-9)))) \times 50 \\359500 &:= (3!! - F(F(F(-(5-9)))) \times 500 \\3595000 &:= (3!! - F(F(F(-(5-9)))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

192.

$$\begin{aligned}3595 &:= (-F(3) \times 5 + C(9)) \times 5 \\35950 &:= (-F(3) \times 5 + C(9)) \times 50 \\359500 &:= (-F(3) \times 5 + C(9)) \times 500 \\3595000 &:= (-F(3) \times 5 + C(9)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

193.

$$\begin{aligned}3600 &:= 3! \times 600 \\36000 &:= 3! \times 6000 \\360000 &:= 3! \times 60000 \\3600000 &:= 3! \times 600000\end{aligned}$$

194.

$$\begin{aligned}3600 &:= T(3) \times 600 \\36000 &:= T(3) \times 6000 \\360000 &:= T(3) \times 60000 \\3600000 &:= T(3) \times 600000\end{aligned}$$

195.

$$\begin{aligned}3605 &:= (F(3) + 6! - 0!) \times 5 \\36050 &:= (F(3) + 6! - 0!) \times 50 \\360500 &:= (F(3) + 6! - 0!) \times 500 \\3605000 &:= (F(3) + 6! - 0!) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

196.

$$\begin{aligned}3605 &:= (T(3)! + (6 \times 0!)) \times 5 \\36050 &:= (T(3)! + (6 \times 0!)) \times 50 \\360500 &:= (T(3)! + (6 \times 0!)) \times 500 \\3605000 &:= (T(3)! + (6 \times 0!)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

197.

$$\begin{aligned}3608 &:= (Q(3) + Q(T(6)) + 0!) \times 8 \\36080 &:= (Q(3) + Q(T(6)) + 0!) \times 80 \\360800 &:= (Q(3) + Q(T(6)) + 0!) \times 800 \\3608000 &:= (Q(3) + Q(T(6)) + 0!) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

198.

$$\begin{aligned}3610 &:= Q(-F(3) + F(F(6))) \times 10 \\36100 &:= Q(-F(3) + F(F(6))) \times 100 \\361000 &:= Q(-F(3) + F(F(6))) \times 1000 \\3610000 &:= Q(-F(3) + F(F(6))) \times 10000\end{aligned}$$

199.

$$\begin{aligned}3622 &:= (3 + Q(Q(6)) + C(C(2))) \times 2 \\36220 &:= (3 + Q(Q(6)) + C(C(2))) \times 20 \\362200 &:= (3 + Q(Q(6)) + C(C(2))) \times 200 \\3622000 &:= (3 + Q(Q(6)) + C(C(2))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

200.

$$\begin{aligned}3624 &:= (3 + T(2 \times T(6))) \times 4 \\36240 &:= (3 + T(2 \times T(6))) \times 40 \\362400 &:= (3 + T(2 \times T(6))) \times 400 \\3624000 &:= (3 + T(2 \times T(6))) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

201.

$$\begin{aligned}3625 &:= (3^6 - Q(2)) \times 5 \\36250 &:= (3^6 - Q(2)) \times 50 \\362500 &:= (3^6 - Q(2)) \times 500 \\3625000 &:= (3^6 - Q(2)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

202.

$$\begin{aligned}3625 &:= (3 + 6! + 2) \times 5 \\36250 &:= (3 + 6! + 2) \times 50 \\362500 &:= (3 + 6! + 2) \times 500 \\3625000 &:= (3 + 6! + 2) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

203.

$$\begin{aligned}3625 &:= (F(3) + 6! + T(2)) \times 5 \\36250 &:= (F(3) + 6! + T(2)) \times 50 \\362500 &:= (F(3) + 6! + T(2)) \times 500 \\3625000 &:= (F(3) + 6! + T(2)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

204.

$$\begin{aligned}3635 &:= (3^6 - F(3)) \times 5 \\36350 &:= (3^6 - F(3)) \times 50 \\363500 &:= (3^6 - F(3)) \times 500 \\3635000 &:= (3^6 - F(3)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

205.

$$\begin{aligned}3635 &:= (C(Q(3)) - 6/3) \times 5 \\36350 &:= (C(Q(3)) - 6/3) \times 50 \\363500 &:= (C(Q(3)) - 6/3) \times 500 \\3635000 &:= (C(Q(3)) - 6/3) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

206.

$$\begin{aligned}3635 &:= (T(3)! + T(6)/3) \times 5 \\36350 &:= (T(3)! + T(6)/3) \times 50 \\363500 &:= (T(3)! + T(6)/3) \times 500 \\3635000 &:= (T(3)! + T(6)/3) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

207.

$$\begin{aligned}3640 &:= T(T(T(3)) - F(6)) \times 40 \\36400 &:= T(T(T(3)) - F(6)) \times 400 \\364000 &:= T(T(T(3)) - F(6)) \times 4000 \\3640000 &:= T(T(T(3)) - F(6)) \times 40000\end{aligned}$$

208.

$$\begin{aligned}3642 &:= (-Q(3) + T(Q(6) + 4!)) \times 2 \\36420 &:= (-Q(3) + T(Q(6) + 4!)) \times 20 \\364200 &:= (-Q(3) + T(Q(6) + 4!)) \times 200 \\3642000 &:= (-Q(3) + T(Q(6) + 4!)) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

209.

$$\begin{aligned}3642 &:= (T(T(3)) + 6 \times T(4!)) \times 2 \\36420 &:= (T(T(3)) + 6 \times T(4!)) \times 20 \\364200 &:= (T(T(3)) + 6 \times T(4!)) \times 200 \\3642000 &:= (T(T(3)) + 6 \times T(4!)) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

210.

$$\begin{aligned}3644 &:= (F(T(3)) + T(T(6) \times \sqrt{4})) \times 4 \\36440 &:= (F(T(3)) + T(T(6) \times \sqrt{4})) \times 40 \\364400 &:= (F(T(3)) + T(T(6) \times \sqrt{4})) \times 400 \\3644000 &:= (F(T(3)) + T(T(6) \times \sqrt{4})) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

211.

$$\begin{aligned} 3645 &:= (3 + 6)^{F(4)} \times 5 \\ 36450 &:= (3 + 6)^{F(4)} \times 50 \\ 364500 &:= (3 + 6)^{F(4)} \times 500 \\ 3645000 &:= (3 + 6)^{F(4)} \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

212.

$$\begin{aligned} 3645 &:= C(36/4) \times 5 \\ 36450 &:= C(36/4) \times 50 \\ 364500 &:= C(36/4) \times 500 \\ 3645000 &:= C(36/4) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

213.

$$\begin{aligned} 3645 &:= \sqrt{3^{(6 \times \text{sqrt}4)}} \times 5 \\ 36450 &:= \sqrt{3^{(6 \times \text{sqrt}4)}} \times 50 \\ 364500 &:= \sqrt{3^{(6 \times \text{sqrt}4)}} \times 500 \\ 3645000 &:= \sqrt{3^{(6 \times \text{sqrt}4)}} \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

214.

$$\begin{aligned} 3647 &:= (3 + 6 + \sqrt{C(C(4))}) \times 7 \\ 36470 &:= (3 + 6 + \sqrt{C(C(4))}) \times 70 \\ 364700 &:= (3 + 6 + \sqrt{C(C(4))}) \times 700 \\ 3647000 &:= (3 + 6 + \sqrt{C(C(4))}) \times 7000 \end{aligned}$$

215.

$$\begin{aligned} 3647 &:= (F(F(3)) + C(F(6)) + \sqrt{C(4)}) \times 7 \\ 36470 &:= (F(F(3)) + C(F(6)) + \sqrt{C(4)}) \times 70 \\ 364700 &:= (F(F(3)) + C(F(6)) + \sqrt{C(4)}) \times 700 \\ 3647000 &:= (F(F(3)) + C(F(6)) + \sqrt{C(4)}) \times 7000 \end{aligned}$$

216.

$$\begin{aligned} 3647 &:= (Q(3) + F(6)^{F(4)}) \times 7 \\ 36470 &:= (Q(3) + F(6)^{F(4)}) \times 70 \\ 364700 &:= (Q(3) + F(6)^{F(4)}) \times 700 \\ 3647000 &:= (Q(3) + F(6)^{F(4)}) \times 7000 \end{aligned}$$

217.

$$\begin{aligned} 3647 &:= (Q(3) + \sqrt{C(64)}) \times 7 \\ 36470 &:= (Q(3) + \sqrt{C(64)}) \times 70 \\ 364700 &:= (Q(3) + \sqrt{C(64)}) \times 700 \\ 3647000 &:= (Q(3) + \sqrt{C(64)}) \times 7000 \end{aligned}$$

218.

$$\begin{aligned} 3647 &:= (Q(3 + T(6)) - T(T(4))) \times 7 \\ 36470 &:= (Q(3 + T(6)) - T(T(4))) \times 70 \\ 364700 &:= (Q(3 + T(6)) - T(T(4))) \times 700 \\ 3647000 &:= (Q(3 + T(6)) - T(T(4))) \times 7000 \end{aligned}$$

219.

$$\begin{aligned} 3648 &:= (-3 + T(T(6))) \times \sqrt{4} \times 8 \\ 36480 &:= (-3 + T(T(6))) \times \sqrt{4} \times 80 \\ 364800 &:= (-3 + T(T(6))) \times \sqrt{4} \times 800 \\ 3648000 &:= (-3 + T(T(6))) \times \sqrt{4} \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

220.

$$\begin{aligned} 3648 &:= (C(3) - F(6)) \times 4! \times 8 \\ 36480 &:= (C(3) - F(6)) \times 4! \times 80 \\ 364800 &:= (C(3) - F(6)) \times 4! \times 800 \\ 3648000 &:= (C(3) - F(6)) \times 4! \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

221.

$$\begin{aligned}3648 &:= (-F(3) + F(F(6))) \times 4! \times 8 \\36480 &:= (-F(3) + F(F(6))) \times 4! \times 80 \\364800 &:= (-F(3) + F(F(6))) \times 4! \times 800 \\3648000 &:= (-F(3) + F(F(6))) \times 4! \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

222.

$$\begin{aligned}3648 &:= (-F(3) + T(6)) \times 4! \times 8 \\36480 &:= (-F(3) + T(6)) \times 4! \times 80 \\364800 &:= (-F(3) + T(6)) \times 4! \times 800 \\3648000 &:= (-F(3) + T(6)) \times 4! \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

223.

$$\begin{aligned}3648 &:= T(3) \times (T(6) + T(T(4))) \times 8 \\36480 &:= T(3) \times (T(6) + T(T(4))) \times 80 \\364800 &:= T(3) \times (T(6) + T(T(4))) \times 800 \\3648000 &:= T(3) \times (T(6) + T(T(4))) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

224.

$$\begin{aligned}3650 &:= (Q(3) + Q(F(6))) \times 50 \\36500 &:= (Q(3) + Q(F(6))) \times 500 \\365000 &:= (Q(3) + Q(F(6))) \times 5000 \\3650000 &:= (Q(3) + Q(F(6))) \times 50000\end{aligned}$$

225.

$$\begin{aligned}3655 &:= (3! + 6! + 5) \times 5 \\36550 &:= (3! + 6! + 5) \times 50 \\365500 &:= (3! + 6! + 5) \times 500 \\3655000 &:= (3! + 6! + 5) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

226.

$$\begin{aligned}3665 &:= (T(3)! + T(6) - F(6)) \times 5 \\36650 &:= (T(3)! + T(6) - F(6)) \times 50 \\366500 &:= (T(3)! + T(6) - F(6)) \times 500 \\3665000 &:= (T(3)! + T(6) - F(6)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

227.

$$\begin{aligned}3666 &:= (C(F(6) + 3) - 6!) \times 6 \\36660 &:= (C(F(6) + 3) - 6!) \times 60 \\366600 &:= (C(F(6) + 3) - 6!) \times 600 \\3666000 &:= (C(F(6) + 3) - 6!) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

228.

$$\begin{aligned}3666 &:= (F(F(3)) + F(-6 + T(6))) \times 6 \\36660 &:= (F(F(3)) + F(-6 + T(6))) \times 60 \\366600 &:= (F(F(3)) + F(-6 + T(6))) \times 600 \\3666000 &:= (F(F(3)) + F(-6 + T(6))) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

229.

$$\begin{aligned}3666 &:= (-T(3)! + C(T(T(6))/T(6))) \times 6 \\36660 &:= (-T(3)! + C(T(T(6))/T(6))) \times 60 \\366600 &:= (-T(3)! + C(T(T(6))/T(6))) \times 600 \\3666000 &:= (-T(3)! + C(T(T(6))/T(6))) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

230.

$$\begin{aligned}3675 &:= (F(3) + 6! + F(7)) \times 5 \\36750 &:= (F(3) + 6! + F(7)) \times 50 \\367500 &:= (F(3) + 6! + F(7)) \times 500 \\3675000 &:= (F(3) + 6! + F(7)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

231.

$$\begin{aligned}3685 &:= (3^6 + 8) \times 5 \\36850 &:= (3^6 + 8) \times 50 \\368500 &:= (3^6 + 8) \times 500 \\3685000 &:= (3^6 + 8) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

232.

$$\begin{aligned}3688 &:= (3!!/Q(6) + Q(F(8))) \times 8 \\36880 &:= (3!!/Q(6) + Q(F(8))) \times 80 \\368800 &:= (3!!/Q(6) + Q(F(8))) \times 800 \\3688000 &:= (3!!/Q(6) + Q(F(8))) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

233.

$$\begin{aligned}3692 &:= (F(T(3)) \times T(T(6)) - F(\sqrt{9})) \times 2 \\36920 &:= (F(T(3)) \times T(T(6)) - F(\sqrt{9})) \times 20 \\369200 &:= (F(T(3)) \times T(T(6)) - F(\sqrt{9})) \times 200 \\3692000 &:= (F(T(3)) \times T(T(6)) - F(\sqrt{9})) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

234.

$$\begin{aligned}3693 &:= (Q(Q(3)) - 6 + Q(F(9))) \times 3 \\36930 &:= (Q(Q(3)) - 6 + Q(F(9))) \times 30 \\369300 &:= (Q(Q(3)) - 6 + Q(F(9))) \times 300 \\3693000 &:= (Q(Q(3)) - 6 + Q(F(9))) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

235.

$$\begin{aligned}3695 &:= (3!! + F(F(6)) - F(\sqrt{9})) \times 5 \\36950 &:= (3!! + F(F(6)) - F(\sqrt{9})) \times 50 \\369500 &:= (3!! + F(F(6)) - F(\sqrt{9})) \times 500 \\3695000 &:= (3!! + F(F(6)) - F(\sqrt{9})) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

236.

$$\begin{aligned}3695 &:= (F(3) + F(6) + C(9)) \times 5 \\36950 &:= (F(3) + F(6) + C(9)) \times 50 \\369500 &:= (F(3) + F(6) + C(9)) \times 500 \\3695000 &:= (F(3) + F(6) + C(9)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

237.

$$\begin{aligned}3695 &:= (F(6 \times F(3)) + T(F(9))) \times 5 \\36950 &:= (F(6 \times F(3)) + T(F(9))) \times 50 \\369500 &:= (F(6 \times F(3)) + T(F(9))) \times 500 \\3695000 &:= (F(6 \times F(3)) + T(F(9))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

238.

$$\begin{aligned}3696 &:= (3! + F(6 + 9)) \times 6 \\36960 &:= (3! + F(6 + 9)) \times 60 \\369600 &:= (3! + F(6 + 9)) \times 600 \\3696000 &:= (3! + F(6 + 9)) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

239.

$$\begin{aligned}3696 &:= (T(3) + F(6 + 9)) \times 6 \\36960 &:= (T(3) + F(6 + 9)) \times 60 \\369600 &:= (T(3) + F(6 + 9)) \times 600 \\3696000 &:= (T(3) + F(6 + 9)) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

240.

$$\begin{aligned}3699 &:= (F(3! + F(6)) + F(9)) \times 9 \\36990 &:= (F(3! + F(6)) + F(9)) \times 90 \\369900 &:= (F(3! + F(6)) + F(9)) \times 900 \\3699000 &:= (F(3! + F(6)) + F(9)) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

241.

$$\begin{aligned}3705 &:= (3!! + F(7 + 0!)) \times 5 \\37050 &:= (3!! + F(7 + 0!)) \times 50 \\370500 &:= (3!! + F(7 + 0!)) \times 500 \\3705000 &:= (3!! + F(7 + 0!)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

242.

$$\begin{aligned}3705 &:= T(37 + 0!) \times 5 \\37050 &:= T(37 + 0!) \times 50 \\370500 &:= T(37 + 0!) \times 500 \\3705000 &:= T(37 + 0!) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

243.

$$\begin{aligned}3710 &:= (T(C(3)) - 7) \times 10 \\37100 &:= (T(C(3)) - 7) \times 100 \\371000 &:= (T(C(3)) - 7) \times 1000 \\3710000 &:= (T(C(3)) - 7) \times 10000\end{aligned}$$

244.

$$\begin{aligned}3722 &:= (F(3!) \times F(F(7)) - F(Q(2))) \times 2 \\37220 &:= (F(3!) \times F(F(7)) - F(Q(2))) \times 20 \\372200 &:= (F(3!) \times F(F(7)) - F(Q(2))) \times 200 \\3722000 &:= (F(3!) \times F(F(7)) - F(Q(2))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

245.

$$\begin{aligned}3722 &:= (F(T(3)) \times F(F(7)) - T(2)) \times 2 \\37220 &:= (F(T(3)) \times F(F(7)) - T(2)) \times 20 \\372200 &:= (F(T(3)) \times F(F(7)) - T(2)) \times 200 \\3722000 &:= (F(T(3)) \times F(F(7)) - T(2)) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

246.

$$\begin{aligned}3722 &:= (Q(3!) + Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(2)!)) \times 2 \\37220 &:= (Q(3!) + Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(2)!)) \times 20 \\372200 &:= (Q(3!) + Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(2)!)) \times 200 \\3722000 &:= (Q(3!) + Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(2)!)) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

247.

$$\begin{aligned}3723 &:= (C(F(3) + 7) + C(C(2))) \times 3 \\37230 &:= (C(F(3) + 7) + C(C(2))) \times 30 \\372300 &:= (C(F(3) + 7) + C(C(2))) \times 300 \\3723000 &:= (C(F(3) + 7) + C(C(2))) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

248.

$$\begin{aligned}3725 &:= (F(3! + 7) + C(C(2))) \times 5 \\37250 &:= (F(3! + 7) + C(C(2))) \times 50 \\372500 &:= (F(3! + 7) + C(C(2))) \times 500 \\3725000 &:= (F(3! + 7) + C(C(2))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

249.

$$\begin{aligned}3725 &:= (T(3)! + T(7) - T(2)) \times 5 \\37250 &:= (T(3)! + T(7) - T(2)) \times 50 \\372500 &:= (T(3)! + T(7) - T(2)) \times 500 \\3725000 &:= (T(3)! + T(7) - T(2)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

250.

$$\begin{aligned}3728 &:= F(T(3) + 7) \times 2 \times 8 \\37280 &:= F(T(3) + 7) \times 2 \times 80 \\372800 &:= F(T(3) + 7) \times 2 \times 800 \\3728000 &:= F(T(3) + 7) \times 2 \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

251.

$$3732 := (C(F(3)) \times F(F(7)) + F(3)) \times 2$$

$$37320 := (C(F(3)) \times F(F(7)) + F(3)) \times 20$$

$$373200 := (C(F(3)) \times F(F(7)) + F(3)) \times 200$$

$$3732000 := (C(F(3)) \times F(F(7)) + F(3)) \times 2000$$

252.

$$3732 := (F(3!) \times F(F(7)) + F(3)) \times 2$$

$$37320 := (F(3!) \times F(F(7)) + F(3)) \times 20$$

$$373200 := (F(3!) \times F(F(7)) + F(3)) \times 200$$

$$3732000 := (F(3!) \times F(F(7)) + F(3)) \times 2000$$

253.

$$3732 := (F(T(3)) \times F(F(7)) + F(3)) \times 2$$

$$37320 := (F(T(3)) \times F(F(7)) + F(3)) \times 20$$

$$373200 := (F(T(3)) \times F(F(7)) + F(3)) \times 200$$

$$3732000 := (F(T(3)) \times F(F(7)) + F(3)) \times 2000$$

254.

$$3735 := (F(Q(3)) + Q(7)) \times Q(3) \times 5$$

$$37350 := (F(Q(3)) + Q(7)) \times Q(3) \times 50$$

$$373500 := (F(Q(3)) + Q(7)) \times Q(3) \times 500$$

$$3735000 := (F(Q(3)) + Q(7)) \times Q(3) \times 5000$$

255.

$$3744 := (C(3 + 7) - C(4)) \times 4$$

$$37440 := (C(3 + 7) - C(4)) \times 40$$

$$374400 := (C(3 + 7) - C(4)) \times 400$$

$$3744000 := (C(3 + 7) - C(4)) \times 4000$$

256.

$$3745 := (F(T(3)) + T(T(7) + T(4))) \times 5$$

$$37450 := (F(T(3)) + T(T(7) + T(4))) \times 50$$

$$374500 := (F(T(3)) + T(T(7) + T(4))) \times 500$$

$$3745000 := (F(T(3)) + T(T(7) + T(4))) \times 5000$$

257.

$$3756 := (-3! + 7 + Q(Q(5))) \times 6$$

$$37560 := (-3! + 7 + Q(Q(5))) \times 60$$

$$375600 := (-3! + 7 + Q(Q(5))) \times 600$$

$$3756000 := (-3! + 7 + Q(Q(5))) \times 6000$$

258.

$$3756 := (3 + F(7) + F(T(5))) \times 6$$

$$37560 := (3 + F(7) + F(T(5))) \times 60$$

$$375600 := (3 + F(7) + F(T(5))) \times 600$$

$$3756000 := (3 + F(7) + F(T(5))) \times 6000$$

259.

$$3756 := (F(Q(3) - 7) + Q(Q(5))) \times 6$$

$$37560 := (F(Q(3) - 7) + Q(Q(5))) \times 60$$

$$375600 := (F(Q(3) - 7) + Q(Q(5))) \times 600$$

$$3756000 := (F(Q(3) - 7) + Q(Q(5))) \times 6000$$

260.

$$3765 := (C(F(3)) + F(F(7)) + C(F(6))) \times 5$$

$$37650 := (C(F(3)) + F(F(7)) + C(F(6))) \times 50$$

$$376500 := (C(F(3)) + F(F(7)) + C(F(6))) \times 500$$

$$3765000 := (C(F(3)) + F(F(7)) + C(F(6))) \times 5000$$

261.

$$\begin{aligned}3768 &:= (3 + F(7) \times T(F(6))) \times 8 \\37680 &:= (3 + F(7) \times T(F(6))) \times 80 \\376800 &:= (3 + F(7) \times T(F(6))) \times 800 \\3768000 &:= (3 + F(7) \times T(F(6))) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

262.

$$\begin{aligned}3768 &:= (T(F(3) + T(7)) + 6) \times 8 \\37680 &:= (T(F(3) + T(7)) + 6) \times 80 \\376800 &:= (T(F(3) + T(7)) + 6) \times 800 \\3768000 &:= (T(F(3) + T(7)) + 6) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

263.

$$\begin{aligned}3768 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + 7!/T(6)) \times 8 \\37680 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + 7!/T(6)) \times 80 \\376800 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + 7!/T(6)) \times 800 \\3768000 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + 7!/T(6)) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

264.

$$\begin{aligned}3774 &:= (F(3) + Q(7)) \times 74 \\37740 &:= (F(3) + Q(7)) \times 740 \\377400 &:= (F(3) + Q(7)) \times 7400 \\3774000 &:= (F(3) + Q(7)) \times 74000\end{aligned}$$

265.

$$\begin{aligned}3775 &:= (T(3)! + T(7) + 7) \times 5 \\37750 &:= (T(3)! + T(7) + 7) \times 50 \\377500 &:= (T(3)! + T(7) + 7) \times 500 \\3775000 &:= (T(3)! + T(7) + 7) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

266.

$$\begin{aligned}3782 &:= T(-3 + T(7) + T(8)) \times 2 \\37820 &:= T(-3 + T(7) + T(8)) \times 20 \\378200 &:= T(-3 + T(7) + T(8)) \times 200 \\3782000 &:= T(-3 + T(7) + T(8)) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

267.

$$\begin{aligned}3783 &:= (T(T(3) + T(7)) + T(T(8))) \times 3 \\37830 &:= (T(T(3) + T(7)) + T(T(8))) \times 30 \\378300 &:= (T(T(3) + T(7)) + T(T(8))) \times 300 \\3783000 &:= (T(T(3) + T(7)) + T(T(8))) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

268.

$$\begin{aligned}3785 &:= (T(T(3) + 7) + T(T(8))) \times 5 \\37850 &:= (T(T(3) + 7) + T(T(8))) \times 50 \\378500 &:= (T(T(3) + 7) + T(T(8))) \times 500 \\3785000 &:= (T(T(3) + 7) + T(T(8))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

269.

$$\begin{aligned}3786 &:= (F(F(3) + F(7)) + F(8)) \times 6 \\37860 &:= (F(F(3) + F(7)) + F(8)) \times 60 \\378600 &:= (F(F(3) + F(7)) + F(8)) \times 600 \\3786000 &:= (F(F(3) + F(7)) + F(8)) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

270.

$$\begin{aligned}3789 &:= (T(T(3)) + T(T(7)) - \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 9 \\37890 &:= (T(T(3)) + T(T(7)) - \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 90 \\378900 &:= (T(T(3)) + T(T(7)) - \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 900 \\3789000 &:= (T(T(3)) + T(T(7)) - \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

271.

$$\begin{aligned} 3795 &:= (3!! + F(7) \times \sqrt{9}) \times 5 \\ 37950 &:= (3!! + F(7) \times \sqrt{9}) \times 50 \\ 379500 &:= (3!! + F(7) \times \sqrt{9}) \times 500 \\ 3795000 &:= (3!! + F(7) \times \sqrt{9}) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

272.

$$\begin{aligned} 3795 &:= (C(3) \times T(7) + \sqrt{9}) \times 5 \\ 37950 &:= (C(3) \times T(7) + \sqrt{9}) \times 50 \\ 379500 &:= (C(3) \times T(7) + \sqrt{9}) \times 500 \\ 3795000 &:= (C(3) \times T(7) + \sqrt{9}) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

273.

$$\begin{aligned} 3804 &:= (T(3)! + T(F(8))) \times 4 \\ 38040 &:= (T(3)! + T(F(8))) \times 40 \\ 380400 &:= (T(3)! + T(F(8))) \times 400 \\ 3804000 &:= (T(3)! + T(F(8))) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

274.

$$\begin{aligned} 3816 &:= (T(3) + T(T(8) - 1)) \times 6 \\ 38160 &:= (T(3) + T(T(8) - 1)) \times 60 \\ 381600 &:= (T(3) + T(T(8) - 1)) \times 600 \\ 3816000 &:= (T(3) + T(T(8) - 1)) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

275.

$$\begin{aligned} 3822 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 8) \times T(T(T(2))) \times 2 \\ 38220 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 8) \times T(T(T(2))) \times 20 \\ 382200 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 8) \times T(T(T(2))) \times 200 \\ 3822000 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 8) \times T(T(T(2))) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

276.

$$\begin{aligned} 3842 &:= (F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 2 \\ 38420 &:= (F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 20 \\ 384200 &:= (F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 200 \\ 3842000 &:= (F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

277.

$$\begin{aligned} 3842 &:= (F(3)!/F(8) + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 2 \\ 38420 &:= (F(3)!/F(8) + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 20 \\ 384200 &:= (F(3)!/F(8) + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 200 \\ 3842000 &:= (F(3)!/F(8) + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

278.

$$\begin{aligned} 3843 &:= (T(3)! + T(T(8) - F(4))) \times 3 \\ 38430 &:= (T(3)! + T(T(8) - F(4))) \times 30 \\ 384300 &:= (T(3)! + T(T(8) - F(4))) \times 300 \\ 3843000 &:= (T(3)! + T(T(8) - F(4))) \times 3000 \end{aligned}$$

279.

$$\begin{aligned} 3845 &:= (T(3)! - \sqrt{T(8)} + T(T(4))) \times 5 \\ 38450 &:= (T(3)! - \sqrt{T(8)} + T(T(4))) \times 50 \\ 384500 &:= (T(3)! - \sqrt{T(8)} + T(T(4))) \times 500 \\ 3845000 &:= (T(3)! - \sqrt{T(8)} + T(T(4))) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

280.

$$\begin{aligned} 3846 &:= (Q(Q(-3 + 8)) + Q(4)) \times 6 \\ 38460 &:= (Q(Q(-3 + 8)) + Q(4)) \times 60 \\ 384600 &:= (Q(Q(-3 + 8)) + Q(4)) \times 600 \\ 3846000 &:= (Q(Q(-3 + 8)) + Q(4)) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

281.

$$\begin{aligned}3848 &:= (-T(T(T(3))) - 8 + (T(T(\sqrt{4})))!) \times 8 \\38480 &:= (-T(T(T(3))) - 8 + (T(T(\sqrt{4})))!) \times 80 \\384800 &:= (-T(T(T(3))) - 8 + (T(T(\sqrt{4})))!) \times 800 \\3848000 &:= (-T(T(T(3))) - 8 + (T(T(\sqrt{4})))!) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

282.

$$\begin{aligned}3855 &:= (T(3)! + T(8) + T(5)) \times 5 \\38550 &:= (T(3)! + T(8) + T(5)) \times 50 \\385500 &:= (T(3)! + T(8) + T(5)) \times 500 \\3855000 &:= (T(3)! + T(8) + T(5)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

283.

$$\begin{aligned}3855 &:= (T(T(3)) \times T(8) + T(5)) \times 5 \\38550 &:= (T(T(3)) \times T(8) + T(5)) \times 50 \\385500 &:= (T(T(3)) \times T(8) + T(5)) \times 500 \\3855000 &:= (T(T(3)) \times T(8) + T(5)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

284.

$$\begin{aligned}3857 &:= (Q(3 \times 8) - Q(5)) \times 7 \\38570 &:= (Q(3 \times 8) - Q(5)) \times 70 \\385700 &:= (Q(3 \times 8) - Q(5)) \times 700 \\3857000 &:= (Q(3 \times 8) - Q(5)) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

285.

$$\begin{aligned}3872 &:= Q(3 - 8 + Q(7)) \times 2 \\38720 &:= Q(3 - 8 + Q(7)) \times 20 \\387200 &:= Q(3 - 8 + Q(7)) \times 200 \\3872000 &:= Q(3 - 8 + Q(7)) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

286.

$$\begin{aligned}3875 &:= (T(3)! - T(8) + T(F(7))) \times 5 \\38750 &:= (T(3)! - T(8) + T(F(7))) \times 50 \\387500 &:= (T(3)! - T(8) + T(F(7))) \times 500 \\3875000 &:= (T(3)! - T(8) + T(F(7))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

287.

$$\begin{aligned}3876 &:= (T(Q(3)) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 76 \\38760 &:= (T(Q(3)) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 760 \\387600 &:= (T(Q(3)) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 7600 \\3876000 &:= (T(Q(3)) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 76000\end{aligned}$$

288.

$$\begin{aligned}3882 &:= (F(F(3!)) + 8!/F(8)) \times 2 \\38820 &:= (F(F(3!)) + 8!/F(8)) \times 20 \\388200 &:= (F(F(3!)) + 8!/F(8)) \times 200 \\3882000 &:= (F(F(3!)) + 8!/F(8)) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

289.

$$\begin{aligned}3885 &:= (T(38) + T(8)) \times 5 \\38850 &:= (T(38) + T(8)) \times 50 \\388500 &:= (T(38) + T(8)) \times 500 \\3885000 &:= (T(38) + T(8)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

290.

$$\begin{aligned}3903 &:= (Q(Q(3!)) + (\sqrt{9})! - 0!) \times 3 \\39030 &:= (Q(Q(3!)) + (\sqrt{9})! - 0!) \times 30 \\390300 &:= (Q(Q(3!)) + (\sqrt{9})! - 0!) \times 300 \\3903000 &:= (Q(Q(3!)) + (\sqrt{9})! - 0!) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

291.

$$3905 := (T(39) + 0!) \times 5$$

$$39050 := (T(39) + 0!) \times 50$$

$$390500 := (T(39) + 0!) \times 500$$

$$3905000 := (T(39) + 0!) \times 5000$$

292.

$$3906 := (T(T(3)) + T(F(9) + 0!)) \times 6$$

$$39060 := (T(T(3)) + T(F(9) + 0!)) \times 60$$

$$390600 := (T(T(3)) + T(F(9) + 0!)) \times 600$$

$$3906000 := (T(T(3)) + T(F(9) + 0!)) \times 6000$$

293.

$$3915 := (C(T(3)) + T(9)) \times 15$$

$$39150 := (C(T(3)) + T(9)) \times 150$$

$$391500 := (C(T(3)) + T(9)) \times 1500$$

$$3915000 := (C(T(3)) + T(9)) \times 15000$$

294.

$$3922 := (3!! + C(9) + C(C(2))) \times 2$$

$$39220 := (3!! + C(9) + C(C(2))) \times 20$$

$$392200 := (3!! + C(9) + C(C(2))) \times 200$$

$$3922000 := (3!! + C(9) + C(C(2))) \times 2000$$

295.

$$3924 := (-3! + F(2 \times F((\sqrt{9})!))) \times 4$$

$$39240 := (-3! + F(2 \times F((\sqrt{9})!))) \times 40$$

$$392400 := (-3! + F(2 \times F((\sqrt{9})!))) \times 400$$

$$3924000 := (-3! + F(2 \times F((\sqrt{9})!))) \times 4000$$

296.

$$3927 := (-3! - 9 + Q(Q(2)!)) \times 7$$

$$39270 := (-3! - 9 + Q(Q(2)!)) \times 70$$

$$392700 := (-3! - 9 + Q(Q(2)!)) \times 700$$

$$3927000 := (-3! - 9 + Q(Q(2)!)) \times 7000$$

297.

$$3927 := T(3 \times (9 + 2)) \times 7$$

$$39270 := T(3 \times (9 + 2)) \times 70$$

$$392700 := T(3 \times (9 + 2)) \times 700$$

$$3927000 := T(3 \times (9 + 2)) \times 7000$$

298.

$$3928 := (-C(3) + (\sqrt{9})! + C(C(2))) \times 8$$

$$39280 := (-C(3) + (\sqrt{9})! + C(C(2))) \times 80$$

$$392800 := (-C(3) + (\sqrt{9})! + C(C(2))) \times 800$$

$$3928000 := (-C(3) + (\sqrt{9})! + C(C(2))) \times 8000$$

299.

$$3928 := (-C(3) + T(\sqrt{9}) + C(C(2))) \times 8$$

$$39280 := (-C(3) + T(\sqrt{9}) + C(C(2))) \times 80$$

$$392800 := (-C(3) + T(\sqrt{9}) + C(C(2))) \times 800$$

$$3928000 := (-C(3) + T(\sqrt{9}) + C(C(2))) \times 8000$$

300.

$$3928 := (F(3)^9 - F(C(2))) \times 8$$

$$39280 := (F(3)^9 - F(C(2))) \times 80$$

$$392800 := (F(3)^9 - F(C(2))) \times 800$$

$$3928000 := (F(3)^9 - F(C(2))) \times 8000$$

301.

$$3928 := (-T(T(T(3))) + T(\sqrt{9})! + 2) \times 8$$

$$39280 := (-T(T(T(3))) + T(\sqrt{9})! + 2) \times 80$$

$$392800 := (-T(T(T(3))) + T(\sqrt{9})! + 2) \times 800$$

$$3928000 := (-T(T(T(3))) + T(\sqrt{9})! + 2) \times 8000$$

302.

$$3933 := (T(3) + Q(T(9)) - T(3)!) \times 3$$

$$39330 := (T(3) + Q(T(9)) - T(3)!) \times 30$$

$$393300 := (T(3) + Q(T(9)) - T(3)!) \times 300$$

$$3933000 := (T(3) + Q(T(9)) - T(3)!) \times 3000$$

303.

$$3935 := (3 + Q(F(9) - 3!)) \times 5$$

$$39350 := (3 + Q(F(9) - 3!)) \times 50$$

$$393500 := (3 + Q(F(9) - 3!)) \times 500$$

$$3935000 := (3 + Q(F(9) - 3!)) \times 5000$$

304.

$$3936 := (-F(3)^{(\sqrt{9})!} + 3!!) \times 6$$

$$39360 := (-F(3)^{(\sqrt{9})!} + 3!!) \times 60$$

$$393600 := (-F(3)^{(\sqrt{9})!} + 3!!) \times 600$$

$$3936000 := (-F(3)^{(\sqrt{9})!} + 3!!) \times 6000$$

305.

$$3944 := (-F(F(3)) + F(F(\sqrt{9})^4)) \times 4$$

$$39440 := (-F(F(3)) + F(F(\sqrt{9})^4)) \times 40$$

$$394400 := (-F(F(3)) + F(F(\sqrt{9})^4)) \times 400$$

$$3944000 := (-F(F(3)) + F(F(\sqrt{9})^4)) \times 4000$$

306.

$$3944 := (T(3) + T(T(9)) - F(T(4))) \times 4$$

$$39440 := (T(3) + T(T(9)) - F(T(4))) \times 40$$

$$394400 := (T(3) + T(T(9)) - F(T(4))) \times 400$$

$$3944000 := (T(3) + T(T(9)) - F(T(4))) \times 4000$$

307.

$$3944 := (T(3) + T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) \times 4$$

$$39440 := (T(3) + T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) \times 40$$

$$394400 := (T(3) + T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) \times 400$$

$$3944000 := (T(3) + T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) \times 4000$$

308.

$$3945 := (T(3)! + T(9) + 4!) \times 5$$

$$39450 := (T(3)! + T(9) + 4!) \times 50$$

$$394500 := (T(3)! + T(9) + 4!) \times 500$$

$$3945000 := (T(3)! + T(9) + 4!) \times 5000$$

309.

$$3955 := (T(C(3) + 9) + C(5)) \times 5$$

$$39550 := (T(C(3) + 9) + C(5)) \times 50$$

$$395500 := (T(C(3) + 9) + C(5)) \times 500$$

$$3955000 := (T(C(3) + 9) + C(5)) \times 5000$$

310.

$$3960 := (T(T(3)) + T(9)) \times 60$$

$$39600 := (T(T(3)) + T(9)) \times 600$$

$$396000 := (T(T(3)) + T(9)) \times 6000$$

$$3960000 := (T(T(3)) + T(9)) \times 60000$$

311.

$$3960 := T(F(3) + 9) \times 60$$

$$39600 := T(F(3) + 9) \times 600$$

$$396000 := T(F(3) + 9) \times 6000$$

$$3960000 := T(F(3) + 9) \times 60000$$

312.

$$3965 := (C(3) + F(9)) \times 65$$

$$39650 := (C(3) + F(9)) \times 650$$

$$396500 := (C(3) + F(9)) \times 6500$$

$$3965000 := (C(3) + F(9)) \times 65000$$

313.

$$3968 := T((T(T(T(3))) - T(9))/6) \times 8$$

$$39680 := T((T(T(T(3))) - T(9))/6) \times 80$$

$$396800 := T((T(T(T(3))) - T(9))/6) \times 800$$

$$3968000 := T((T(T(T(3))) - T(9))/6) \times 8000$$

314.

$$3968 := T(3 + F(9) - 6) \times 8$$

$$39680 := T(3 + F(9) - 6) \times 80$$

$$396800 := T(3 + F(9) - 6) \times 800$$

$$3968000 := T(3 + F(9) - 6) \times 8000$$

315.

$$3969 := F(F(-3 + 9)) \times F(F(6)) \times 9$$

$$39690 := F(F(-3 + 9)) \times F(F(6)) \times 90$$

$$396900 := F(F(-3 + 9)) \times F(F(6)) \times 900$$

$$3969000 := F(F(-3 + 9)) \times F(F(6)) \times 9000$$

316.

$$3969 := T(-3 + 9) \times T(6) \times 9$$

$$39690 := T(-3 + 9) \times T(6) \times 90$$

$$396900 := T(-3 + 9) \times T(6) \times 900$$

$$3969000 := T(-3 + 9) \times T(6) \times 9000$$

317.

$$3975 := (F(T(3)) + T(9)) \times 75$$

$$39750 := (F(T(3)) + T(9)) \times 750$$

$$397500 := (F(T(3)) + T(9)) \times 7500$$

$$3975000 := (F(T(3)) + T(9)) \times 75000$$

318.

$$3978 := (T(3) + T(9)) \times 78$$

$$39780 := (T(3) + T(9)) \times 780$$

$$397800 := (T(3) + T(9)) \times 7800$$

$$3978000 := (T(3) + T(9)) \times 78000$$

319.

$$3995 := (3!! - F(\sqrt{9}) + Q(9)) \times 5$$

$$39950 := (3!! - F(\sqrt{9}) + Q(9)) \times 50$$

$$399500 := (3!! - F(\sqrt{9}) + Q(9)) \times 500$$

$$3995000 := (3!! - F(\sqrt{9}) + Q(9)) \times 5000$$

320.

$$3995 := (T(3)! + F(9) + T(9)) \times 5$$

$$39950 := (T(3)! + F(9) + T(9)) \times 50$$

$$399500 := (T(3)! + F(9) + T(9)) \times 500$$

$$3995000 := (T(3)! + F(9) + T(9)) \times 5000$$

321.

$$\begin{aligned}3995 &:= (T(3) \times F(9) + T(F(9))) \times 5 \\39950 &:= (T(3) \times F(9) + T(F(9))) \times 50 \\399500 &:= (T(3) \times F(9) + T(F(9))) \times 500 \\3995000 &:= (T(3) \times F(9) + T(F(9))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

322.

$$\begin{aligned}3996 &:= T(3 \times 9 + 9) \times 6 \\39960 &:= T(3 \times 9 + 9) \times 60 \\399600 &:= T(3 \times 9 + 9) \times 600 \\3996000 &:= T(3 \times 9 + 9) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

323.

$$\begin{aligned}3997 &:= (T(T(3)) + T(F(9)) - T(9)) \times 7 \\39970 &:= (T(T(3)) + T(F(9)) - T(9)) \times 70 \\399700 &:= (T(T(3)) + T(F(9)) - T(9)) \times 700 \\3997000 &:= (T(T(3)) + T(F(9)) - T(9)) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

324.

$$\begin{aligned}4004 &:= (C(T(4)) + 0!) \times 4 \\40040 &:= (C(T(4)) + 0!) \times 40 \\400400 &:= (C(T(4)) + 0!) \times 400 \\4004000 &:= (C(T(4)) + 0!) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

325.

$$\begin{aligned}4023 &:= (-Q(Q(4)) + F(0! + Q(Q(2)))) \times 3 \\40230 &:= (-Q(Q(4)) + F(0! + Q(Q(2)))) \times 30 \\402300 &:= (-Q(Q(4)) + F(0! + Q(Q(2)))) \times 300 \\4023000 &:= (-Q(Q(4)) + F(0! + Q(Q(2)))) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

326.

$$\begin{aligned}4040 &:= (Q(T(4)) + 0!) \times 40 \\40400 &:= (Q(T(4)) + 0!) \times 400 \\404000 &:= (Q(T(4)) + 0!) \times 4000 \\4040000 &:= (Q(T(4)) + 0!) \times 40000\end{aligned}$$

327.

$$\begin{aligned}4044 &:= (4! + F(Q(4))) \times 4 \\40440 &:= (4! + F(Q(4))) \times 40 \\404400 &:= (4! + F(Q(4))) \times 400 \\4044000 &:= (4! + F(Q(4))) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

328.

$$\begin{aligned}4044 &:= (C(T(4)) + 0! + T(4)) \times 4 \\40440 &:= (C(T(4)) + 0! + T(4)) \times 40 \\404400 &:= (C(T(4)) + 0! + T(4)) \times 400 \\4044000 &:= (C(T(4)) + 0! + T(4)) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

329.

$$\begin{aligned}4044 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - Q(-0! + 4!)) \times 4 \\40440 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - Q(-0! + 4!)) \times 40 \\404400 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - Q(-0! + 4!)) \times 400 \\4044000 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - Q(-0! + 4!)) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

330.

$$\begin{aligned}4044 &:= (T(T(T(4) - 0!)) - 4!) \times 4 \\40440 &:= (T(T(T(4) - 0!)) - 4!) \times 40 \\404400 &:= (T(T(T(4) - 0!)) - 4!) \times 400 \\4044000 &:= (T(T(T(4) - 0!)) - 4!) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

331.

$$\begin{aligned} 4050 &:= Q(Q(4 - 0!)) \times 50 \\ 40500 &:= Q(Q(4 - 0!)) \times 500 \\ 405000 &:= Q(Q(4 - 0!)) \times 5000 \\ 4050000 &:= Q(Q(4 - 0!)) \times 50000 \end{aligned}$$

332.

$$\begin{aligned} 4050 &:= Q(Q(\sqrt{4} + 0!)) \times 50 \\ 40500 &:= Q(Q(\sqrt{4} + 0!)) \times 500 \\ 405000 &:= Q(Q(\sqrt{4} + 0!)) \times 5000 \\ 4050000 &:= Q(Q(\sqrt{4} + 0!)) \times 50000 \end{aligned}$$

333.

$$\begin{aligned} 4050 &:= Q(T(4) - 0!) \times 50 \\ 40500 &:= Q(T(4) - 0!) \times 500 \\ 405000 &:= Q(T(4) - 0!) \times 5000 \\ 4050000 &:= Q(T(4) - 0!) \times 50000 \end{aligned}$$

334.

$$\begin{aligned} 4056 &:= (T(T(4) + 0!) + F(T(5))) \times 6 \\ 40560 &:= (T(T(4) + 0!) + F(T(5))) \times 60 \\ 405600 &:= (T(T(4) + 0!) + F(T(5))) \times 600 \\ 4056000 &:= (T(T(4) + 0!) + F(T(5))) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

335.

$$\begin{aligned} 4056 &:= Q((4 \times 0!) + Q(5)) \times 6 \\ 40560 &:= Q((4 \times 0!) + Q(5)) \times 60 \\ 405600 &:= Q((4 \times 0!) + Q(5)) \times 600 \\ 4056000 &:= Q((4 \times 0!) + Q(5)) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

336.

$$\begin{aligned} 4059 &:= (Q(T(4)) + T(Q(5) + 0!)) \times 9 \\ 40590 &:= (Q(T(4)) + T(Q(5) + 0!)) \times 90 \\ 405900 &:= (Q(T(4)) + T(Q(5) + 0!)) \times 900 \\ 4059000 &:= (Q(T(4)) + T(Q(5) + 0!)) \times 9000 \end{aligned}$$

337.

$$\begin{aligned} 4067 &:= (Q(4!) - 0! + 6) \times 7 \\ 40670 &:= (Q(4!) - 0! + 6) \times 70 \\ 406700 &:= (Q(4!) - 0! + 6) \times 700 \\ 4067000 &:= (Q(4!) - 0! + 6) \times 7000 \end{aligned}$$

338.

$$\begin{aligned} 4082 &:= (Q(40) + Q(F(8))) \times 2 \\ 40820 &:= (Q(40) + Q(F(8))) \times 20 \\ 408200 &:= (Q(40) + Q(F(8))) \times 200 \\ 4082000 &:= (Q(40) + Q(F(8))) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

339.

$$\begin{aligned} 4084 &:= (F(Q(4)) + F(0! + 8)) \times 4 \\ 40840 &:= (F(Q(4)) + F(0! + 8)) \times 40 \\ 408400 &:= (F(Q(4)) + F(0! + 8)) \times 400 \\ 4084000 &:= (F(Q(4)) + F(0! + 8)) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

340.

$$\begin{aligned} 4084 &:= (T(4!) + 0! + (\sqrt{T(8)!})) \times 4 \\ 40840 &:= (T(4!) + 0! + (\sqrt{T(8)!})) \times 40 \\ 408400 &:= (T(4!) + 0! + (\sqrt{T(8)!})) \times 400 \\ 4084000 &:= (T(4!) + 0! + (\sqrt{T(8)!})) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

341.

$$\begin{aligned}4086 &:= (Q(4) - 0! + T(T(8))) \times 6 \\40860 &:= (Q(4) - 0! + T(T(8))) \times 60 \\408600 &:= (Q(4) - 0! + T(T(8))) \times 600 \\4086000 &:= (Q(4) - 0! + T(T(8))) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

342.

$$\begin{aligned}4086 &:= (T(0! + 4) + T(T(8))) \times 6 \\40860 &:= (T(0! + 4) + T(T(8))) \times 60 \\408600 &:= (T(0! + 4) + T(T(8))) \times 600 \\4086000 &:= (T(0! + 4) + T(T(8))) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

343.

$$\begin{aligned}4128 &:= (4 + C(C(2))) \times 8 \\41280 &:= (4 + C(C(2))) \times 80 \\412800 &:= (4 + C(C(2))) \times 800 \\4128000 &:= (4 + C(C(2))) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

344.

$$\begin{aligned}4137 &:= (Q(4!) + T(-1 + T(3))) \times 7 \\41370 &:= (Q(4!) + T(-1 + T(3))) \times 70 \\413700 &:= (Q(4!) + T(-1 + T(3))) \times 700 \\4137000 &:= (Q(4!) + T(-1 + T(3))) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

345.

$$\begin{aligned}4137 &:= (Q(Q(4+1)) - F(Q(3))) \times 7 \\41370 &:= (Q(Q(4+1)) - F(Q(3))) \times 70 \\413700 &:= (Q(Q(4+1)) - F(Q(3))) \times 700 \\4137000 &:= (Q(Q(4+1)) - F(Q(3))) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

346.

$$\begin{aligned}4141 &:= (Q(T(4)) + 1) \times 41 \\41410 &:= (Q(T(4)) + 1) \times 410 \\414100 &:= (Q(T(4)) + 1) \times 4100 \\4141000 &:= (Q(T(4)) + 1) \times 41000\end{aligned}$$

347.

$$\begin{aligned}4142 &:= (-T(4) + 1 + T(C(4))) \times 2 \\41420 &:= (-T(4) + 1 + T(C(4))) \times 20 \\414200 &:= (-T(4) + 1 + T(C(4))) \times 200 \\4142000 &:= (-T(4) + 1 + T(C(4))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

348.

$$\begin{aligned}4143 &:= (Q(41) - T(4!)) \times 3 \\41430 &:= (Q(41) - T(4!)) \times 30 \\414300 &:= (Q(41) - T(4!)) \times 300 \\4143000 &:= (Q(41) - T(4!)) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

349.

$$\begin{aligned}4144 &:= (F(F(F(4))) + T(T(T(4) - 1))) \times 4 \\41440 &:= (F(F(F(4))) + T(T(T(4) - 1))) \times 40 \\414400 &:= (F(F(F(4))) + T(T(T(4) - 1))) \times 400 \\4144000 &:= (F(F(F(4))) + T(T(T(4) - 1))) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

350.

$$\begin{aligned}4144 &:= (F(\sqrt{4}) + T(T(T(4) - 1))) \times 4 \\41440 &:= (F(\sqrt{4}) + T(T(T(4) - 1))) \times 40 \\414400 &:= (F(\sqrt{4}) + T(T(T(4) - 1))) \times 400 \\4144000 &:= (F(\sqrt{4}) + T(T(T(4) - 1))) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

351.

$$\begin{aligned}4145 &:= (T(4!) + Q(-1 + 4!)) \times 5 \\41450 &:= (T(4!) + Q(-1 + 4!)) \times 50 \\414500 &:= (T(4!) + Q(-1 + 4!)) \times 500 \\4145000 &:= (T(4!) + Q(-1 + 4!)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

352.

$$\begin{aligned}4152 &:= (T(C(4)) + 1 - 5) \times 2 \\41520 &:= (T(C(4)) + 1 - 5) \times 20 \\415200 &:= (T(C(4)) + 1 - 5) \times 200 \\4152000 &:= (T(C(4)) + 1 - 5) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

353.

$$\begin{aligned}4164 &:= (T(T(T(4) - 1)) + 6) \times 4 \\41640 &:= (T(T(T(4) - 1)) + 6) \times 40 \\416400 &:= (T(T(T(4) - 1)) + 6) \times 400 \\4164000 &:= (T(T(T(4) - 1)) + 6) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

354.

$$\begin{aligned}4172 &:= (T(41) + T(Q(7))) \times 2 \\41720 &:= (T(41) + T(Q(7))) \times 20 \\417200 &:= (T(41) + T(Q(7))) \times 200 \\4172000 &:= (T(41) + T(Q(7))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

355.

$$\begin{aligned}4172 &:= (T(C(4)) - (1 - 7)) \times 2 \\41720 &:= (T(C(4)) - (1 - 7)) \times 20 \\417200 &:= (T(C(4)) - (1 - 7)) \times 200 \\4172000 &:= (T(C(4)) - (1 - 7)) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

356.

$$\begin{aligned}4176 &:= (-4! + (-1 + 7!)) \times 6 \\41760 &:= (-4! + (-1 + 7!)) \times 60 \\417600 &:= (-4! + (-1 + 7!)) \times 600 \\4176000 &:= (-4! + (-1 + 7!)) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

357.

$$\begin{aligned}4182 &:= (T(4) + 1 + T(Q(8))) \times 2 \\41820 &:= (T(4) + 1 + T(Q(8))) \times 20 \\418200 &:= (T(4) + 1 + T(Q(8))) \times 200 \\4182000 &:= (T(4) + 1 + T(Q(8))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

358.

$$\begin{aligned}4185 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - T(1 + T(8))) \times 5 \\41850 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - T(1 + T(8))) \times 50 \\418500 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - T(1 + T(8))) \times 500 \\4185000 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - T(1 + T(8))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

359.

$$\begin{aligned}4202 &:= (T(C(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 2 \\42020 &:= (T(C(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 20 \\420200 &:= (T(C(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 200 \\4202000 &:= (T(C(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

360.

$$\begin{aligned}4205 &:= Q(4! + Q(2) + 0!) \times 5 \\42050 &:= Q(4! + Q(2) + 0!) \times 50 \\420500 &:= Q(4! + Q(2) + 0!) \times 500 \\4205000 &:= Q(4! + Q(2) + 0!) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

361.

$$4206 := (Q(4!) + C(Q(2) + 0!)) \times 6$$

$$42060 := (Q(4!) + C(Q(2) + 0!)) \times 60$$

$$420600 := (Q(4!) + C(Q(2) + 0!)) \times 600$$

$$4206000 := (Q(4!) + C(Q(2) + 0!)) \times 6000$$

362.

$$4207 := (Q(4!) + Q(Q(2) + 0!)) \times 7$$

$$42070 := (Q(4!) + Q(Q(2) + 0!)) \times 70$$

$$420700 := (Q(4!) + Q(Q(2) + 0!)) \times 700$$

$$4207000 := (Q(4!) + Q(Q(2) + 0!)) \times 7000$$

363.

$$4207 := (T(4!) \times 2 + 0!) \times 7$$

$$42070 := (T(4!) \times 2 + 0!) \times 70$$

$$420700 := (T(4!) \times 2 + 0!) \times 700$$

$$4207000 := (T(4!) \times 2 + 0!) \times 7000$$

364.

$$4212 := T(4! + 2) \times 12$$

$$42120 := T(4! + 2) \times 120$$

$$421200 := T(4! + 2) \times 1200$$

$$4212000 := T(4! + 2) \times 12000$$

365.

$$4214 := (T(4!) + F(2)) \times 14$$

$$42140 := (T(4!) + F(2)) \times 140$$

$$421400 := (T(4!) + F(2)) \times 1400$$

$$4214000 := (T(4!) + F(2)) \times 14000$$

366.

$$4232 := 4 \times Q(23) \times 2$$

$$42320 := 4 \times Q(23) \times 20$$

$$423200 := 4 \times Q(23) \times 200$$

$$4232000 := 4 \times Q(23) \times 2000$$

367.

$$4236 := (-Q(4) + 2 + 3!!) \times 6$$

$$42360 := (-Q(4) + 2 + 3!!) \times 60$$

$$423600 := (-Q(4) + 2 + 3!!) \times 600$$

$$4236000 := (-Q(4) + 2 + 3!!) \times 6000$$

368.

$$4239 := (T(4!) + T(T(2) \times T(3))) \times 9$$

$$42390 := (T(4!) + T(T(2) \times T(3))) \times 90$$

$$423900 := (T(4!) + T(T(2) \times T(3))) \times 900$$

$$4239000 := (T(4!) + T(T(2) \times T(3))) \times 9000$$

369.

$$4239 := (T(T(4) \times T(2)) + T(3)) \times 9$$

$$42390 := (T(T(4) \times T(2)) + T(3)) \times 90$$

$$423900 := (T(T(4) \times T(2)) + T(3)) \times 900$$

$$4239000 := (T(T(4) \times T(2)) + T(3)) \times 9000$$

370.

$$4240 := (Q(T(4)) + T(T(2))) \times 40$$

$$42400 := (Q(T(4)) + T(T(2))) \times 400$$

$$424000 := (Q(T(4)) + T(T(2))) \times 4000$$

$$4240000 := (Q(T(4)) + T(T(2))) \times 40000$$

371.

$$4248 := (C(F(4)) + C(C(2)) - \sqrt{C(4)}) \times 8$$

$$42480 := (C(F(4)) + C(C(2)) - \sqrt{C(4)}) \times 80$$

$$424800 := (C(F(4)) + C(C(2)) - \sqrt{C(4)}) \times 800$$

$$4248000 := (C(F(4)) + C(C(2)) - \sqrt{C(4)}) \times 8000$$

372.

$$4248 := (T(4!) + T(T(2+4))) \times 8$$

$$42480 := (T(4!) + T(T(2+4))) \times 80$$

$$424800 := (T(4!) + T(T(2+4))) \times 800$$

$$4248000 := (T(4!) + T(T(2+4))) \times 8000$$

373.

$$4255 := (F(Q(4)) - Q(Q(2)) - 5!) \times 5$$

$$42550 := (F(Q(4)) - Q(Q(2)) - 5!) \times 50$$

$$425500 := (F(Q(4)) - Q(Q(2)) - 5!) \times 500$$

$$4255000 := (F(Q(4)) - Q(Q(2)) - 5!) \times 5000$$

374.

$$4255 := (T(4) + Q(Q(2) + Q(5))) \times 5$$

$$42550 := (T(4) + Q(Q(2) + Q(5))) \times 50$$

$$425500 := (T(4) + Q(Q(2) + Q(5))) \times 500$$

$$4255000 := (T(4) + Q(Q(2) + Q(5))) \times 5000$$

375.

$$4256 := (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 56$$

$$42560 := (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 560$$

$$425600 := (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 5600$$

$$4256000 := (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 56000$$

376.

$$4260 := (T(T(4)) + Q(Q(2))) \times 60$$

$$42600 := (T(T(4)) + Q(Q(2))) \times 600$$

$$426000 := (T(T(4)) + Q(Q(2))) \times 6000$$

$$4260000 := (T(T(4)) + Q(Q(2))) \times 60000$$

377.

$$4270 := (F(T(4)) + T(T(2))) \times 70$$

$$42700 := (F(T(4)) + T(T(2))) \times 700$$

$$427000 := (F(T(4)) + T(T(2))) \times 7000$$

$$4270000 := (F(T(4)) + T(T(2))) \times 70000$$

378.

$$4270 := (-T(2) + C(4)) \times 70$$

$$42700 := (-T(2) + C(4)) \times 700$$

$$427000 := (-T(2) + C(4)) \times 7000$$

$$4270000 := (-T(2) + C(4)) \times 70000$$

379.

$$4270 := (T(T(4)) + T(T(2))) \times 70$$

$$42700 := (T(T(4)) + T(T(2))) \times 700$$

$$427000 := (T(T(4)) + T(T(2))) \times 7000$$

$$4270000 := (T(T(4)) + T(T(2))) \times 70000$$

380.

$$4275 := (C(4 \times 2) + C(7)) \times 5$$

$$42750 := (C(4 \times 2) + C(7)) \times 50$$

$$427500 := (C(4 \times 2) + C(7)) \times 500$$

$$4275000 := (C(4 \times 2) + C(7)) \times 5000$$

381.

$$\begin{aligned} 4275 &:= (F(T(4)) + 2) \times 75 \\ 42750 &:= (F(T(4)) + 2) \times 750 \\ 427500 &:= (F(T(4)) + 2) \times 7500 \\ 4275000 &:= (F(T(4)) + 2) \times 75000 \end{aligned}$$

382.

$$\begin{aligned} 4275 &:= (T(T(4)) + 2) \times 75 \\ 42750 &:= (T(T(4)) + 2) \times 750 \\ 427500 &:= (T(T(4)) + 2) \times 7500 \\ 4275000 &:= (T(T(4)) + 2) \times 75000 \end{aligned}$$

383.

$$\begin{aligned} 4277 &:= (F(F(F(4))) + F(2 + F(7))) \times 7 \\ 42770 &:= (F(F(F(4))) + F(2 + F(7))) \times 70 \\ 427700 &:= (F(F(F(4))) + F(2 + F(7))) \times 700 \\ 4277000 &:= (F(F(F(4))) + F(2 + F(7))) \times 7000 \end{aligned}$$

384.

$$\begin{aligned} 4277 &:= (F(\sqrt{4}) + F(2 + F(7))) \times 7 \\ 42770 &:= (F(\sqrt{4}) + F(2 + F(7))) \times 70 \\ 427700 &:= (F(\sqrt{4}) + F(2 + F(7))) \times 700 \\ 4277000 &:= (F(\sqrt{4}) + F(2 + F(7))) \times 7000 \end{aligned}$$

385.

$$\begin{aligned} 4277 &:= (F(\sqrt{4}) + F(C(2) + 7)) \times 7 \\ 42770 &:= (F(\sqrt{4}) + F(C(2) + 7)) \times 70 \\ 427700 &:= (F(\sqrt{4}) + F(C(2) + 7)) \times 700 \\ 4277000 &:= (F(\sqrt{4}) + F(C(2) + 7)) \times 7000 \end{aligned}$$

386.

$$\begin{aligned} 4282 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T(2)) + T(Q(8))) \times 2 \\ 42820 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T(2)) + T(Q(8))) \times 20 \\ 428200 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T(2)) + T(Q(8))) \times 200 \\ 4282000 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T(2)) + T(Q(8))) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

387.

$$\begin{aligned} 4288 &:= (\sqrt{C(4) + C(C(2))} + C(8)) \times 8 \\ 42880 &:= (\sqrt{C(4) + C(C(2))} + C(8)) \times 80 \\ 428800 &:= (\sqrt{C(4) + C(C(2))} + C(8)) \times 800 \\ 4288000 &:= (\sqrt{C(4) + C(C(2))} + C(8)) \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

388.

$$\begin{aligned} 4292 &:= (F(Q(4)) + F(Q(2)) + Q(F(9))) \times 2 \\ 42920 &:= (F(Q(4)) + F(Q(2)) + Q(F(9))) \times 20 \\ 429200 &:= (F(Q(4)) + F(Q(2)) + Q(F(9))) \times 200 \\ 4292000 &:= (F(Q(4)) + F(Q(2)) + Q(F(9))) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

389.

$$\begin{aligned} 4293 &:= (F(4)!! \times 2 - 9) \times 3 \\ 42930 &:= (F(4)!! \times 2 - 9) \times 30 \\ 429300 &:= (F(4)!! \times 2 - 9) \times 300 \\ 4293000 &:= (F(4)!! \times 2 - 9) \times 3000 \end{aligned}$$

390.

$$\begin{aligned} 4293 &:= T(4! + 29) \times 3 \\ 42930 &:= T(4! + 29) \times 30 \\ 429300 &:= T(4! + 29) \times 300 \\ 4293000 &:= T(4! + 29) \times 3000 \end{aligned}$$

391.

$$4310 := (-T(4) + Q(T(T(3)))) \times 10$$

$$43100 := (-T(4) + Q(T(T(3)))) \times 100$$

$$431000 := (-T(4) + Q(T(T(3)))) \times 1000$$

$$4310000 := (-T(4) + Q(T(T(3)))) \times 10000$$

392.

$$4311 := (Q(C(4)) + C(3!) - 1) \times 1$$

$$43110 := (Q(C(4)) + C(3!) - 1) \times 10$$

$$431100 := (Q(C(4)) + C(3!) - 1) \times 100$$

$$4311000 := (Q(C(4)) + C(3!) - 1) \times 1000$$

393.

$$4315 := (4! \times Q(3!) - 1) \times 5$$

$$43150 := (4! \times Q(3!) - 1) \times 50$$

$$431500 := (4! \times Q(3!) - 1) \times 500$$

$$4315000 := (4! \times Q(3!) - 1) \times 5000$$

394.

$$4315 := (4! \times Q(T(3)) - 1) \times 5$$

$$43150 := (4! \times Q(T(3)) - 1) \times 50$$

$$431500 := (4! \times Q(T(3)) - 1) \times 500$$

$$4315000 := (4! \times Q(T(3)) - 1) \times 5000$$

395.

$$4315 := (4 \times C(3!) - 1) \times 5$$

$$43150 := (4 \times C(3!) - 1) \times 50$$

$$431500 := (4 \times C(3!) - 1) \times 500$$

$$4315000 := (4 \times C(3!) - 1) \times 5000$$

396.

$$4326 := (F(4)^{3!} - C(2)) \times 6$$

$$43260 := (F(4)^{3!} - C(2)) \times 60$$

$$432600 := (F(4)^{3!} - C(2)) \times 600$$

$$4326000 := (F(4)^{3!} - C(2)) \times 6000$$

397.

$$4329 := (-4 - C(3) + C(C(2))) \times 9$$

$$43290 := (-4 - C(3) + C(C(2))) \times 90$$

$$432900 := (-4 - C(3) + C(C(2))) \times 900$$

$$4329000 := (-4 - C(3) + C(C(2))) \times 9000$$

398.

$$4335 := (4! \times Q(3!) + 3) \times 5$$

$$43350 := (4! \times Q(3!) + 3) \times 50$$

$$433500 := (4! \times Q(3!) + 3) \times 500$$

$$4335000 := (4! \times Q(3!) + 3) \times 5000$$

399.

$$4335 := (4 \times C(3!) + 3) \times 5$$

$$43350 := (4 \times C(3!) + 3) \times 50$$

$$433500 := (4 \times C(3!) + 3) \times 500$$

$$4335000 := (4 \times C(3!) + 3) \times 5000$$

400.

$$4335 := Q(4! + C(3))/3 \times 5$$

$$43350 := Q(4! + C(3))/3 \times 50$$

$$433500 := Q(4! + C(3))/3 \times 500$$

$$4335000 := Q(4! + C(3))/3 \times 5000$$

401.

$$4342 := (T(C(4)) + C(3) + C(4)) \times 2$$

$$43420 := (T(C(4)) + C(3) + C(4)) \times 20$$

$$434200 := (T(C(4)) + C(3) + C(4)) \times 200$$

$$4342000 := (T(C(4)) + C(3) + C(4)) \times 2000$$

402.

$$4347 := (-4 + Q(C(3) - \sqrt{4})) \times 7$$

$$43470 := (-4 + Q(C(3) - \sqrt{4})) \times 70$$

$$434700 := (-4 + Q(C(3) - \sqrt{4})) \times 700$$

$$4347000 := (-4 + Q(C(3) - \sqrt{4})) \times 7000$$

403.

$$4347 := (-4 + Q(Q(3) + Q(4))) \times 7$$

$$43470 := (-4 + Q(Q(3) + Q(4))) \times 70$$

$$434700 := (-4 + Q(Q(3) + Q(4))) \times 700$$

$$4347000 := (-4 + Q(Q(3) + Q(4))) \times 7000$$

404.

$$4350 := (F(4)! + Q(Q(3))) \times 50$$

$$43500 := (F(4)! + Q(Q(3))) \times 500$$

$$435000 := (F(4)! + Q(Q(3))) \times 5000$$

$$4350000 := (F(4)! + Q(Q(3))) \times 50000$$

405.

$$4353 := (C(\sqrt{4} + Q(3)) + 5!) \times 3$$

$$43530 := (C(\sqrt{4} + Q(3)) + 5!) \times 30$$

$$435300 := (C(\sqrt{4} + Q(3)) + 5!) \times 300$$

$$4353000 := (C(\sqrt{4} + Q(3)) + 5!) \times 3000$$

406.

$$4353 := (C(\sqrt{C(4)} + 3) + 5!) \times 3$$

$$43530 := (C(\sqrt{C(4)} + 3) + 5!) \times 30$$

$$435300 := (C(\sqrt{C(4)} + 3) + 5!) \times 300$$

$$4353000 := (C(\sqrt{C(4)} + 3) + 5!) \times 3000$$

407.

$$4355 := (F(Q(4)) + Q(F(3)) - 5!) \times 5$$

$$43550 := (F(Q(4)) + Q(F(3)) - 5!) \times 50$$

$$435500 := (F(Q(4)) + Q(F(3)) - 5!) \times 500$$

$$4355000 := (F(Q(4)) + Q(F(3)) - 5!) \times 5000$$

408.

$$4364 := (\sqrt{4} + Q(-3 + Q(6))) \times 4$$

$$43640 := (\sqrt{4} + Q(-3 + Q(6))) \times 40$$

$$436400 := (\sqrt{4} + Q(-3 + Q(6))) \times 400$$

$$4364000 := (\sqrt{4} + Q(-3 + Q(6))) \times 4000$$

409.

$$4365 := (Q(4! + Q(3)) - C(6)) \times 5$$

$$43650 := (Q(4! + Q(3)) - C(6)) \times 50$$

$$436500 := (Q(4! + Q(3)) - C(6)) \times 500$$

$$4365000 := (Q(4! + Q(3)) - C(6)) \times 5000$$

410.

$$4375 := (T(\sqrt{4} \times T(T(3))) - T(7)) \times 5$$

$$43750 := (T(\sqrt{4} \times T(T(3))) - T(7)) \times 50$$

$$437500 := (T(\sqrt{4} \times T(T(3))) - T(7)) \times 500$$

$$4375000 := (T(\sqrt{4} \times T(T(3))) - T(7)) \times 5000$$

411.

$$4383 := (-4! + T(T(3)! - T(T(8)))) \times 3$$

$$43830 := (-4! + T(T(3)! - T(T(8)))) \times 30$$

$$438300 := (-4! + T(T(3)! - T(T(8)))) \times 300$$

$$4383000 := (-4! + T(T(3)! - T(T(8)))) \times 3000$$

412.

$$4385 := (T(T(T(4))) + 3 - T(T(8))) \times 5$$

$$43850 := (T(T(T(4))) + 3 - T(T(8))) \times 50$$

$$438500 := (T(T(T(4))) + 3 - T(T(8))) \times 500$$

$$4385000 := (T(T(T(4))) + 3 - T(T(8))) \times 5000$$

413.

$$4386 := (4! + C(3)) \times 86$$

$$43860 := (4! + C(3)) \times 860$$

$$438600 := (4! + C(3)) \times 8600$$

$$4386000 := (4! + C(3)) \times 86000$$

414.

$$4386 := (\sqrt{4} + C(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}})) \times 6$$

$$43860 := (\sqrt{4} + C(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}})) \times 60$$

$$438600 := (\sqrt{4} + C(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}})) \times 600$$

$$4386000 := (\sqrt{4} + C(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}})) \times 6000$$

415.

$$4405 := (Q(Q(4)) + Q(4! + 0!)) \times 5$$

$$44050 := (Q(Q(4)) + Q(4! + 0!)) \times 50$$

$$440500 := (Q(Q(4)) + Q(4! + 0!)) \times 500$$

$$4405000 := (Q(Q(4)) + Q(4! + 0!)) \times 5000$$

416.

$$4405 := (T(T(\sqrt{C(4)})) + C(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - 0!) \times 5$$

$$44050 := (T(T(\sqrt{C(4)})) + C(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - 0!) \times 50$$

$$440500 := (T(T(\sqrt{C(4)})) + C(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - 0!) \times 500$$

$$4405000 := (T(T(\sqrt{C(4)})) + C(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - 0!) \times 5000$$

417.

$$4408 := (Q(4!) - 4! - 0!) \times 8$$

$$44080 := (Q(4!) - 4! - 0!) \times 80$$

$$440800 := (Q(4!) - 4! - 0!) \times 800$$

$$4408000 := (Q(4!) - 4! - 0!) \times 8000$$

418.

$$4408 := (T(4) \times F(T(4)) + 0!) \times 8$$

$$44080 := (T(4) \times F(T(4)) + 0!) \times 80$$

$$440800 := (T(4) \times F(T(4)) + 0!) \times 800$$

$$4408000 := (T(4) \times F(T(4)) + 0!) \times 8000$$

419.

$$4408 := (T(4) \times T(T(4)) + 0!) \times 8$$

$$44080 := (T(4) \times T(T(4)) + 0!) \times 80$$

$$440800 := (T(4) \times T(T(4)) + 0!) \times 800$$

$$4408000 := (T(4) \times T(T(4)) + 0!) \times 8000$$

420.

$$4410 := F(F(F(4)!))^{F(F(4))} \times 10$$

$$44100 := F(F(F(4)!))^{F(F(4))} \times 100$$

$$441000 := F(F(F(4)!))^{F(F(4))} \times 1000$$

$$4410000 := F(F(F(4)!))^{F(F(4))} \times 10000$$

421.

$$4410 := F(F(F(4)!))^{√4} \times 10$$

$$44100 := F(F(F(4)!))^{√4} \times 100$$

$$441000 := F(F(F(4)!))^{√4} \times 1000$$

$$4410000 := F(F(F(4)!))^{√4} \times 10000$$

422.

$$4410 := Q(F(4 + 4)) \times 10$$

$$44100 := Q(F(4 + 4)) \times 100$$

$$441000 := Q(F(4 + 4)) \times 1000$$

$$4410000 := Q(F(4 + 4)) \times 10000$$

423.

$$4416 := (Q(4) + (4 - 1)!) \times 6$$

$$44160 := (Q(4) + (4 - 1)!) \times 60$$

$$441600 := (Q(4) + (4 - 1)!) \times 600$$

$$4416000 := (Q(4) + (4 - 1)!) \times 6000$$

424.

$$4417 := ((\sqrt{C(4)!}/C(4) + 1) \times 7$$

$$44170 := ((\sqrt{C(4)!}/C(4) + 1) \times 70$$

$$441700 := ((\sqrt{C(4)!}/C(4) + 1) \times 700$$

$$4417000 := ((\sqrt{C(4)!}/C(4) + 1) \times 7000$$

425.

$$4417 := (F(4)! + Q(Q(4 + 1))) \times 7$$

$$44170 := (F(4)! + Q(Q(4 + 1))) \times 70$$

$$441700 := (F(4)! + Q(Q(4 + 1))) \times 700$$

$$4417000 := (F(4)! + Q(Q(4 + 1))) \times 7000$$

426.

$$4417 := (Q(4!) + T(T(4))) \times 7$$

$$44170 := (Q(4!) + T(T(4))) \times 70$$

$$441700 := (Q(4!) + T(T(4))) \times 700$$

$$4417000 := (Q(4!) + T(T(4))) \times 7000$$

427.

$$4419 := (\sqrt{C(C(4))} - F(\sqrt{C(4)})) \times 9$$

$$44190 := (\sqrt{C(C(4))} - F(\sqrt{C(4)})) \times 90$$

$$441900 := (\sqrt{C(C(4))} - F(\sqrt{C(4)})) \times 900$$

$$4419000 := (\sqrt{C(C(4))} - F(\sqrt{C(4)})) \times 9000$$

428.

$$4419 := (\sqrt{C(C(4))} - T(T(4 - 1))) \times 9$$

$$44190 := (\sqrt{C(C(4))} - T(T(4 - 1))) \times 90$$

$$441900 := (\sqrt{C(C(4))} - T(T(4 - 1))) \times 900$$

$$4419000 := (\sqrt{C(C(4))} - T(T(4 - 1))) \times 9000$$

429.

$$4422 := T(4! + 42) \times 2$$

$$44220 := T(4! + 42) \times 20$$

$$442200 := T(4! + 42) \times 200$$

$$4422000 := T(4! + 42) \times 2000$$

430.

$$4422 := T(4^{F(4)} + 2) \times 2$$

$$44220 := T(4^{F(4)} + 2) \times 20$$

$$442200 := T(4^{F(4)} + 2) \times 200$$

$$4422000 := T(4^{F(4)} + 2) \times 2000$$

431.

$$\begin{aligned} 4422 &:= T(T(4 + 4 + T(2))) \times 2 \\ 44220 &:= T(T(4 + 4 + T(2))) \times 20 \\ 442200 &:= T(T(4 + 4 + T(2))) \times 200 \\ 4422000 &:= T(T(4 + 4 + T(2))) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

432.

$$\begin{aligned} 4432 &:= (F(F(4)!) + F(4!)/F(F(3!))) \times 2 \\ 44320 &:= (F(F(4)!) + F(4!)/F(F(3!))) \times 20 \\ 443200 &:= (F(F(4)!) + F(4!)/F(F(3!))) \times 200 \\ 4432000 &:= (F(F(4)!) + F(4!)/F(F(3!))) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

433.

$$\begin{aligned} 4432 &:= (T(C(4)) + T(T(4) + T(3))) \times 2 \\ 44320 &:= (T(C(4)) + T(T(4) + T(3))) \times 20 \\ 443200 &:= (T(C(4)) + T(T(4) + T(3))) \times 200 \\ 4432000 &:= (T(C(4)) + T(T(4) + T(3))) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

434.

$$\begin{aligned} 4435 &:= (F(Q(4)) - Q(4 + 3!)) \times 5 \\ 44350 &:= (F(Q(4)) - Q(4 + 3!)) \times 50 \\ 443500 &:= (F(Q(4)) - Q(4 + 3!)) \times 500 \\ 4435000 &:= (F(Q(4)) - Q(4 + 3!)) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

435.

$$\begin{aligned} 4435 &:= (T(T(T(F(4)))) - T(4) + T(T(F(T(3)))) \times 5 \\ 44350 &:= (T(T(T(F(4)))) - T(4) + T(T(F(T(3)))) \times 50 \\ 443500 &:= (T(T(T(F(4)))) - T(4) + T(T(F(T(3)))) \times 500 \\ 4435000 &:= (T(T(T(F(4)))) - T(4) + T(T(F(T(3)))) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

436.

$$\begin{aligned} 4442 &:= (4! + C(F(F(4) + 4))) \times 2 \\ 44420 &:= (4! + C(F(F(4) + 4))) \times 20 \\ 444200 &:= (4! + C(F(F(4) + 4))) \times 200 \\ 4442000 &:= (4! + C(F(F(4) + 4))) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

437.

$$\begin{aligned} 4442 &:= (T(4) + T(C(4) + \sqrt{4})) \times 2 \\ 44420 &:= (T(4) + T(C(4) + \sqrt{4})) \times 20 \\ 444200 &:= (T(4) + T(C(4) + \sqrt{4})) \times 200 \\ 4442000 &:= (T(4) + T(C(4) + \sqrt{4})) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

438.

$$\begin{aligned} 4443 &:= (-4 + T(C(4) - T(4))) \times 3 \\ 44430 &:= (-4 + T(C(4) - T(4))) \times 30 \\ 444300 &:= (-4 + T(C(4) - T(4))) \times 300 \\ 4443000 &:= (-4 + T(C(4) - T(4))) \times 3000 \end{aligned}$$

439.

$$\begin{aligned} 4443 &:= (T(F(T(4))) - 4 - F(T(4))) \times 3 \\ 44430 &:= (T(F(T(4))) - 4 - F(T(4))) \times 30 \\ 444300 &:= (T(F(T(4))) - 4 - F(T(4))) \times 300 \\ 4443000 &:= (T(F(T(4))) - 4 - F(T(4))) \times 3000 \end{aligned}$$

440.

$$\begin{aligned} 4443 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - 4 - T(T(4))) \times 3 \\ 44430 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - 4 - T(T(4))) \times 30 \\ 444300 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - 4 - T(T(4))) \times 300 \\ 4443000 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - 4 - T(T(4))) \times 3000 \end{aligned}$$

441.

$$4446 := T(T(T(T(4)))/T(T(4)) + T(4)) \times 6$$

$$44460 := T(T(T(T(4)))/T(T(4)) + T(4)) \times 60$$

$$444600 := T(T(T(T(4)))/T(T(4)) + T(4)) \times 600$$

$$4446000 := T(T(T(T(4)))/T(T(4)) + T(4)) \times 6000$$

442.

$$4448 := (T(4!) + 4^4) \times 8$$

$$44480 := (T(4!) + 4^4) \times 80$$

$$444800 := (T(4!) + 4^4) \times 800$$

$$4448000 := (T(4!) + 4^4) \times 8000$$

443.

$$4448 := (T(4) \times F(T(4)) + T(F(4))) \times 8$$

$$44480 := (T(4) \times F(T(4)) + T(F(4))) \times 80$$

$$444800 := (T(4) \times F(T(4)) + T(F(4))) \times 800$$

$$4448000 := (T(4) \times F(T(4)) + T(F(4))) \times 8000$$

444.

$$4448 := (T(T(\sqrt{4})) + T(4) \times T(T(4))) \times 8$$

$$44480 := (T(T(\sqrt{4})) + T(4) \times T(T(4))) \times 80$$

$$444800 := (T(T(\sqrt{4})) + T(4) \times T(T(4))) \times 800$$

$$4448000 := (T(T(\sqrt{4})) + T(4) \times T(T(4))) \times 8000$$

445.

$$4450 := F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) \times 50$$

$$44500 := F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) \times 500$$

$$445000 := F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5000$$

$$4450000 := F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) \times 50000$$

446.

$$4450 := F(F(4) + \sqrt{C(4)}) \times 50$$

$$44500 := F(F(4) + \sqrt{C(4)}) \times 500$$

$$445000 := F(F(4) + \sqrt{C(4)}) \times 5000$$

$$4450000 := F(F(4) + \sqrt{C(4)}) \times 50000$$

447.

$$4450 := F(F(F(F(4))) + T(4)) \times 50$$

$$44500 := F(F(F(F(4))) + T(4)) \times 500$$

$$445000 := F(F(F(F(4))) + T(4)) \times 5000$$

$$4450000 := F(F(F(F(4))) + T(4)) \times 50000$$

448.

$$4450 := F(F(\sqrt{4}) + T(4)) \times 50$$

$$44500 := F(F(\sqrt{4}) + T(4)) \times 500$$

$$445000 := F(F(\sqrt{4}) + T(4)) \times 5000$$

$$4450000 := F(F(\sqrt{4}) + T(4)) \times 50000$$

449.

$$4452 := (T(C(4) + \sqrt{4}) + T(5)) \times 2$$

$$44520 := (T(C(4) + \sqrt{4}) + T(5)) \times 20$$

$$445200 := (T(C(4) + \sqrt{4}) + T(5)) \times 200$$

$$4452000 := (T(C(4) + \sqrt{4}) + T(5)) \times 2000$$

450.

$$4455 := F(4)^4 \times 55$$

$$44550 := F(4)^4 \times 550$$

$$445500 := F(4)^4 \times 5500$$

$$4455000 := F(4)^4 \times 55000$$

451.

$$4455 := Q(Q(4!)/C(4)) \times 55$$

$$44550 := Q(Q(4!)/C(4)) \times 550$$

$$445500 := Q(Q(4!)/C(4)) \times 5500$$

$$4455000 := Q(Q(4!)/C(4)) \times 55000$$

452.

$$4455 := T(\sqrt{4})^4 \times 55$$

$$44550 := T(\sqrt{4})^4 \times 550$$

$$445500 := T(\sqrt{4})^4 \times 5500$$

$$4455000 := T(\sqrt{4})^4 \times 55000$$

453.

$$4462 := (\sqrt{4} \times C(T(4)) + T(T(6))) \times 2$$

$$44620 := (\sqrt{4} \times C(T(4)) + T(T(6))) \times 20$$

$$446200 := (\sqrt{4} \times C(T(4)) + T(T(6))) \times 200$$

$$4462000 := (\sqrt{4} \times C(T(4)) + T(T(6))) \times 2000$$

454.

$$4472 := (T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \times T(4) + T(T(7))) \times 2$$

$$44720 := (T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \times T(4) + T(T(7))) \times 20$$

$$447200 := (T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \times T(4) + T(T(7))) \times 200$$

$$4472000 := (T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \times T(4) + T(T(7))) \times 2000$$

455.

$$4480 := (C(4) - \sqrt{C(4)}) \times 80$$

$$44800 := (C(4) - \sqrt{C(4)}) \times 800$$

$$448000 := (C(4) - \sqrt{C(4)}) \times 8000$$

$$4480000 := (C(4) - \sqrt{C(4)}) \times 80000$$

456.

$$4480 := (F(F(F(4))) + F(T(4))) \times 80$$

$$44800 := (F(F(F(4))) + F(T(4))) \times 800$$

$$448000 := (F(F(F(4))) + F(T(4))) \times 8000$$

$$4480000 := (F(F(F(4))) + F(T(4))) \times 80000$$

457.

$$4480 := (F(\sqrt{4}) + F(T(4))) \times 80$$

$$44800 := (F(\sqrt{4}) + F(T(4))) \times 800$$

$$448000 := (F(\sqrt{4}) + F(T(4))) \times 8000$$

$$4480000 := (F(\sqrt{4}) + F(T(4))) \times 80000$$

458.

$$4484 := (-T(T(4)) + T(48)) \times 4$$

$$44840 := (-T(T(4)) + T(48)) \times 40$$

$$448400 := (-T(T(4)) + T(48)) \times 400$$

$$4484000 := (-T(T(4)) + T(48)) \times 4000$$

459.

$$4485 := (T(T(4!/4)) + T(T(8))) \times 5$$

$$44850 := (T(T(4!/4)) + T(T(8))) \times 50$$

$$448500 := (T(T(4!/4)) + T(T(8))) \times 500$$

$$4485000 := (T(T(4!/4)) + T(T(8))) \times 5000$$

460.

$$4485 := (T(T(4+4)) + T(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$44850 := (T(T(4+4)) + T(F(8))) \times 50$$

$$448500 := (T(T(4+4)) + T(F(8))) \times 500$$

$$4485000 := (T(T(4+4)) + T(F(8))) \times 5000$$

461.

$$4485 := (T(T(-4 + T(4))) + T(T(8))) \times 5$$

$$44850 := (T(T(-4 + T(4))) + T(T(8))) \times 50$$

$$448500 := (T(T(-4 + T(4))) + T(T(8))) \times 500$$

$$4485000 := (T(T(-4 + T(4))) + T(T(8))) \times 5000$$

462.

$$4487 := (-4! - F(\sqrt{4}) + T(T(8))) \times 7$$

$$44870 := (-4! - F(\sqrt{4}) + T(T(8))) \times 70$$

$$448700 := (-4! - F(\sqrt{4}) + T(T(8))) \times 700$$

$$4487000 := (-4! - F(\sqrt{4}) + T(T(8))) \times 7000$$

463.

$$4487 := (-4! - T(T(4)) + (\sqrt{T(8)!}) \times 7$$

$$44870 := (-4! - T(T(4)) + (\sqrt{T(8)!}) \times 70$$

$$448700 := (-4! - T(T(4)) + (\sqrt{T(8)!}) \times 700$$

$$4487000 := (-4! - T(T(4)) + (\sqrt{T(8)!}) \times 7000$$

464.

$$4488 := (4! + C(F(4))) \times 88$$

$$44880 := (4! + C(F(4))) \times 880$$

$$448800 := (4! + C(F(4))) \times 8800$$

$$4488000 := (4! + C(F(4))) \times 88000$$

465.

$$4488 := (-4 + T(T(4))) \times 88$$

$$44880 := (-4 + T(T(4))) \times 880$$

$$448800 := (-4 + T(T(4))) \times 8800$$

$$4488000 := (-4 + T(T(4))) \times 88000$$

466.

$$4488 := (F(T(4)) - 4) \times 88$$

$$44880 := (F(T(4)) - 4) \times 880$$

$$448800 := (F(T(4)) - 4) \times 8800$$

$$4488000 := (F(T(4)) - 4) \times 88000$$

467.

$$4500 := Q(F(4)) \times 500$$

$$45000 := Q(F(4)) \times 5000$$

$$450000 := Q(F(4)) \times 50000$$

$$4500000 := Q(F(4)) \times 500000$$

468.

$$4505 := (Q(5 \times F(4)!) + 0!) \times 5$$

$$45050 := (Q(5 \times F(4)!) + 0!) \times 50$$

$$450500 := (Q(5 \times F(4)!) + 0!) \times 500$$

$$4505000 := (Q(5 \times F(4)!) + 0!) \times 5000$$

469.

$$4506 := (F(4)! \times C(5) + 0!) \times 6$$

$$45060 := (F(4)! \times C(5) + 0!) \times 60$$

$$450600 := (F(4)! \times C(5) + 0!) \times 600$$

$$4506000 := (F(4)! \times C(5) + 0!) \times 6000$$

470.

$$4510 := (Q(4!) - C(5)) \times 10$$

$$45100 := (Q(4!) - C(5)) \times 100$$

$$451000 := (Q(4!) - C(5)) \times 1000$$

$$4510000 := (Q(4!) - C(5)) \times 10000$$

471.

$$\begin{aligned}4512 &:= (Q(Q(4)) + 5!) \times 12 \\45120 &:= (Q(Q(4)) + 5!) \times 120 \\451200 &:= (Q(Q(4)) + 5!) \times 1200 \\4512000 &:= (Q(Q(4)) + 5!) \times 12000\end{aligned}$$

472.

$$\begin{aligned}4515 &:= T(F(4) \times (T(5) - 1)) \times 5 \\45150 &:= T(F(4) \times (T(5) - 1)) \times 50 \\451500 &:= T(F(4) \times (T(5) - 1)) \times 500 \\4515000 &:= T(F(4) \times (T(5) - 1)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

473.

$$\begin{aligned}4515 &:= T(\sqrt{4} \times T(5 + 1)) \times 5 \\45150 &:= T(\sqrt{4} \times T(5 + 1)) \times 50 \\451500 &:= T(\sqrt{4} \times T(5 + 1)) \times 500 \\4515000 &:= T(\sqrt{4} \times T(5 + 1)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

474.

$$\begin{aligned}4518 &:= (Q(Q(4)) - 5) \times 18 \\45180 &:= (Q(Q(4)) - 5) \times 180 \\451800 &:= (Q(Q(4)) - 5) \times 1800 \\4518000 &:= (Q(Q(4)) - 5) \times 18000\end{aligned}$$

475.

$$\begin{aligned}4520 &:= (T(T(T(F(4)))) - 5) \times 20 \\45200 &:= (T(T(T(F(4)))) - 5) \times 200 \\452000 &:= (T(T(T(F(4)))) - 5) \times 2000 \\4520000 &:= (T(T(T(F(4)))) - 5) \times 20000\end{aligned}$$

476.

$$\begin{aligned}4520 &:= (T(T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) - 5) \times 20 \\45200 &:= (T(T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) - 5) \times 200 \\452000 &:= (T(T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) - 5) \times 2000 \\4520000 &:= (T(T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) - 5) \times 20000\end{aligned}$$

477.

$$\begin{aligned}4522 &:= (C(4) + C(5 + C(2))) \times 2 \\45220 &:= (C(4) + C(5 + C(2))) \times 20 \\452200 &:= (C(4) + C(5 + C(2))) \times 200 \\4522000 &:= (C(4) + C(5 + C(2))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

478.

$$\begin{aligned}4525 &:= (-F(T(4)) + T(T(5)) \times F(T(T(2)))) \times 5 \\45250 &:= (-F(T(4)) + T(T(5)) \times F(T(T(2)))) \times 50 \\452500 &:= (-F(T(4)) + T(T(5)) \times F(T(T(2)))) \times 500 \\4525000 &:= (-F(T(4)) + T(T(5)) \times F(T(T(2)))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

479.

$$\begin{aligned}4530 &:= (T(Q(4)) + T(5)) \times 30 \\45300 &:= (T(Q(4)) + T(5)) \times 300 \\453000 &:= (T(Q(4)) + T(5)) \times 3000 \\4530000 &:= (T(Q(4)) + T(5)) \times 30000\end{aligned}$$

480.

$$\begin{aligned}4532 &:= (F(T(4)) + T(T(5 + T(3)))) \times 2 \\45320 &:= (F(T(4)) + T(T(5 + T(3)))) \times 20 \\453200 &:= (F(T(4)) + T(T(5 + T(3)))) \times 200 \\4532000 &:= (F(T(4)) + T(T(5 + T(3)))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

481.

$$\begin{aligned}4532 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T(5 + T(3)))) \times 2 \\45320 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T(5 + T(3)))) \times 20 \\453200 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T(5 + T(3)))) \times 200 \\4532000 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T(5 + T(3)))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

482.

$$\begin{aligned}4536 &:= (C(4 + 5) + C(3)) \times 6 \\45360 &:= (C(4 + 5) + C(3)) \times 60 \\453600 &:= (C(4 + 5) + C(3)) \times 600 \\4536000 &:= (C(4 + 5) + C(3)) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

483.

$$\begin{aligned}4550 &:= (C(F(4)!) - C(5)) \times 50 \\45500 &:= (C(F(4)!) - C(5)) \times 500 \\455000 &:= (C(F(4)!) - C(5)) \times 5000 \\4550000 &:= (C(F(4)!) - C(5)) \times 50000\end{aligned}$$

484.

$$\begin{aligned}4550 &:= T(F(F(F(4)) + 5)) \times 50 \\45500 &:= T(F(F(F(4)) + 5)) \times 500 \\455000 &:= T(F(F(F(4)) + 5)) \times 5000 \\4550000 &:= T(F(F(F(4)) + 5)) \times 50000\end{aligned}$$

485.

$$\begin{aligned}4550 &:= T(F(\sqrt{4} + 5)) \times 50 \\45500 &:= T(F(\sqrt{4} + 5)) \times 500 \\455000 &:= T(F(\sqrt{4} + 5)) \times 5000 \\4550000 &:= T(F(\sqrt{4} + 5)) \times 50000\end{aligned}$$

486.

$$\begin{aligned}4550 &:= T(T(5) - \sqrt{4}) \times 50 \\45500 &:= T(T(5) - \sqrt{4}) \times 500 \\455000 &:= T(T(5) - \sqrt{4}) \times 5000 \\4550000 &:= T(T(5) - \sqrt{4}) \times 50000\end{aligned}$$

487.

$$\begin{aligned}4563 &:= Q(45 - 6) \times 3 \\45630 &:= Q(45 - 6) \times 30 \\456300 &:= Q(45 - 6) \times 300 \\4563000 &:= Q(45 - 6) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

488.

$$\begin{aligned}4566 &:= (Q(4) + Q(5) + 6!) \times 6 \\45660 &:= (Q(4) + Q(5) + 6!) \times 60 \\456600 &:= (Q(4) + Q(5) + 6!) \times 600 \\4566000 &:= (Q(4) + Q(5) + 6!) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

489.

$$\begin{aligned}4568 &:= (-F(4) + F(T(5)) - T(F(6))) \times 8 \\45680 &:= (-F(4) + F(T(5)) - T(F(6))) \times 80 \\456800 &:= (-F(4) + F(T(5)) - T(F(6))) \times 800 \\4568000 &:= (-F(4) + F(T(5)) - T(F(6))) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

490.

$$\begin{aligned}4584 &:= (4 \times T(T(5)) + T(T(8))) \times 4 \\45840 &:= (4 \times T(T(5)) + T(T(8))) \times 40 \\458400 &:= (4 \times T(T(5)) + T(T(8))) \times 400 \\4584000 &:= (4 \times T(T(5)) + T(T(8))) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

491.

$$4590 := (T(F(T(F(4)))) + T(5)) \times 90$$

$$45900 := (T(F(T(F(4)))) + T(5)) \times 900$$

$$459000 := (T(F(T(F(4)))) + T(5)) \times 9000$$

$$4590000 := (T(F(T(F(4)))) + T(5)) \times 90000$$

492.

$$4593 := (F(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5)) - Q(9)) \times 3$$

$$45930 := (F(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5)) - Q(9)) \times 30$$

$$459300 := (F(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5)) - Q(9)) \times 300$$

$$4593000 := (F(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5)) - Q(9)) \times 3000$$

493.

$$4593 := (T(F(T(4))) - T(5) + T(\sqrt{9})) \times 3$$

$$45930 := (T(F(T(4))) - T(5) + T(\sqrt{9})) \times 30$$

$$459300 := (T(F(T(4))) - T(5) + T(\sqrt{9})) \times 300$$

$$4593000 := (T(F(T(4))) - T(5) + T(\sqrt{9})) \times 3000$$

494.

$$4593 := (T(T(T(4))) - T(5) + T(\sqrt{9})) \times 3$$

$$45930 := (T(T(T(4))) - T(5) + T(\sqrt{9})) \times 30$$

$$459300 := (T(T(T(4))) - T(5) + T(\sqrt{9})) \times 300$$

$$4593000 := (T(T(T(4))) - T(5) + T(\sqrt{9})) \times 3000$$

495.

$$4599 := (F(\sqrt{4}) + T(5) \times F(9)) \times 9$$

$$45990 := (F(\sqrt{4}) + T(5) \times F(9)) \times 90$$

$$459900 := (F(\sqrt{4}) + T(5) \times F(9)) \times 900$$

$$4599000 := (F(\sqrt{4}) + T(5) \times F(9)) \times 9000$$

496.

$$4599 := (\sqrt{C(C(4))} + 5 - (\sqrt{9})!) \times 9$$

$$45990 := (\sqrt{C(C(4))} + 5 - (\sqrt{9})!) \times 90$$

$$459900 := (\sqrt{C(C(4))} + 5 - (\sqrt{9})!) \times 900$$

$$4599000 := (\sqrt{C(C(4))} + 5 - (\sqrt{9})!) \times 9000$$

497.

$$4608 := 4!^{F(\sqrt{F(6)+0!})} \times 8$$

$$46080 := 4!^{F(\sqrt{F(6)+0!})} \times 80$$

$$460800 := 4!^{F(\sqrt{F(6)+0!})} \times 800$$

$$4608000 := 4!^{F(\sqrt{F(6)+0!})} \times 8000$$

498.

$$4608 := Q(4 \times 6) \times 8$$

$$46080 := Q(4 \times 6) \times 80$$

$$460800 := Q(4 \times 6) \times 800$$

$$4608000 := Q(4 \times 6) \times 8000$$

499.

$$4615 := (4 \times T(T(6)) - 1) \times 5$$

$$46150 := (4 \times T(T(6)) - 1) \times 50$$

$$461500 := (4 \times T(T(6)) - 1) \times 500$$

$$4615000 := (4 \times T(T(6)) - 1) \times 5000$$

500.

$$4615 := (F(Q(4)) - Q(F(6))) \times 5$$

$$46150 := (F(Q(4)) - Q(F(6))) \times 50$$

$$461500 := (F(Q(4)) - Q(F(6))) \times 500$$

$$4615000 := (F(Q(4)) - Q(F(6))) \times 5000$$

501.

$$4622 := (T(4) \times T(T(6)) + F(2)) \times 2$$

$$46220 := (T(4) \times T(T(6)) + F(2)) \times 20$$

$$462200 := (T(4) \times T(T(6)) + F(2)) \times 200$$

$$4622000 := (T(4) \times T(T(6)) + F(2)) \times 2000$$

502.

$$4623 := (T(F(4 + 6)) + F(2)) \times 3$$

$$46230 := (T(F(4 + 6)) + F(2)) \times 30$$

$$462300 := (T(F(4 + 6)) + F(2)) \times 300$$

$$4623000 := (T(F(4 + 6)) + F(2)) \times 3000$$

503.

$$4625 := (4 \times T(T(6)) + F(2)) \times 5$$

$$46250 := (4 \times T(T(6)) + F(2)) \times 50$$

$$462500 := (4 \times T(T(6)) + F(2)) \times 500$$

$$4625000 := (4 \times T(T(6)) + F(2)) \times 5000$$

504.

$$4632 := (T(4) \times T(T(6)) + T(3)) \times 2$$

$$46320 := (T(4) \times T(T(6)) + T(3)) \times 20$$

$$463200 := (T(4) \times T(T(6)) + T(3)) \times 200$$

$$4632000 := (T(4) \times T(T(6)) + T(3)) \times 2000$$

505.

$$4642 := (T(4) + T(T(6)) + T(C(4))) \times 2$$

$$46420 := (T(4) + T(T(6)) + T(C(4))) \times 20$$

$$464200 := (T(4) + T(T(6)) + T(C(4))) \times 200$$

$$4642000 := (T(4) + T(T(6)) + T(C(4))) \times 2000$$

506.

$$4644 := (F(4)!! + F(F(6))^{F(F(4))}) \times 4$$

$$46440 := (F(4)!! + F(F(6))^{F(F(4))}) \times 40$$

$$464400 := (F(4)!! + F(F(6))^{F(F(4))}) \times 400$$

$$4644000 := (F(4)!! + F(F(6))^{F(F(4))}) \times 4000$$

507.

$$4644 := (F(4)!! + F(F(6))^{\sqrt{4}}) \times 4$$

$$46440 := (F(4)!! + F(F(6))^{\sqrt{4}}) \times 40$$

$$464400 := (F(4)!! + F(F(6))^{\sqrt{4}}) \times 400$$

$$4644000 := (F(4)!! + F(F(6))^{\sqrt{4}}) \times 4000$$

508.

$$4644 := (F(T(4)) \times T(6) + T(F(4))) \times 4$$

$$46440 := (F(T(4)) \times T(6) + T(F(4))) \times 40$$

$$464400 := (F(T(4)) \times T(6) + T(F(4))) \times 400$$

$$4644000 := (F(T(4)) \times T(6) + T(F(4))) \times 4000$$

509.

$$4644 := (T(T(\sqrt{4})) + T(T(4)) \times T(6)) \times 4$$

$$46440 := (T(T(\sqrt{4})) + T(T(4)) \times T(6)) \times 40$$

$$464400 := (T(T(\sqrt{4})) + T(T(4)) \times T(6)) \times 400$$

$$4644000 := (T(T(\sqrt{4})) + T(T(4)) \times T(6)) \times 4000$$

510.

$$4645 := (F(Q(4)) - Q(F(6)) + F(4)!) \times 5$$

$$46450 := (F(Q(4)) - Q(F(6)) + F(4)!) \times 50$$

$$464500 := (F(Q(4)) - Q(F(6)) + F(4)!) \times 500$$

$$4645000 := (F(Q(4)) - Q(F(6)) + F(4)!) \times 5000$$

511.

$$\begin{aligned} 4645 &:= (T(F(T(4))) - T(T(F(6))) + F(T(4))) \times 5 \\ 46450 &:= (T(F(T(4))) - T(T(F(6))) + F(T(4))) \times 50 \\ 464500 &:= (T(F(T(4))) - T(T(F(6))) + F(T(4))) \times 500 \\ 4645000 &:= (T(F(T(4))) - T(T(F(6))) + F(T(4))) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

512.

$$\begin{aligned} 4662 &:= (T(4) \times T(T(6)) + T(6)) \times 2 \\ 46620 &:= (T(4) \times T(T(6)) + T(6)) \times 20 \\ 466200 &:= (T(4) \times T(T(6)) + T(6)) \times 200 \\ 4662000 &:= (T(4) \times T(T(6)) + T(6)) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

513.

$$\begin{aligned} 4664 &:= (-T(4) + T(6 \times F(6))) \times 4 \\ 46640 &:= (-T(4) + T(6 \times F(6))) \times 40 \\ 466400 &:= (-T(4) + T(6 \times F(6))) \times 400 \\ 4664000 &:= (-T(4) + T(6 \times F(6))) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

514.

$$\begin{aligned} 4683 &:= (F(-4 + T(6)) - T(8)) \times 3 \\ 46830 &:= (F(-4 + T(6)) - T(8)) \times 30 \\ 468300 &:= (F(-4 + T(6)) - T(8)) \times 300 \\ 4683000 &:= (F(-4 + T(6)) - T(8)) \times 3000 \end{aligned}$$

515.

$$\begin{aligned} 4688 &:= (-4! + F(-6 + F(8))) \times 8 \\ 46880 &:= (-4! + F(-6 + F(8))) \times 80 \\ 468800 &:= (-4! + F(-6 + F(8))) \times 800 \\ 4688000 &:= (-4! + F(-6 + F(8))) \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

516.

$$\begin{aligned} 4688 &:= (-T(4) \times F(6) + T(T(8))) \times 8 \\ 46880 &:= (-T(4) \times F(6) + T(T(8))) \times 80 \\ 468800 &:= (-T(4) \times F(6) + T(T(8))) \times 800 \\ 4688000 &:= (-T(4) \times F(6) + T(T(8))) \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

517.

$$\begin{aligned} 4689 &:= (F(4) + 6 + C(8)) \times 9 \\ 46890 &:= (F(4) + 6 + C(8)) \times 90 \\ 468900 &:= (F(4) + 6 + C(8)) \times 900 \\ 4689000 &:= (F(4) + 6 + C(8)) \times 9000 \end{aligned}$$

518.

$$\begin{aligned} 4695 &:= (F(Q(4)) - F(6) \times (\sqrt{9})!) \times 5 \\ 46950 &:= (F(Q(4)) - F(6) \times (\sqrt{9})!) \times 50 \\ 469500 &:= (F(Q(4)) - F(6) \times (\sqrt{9})!) \times 500 \\ 4695000 &:= (F(Q(4)) - F(6) \times (\sqrt{9})!) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

519.

$$\begin{aligned} 4695 &:= (T(4) \times T(6) + C(9)) \times 5 \\ 46950 &:= (T(4) \times T(6) + C(9)) \times 50 \\ 469500 &:= (T(4) \times T(6) + C(9)) \times 500 \\ 4695000 &:= (T(4) \times T(6) + C(9)) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

520.

$$\begin{aligned} 4697 &:= (-4 + 6! - T(9)) \times 7 \\ 46970 &:= (-4 + 6! - T(9)) \times 70 \\ 469700 &:= (-4 + 6! - T(9)) \times 700 \\ 4697000 &:= (-4 + 6! - T(9)) \times 7000 \end{aligned}$$

521.

$$\begin{aligned}4697 &:= (F(T(4)) + T(6) + T(F(9))) \times 7 \\46970 &:= (F(T(4)) + T(6) + T(F(9))) \times 70 \\469700 &:= (F(T(4)) + T(6) + T(F(9))) \times 700 \\4697000 &:= (F(T(4)) + T(6) + T(F(9))) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

522.

$$\begin{aligned}4702 &:= (T(\sqrt{4}) \times Q(T(7)) - 0!) \times 2 \\47020 &:= (T(\sqrt{4}) \times Q(T(7)) - 0!) \times 20 \\470200 &:= (T(\sqrt{4}) \times Q(T(7)) - 0!) \times 200 \\4702000 &:= (T(\sqrt{4}) \times Q(T(7)) - 0!) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

523.

$$\begin{aligned}4716 &:= (\sqrt{4} + Q(T(7))) \times 6 \\47160 &:= (\sqrt{4} + Q(T(7))) \times 60 \\471600 &:= (\sqrt{4} + Q(T(7))) \times 600 \\4716000 &:= (\sqrt{4} + Q(T(7))) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

524.

$$\begin{aligned}4720 &:= (F(4) + F(F(7))) \times 20 \\47200 &:= (F(4) + F(F(7))) \times 200 \\472000 &:= (F(4) + F(F(7))) \times 2000 \\4720000 &:= (F(4) + F(F(7))) \times 20000\end{aligned}$$

525.

$$\begin{aligned}4722 &:= (T(\sqrt{4}) + Q(T(7))) \times T(2) \times 2 \\47220 &:= (T(\sqrt{4}) + Q(T(7))) \times T(2) \times 20 \\472200 &:= (T(\sqrt{4}) + Q(T(7))) \times T(2) \times 200 \\4722000 &:= (T(\sqrt{4}) + Q(T(7))) \times T(2) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

526.

$$\begin{aligned}4725 &:= (Q(4! + 7) - Q(Q(2))) \times 5 \\47250 &:= (Q(4! + 7) - Q(Q(2))) \times 50 \\472500 &:= (Q(4! + 7) - Q(Q(2))) \times 500 \\4725000 &:= (Q(4! + 7) - Q(Q(2))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

527.

$$\begin{aligned}4728 &:= (-4 + T(F(7 + 2))) \times 8 \\47280 &:= (-4 + T(F(7 + 2))) \times 80 \\472800 &:= (-4 + T(F(7 + 2))) \times 800 \\4728000 &:= (-4 + T(F(7 + 2))) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

528.

$$\begin{aligned}4728 &:= (Q(4!) + F(7) + 2) \times 8 \\47280 &:= (Q(4!) + F(7) + 2) \times 80 \\472800 &:= (Q(4!) + F(7) + 2) \times 800 \\4728000 &:= (Q(4!) + F(7) + 2) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

529.

$$\begin{aligned}4732 &:= (C(7 \times \sqrt{4}) - T(C(3))) \times 2 \\47320 &:= (C(7 \times \sqrt{4}) - T(C(3))) \times 20 \\473200 &:= (C(7 \times \sqrt{4}) - T(C(3))) \times 200 \\4732000 &:= (C(7 \times \sqrt{4}) - T(C(3))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

530.

$$\begin{aligned}4735 &:= (F(Q(4)) - Q(7) + Q(3)) \times 5 \\47350 &:= (F(Q(4)) - Q(7) + Q(3)) \times 50 \\473500 &:= (F(Q(4)) - Q(7) + Q(3)) \times 500 \\4735000 &:= (F(Q(4)) - Q(7) + Q(3)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

531.

$$\begin{aligned}4742 &:= (-4! + Q(Q(7)) - F(4)!) \times 2 \\47420 &:= (-4! + Q(Q(7)) - F(4)!) \times 20 \\474200 &:= (-4! + Q(Q(7)) - F(4)!) \times 200 \\4742000 &:= (-4! + Q(Q(7)) - F(4)!) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

532.

$$\begin{aligned}4744 &:= (4! \times Q(7) + T(4)) \times 4 \\47440 &:= (4! \times Q(7) + T(4)) \times 40 \\474400 &:= (4! \times Q(7) + T(4)) \times 400 \\4744000 &:= (4! \times Q(7) + T(4)) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

533.

$$\begin{aligned}4744 &:= (F(4)!! + F(F(7)) \times F(F(4))) \times 4 \\47440 &:= (F(4)!! + F(F(7)) \times F(F(4))) \times 40 \\474400 &:= (F(4)!! + F(F(7)) \times F(F(4))) \times 400 \\4744000 &:= (F(4)!! + F(F(7)) \times F(F(4))) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

534.

$$\begin{aligned}4744 &:= (F(4)!! + F(F(7)) \times \sqrt{4}) \times 4 \\47440 &:= (F(4)!! + F(F(7)) \times \sqrt{4}) \times 40 \\474400 &:= (F(4)!! + F(F(7)) \times \sqrt{4}) \times 400 \\4744000 &:= (F(4)!! + F(F(7)) \times \sqrt{4}) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

535.

$$\begin{aligned}4744 &:= (T(4) + T(-7 + T(T(4)))) \times 4 \\47440 &:= (T(4) + T(-7 + T(T(4)))) \times 40 \\474400 &:= (T(4) + T(-7 + T(T(4)))) \times 400 \\4744000 &:= (T(4) + T(-7 + T(T(4)))) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

536.

$$\begin{aligned}4745 &:= (F(4)!! + F(F(7)) - 4) \times 5 \\47450 &:= (F(4)!! + F(F(7)) - 4) \times 50 \\474500 &:= (F(4)!! + F(F(7)) - 4) \times 500 \\4745000 &:= (F(4)!! + F(F(7)) - 4) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

537.

$$\begin{aligned}4747 &:= (T(4) + T(F(7))) \times 47 \\47470 &:= (T(4) + T(F(7))) \times 470 \\474700 &:= (T(4) + T(F(7))) \times 4700 \\4747000 &:= (T(4) + T(F(7))) \times 47000\end{aligned}$$

538.

$$\begin{aligned}4750 &:= (4 + T(F(7))) \times 50 \\47500 &:= (4 + T(F(7))) \times 500 \\475000 &:= (4 + T(F(7))) \times 5000 \\4750000 &:= (4 + T(F(7))) \times 50000\end{aligned}$$

539.

$$\begin{aligned}4762 &:= (Q(4) + Q(Q(7)) - Q(6)) \times 2 \\47620 &:= (Q(4) + Q(Q(7)) - Q(6)) \times 20 \\476200 &:= (Q(4) + Q(Q(7)) - Q(6)) \times 200 \\4762000 &:= (Q(4) + Q(Q(7)) - Q(6)) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

540.

$$\begin{aligned}4765 &:= (4 \times F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) \times 5 \\47650 &:= (4 \times F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) \times 50 \\476500 &:= (4 \times F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) \times 500 \\4765000 &:= (4 \times F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

541.

$$4765 := (4 \times F(F(7)) + T(6)) \times 5$$

$$47650 := (4 \times F(F(7)) + T(6)) \times 50$$

$$476500 := (4 \times F(F(7)) + T(6)) \times 500$$

$$4765000 := (4 \times F(F(7)) + T(6)) \times 5000$$

542.

$$4765 := (F(\sqrt{4}) \times F(F(7)) + 6!) \times 5$$

$$47650 := (F(\sqrt{4}) \times F(F(7)) + 6!) \times 50$$

$$476500 := (F(\sqrt{4}) \times F(F(7)) + 6!) \times 500$$

$$4765000 := (F(\sqrt{4}) \times F(F(7)) + 6!) \times 5000$$

543.

$$4767 := (T(4) - Q(7) + 6!) \times 7$$

$$47670 := (T(4) - Q(7) + 6!) \times 70$$

$$476700 := (T(4) - Q(7) + 6!) \times 700$$

$$4767000 := (T(4) - Q(7) + 6!) \times 7000$$

544.

$$4768 := (F(\sqrt{4}) + T(T(7) + 6)) \times 8$$

$$47680 := (F(\sqrt{4}) + T(T(7) + 6)) \times 80$$

$$476800 := (F(\sqrt{4}) + T(T(7) + 6)) \times 800$$

$$4768000 := (F(\sqrt{4}) + T(T(7) + 6)) \times 8000$$

545.

$$4772 := (-C(4) + Q(Q(7)) + Q(7)) \times 2$$

$$47720 := (-C(4) + Q(Q(7)) + Q(7)) \times 20$$

$$477200 := (-C(4) + Q(Q(7)) + Q(7)) \times 200$$

$$4772000 := (-C(4) + Q(Q(7)) + Q(7)) \times 2000$$

546.

$$4772 := (-\sqrt{4} + Q(Q(7)) - F(7)) \times 2$$

$$47720 := (-\sqrt{4} + Q(Q(7)) - F(7)) \times 20$$

$$477200 := (-\sqrt{4} + Q(Q(7)) - F(7)) \times 200$$

$$4772000 := (-\sqrt{4} + Q(Q(7)) - F(7)) \times 2000$$

547.

$$4779 := (T(4!) + T(-7 + T(7))) \times 9$$

$$47790 := (T(4!) + T(-7 + T(7))) \times 90$$

$$477900 := (T(4!) + T(-7 + T(7))) \times 900$$

$$4779000 := (T(4!) + T(-7 + T(7))) \times 9000$$

548.

$$4782 := (-\sqrt{4} + Q(Q(7)) - 8) \times 2$$

$$47820 := (-\sqrt{4} + Q(Q(7)) - 8) \times 20$$

$$478200 := (-\sqrt{4} + Q(Q(7)) - 8) \times 200$$

$$4782000 := (-\sqrt{4} + Q(Q(7)) - 8) \times 2000$$

549.

$$4792 := (4 + Q(Q(7)) - 9) \times 2$$

$$47920 := (4 + Q(Q(7)) - 9) \times 20$$

$$479200 := (4 + Q(Q(7)) - 9) \times 200$$

$$4792000 := (4 + Q(Q(7)) - 9) \times 2000$$

550.

$$4792 := (-\sqrt{4} + Q(Q(7)) - \sqrt{9}) \times 2$$

$$47920 := (-\sqrt{4} + Q(Q(7)) - \sqrt{9}) \times 20$$

$$479200 := (-\sqrt{4} + Q(Q(7)) - \sqrt{9}) \times 200$$

$$4792000 := (-\sqrt{4} + Q(Q(7)) - \sqrt{9}) \times 2000$$

551.

$$4794 := (C(4) - F(7)) \times 94$$

$$47940 := (C(4) - F(7)) \times 940$$

$$479400 := (C(4) - F(7)) \times 9400$$

$$4794000 := (C(4) - F(7)) \times 94000$$

552.

$$4794 := (\sqrt{4} + Q(7)) \times 94$$

$$47940 := (\sqrt{4} + Q(7)) \times 940$$

$$479400 := (\sqrt{4} + Q(7)) \times 9400$$

$$4794000 := (\sqrt{4} + Q(7)) \times 94000$$

553.

$$4795 := (4 \times T(F(7)) + T(F(9))) \times 5$$

$$47950 := (4 \times T(F(7)) + T(F(9))) \times 50$$

$$479500 := (4 \times T(F(7)) + T(F(9))) \times 500$$

$$4795000 := (4 \times T(F(7)) + T(F(9))) \times 5000$$

554.

$$4800 := F(4)! \times 800$$

$$48000 := F(4)! \times 8000$$

$$480000 := F(4)! \times 80000$$

$$4800000 := F(4)! \times 800000$$

555.

$$4800 := T(F(4)) \times 800$$

$$48000 := T(F(4)) \times 8000$$

$$480000 := T(F(4)) \times 80000$$

$$4800000 := T(F(4)) \times 800000$$

556.

$$4800 := T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times 800$$

$$48000 := T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times 8000$$

$$480000 := T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times 80000$$

$$4800000 := T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times 800000$$

557.

$$4802 := (T(4!) \times 8 + 0!) \times 2$$

$$48020 := (T(4!) \times 8 + 0!) \times 20$$

$$480200 := (T(4!) \times 8 + 0!) \times 200$$

$$4802000 := (T(4!) \times 8 + 0!) \times 2000$$

558.

$$4802 := Q(48 + 0!) \times 2$$

$$48020 := Q(48 + 0!) \times 20$$

$$480200 := Q(48 + 0!) \times 200$$

$$4802000 := Q(48 + 0!) \times 2000$$

559.

$$4803 := (Q(-4! + Q(8)) + 0!) \times 3$$

$$48030 := (Q(-4! + Q(8)) + 0!) \times 30$$

$$480300 := (Q(-4! + Q(8)) + 0!) \times 300$$

$$4803000 := (Q(-4! + Q(8)) + 0!) \times 3000$$

560.

$$4803 := (Q(4 + T(8)) + 0!) \times 3$$

$$48030 := (Q(4 + T(8)) + 0!) \times 30$$

$$480300 := (Q(4 + T(8)) + 0!) \times 300$$

$$4803000 := (Q(4 + T(8)) + 0!) \times 3000$$

561.

$$4804 := (-4! + Q(T(8) - 0!)) \times 4$$

$$48040 := (-4! + Q(T(8) - 0!)) \times 40$$

$$480400 := (-4! + Q(T(8) - 0!)) \times 400$$

$$4804000 := (-4! + Q(T(8) - 0!)) \times 4000$$

562.

$$4805 := Q(4 \times 8 - 0!) \times 5$$

$$48050 := Q(4 \times 8 - 0!) \times 50$$

$$480500 := Q(4 \times 8 - 0!) \times 500$$

$$4805000 := Q(4 \times 8 - 0!) \times 5000$$

563.

$$4808 := (Q(T(4)) \times \sqrt{T(8)} + 0!) \times 8$$

$$48080 := (Q(T(4)) \times \sqrt{T(8)} + 0!) \times 80$$

$$480800 := (Q(T(4)) \times \sqrt{T(8)} + 0!) \times 800$$

$$4808000 := (Q(T(4)) \times \sqrt{T(8)} + 0!) \times 8000$$

564.

$$4808 := (T(F(4)) + T(F(8 + 0!))) \times 8$$

$$48080 := (T(F(4)) + T(F(8 + 0!))) \times 80$$

$$480800 := (T(F(4)) + T(F(8 + 0!))) \times 800$$

$$4808000 := (T(F(4)) + T(F(8 + 0!))) \times 8000$$

565.

$$4815 := (C(T(4)) - T(8) - 1) \times 5$$

$$48150 := (C(T(4)) - T(8) - 1) \times 50$$

$$481500 := (C(T(4)) - T(8) - 1) \times 500$$

$$4815000 := (C(T(4)) - T(8) - 1) \times 5000$$

566.

$$4815 := (T(4!) + F(8)) \times 15$$

$$48150 := (T(4!) + F(8)) \times 150$$

$$481500 := (T(4!) + F(8)) \times 1500$$

$$4815000 := (T(4!) + F(8)) \times 15000$$

567.

$$4815 := (T(4!) + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 15$$

$$48150 := (T(4!) + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 150$$

$$481500 := (T(4!) + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 1500$$

$$4815000 := (T(4!) + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 15000$$

568.

$$4820 := (T(4) + T(F(8))) \times 20$$

$$48200 := (T(4) + T(F(8))) \times 200$$

$$482000 := (T(4) + T(F(8))) \times 2000$$

$$4820000 := (T(4) + T(F(8))) \times 20000$$

569.

$$4820 := (T(4) + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times 20$$

$$48200 := (T(4) + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times 200$$

$$482000 := (T(4) + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times 2000$$

$$4820000 := (T(4) + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times 20000$$

570.

$$4825 := (T(4!) + T(T(8)) - F(2)) \times 5$$

$$48250 := (T(4!) + T(T(8)) - F(2)) \times 50$$

$$482500 := (T(4!) + T(T(8)) - F(2)) \times 500$$

$$4825000 := (T(4!) + T(T(8)) - F(2)) \times 5000$$

571.

$$4835 := (T(4!) + T(T(8)) + F(F(3))) \times 5$$

$$48350 := (T(4!) + T(T(8)) + F(F(3))) \times 50$$

$$483500 := (T(4!) + T(T(8)) + F(F(3))) \times 500$$

$$4835000 := (T(4!) + T(T(8)) + F(F(3))) \times 5000$$

572.

$$4837 := (4 + T(T(8)) + T(T(3))) \times 7$$

$$48370 := (4 + T(T(8)) + T(T(3))) \times 70$$

$$483700 := (4 + T(T(8)) + T(T(3))) \times 700$$

$$4837000 := (4 + T(T(8)) + T(T(3))) \times 7000$$

573.

$$4837 := (F(4)!! - F(8) - F(3!)) \times 7$$

$$48370 := (F(4)!! - F(8) - F(3!)) \times 70$$

$$483700 := (F(4)!! - F(8) - F(3!)) \times 700$$

$$4837000 := (F(4)!! - F(8) - F(3!)) \times 7000$$

574.

$$4837 := (F(4) \times T(F(8)) - F(3)) \times 7$$

$$48370 := (F(4) \times T(F(8)) - F(3)) \times 70$$

$$483700 := (F(4) \times T(F(8)) - F(3)) \times 700$$

$$4837000 := (F(4) \times T(F(8)) - F(3)) \times 7000$$

575.

$$4844 := (\sqrt{C(C(4))} - F(8) + F(4)!!) \times 4$$

$$48440 := (\sqrt{C(C(4))} - F(8) + F(4)!!) \times 40$$

$$484400 := (\sqrt{C(C(4))} - F(8) + F(4)!!) \times 400$$

$$4844000 := (\sqrt{C(C(4))} - F(8) + F(4)!!) \times 4000$$

576.

$$4844 := (T(T(4)) + Q(T(8) - \sqrt{4})) \times 4$$

$$48440 := (T(T(4)) + Q(T(8) - \sqrt{4})) \times 40$$

$$484400 := (T(T(4)) + Q(T(8) - \sqrt{4})) \times 400$$

$$4844000 := (T(T(4)) + Q(T(8) - \sqrt{4})) \times 4000$$

577.

$$4845 := (F(Q(4)) - F(8) + F(4)) \times 5$$

$$48450 := (F(Q(4)) - F(8) + F(4)) \times 50$$

$$484500 := (F(Q(4)) - F(8) + F(4)) \times 500$$

$$4845000 := (F(Q(4)) - F(8) + F(4)) \times 5000$$

578.

$$4845 := (T(\sqrt{4}) + T(T(8)) + T(4!)) \times 5$$

$$48450 := (T(\sqrt{4}) + T(T(8)) + T(4!)) \times 50$$

$$484500 := (T(\sqrt{4}) + T(T(8)) + T(4!)) \times 500$$

$$4845000 := (T(\sqrt{4}) + T(T(8)) + T(4!)) \times 5000$$

579.

$$4855 := (-Q(4) + F(F(8) - 5)) \times 5$$

$$48550 := (-Q(4) + F(F(8) - 5)) \times 50$$

$$485500 := (-Q(4) + F(F(8) - 5)) \times 500$$

$$4855000 := (-Q(4) + F(F(8) - 5)) \times 5000$$

580.

$$4860 := Q(Q(4!/8)) \times 60$$

$$48600 := Q(Q(4!/8)) \times 600$$

$$486000 := Q(Q(4!/8)) \times 6000$$

$$4860000 := Q(Q(4!/8)) \times 60000$$

581.

$$4860 := \sqrt{F(4)^8} \times 60$$

$$48600 := \sqrt{F(4)^8} \times 600$$

$$486000 := \sqrt{F(4)^8} \times 6000$$

$$4860000 := \sqrt{F(4)^8} \times 60000$$

582.

$$4860 := \sqrt{T(\sqrt{4})^8} \times 60$$

$$48600 := \sqrt{T(\sqrt{4})^8} \times 600$$

$$486000 := \sqrt{T(\sqrt{4})^8} \times 6000$$

$$4860000 := \sqrt{T(\sqrt{4})^8} \times 60000$$

583.

$$4863 := (-C(4) - C(F(8)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 3$$

$$48630 := (-C(4) - C(F(8)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 30$$

$$486300 := (-C(4) - C(F(8)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 300$$

$$4863000 := (-C(4) - C(F(8)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 3000$$

584.

$$4864 := (F(T(4)) + F(8)) \times 64$$

$$48640 := (F(T(4)) + F(8)) \times 640$$

$$486400 := (F(T(4)) + F(8)) \times 6400$$

$$4864000 := (F(T(4)) + F(8)) \times 64000$$

585.

$$4865 := (C(T(4)) - C(T(8 - 6))) \times 5$$

$$48650 := (C(T(4)) - C(T(8 - 6))) \times 50$$

$$486500 := (C(T(4)) - C(T(8 - 6))) \times 500$$

$$4865000 := (C(T(4)) - C(T(8 - 6))) \times 5000$$

586.

$$4866 := (F(T(4)) + T(8) \times T(6)) \times 6$$

$$48660 := (F(T(4)) + T(8) \times T(6)) \times 60$$

$$486600 := (F(T(4)) + T(8) \times T(6)) \times 600$$

$$4866000 := (F(T(4)) + T(8) \times T(6)) \times 6000$$

587.

$$4866 := (F(T(4)) + T(8) + 6!) \times 6$$

$$48660 := (F(T(4)) + T(8) + 6!) \times 60$$

$$486600 := (F(T(4)) + T(8) + 6!) \times 600$$

$$4866000 := (F(T(4)) + T(8) + 6!) \times 6000$$

588.

$$4866 := (T(T(4)) + T(8) \times T(6)) \times 6$$

$$48660 := (T(T(4)) + T(8) \times T(6)) \times 60$$

$$486600 := (T(T(4)) + T(8) \times T(6)) \times 600$$

$$4866000 := (T(T(4)) + T(8) \times T(6)) \times 6000$$

589.

$$4866 := (T(T(4)) + T(8) + 6!) \times 6$$

$$48660 := (T(T(4)) + T(8) + 6!) \times 60$$

$$486600 := (T(T(4)) + T(8) + 6!) \times 600$$

$$4866000 := (T(T(4)) + T(8) + 6!) \times 6000$$

590.

$$4869 := (\sqrt{C(4)} + F(8) + C(F(6))) \times 9$$

$$48690 := (\sqrt{C(4)} + F(8) + C(F(6))) \times 90$$

$$486900 := (\sqrt{C(4)} + F(8) + C(F(6))) \times 900$$

$$4869000 := (\sqrt{C(4)} + F(8) + C(F(6))) \times 9000$$

591.

$$\begin{aligned} 4875 &:= (Q(4 \times 8) - Q(7)) \times 5 \\ 48750 &:= (Q(4 \times 8) - Q(7)) \times 50 \\ 487500 &:= (Q(4 \times 8) - Q(7)) \times 500 \\ 4875000 &:= (Q(4 \times 8) - Q(7)) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

592.

$$\begin{aligned} 4880 &:= (F(T(4)) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 80 \\ 48800 &:= (F(T(4)) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 800 \\ 488000 &:= (F(T(4)) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 8000 \\ 4880000 &:= (F(T(4)) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 80000 \end{aligned}$$

593.

$$\begin{aligned} 4880 &:= (T(T(4)) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 80 \\ 48800 &:= (T(T(4)) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 800 \\ 488000 &:= (T(T(4)) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 8000 \\ 4880000 &:= (T(T(4)) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 80000 \end{aligned}$$

594.

$$\begin{aligned} 4884 &:= (C(\sqrt{4} + F(8)) - F(F(8))) \times 4 \\ 48840 &:= (C(\sqrt{4} + F(8)) - F(F(8))) \times 40 \\ 488400 &:= (C(\sqrt{4} + F(8)) - F(F(8))) \times 400 \\ 4884000 &:= (C(\sqrt{4} + F(8)) - F(F(8))) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

595.

$$\begin{aligned} 4885 &:= (-T(4) + F(8 + 8)) \times 5 \\ 48850 &:= (-T(4) + F(8 + 8)) \times 50 \\ 488500 &:= (-T(4) + F(8 + 8)) \times 500 \\ 4885000 &:= (-T(4) + F(8 + 8)) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

596.

$$\begin{aligned} 4893 &:= (Q(4) \times C(8) - Q(Q(9))) \times 3 \\ 48930 &:= (Q(4) \times C(8) - Q(Q(9))) \times 30 \\ 489300 &:= (Q(4) \times C(8) - Q(Q(9))) \times 300 \\ 4893000 &:= (Q(4) \times C(8) - Q(Q(9))) \times 3000 \end{aligned}$$

597.

$$\begin{aligned} 4895 &:= (Q(4 \times 8) - T(9)) \times 5 \\ 48950 &:= (Q(4 \times 8) - T(9)) \times 50 \\ 489500 &:= (Q(4 \times 8) - T(9)) \times 500 \\ 4895000 &:= (Q(4 \times 8) - T(9)) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

598.

$$\begin{aligned} 4895 &:= (\sqrt{4} \times C(8) - T(9)) \times 5 \\ 48950 &:= (\sqrt{4} \times C(8) - T(9)) \times 50 \\ 489500 &:= (\sqrt{4} \times C(8) - T(9)) \times 500 \\ 4895000 &:= (\sqrt{4} \times C(8) - T(9)) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

599.

$$\begin{aligned} 4896 &:= F(4) \times 8 \times F(9) \times 6 \\ 48960 &:= F(4) \times 8 \times F(9) \times 60 \\ 489600 &:= F(4) \times 8 \times F(9) \times 600 \\ 4896000 &:= F(4) \times 8 \times F(9) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

600.

$$\begin{aligned} 4896 &:= T(8 \times \sqrt{4}) \times T(\sqrt{9}) \times 6 \\ 48960 &:= T(8 \times \sqrt{4}) \times T(\sqrt{9}) \times 60 \\ 489600 &:= T(8 \times \sqrt{4}) \times T(\sqrt{9}) \times 600 \\ 4896000 &:= T(8 \times \sqrt{4}) \times T(\sqrt{9}) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

601.

$$\begin{aligned}4904 &:= (T(49) + 0!) \times 4 \\49040 &:= (T(49) + 0!) \times 40 \\490400 &:= (T(49) + 0!) \times 400 \\4904000 &:= (T(49) + 0!) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

602.

$$\begin{aligned}4905 &:= (F(Q(4)) - (\sqrt{9})!) \times 5 \\49050 &:= (F(Q(4)) - (\sqrt{9})!) \times 50 \\490500 &:= (F(Q(4)) - (\sqrt{9})!) \times 500 \\4905000 &:= (F(Q(4)) - (\sqrt{9})!) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

603.

$$\begin{aligned}4905 &:= (-F(T(4)) + T(T(9)) + 0!) \times 5 \\49050 &:= (-F(T(4)) + T(T(9)) + 0!) \times 50 \\490500 &:= (-F(T(4)) + T(T(9)) + 0!) \times 500 \\4905000 &:= (-F(T(4)) + T(T(9)) + 0!) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

604.

$$\begin{aligned}4905 &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(T(9)) + 0!) \times 5 \\49050 &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(T(9)) + 0!) \times 50 \\490500 &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(T(9)) + 0!) \times 500 \\4905000 &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(T(9)) + 0!) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

605.

$$\begin{aligned}4907 &:= (-C(F(4)) + C(9) - 0!) \times 7 \\49070 &:= (-C(F(4)) + C(9) - 0!) \times 70 \\490700 &:= (-C(F(4)) + C(9) - 0!) \times 700 \\4907000 &:= (-C(F(4)) + C(9) - 0!) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

606.

$$\begin{aligned}4915 &:= (F(Q(4)) - \sqrt{9} - 1) \times 5 \\49150 &:= (F(Q(4)) - \sqrt{9} - 1) \times 50 \\491500 &:= (F(Q(4)) - \sqrt{9} - 1) \times 500 \\4915000 &:= (F(Q(4)) - \sqrt{9} - 1) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

607.

$$\begin{aligned}4924 &:= (F(T(4)) + T(T(9)) + T(2)) \times 4 \\49240 &:= (F(T(4)) + T(T(9)) + T(2)) \times 40 \\492400 &:= (F(T(4)) + T(T(9)) + T(2)) \times 400 \\4924000 &:= (F(T(4)) + T(T(9)) + T(2)) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

608.

$$\begin{aligned}4925 &:= (F(4^{F(\sqrt{9})}) - 2) \times 5 \\49250 &:= (F(4^{F(\sqrt{9})}) - 2) \times 50 \\492500 &:= (F(4^{F(\sqrt{9})}) - 2) \times 500 \\4925000 &:= (F(4^{F(\sqrt{9})}) - 2) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

609.

$$\begin{aligned}4925 &:= (-\sqrt{4} + F(F(\sqrt{9}) \times C(2))) \times 5 \\49250 &:= (-\sqrt{4} + F(F(\sqrt{9}) \times C(2))) \times 50 \\492500 &:= (-\sqrt{4} + F(F(\sqrt{9}) \times C(2))) \times 500 \\4925000 &:= (-\sqrt{4} + F(F(\sqrt{9}) \times C(2))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

610.

$$\begin{aligned}4926 &:= (F(F(F(4))) + T(F(9)) + T(T(2))) \times 6 \\49260 &:= (F(F(F(4))) + T(F(9)) + T(T(2))) \times 60 \\492600 &:= (F(F(F(4))) + T(F(9)) + T(T(2))) \times 600 \\4926000 &:= (F(F(F(4))) + T(F(9)) + T(T(2))) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

611.

$$\begin{aligned} 4926 &:= (F(\sqrt{4}) + T(F(9) + T(T(2)))) \times 6 \\ 49260 &:= (F(\sqrt{4}) + T(F(9) + T(T(2)))) \times 60 \\ 492600 &:= (F(\sqrt{4}) + T(F(9) + T(T(2)))) \times 600 \\ 4926000 &:= (F(\sqrt{4}) + T(F(9) + T(T(2)))) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

612.

$$\begin{aligned} 4926 &:= (T(4!) + 9 + C(C(2))) \times 6 \\ 49260 &:= (T(4!) + 9 + C(C(2))) \times 60 \\ 492600 &:= (T(4!) + 9 + C(C(2))) \times 600 \\ 4926000 &:= (T(4!) + 9 + C(C(2))) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

613.

$$\begin{aligned} 4928 &:= (T(F(4)) + F(T(9)/T(2))) \times 8 \\ 49280 &:= (T(F(4)) + F(T(9)/T(2))) \times 80 \\ 492800 &:= (T(F(4)) + F(T(9)/T(2))) \times 800 \\ 4928000 &:= (T(F(4)) + F(T(9)/T(2))) \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

614.

$$\begin{aligned} 4928 &:= (T(\sqrt{4} + T(9)) - C(C(2))) \times 8 \\ 49280 &:= (T(\sqrt{4} + T(9)) - C(C(2))) \times 80 \\ 492800 &:= (T(\sqrt{4} + T(9)) - C(C(2))) \times 800 \\ 4928000 &:= (T(\sqrt{4} + T(9)) - C(C(2))) \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

615.

$$\begin{aligned} 4928 &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(T(T(\sqrt{9})))) \times 28 \\ 49280 &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(T(T(\sqrt{9})))) \times 280 \\ 492800 &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(T(T(\sqrt{9})))) \times 2800 \\ 4928000 &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(T(T(\sqrt{9})))) \times 28000 \end{aligned}$$

616.

$$\begin{aligned} 4935 &:= (\sqrt{4} + T(9)) \times T(T(3)) \times 5 \\ 49350 &:= (\sqrt{4} + T(9)) \times T(T(3)) \times 50 \\ 493500 &:= (\sqrt{4} + T(9)) \times T(T(3)) \times 500 \\ 4935000 &:= (\sqrt{4} + T(9)) \times T(T(3)) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

617.

$$\begin{aligned} 4935 &:= F(4 + 9 + 3) \times 5 \\ 49350 &:= F(4 + 9 + 3) \times 50 \\ 493500 &:= F(4 + 9 + 3) \times 500 \\ 4935000 &:= F(4 + 9 + 3) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

618.

$$\begin{aligned} 4942 &:= (F(T(4)) \times T(9) - 4) \times 2 \\ 49420 &:= (F(T(4)) \times T(9) - 4) \times 20 \\ 494200 &:= (F(T(4)) \times T(9) - 4) \times 200 \\ 4942000 &:= (F(T(4)) \times T(9) - 4) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

619.

$$\begin{aligned} 4942 &:= (T(T(4)) \times T(9) - 4) \times 2 \\ 49420 &:= (T(T(4)) \times T(9) - 4) \times 20 \\ 494200 &:= (T(T(4)) \times T(9) - 4) \times 200 \\ 4942000 &:= (T(T(4)) \times T(9) - 4) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

620.

$$\begin{aligned} 4945 &:= (F(Q(4)) + F(9/F(4))) \times 5 \\ 49450 &:= (F(Q(4)) + F(9/F(4))) \times 50 \\ 494500 &:= (F(Q(4)) + F(9/F(4))) \times 500 \\ 4945000 &:= (F(Q(4)) + F(9/F(4))) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

621.

$$\begin{aligned}4945 &:= (\sqrt{4} + F(F(\sqrt{9})^4)) \times 5 \\49450 &:= (\sqrt{4} + F(F(\sqrt{9})^4)) \times 50 \\494500 &:= (\sqrt{4} + F(F(\sqrt{9})^4)) \times 500 \\4945000 &:= (\sqrt{4} + F(F(\sqrt{9})^4)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

622.

$$\begin{aligned}4945 &:= (T(T(4) + F(9)) - F(\sqrt{4})) \times 5 \\49450 &:= (T(T(4) + F(9)) - F(\sqrt{4})) \times 50 \\494500 &:= (T(T(4) + F(9)) - F(\sqrt{4})) \times 500 \\4945000 &:= (T(T(4) + F(9)) - F(\sqrt{4})) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

623.

$$\begin{aligned}4955 &:= (4 + F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) - 5)) \times 5 \\49550 &:= (4 + F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) - 5)) \times 50 \\495500 &:= (4 + F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) - 5)) \times 500 \\4955000 &:= (4 + F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) - 5)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

624.

$$\begin{aligned}4955 &:= (4 + F(Q(9 - 5))) \times 5 \\49550 &:= (4 + F(Q(9 - 5))) \times 50 \\495500 &:= (4 + F(Q(9 - 5))) \times 500 \\4955000 &:= (4 + F(Q(9 - 5))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

625.

$$\begin{aligned}4959 &:= (C(4) \times 9 - Q(5)) \times 9 \\49590 &:= (C(4) \times 9 - Q(5)) \times 90 \\495900 &:= (C(4) \times 9 - Q(5)) \times 900 \\4959000 &:= (C(4) \times 9 - Q(5)) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

626.

$$\begin{aligned}4962 &:= (F(T(4)) \times T(9) + 6) \times 2 \\49620 &:= (F(T(4)) \times T(9) + 6) \times 20 \\496200 &:= (F(T(4)) \times T(9) + 6) \times 200 \\4962000 &:= (F(T(4)) \times T(9) + 6) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

627.

$$\begin{aligned}4962 &:= (T(T(4)) \times T(9) + 6) \times 2 \\49620 &:= (T(T(4)) \times T(9) + 6) \times 20 \\496200 &:= (T(T(4)) \times T(9) + 6) \times 200 \\4962000 &:= (T(T(4)) \times T(9) + 6) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

628.

$$\begin{aligned}4965 &:= (F(4)! + F(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(6))) \times 5 \\49650 &:= (F(4)! + F(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(6))) \times 50 \\496500 &:= (F(4)! + F(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(6))) \times 500 \\4965000 &:= (F(4)! + F(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(6))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

629.

$$\begin{aligned}4965 &:= (F(4^{F(\sqrt{9})}) + 6) \times 5 \\49650 &:= (F(4^{F(\sqrt{9})}) + 6) \times 50 \\496500 &:= (F(4^{F(\sqrt{9})}) + 6) \times 500 \\4965000 &:= (F(4^{F(\sqrt{9})}) + 6) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

630.

$$\begin{aligned}4968 &:= F(4) \times (-9 + C(6)) \times 8 \\49680 &:= F(4) \times (-9 + C(6)) \times 80 \\496800 &:= F(4) \times (-9 + C(6)) \times 800 \\4968000 &:= F(4) \times (-9 + C(6)) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

631.

$$4972 := (4 + Q(9) + Q(Q(7))) \times 2$$

$$49720 := (4 + Q(9) + Q(Q(7))) \times 20$$

$$497200 := (4 + Q(9) + Q(Q(7))) \times 200$$

$$4972000 := (4 + Q(9) + Q(Q(7))) \times 2000$$

632.

$$4972 := (T(4^{\sqrt{9}}) + T(T(7))) \times 2$$

$$49720 := (T(4^{\sqrt{9}}) + T(T(7))) \times 20$$

$$497200 := (T(4^{\sqrt{9}}) + T(T(7))) \times 200$$

$$4972000 := (T(4^{\sqrt{9}}) + T(T(7))) \times 2000$$

633.

$$4977 := (-\sqrt{4} + (\sqrt{9})!! - 7) \times 7$$

$$49770 := (-\sqrt{4} + (\sqrt{9})!! - 7) \times 70$$

$$497700 := (-\sqrt{4} + (\sqrt{9})!! - 7) \times 700$$

$$4977000 := (-\sqrt{4} + (\sqrt{9})!! - 7) \times 7000$$

634.

$$4977 := (T(4) + C(9) - T(7)) \times 7$$

$$49770 := (T(4) + C(9) - T(7)) \times 70$$

$$497700 := (T(4) + C(9) - T(7)) \times 700$$

$$4977000 := (T(4) + C(9) - T(7)) \times 7000$$

635.

$$4982 := (T(F(4)) + T(F(9) + T(8))) \times 2$$

$$49820 := (T(F(4)) + T(F(9) + T(8))) \times 20$$

$$498200 := (T(F(4)) + T(F(9) + T(8))) \times 200$$

$$4982000 := (T(F(4)) + T(F(9) + T(8))) \times 2000$$

636.

$$4984 := (T(49) + F(8)) \times 4$$

$$49840 := (T(49) + F(8)) \times 40$$

$$498400 := (T(49) + F(8)) \times 400$$

$$4984000 := (T(49) + F(8)) \times 4000$$

637.

$$4984 := (T(49) + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 4$$

$$49840 := (T(49) + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 40$$

$$498400 := (T(49) + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 400$$

$$4984000 := (T(49) + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 4000$$

638.

$$4985 := (-\sqrt{4} + T(T(9)) - T(8)) \times 5$$

$$49850 := (-\sqrt{4} + T(T(9)) - T(8)) \times 50$$

$$498500 := (-\sqrt{4} + T(T(9)) - T(8)) \times 500$$

$$4985000 := (-\sqrt{4} + T(T(9)) - T(8)) \times 5000$$

639.

$$4985 := (\sqrt{C(C(4))} - \sqrt{C(9)} + C(8)) \times 5$$

$$49850 := (\sqrt{C(C(4))} - \sqrt{C(9)} + C(8)) \times 50$$

$$498500 := (\sqrt{C(C(4))} - \sqrt{C(9)} + C(8)) \times 500$$

$$4985000 := (\sqrt{C(C(4))} - \sqrt{C(9)} + C(8)) \times 5000$$

640.

$$4986 := (F(T(4)) \times \sqrt{9} + T(T(8))) \times 6$$

$$49860 := (F(T(4)) \times \sqrt{9} + T(T(8))) \times 60$$

$$498600 := (F(T(4)) \times \sqrt{9} + T(T(8))) \times 600$$

$$4986000 := (F(T(4)) \times \sqrt{9} + T(T(8))) \times 6000$$

641.

$$\begin{aligned} 4986 &:= (T(T(4)) \times \sqrt{9} + T(T(8))) \times 6 \\ 49860 &:= (T(T(4)) \times \sqrt{9} + T(T(8))) \times 60 \\ 498600 &:= (T(T(4)) \times \sqrt{9} + T(T(8))) \times 600 \\ 4986000 &:= (T(T(4)) \times \sqrt{9} + T(T(8))) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

642.

$$\begin{aligned} 4995 &:= (-4 \times 9 + T(T(9))) \times 5 \\ 49950 &:= (-4 \times 9 + T(T(9))) \times 50 \\ 499500 &:= (-4 \times 9 + T(T(9))) \times 500 \\ 4995000 &:= (-4 \times 9 + T(T(9))) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

643.

$$\begin{aligned} 4995 &:= (C(4) - \sqrt{C(9)}) \times \sqrt{C(9)} \times 5 \\ 49950 &:= (C(4) - \sqrt{C(9)}) \times \sqrt{C(9)} \times 50 \\ 499500 &:= (C(4) - \sqrt{C(9)}) \times \sqrt{C(9)} \times 500 \\ 4995000 &:= (C(4) - \sqrt{C(9)}) \times \sqrt{C(9)} \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

644.

$$\begin{aligned} 4998 &:= (4! + C(\sqrt{9})) \times 98 \\ 49980 &:= (4! + C(\sqrt{9})) \times 980 \\ 499800 &:= (4! + C(\sqrt{9})) \times 9800 \\ 4998000 &:= (4! + C(\sqrt{9})) \times 98000 \end{aligned}$$

645.

$$\begin{aligned} 4998 &:= (4! + \sqrt{C(9)}) \times 98 \\ 49980 &:= (4! + \sqrt{C(9)}) \times 980 \\ 499800 &:= (4! + \sqrt{C(9)}) \times 9800 \\ 4998000 &:= (4! + \sqrt{C(9)}) \times 98000 \end{aligned}$$

646.

$$\begin{aligned} 4998 &:= (T(F(4)) + T(9)) \times 98 \\ 49980 &:= (T(F(4)) + T(9)) \times 980 \\ 499800 &:= (T(F(4)) + T(9)) \times 9800 \\ 4998000 &:= (T(F(4)) + T(9)) \times 98000 \end{aligned}$$

647.

$$\begin{aligned} 4998 &:= (T(T(\sqrt{4})) + T(9)) \times 98 \\ 49980 &:= (T(T(\sqrt{4})) + T(9)) \times 980 \\ 499800 &:= (T(T(\sqrt{4})) + T(9)) \times 9800 \\ 4998000 &:= (T(T(\sqrt{4})) + T(9)) \times 98000 \end{aligned}$$

648.

$$\begin{aligned} 5002 &:= (Q(50) + 0!) \times 2 \\ 50020 &:= (Q(50) + 0!) \times 20 \\ 500200 &:= (Q(50) + 0!) \times 200 \\ 5002000 &:= (Q(50) + 0!) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

649.

$$\begin{aligned} 5005 &:= (C(T(5 - 0!)) + 0!) \times 5 \\ 50050 &:= (C(T(5 - 0!)) + 0!) \times 50 \\ 500500 &:= (C(T(5 - 0!)) + 0!) \times 500 \\ 5005000 &:= (C(T(5 - 0!)) + 0!) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

650.

$$\begin{aligned} 5008 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + 0!) \times 8 \\ 50080 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + 0!) \times 80 \\ 500800 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + 0!) \times 800 \\ 5008000 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + 0!) \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

651.

$$5040 := (C(5) + 0!) \times 40$$

$$50400 := (C(5) + 0!) \times 400$$

$$504000 := (C(5) + 0!) \times 4000$$

$$5040000 := (C(5) + 0!) \times 40000$$

652.

$$5043 := Q(Q(5) + Q(04)) \times 3$$

$$50430 := Q(Q(5) + Q(04)) \times 30$$

$$504300 := Q(Q(5) + Q(04)) \times 300$$

$$5043000 := Q(Q(5) + Q(04)) \times 3000$$

653.

$$5046 := (F(T(5)) + T(T(T(F(4)))) \times 6$$

$$50460 := (F(T(5)) + T(T(T(F(4)))) \times 60$$

$$504600 := (F(T(5)) + T(T(T(F(4)))) \times 600$$

$$5046000 := (F(T(5)) + T(T(T(F(4)))) \times 6000$$

654.

$$5046 := Q(Q(5) + 04) \times 6$$

$$50460 := Q(Q(5) + 04) \times 60$$

$$504600 := Q(Q(5) + 04) \times 600$$

$$5046000 := Q(Q(5) + 04) \times 6000$$

655.

$$5048 := (F(T(5)) + T(T(F(4)))) \times 8$$

$$50480 := (F(T(5)) + T(T(F(4)))) \times 80$$

$$504800 := (F(T(5)) + T(T(F(4)))) \times 800$$

$$5048000 := (F(T(5)) + T(T(F(4)))) \times 8000$$

656.

$$5048 := (Q(Q(5)) + (-0! + 4!)) \times 8$$

$$50480 := (Q(Q(5)) + (-0! + 4!)) \times 80$$

$$504800 := (Q(Q(5)) + (-0! + 4!)) \times 800$$

$$5048000 := (Q(Q(5)) + (-0! + 4!)) \times 8000$$

657.

$$5048 := (Q(Q(5)) + (0! + \sqrt{4}!)) \times 8$$

$$50480 := (Q(Q(5)) + (0! + \sqrt{4}!)) \times 80$$

$$504800 := (Q(Q(5)) + (0! + \sqrt{4}!)) \times 800$$

$$5048000 := (Q(Q(5)) + (0! + \sqrt{4}!)) \times 8000$$

658.

$$5048 := (Q(Q(5)) + F(4!)) \times 8$$

$$50480 := (Q(Q(5)) + F(4!)) \times 80$$

$$504800 := (Q(Q(5)) + F(4!)) \times 800$$

$$5048000 := (Q(Q(5)) + F(4!)) \times 8000$$

659.

$$5048 := (Q(Q(5)) + T(0! + \sqrt{4})) \times 8$$

$$50480 := (Q(Q(5)) + T(0! + \sqrt{4})) \times 80$$

$$504800 := (Q(Q(5)) + T(0! + \sqrt{4})) \times 800$$

$$5048000 := (Q(Q(5)) + T(0! + \sqrt{4})) \times 8000$$

660.

$$5049 := (Q(Q(5)) + 0 - C(4)) \times 9$$

$$50490 := (Q(Q(5)) + 0 - C(4)) \times 90$$

$$504900 := (Q(Q(5)) + 0 - C(4)) \times 900$$

$$5049000 := (Q(Q(5)) + 0 - C(4)) \times 9000$$

661.

$$\begin{aligned} 5049 &:= (-T(5) + Q(4!)) \times 9 \\ 50490 &:= (-T(5) + Q(4!)) \times 90 \\ 504900 &:= (-T(5) + Q(4!)) \times 900 \\ 5049000 &:= (-T(5) + Q(4!)) \times 9000 \end{aligned}$$

662.

$$\begin{aligned} 5082 &:= (5! + 0!) \times F(8) \times 2 \\ 50820 &:= (5! + 0!) \times F(8) \times 20 \\ 508200 &:= (5! + 0!) \times F(8) \times 200 \\ 5082000 &:= (5! + 0!) \times F(8) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

663.

$$\begin{aligned} 5084 &:= (-Q(5) + Q(Q((\sqrt{0! + 8}!))) \times 4 \\ 50840 &:= (-Q(5) + Q(Q((\sqrt{0! + 8}!))) \times 40 \\ 508400 &:= (-Q(5) + Q(Q((\sqrt{0! + 8}!))) \times 400 \\ 5084000 &:= (-Q(5) + Q(Q((\sqrt{0! + 8}!))) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

664.

$$\begin{aligned} 5084 &:= (-Q(5) + Q(T(8))) \times 4 \\ 50840 &:= (-Q(5) + Q(T(8))) \times 40 \\ 508400 &:= (-Q(5) + Q(T(8))) \times 400 \\ 5084000 &:= (-Q(5) + Q(T(8))) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

665.

$$\begin{aligned} 5085 &:= (Q(Q(5) - 0!) + Q(F(8))) \times 5 \\ 50850 &:= (Q(Q(5) - 0!) + Q(F(8))) \times 50 \\ 508500 &:= (Q(Q(5) - 0!) + Q(F(8))) \times 500 \\ 5085000 &:= (Q(Q(5) - 0!) + Q(F(8))) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

666.

$$\begin{aligned} 5088 &:= (C(5) - 0! + C(8)) \times 8 \\ 50880 &:= (C(5) - 0! + C(8)) \times 80 \\ 508800 &:= (C(5) - 0! + C(8)) \times 800 \\ 5088000 &:= (C(5) - 0! + C(8)) \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

667.

$$\begin{aligned} 5112 &:= T(5 + T(11)) \times 2 \\ 51120 &:= T(5 + T(11)) \times 20 \\ 511200 &:= T(5 + T(11)) \times 200 \\ 5112000 &:= T(5 + T(11)) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

668.

$$\begin{aligned} 5128 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + Q(Q(2))) \times 8 \\ 51280 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + Q(Q(2))) \times 80 \\ 512800 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + Q(Q(2))) \times 800 \\ 5128000 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + Q(Q(2))) \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

669.

$$\begin{aligned} 5130 &:= T(\sqrt{T(Q(5)) - 1}) \times 30 \\ 51300 &:= T(\sqrt{T(Q(5)) - 1}) \times 300 \\ 513000 &:= T(\sqrt{T(Q(5)) - 1}) \times 3000 \\ 5130000 &:= T(\sqrt{T(Q(5)) - 1}) \times 30000 \end{aligned}$$

670.

$$\begin{aligned} 5133 &:= T(C(5 - 1) - T(3)) \times 3 \\ 51330 &:= T(C(5 - 1) - T(3)) \times 30 \\ 513300 &:= T(C(5 - 1) - T(3)) \times 300 \\ 5133000 &:= T(C(5 - 1) - T(3)) \times 3000 \end{aligned}$$

671.

$$5133 := T(F(T(5 - 1)) + 3) \times 3$$

$$51330 := T(F(T(5 - 1)) + 3) \times 30$$

$$513300 := T(F(T(5 - 1)) + 3) \times 300$$

$$5133000 := T(F(T(5 - 1)) + 3) \times 3000$$

672.

$$5133 := T(T(T(5 - 1)) + 3) \times 3$$

$$51330 := T(T(T(5 - 1)) + 3) \times 30$$

$$513300 := T(T(T(5 - 1)) + 3) \times 300$$

$$5133000 := T(T(T(5 - 1)) + 3) \times 3000$$

673.

$$5135 := (C(T(5 - 1)) + C(3)) \times 5$$

$$51350 := (C(T(5 - 1)) + C(3)) \times 50$$

$$513500 := (C(T(5 - 1)) + C(3)) \times 500$$

$$5135000 := (C(T(5 - 1)) + C(3)) \times 5000$$

674.

$$5136 := (T(Q(5 - 1)) + T(3!)) \times 6$$

$$51360 := (T(Q(5 - 1)) + T(3!)) \times 60$$

$$513600 := (T(Q(5 - 1)) + T(3!)) \times 600$$

$$5136000 := (T(Q(5 - 1)) + T(3!)) \times 6000$$

675.

$$5136 := (T(T(5) + 1) + T(3!)) \times 6$$

$$51360 := (T(T(5) + 1) + T(3!)) \times 60$$

$$513600 := (T(T(5) + 1) + T(3!)) \times 600$$

$$5136000 := (T(T(5) + 1) + T(3!)) \times 6000$$

676.

$$5139 := (-5 + Q((1 + 3)!)) \times 9$$

$$51390 := (-5 + Q((1 + 3)!)) \times 90$$

$$513900 := (-5 + Q((1 + 3)!)) \times 900$$

$$5139000 := (-5 + Q((1 + 3)!)) \times 9000$$

677.

$$5144 := (Q(Q(5 + 1)) - T(4)) \times 4$$

$$51440 := (Q(Q(5 + 1)) - T(4)) \times 40$$

$$514400 := (Q(Q(5 + 1)) - T(4)) \times 400$$

$$5144000 := (Q(Q(5 + 1)) - T(4)) \times 4000$$

678.

$$5152 := (Q(51) - Q(5)) \times 2$$

$$51520 := (Q(51) - Q(5)) \times 20$$

$$515200 := (Q(51) - Q(5)) \times 200$$

$$5152000 := (Q(51) - Q(5)) \times 2000$$

679.

$$5168 := (F(T(5)) + T(F(6))) \times 8$$

$$51680 := (F(T(5)) + T(F(6))) \times 80$$

$$516800 := (F(T(5)) + T(F(6))) \times 800$$

$$5168000 := (F(T(5)) + T(F(6))) \times 8000$$

680.

$$5184 := \sqrt{(5 + 1)^8} \times 4$$

$$51840 := \sqrt{(5 + 1)^8} \times 40$$

$$518400 := \sqrt{(5 + 1)^8} \times 400$$

$$5184000 := \sqrt{(5 + 1)^8} \times 4000$$

681.

$$5187 := ((5 + 1)! + F(8)) \times 7$$

$$51870 := ((5 + 1)! + F(8)) \times 70$$

$$518700 := ((5 + 1)! + F(8)) \times 700$$

$$5187000 := ((5 + 1)! + F(8)) \times 7000$$

682.

$$5187 := T(\sqrt{5-1} + T(8)) \times 7$$

$$51870 := T(\sqrt{5-1} + T(8)) \times 70$$

$$518700 := T(\sqrt{5-1} + T(8)) \times 700$$

$$5187000 := T(\sqrt{5-1} + T(8)) \times 7000$$

683.

$$5202 := Q(Q(5) \times 2 + 0!) \times 2$$

$$52020 := Q(Q(5) \times 2 + 0!) \times 20$$

$$520200 := Q(Q(5) \times 2 + 0!) \times 200$$

$$5202000 := Q(Q(5) \times 2 + 0!) \times 2000$$

684.

$$5204 := (5 + Q(Q((2 + 0)!))) \times 4$$

$$52040 := (5 + Q(Q((2 + 0)!))) \times 40$$

$$520400 := (5 + Q(Q((2 + 0)!))) \times 400$$

$$5204000 := (5 + Q(Q((2 + 0)!))) \times 4000$$

685.

$$5220 := (5 + Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times 20$$

$$52200 := (5 + Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times 200$$

$$522000 := (5 + Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times 2000$$

$$5220000 := (5 + Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times 20000$$

686.

$$5225 := (Q(T(5)) - Q(Q(2))) \times 25$$

$$52250 := (Q(T(5)) - Q(Q(2))) \times 250$$

$$522500 := (Q(T(5)) - Q(Q(2))) \times 2500$$

$$5225000 := (Q(T(5)) - Q(Q(2))) \times 25000$$

687.

$$5225 := (T(5^2) + T(T(2)!)) \times 5$$

$$52250 := (T(5^2) + T(T(2)!)) \times 50$$

$$522500 := (T(5^2) + T(T(2)!)) \times 500$$

$$5225000 := (T(5^2) + T(T(2)!)) \times 5000$$

688.

$$5226 := (-5! + F(Q(Q(2))) + Q(2)) \times 6$$

$$52260 := (-5! + F(Q(Q(2))) + Q(2)) \times 60$$

$$522600 := (-5! + F(Q(Q(2))) + Q(2)) \times 600$$

$$5226000 := (-5! + F(Q(Q(2))) + Q(2)) \times 6000$$

689.

$$5226 := (Q(T(5)) - Q(2!)) \times 26$$

$$52260 := (Q(T(5)) - Q(2!)) \times 260$$

$$522600 := (Q(T(5)) - Q(2!)) \times 2600$$

$$5226000 := (Q(T(5)) - Q(2!)) \times 26000$$

690.

$$5229 := (5 + Q((2 + 2)!)) \times 9$$

$$52290 := (5 + Q((2 + 2)!)) \times 90$$

$$522900 := (5 + Q((2 + 2)!)) \times 900$$

$$5229000 := (5 + Q((2 + 2)!)) \times 9000$$

691.

$$\begin{aligned}5229 &:= (F(T(5)) - T(T(T(2))) - F(T(T(2)))) \times 9 \\52290 &:= (F(T(5)) - T(T(T(2))) - F(T(T(2)))) \times 90 \\522900 &:= (F(T(5)) - T(T(T(2))) - F(T(T(2)))) \times 900 \\5229000 &:= (F(T(5)) - T(T(T(2))) - F(T(T(2)))) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

692.

$$\begin{aligned}5240 &:= (-C(5) + Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times 40 \\52400 &:= (-C(5) + Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times 400 \\524000 &:= (-C(5) + Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times 4000 \\5240000 &:= (-C(5) + Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times 40000\end{aligned}$$

693.

$$\begin{aligned}5240 &:= (C(5) + T(T(2))) \times 40 \\52400 &:= (C(5) + T(T(2))) \times 400 \\524000 &:= (C(5) + T(T(2))) \times 4000 \\5240000 &:= (C(5) + T(T(2))) \times 40000\end{aligned}$$

694.

$$\begin{aligned}5242 &:= (C(5) \times F(C(2)) - 4) \times 2 \\52420 &:= (C(5) \times F(C(2)) - 4) \times 20 \\524200 &:= (C(5) \times F(C(2)) - 4) \times 200 \\5242000 &:= (C(5) \times F(C(2)) - 4) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

695.

$$\begin{aligned}5244 &:= (T(5) + T(T(2))^4) \times 4 \\52440 &:= (T(5) + T(T(2))^4) \times 40 \\524400 &:= (T(5) + T(T(2))^4) \times 400 \\5244000 &:= (T(5) + T(T(2))^4) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

696.

$$\begin{aligned}5245 &:= (Q(5) + Q(2 \times Q(4))) \times 5 \\52450 &:= (Q(5) + Q(2 \times Q(4))) \times 50 \\524500 &:= (Q(5) + Q(2 \times Q(4))) \times 500 \\5245000 &:= (Q(5) + Q(2 \times Q(4))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

697.

$$\begin{aligned}5245 &:= (Q(5) + Q(C(2) \times 4)) \times 5 \\52450 &:= (Q(5) + Q(C(2) \times 4)) \times 50 \\524500 &:= (Q(5) + Q(C(2) \times 4)) \times 500 \\5245000 &:= (Q(5) + Q(C(2) \times 4)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

698.

$$\begin{aligned}5248 &:= (Q(5) + Q(Q(2))) \times Q(4) \times 8 \\52480 &:= (Q(5) + Q(Q(2))) \times Q(4) \times 80 \\524800 &:= (Q(5) + Q(Q(2))) \times Q(4) \times 800 \\5248000 &:= (Q(5) + Q(Q(2))) \times Q(4) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

699.

$$\begin{aligned}5250 &:= 5 \times F(F(F(Q(2)!)) \times 50 \\52500 &:= 5 \times F(F(F(Q(2)!)) \times 500 \\525000 &:= 5 \times F(F(F(Q(2)!)) \times 5000 \\5250000 &:= 5 \times F(F(F(Q(2)!)) \times 50000\end{aligned}$$

700.

$$\begin{aligned}5250 &:= 5 \times T(T(T(2))) \times 50 \\52500 &:= 5 \times T(T(T(2))) \times 500 \\525000 &:= 5 \times T(T(T(2))) \times 5000 \\5250000 &:= 5 \times T(T(T(2))) \times 50000\end{aligned}$$

701.

$$\begin{aligned}5252 &:= (C(5) - Q(2)!) \times 52 \\52520 &:= (C(5) - Q(2)!) \times 520 \\525200 &:= (C(5) - Q(2)!) \times 5200 \\5252000 &:= (C(5) - Q(2)!) \times 52000\end{aligned}$$

702.

$$\begin{aligned}5262 &:= (C(5) \times F(C(2)) + 6) \times 2 \\52620 &:= (C(5) \times F(C(2)) + 6) \times 20 \\526200 &:= (C(5) \times F(C(2)) + 6) \times 200 \\5262000 &:= (C(5) \times F(C(2)) + 6) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

703.

$$\begin{aligned}5265 &:= Q(Q(5 - 2)) \times 65 \\52650 &:= Q(Q(5 - 2)) \times 650 \\526500 &:= Q(Q(5 - 2)) \times 6500 \\5265000 &:= Q(Q(5 - 2)) \times 65000\end{aligned}$$

704.

$$\begin{aligned}5280 &:= T(5 + T(T(2))) \times 80 \\52800 &:= T(5 + T(T(2))) \times 800 \\528000 &:= T(5 + T(T(2))) \times 8000 \\5280000 &:= T(5 + T(T(2))) \times 80000\end{aligned}$$

705.

$$\begin{aligned}5280 &:= T(T(5) - Q(2)) \times 80 \\52800 &:= T(T(5) - Q(2)) \times 800 \\528000 &:= T(T(5) - Q(2)) \times 8000 \\5280000 &:= T(T(5) - Q(2)) \times 80000\end{aligned}$$

706.

$$\begin{aligned}5285 &:= (Q(Q(5)) - Q(F(Q(2))) + Q(F(8))) \times 5 \\52850 &:= (Q(Q(5)) - Q(F(Q(2))) + Q(F(8))) \times 50 \\528500 &:= (Q(Q(5)) - Q(F(Q(2))) + Q(F(8))) \times 500 \\5285000 &:= (Q(Q(5)) - Q(F(Q(2))) + Q(F(8))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

707.

$$\begin{aligned}5286 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + 2^8) \times 6 \\52860 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + 2^8) \times 60 \\528600 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + 2^8) \times 600 \\5286000 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + 2^8) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

708.

$$\begin{aligned}5288 &:= (-5 + T(F(2) \times T(8))) \times 8 \\52880 &:= (-5 + T(F(2) \times T(8))) \times 80 \\528800 &:= (-5 + T(F(2) \times T(8))) \times 800 \\5288000 &:= (-5 + T(F(2) \times T(8))) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

709.

$$\begin{aligned}5288 &:= (Q(5^2) + T(8)) \times 8 \\52880 &:= (Q(5^2) + T(8)) \times 80 \\528800 &:= (Q(5^2) + T(8)) \times 800 \\5288000 &:= (Q(5^2) + T(8)) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

710.

$$\begin{aligned}5288 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + Q(-2 + 8)) \times 8 \\52880 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + Q(-2 + 8)) \times 80 \\528800 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + Q(-2 + 8)) \times 800 \\5288000 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + Q(-2 + 8)) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

711.

$$\begin{aligned} 5288 &:= (-\sqrt{5^2} + T(T(8))) \times 8 \\ 52880 &:= (-\sqrt{5^2} + T(T(8))) \times 80 \\ 528800 &:= (-\sqrt{5^2} + T(T(8))) \times 800 \\ 5288000 &:= (-\sqrt{5^2} + T(T(8))) \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

712.

$$\begin{aligned} 5288 &:= (-T(5)/T(2) + T(T(8))) \times 8 \\ 52880 &:= (-T(5)/T(2) + T(T(8))) \times 80 \\ 528800 &:= (-T(5)/T(2) + T(T(8))) \times 800 \\ 5288000 &:= (-T(5)/T(2) + T(T(8))) \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

713.

$$\begin{aligned} 5292 &:= (C(5!/C(2)) - C(9)) \times 2 \\ 52920 &:= (C(5!/C(2)) - C(9)) \times 20 \\ 529200 &:= (C(5!/C(2)) - C(9)) \times 200 \\ 5292000 &:= (C(5!/C(2)) - C(9)) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

714.

$$\begin{aligned} 5292 &:= (T(5)^{T(2)} - C(9)) \times 2 \\ 52920 &:= (T(5)^{T(2)} - C(9)) \times 20 \\ 529200 &:= (T(5)^{T(2)} - C(9)) \times 200 \\ 5292000 &:= (T(5)^{T(2)} - C(9)) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

715.

$$\begin{aligned} 5302 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + Q(T(Q(3))) + 0!) \times 2 \\ 53020 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + Q(T(Q(3))) + 0!) \times 20 \\ 530200 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + Q(T(Q(3))) + 0!) \times 200 \\ 5302000 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + Q(T(Q(3))) + 0!) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

716.

$$\begin{aligned} 5304 &:= T(T(5) + T(F(T(3)))) \times 04 \\ 53040 &:= T(T(5) + T(F(T(3)))) \times 040 \\ 530400 &:= T(T(5) + T(F(T(3)))) \times 0400 \\ 5304000 &:= T(T(5) + T(F(T(3)))) \times 04000 \end{aligned}$$

717.

$$\begin{aligned} 5310 &:= (-Q(Q(5)) + Q(F(Q(3)))) \times 10 \\ 53100 &:= (-Q(Q(5)) + Q(F(Q(3)))) \times 100 \\ 531000 &:= (-Q(Q(5)) + Q(F(Q(3)))) \times 1000 \\ 5310000 &:= (-Q(Q(5)) + Q(F(Q(3)))) \times 10000 \end{aligned}$$

718.

$$\begin{aligned} 5312 &:= (C(T(5)) - T(3)! + 1) \times 2 \\ 53120 &:= (C(T(5)) - T(3)! + 1) \times 20 \\ 531200 &:= (C(T(5)) - T(3)! + 1) \times 200 \\ 5312000 &:= (C(T(5)) - T(3)! + 1) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

719.

$$\begin{aligned} 5319 &:= (Q(Q(5)) - F(Q(3))) \times 9 \\ 53190 &:= (Q(Q(5)) - F(Q(3))) \times 90 \\ 531900 &:= (Q(Q(5)) - F(Q(3))) \times 900 \\ 5319000 &:= (Q(Q(5)) - F(Q(3))) \times 9000 \end{aligned}$$

720.

$$\begin{aligned} 5324 &:= (5 + T(3))^{T(2)} \times 4 \\ 53240 &:= (5 + T(3))^{T(2)} \times 40 \\ 532400 &:= (5 + T(3))^{T(2)} \times 400 \\ 5324000 &:= (5 + T(3))^{T(2)} \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

721.

$$\begin{aligned} 5324 &:= C(5 + 3 \times 2) \times 4 \\ 53240 &:= C(5 + 3 \times 2) \times 40 \\ 532400 &:= C(5 + 3 \times 2) \times 400 \\ 5324000 &:= C(5 + 3 \times 2) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

722.

$$\begin{aligned} 5325 &:= (Q(5) + Q(Q(3!)) - Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times 5 \\ 53250 &:= (Q(5) + Q(Q(3!)) - Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times 50 \\ 532500 &:= (Q(5) + Q(Q(3!)) - Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times 500 \\ 5325000 &:= (Q(5) + Q(Q(3!)) - Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

723.

$$\begin{aligned} 5325 &:= (Q(Q(5) + F(3!)) - Q(2!)) \times 5 \\ 53250 &:= (Q(Q(5) + F(3!)) - Q(2!)) \times 50 \\ 532500 &:= (Q(Q(5) + F(3!)) - Q(2!)) \times 500 \\ 5325000 &:= (Q(Q(5) + F(3!)) - Q(2!)) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

724.

$$\begin{aligned} 5327 &:= (5 + T(3!) + T(C(2))) \times 7 \\ 53270 &:= (5 + T(3!) + T(C(2))) \times 70 \\ 532700 &:= (5 + T(3!) + T(C(2))) \times 700 \\ 5327000 &:= (5 + T(3!) + T(C(2))) \times 7000 \end{aligned}$$

725.

$$\begin{aligned} 5343 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + Q(34)) \times 3 \\ 53430 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + Q(34)) \times 30 \\ 534300 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + Q(34)) \times 300 \\ 5343000 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + Q(34)) \times 3000 \end{aligned}$$

726.

$$\begin{aligned} 5344 &:= (5 + C(3 + \sqrt{C(4)})) \times 4 \\ 53440 &:= (5 + C(3 + \sqrt{C(4)})) \times 40 \\ 534400 &:= (5 + C(3 + \sqrt{C(4)})) \times 400 \\ 5344000 &:= (5 + C(3 + \sqrt{C(4)})) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

727.

$$\begin{aligned} 5346 &:= (Q(T(5)) + T(4 \times Q(3))) \times 6 \\ 53460 &:= (Q(T(5)) + T(4 \times Q(3))) \times 60 \\ 534600 &:= (Q(T(5)) + T(4 \times Q(3))) \times 600 \\ 5346000 &:= (Q(T(5)) + T(4 \times Q(3))) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

728.

$$\begin{aligned} 5346 &:= (T(T(5) + 3) + (T(T(\sqrt{4})))!) \times 6 \\ 53460 &:= (T(T(5) + 3) + (T(T(\sqrt{4})))!) \times 60 \\ 534600 &:= (T(T(5) + 3) + (T(T(\sqrt{4})))!) \times 600 \\ 5346000 &:= (T(T(5) + 3) + (T(T(\sqrt{4})))!) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

729.

$$\begin{aligned} 5355 &:= (5 + Q(F(F(3!))) + Q(Q(5))) \times 5 \\ 53550 &:= (5 + Q(F(F(3!))) + Q(Q(5))) \times 50 \\ 535500 &:= (5 + Q(F(F(3!))) + Q(Q(5))) \times 500 \\ 5355000 &:= (5 + Q(F(F(3!))) + Q(Q(5))) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

730.

$$\begin{aligned} 5364 &:= (5 \times Q(3) + Q(Q(6))) \times 4 \\ 53640 &:= (5 \times Q(3) + Q(Q(6))) \times 40 \\ 536400 &:= (5 \times Q(3) + Q(Q(6))) \times 400 \\ 5364000 &:= (5 \times Q(3) + Q(Q(6))) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

731.

$$\begin{aligned}5364 &:= (C(5) \times Q(3) + C(6)) \times 4 \\53640 &:= (C(5) \times Q(3) + C(6)) \times 40 \\536400 &:= (C(5) \times Q(3) + C(6)) \times 400 \\5364000 &:= (C(5) \times Q(3) + C(6)) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

732.

$$\begin{aligned}5364 &:= (C(T(5))/3 + C(6)) \times 4 \\53640 &:= (C(T(5))/3 + C(6)) \times 40 \\536400 &:= (C(T(5))/3 + C(6)) \times 400 \\5364000 &:= (C(T(5))/3 + C(6)) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

733.

$$\begin{aligned}5368 &:= (5 + T(36)) \times 8 \\53680 &:= (5 + T(36)) \times 80 \\536800 &:= (5 + T(36)) \times 800 \\5368000 &:= (5 + T(36)) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

734.

$$\begin{aligned}5376 &:= (5! + F(3!)) \times 7 \times 6 \\53760 &:= (5! + F(3!)) \times 7 \times 60 \\537600 &:= (5! + F(3!)) \times 7 \times 600 \\5376000 &:= (5! + F(3!)) \times 7 \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

735.

$$\begin{aligned}5376 &:= (5! + F(T(3))) \times 7 \times 6 \\53760 &:= (5! + F(T(3))) \times 7 \times 60 \\537600 &:= (5! + F(T(3))) \times 7 \times 600 \\5376000 &:= (5! + F(T(3))) \times 7 \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

736.

$$\begin{aligned}5376 &:= (C(5) + 3) \times 7 \times 6 \\53760 &:= (C(5) + 3) \times 7 \times 60 \\537600 &:= (C(5) + 3) \times 7 \times 600 \\5376000 &:= (C(5) + 3) \times 7 \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

737.

$$\begin{aligned}5376 &:= (T(T(5)) + F(T(3))) \times 7 \times 6 \\53760 &:= (T(T(5)) + F(T(3))) \times 7 \times 60 \\537600 &:= (T(T(5)) + F(T(3))) \times 7 \times 600 \\5376000 &:= (T(T(5)) + F(T(3))) \times 7 \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

738.

$$\begin{aligned}5384 &:= (T(5) + C(3 + 8)) \times 4 \\53840 &:= (T(5) + C(3 + 8)) \times 40 \\538400 &:= (T(5) + C(3 + 8)) \times 400 \\5384000 &:= (T(5) + C(3 + 8)) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

739.

$$\begin{aligned}5403 &:= (C(Q(5)) - C(4!)) \times 3 \\54030 &:= (C(Q(5)) - C(4!)) \times 30 \\540300 &:= (C(Q(5)) - C(4!)) \times 300 \\5403000 &:= (C(Q(5)) - C(4!)) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

740.

$$\begin{aligned}5405 &:= (5! \times Q(F(4)) + 0!) \times 5 \\54050 &:= (5! \times Q(F(4)) + 0!) \times 50 \\540500 &:= (5! \times Q(F(4)) + 0!) \times 500 \\5405000 &:= (5! \times Q(F(4)) + 0!) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

741.

$$\begin{aligned}5405 &:= (5 \times C(F(4)!) + 0!) \times 5 \\54050 &:= (5 \times C(F(4)!) + 0!) \times 50 \\540500 &:= (5 \times C(F(4)!) + 0!) \times 500 \\5405000 &:= (5 \times C(F(4)!) + 0!) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

742.

$$\begin{aligned}5406 &:= (Q(5!/4) + 0!) \times 6 \\54060 &:= (Q(5!/4) + 0!) \times 60 \\540600 &:= (Q(5!/4) + 0!) \times 600 \\5406000 &:= (Q(5!/4) + 0!) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

743.

$$\begin{aligned}5406 &:= (T(Q(5)) + Q(4!)) \times 6 \\54060 &:= (T(Q(5)) + Q(4!)) \times 60 \\540600 &:= (T(Q(5)) + Q(4!)) \times 600 \\5406000 &:= (T(Q(5)) + Q(4!)) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

744.

$$\begin{aligned}5408 &:= (F(T(5)) + T(T(4) + 0!)) \times 8 \\54080 &:= (F(T(5)) + T(T(4) + 0!)) \times 80 \\540800 &:= (F(T(5)) + T(T(4) + 0!)) \times 800 \\5408000 &:= (F(T(5)) + T(T(4) + 0!)) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

745.

$$\begin{aligned}5408 &:= Q(Q(5) + (4 \times 0!)) \times 8 \\54080 &:= Q(Q(5) + (4 \times 0!)) \times 80 \\540800 &:= Q(Q(5) + (4 \times 0!)) \times 800 \\5408000 &:= Q(Q(5) + (4 \times 0!)) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

746.

$$\begin{aligned}5409 &:= (-5! + F(4)!! + 0!) \times 9 \\54090 &:= (-5! + F(4)!! + 0!) \times 90 \\540900 &:= (-5! + F(4)!! + 0!) \times 900 \\5409000 &:= (-5! + F(4)!! + 0!) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

747.

$$\begin{aligned}5409 &:= (F(T(5)) + (0! - T(4))) \times 9 \\54090 &:= (F(T(5)) + (0! - T(4))) \times 90 \\540900 &:= (F(T(5)) + (0! - T(4))) \times 900 \\5409000 &:= (F(T(5)) + (0! - T(4))) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

748.

$$\begin{aligned}5409 &:= (Q(5) \times 4! + 0!) \times 9 \\54090 &:= (Q(5) \times 4! + 0!) \times 90 \\540900 &:= (Q(5) \times 4! + 0!) \times 900 \\5409000 &:= (Q(5) \times 4! + 0!) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

749.

$$\begin{aligned}5410 &:= (-C(5) + T(T(\sqrt{C(4)}))) \times 10 \\54100 &:= (-C(5) + T(T(\sqrt{C(4)}))) \times 100 \\541000 &:= (-C(5) + T(T(\sqrt{C(4)}))) \times 1000 \\5410000 &:= (-C(5) + T(T(\sqrt{C(4)}))) \times 10000\end{aligned}$$

750.

$$\begin{aligned}5412 &:= (-C(5) + Q(4!)) \times 12 \\54120 &:= (-C(5) + Q(4!)) \times 120 \\541200 &:= (-C(5) + Q(4!)) \times 1200 \\5412000 &:= (-C(5) + Q(4!)) \times 12000\end{aligned}$$

751.

$$5415 := Q(-5 + 4!) \times 15$$

$$54150 := Q(-5 + 4!) \times 150$$

$$541500 := Q(-5 + 4!) \times 1500$$

$$5415000 := Q(-5 + 4!) \times 15000$$

752.

$$5424 := (-5 + T(T(T(F(4)))) \times 24$$

$$54240 := (-5 + T(T(T(F(4)))) \times 240$$

$$542400 := (-5 + T(T(T(F(4)))) \times 2400$$

$$5424000 := (-5 + T(T(T(F(4)))) \times 24000$$

753.

$$5427 := (Q(T(5)) - 4!) \times 27$$

$$54270 := (Q(T(5)) - 4!) \times 270$$

$$542700 := (Q(T(5)) - 4!) \times 2700$$

$$5427000 := (Q(T(5)) - 4!) \times 27000$$

754.

$$5432 := (T(T(5) + F(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 2$$

$$54320 := (T(T(5) + F(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 20$$

$$543200 := (T(T(5) + F(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 200$$

$$5432000 := (T(T(5) + F(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 2000$$

755.

$$5432 := (T(T(5) + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 2$$

$$54320 := (T(T(5) + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 20$$

$$543200 := (T(T(5) + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 200$$

$$5432000 := (T(T(5) + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 2000$$

756.

$$5440 := (5! + Q(4)) \times 40$$

$$54400 := (5! + Q(4)) \times 400$$

$$544000 := (5! + Q(4)) \times 4000$$

$$5440000 := (5! + Q(4)) \times 40000$$

757.

$$5440 := T(-5 + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) \times 40$$

$$54400 := T(-5 + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) \times 400$$

$$544000 := T(-5 + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) \times 4000$$

$$5440000 := T(-5 + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) \times 40000$$

758.

$$5440 := T(T(5) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 40$$

$$54400 := T(T(5) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 400$$

$$544000 := T(T(5) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 4000$$

$$5440000 := T(T(5) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 40000$$

759.

$$5440 := T(T(5) + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 40$$

$$54400 := T(T(5) + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 400$$

$$544000 := T(T(5) + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 4000$$

$$5440000 := T(T(5) + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 40000$$

760.

$$5445 := (5! + F(F(F(4)))) \times 45$$

$$54450 := (5! + F(F(F(4)))) \times 450$$

$$544500 := (5! + F(F(F(4)))) \times 4500$$

$$5445000 := (5! + F(F(F(4)))) \times 45000$$

761.

$$\begin{aligned}5445 &:= (5! + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 45 \\54450 &:= (5! + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 450 \\544500 &:= (5! + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 4500 \\5445000 &:= (5! + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 45000\end{aligned}$$

762.

$$\begin{aligned}5445 &:= (C(5) - 4) \times 45 \\54450 &:= (C(5) - 4) \times 450 \\544500 &:= (C(5) - 4) \times 4500 \\5445000 &:= (C(5) - 4) \times 45000\end{aligned}$$

763.

$$\begin{aligned}5445 &:= (T(T(5)) + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 45 \\54450 &:= (T(T(5)) + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 450 \\544500 &:= (T(T(5)) + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 4500 \\5445000 &:= (T(T(5)) + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 45000\end{aligned}$$

764.

$$\begin{aligned}5448 &:= (5 + Q(\sqrt{4} + 4!)) \times 8 \\54480 &:= (5 + Q(\sqrt{4} + 4!)) \times 80 \\544800 &:= (5 + Q(\sqrt{4} + 4!)) \times 800 \\5448000 &:= (5 + Q(\sqrt{4} + 4!)) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

765.

$$\begin{aligned}5448 &:= (T(5) + T(T(4 + 4))) \times 8 \\54480 &:= (T(5) + T(T(4 + 4))) \times 80 \\544800 &:= (T(5) + T(T(4 + 4))) \times 800 \\5448000 &:= (T(5) + T(T(4 + 4))) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

766.

$$\begin{aligned}5450 &:= (C(5) - Q(4)) \times 50 \\54500 &:= (C(5) - Q(4)) \times 500 \\545000 &:= (C(5) - Q(4)) \times 5000 \\5450000 &:= (C(5) - Q(4)) \times 50000\end{aligned}$$

767.

$$\begin{aligned}5454 &:= (C(5) - 4!) \times 54 \\54540 &:= (C(5) - 4!) \times 540 \\545400 &:= (C(5) - 4!) \times 5400 \\5454000 &:= (C(5) - 4!) \times 54000\end{aligned}$$

768.

$$\begin{aligned}5460 &:= (-C(5) + C(F(4)!)) \times 60 \\54600 &:= (-C(5) + C(F(4)!)) \times 600 \\546000 &:= (-C(5) + C(F(4)!)) \times 6000 \\5460000 &:= (-C(5) + C(F(4)!)) \times 60000\end{aligned}$$

769.

$$\begin{aligned}5460 &:= T(T(5) - F(F(4))) \times 60 \\54600 &:= T(T(5) - F(F(4))) \times 600 \\546000 &:= T(T(5) - F(F(4))) \times 6000 \\5460000 &:= T(T(5) - F(F(4))) \times 60000\end{aligned}$$

770.

$$\begin{aligned}5460 &:= T(T(5) - \sqrt{4}) \times 60 \\54600 &:= T(T(5) - \sqrt{4}) \times 600 \\546000 &:= T(T(5) - \sqrt{4}) \times 6000 \\5460000 &:= T(T(5) - \sqrt{4}) \times 60000\end{aligned}$$

771.

$$\begin{aligned}5461 &:= (C(T(5)) + T(C(4)) + 6) \times 1 \\54610 &:= (C(T(5)) + T(C(4)) + 6) \times 10 \\546100 &:= (C(T(5)) + T(C(4)) + 6) \times 100 \\5461000 &:= (C(T(5)) + T(C(4)) + 6) \times 1000\end{aligned}$$

772.

$$\begin{aligned}5464 &:= (F(T(5) + \sqrt{4}) - T(T(6))) \times 4 \\54640 &:= (F(T(5) + \sqrt{4}) - T(T(6))) \times 40 \\546400 &:= (F(T(5) + \sqrt{4}) - T(T(6))) \times 400 \\5464000 &:= (F(T(5) + \sqrt{4}) - T(T(6))) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

773.

$$\begin{aligned}5467 &:= (C(5) - C(4) + 6!) \times 7 \\54670 &:= (C(5) - C(4) + 6!) \times 70 \\546700 &:= (C(5) - C(4) + 6!) \times 700 \\5467000 &:= (C(5) - C(4) + 6!) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

774.

$$\begin{aligned}5467 &:= (F(T(5)) + T(6 \times F(4))) \times 7 \\54670 &:= (F(T(5)) + T(6 \times F(4))) \times 70 \\546700 &:= (F(T(5)) + T(6 \times F(4))) \times 700 \\5467000 &:= (F(T(5)) + T(6 \times F(4))) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

775.

$$\begin{aligned}5467 &:= (F(T(5)) + T(T(4) + F(6))) \times 7 \\54670 &:= (F(T(5)) + T(T(4) + F(6))) \times 70 \\546700 &:= (F(T(5)) + T(T(4) + F(6))) \times 700 \\5467000 &:= (F(T(5)) + T(T(4) + F(6))) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

776.

$$\begin{aligned}5482 &:= (-5 + T(C(4)) + T(T(8))) \times 2 \\54820 &:= (-5 + T(C(4)) + T(T(8))) \times 20 \\548200 &:= (-5 + T(C(4)) + T(T(8))) \times 200 \\5482000 &:= (-5 + T(C(4)) + T(T(8))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

777.

$$\begin{aligned}5484 &:= (-T(5) + T(F(4)) \times T(F(8))) \times 4 \\54840 &:= (-T(5) + T(F(4)) \times T(F(8))) \times 40 \\548400 &:= (-T(5) + T(F(4)) \times T(F(8))) \times 400 \\5484000 &:= (-T(5) + T(F(4)) \times T(F(8))) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

778.

$$\begin{aligned}5484 &:= (-T(5) + T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times 4 \\54840 &:= (-T(5) + T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times 40 \\548400 &:= (-T(5) + T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times 400 \\5484000 &:= (-T(5) + T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

779.

$$\begin{aligned}5488 &:= (5 \times 4 + T(T(8))) \times 8 \\54880 &:= (5 \times 4 + T(T(8))) \times 80 \\548800 &:= (5 \times 4 + T(T(8))) \times 800 \\5488000 &:= (5 \times 4 + T(T(8))) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

780.

$$\begin{aligned}5488 &:= (F(T(5)) + F(T(4)) + F(8)) \times 8 \\54880 &:= (F(T(5)) + F(T(4)) + F(8)) \times 80 \\548800 &:= (F(T(5)) + F(T(4)) + F(8)) \times 800 \\5488000 &:= (F(T(5)) + F(T(4)) + F(8)) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

781.

$$5488 := (Q(Q(5)) - F(4) + Q(8)) \times 8$$

$$54880 := (Q(Q(5)) - F(4) + Q(8)) \times 80$$

$$548800 := (Q(Q(5)) - F(4) + Q(8)) \times 800$$

$$5488000 := (Q(Q(5)) - F(4) + Q(8)) \times 8000$$

782.

$$5490 := (C(5) - C(4)) \times 90$$

$$54900 := (C(5) - C(4)) \times 900$$

$$549000 := (C(5) - C(4)) \times 9000$$

$$5490000 := (C(5) - C(4)) \times 90000$$

783.

$$5490 := F(T(5))/T(4) \times 90$$

$$54900 := F(T(5))/T(4) \times 900$$

$$549000 := F(T(5))/T(4) \times 9000$$

$$5490000 := F(T(5))/T(4) \times 90000$$

784.

$$5493 := (5! + T(4! + F(9))) \times 3$$

$$54930 := (5! + T(4! + F(9))) \times 30$$

$$549300 := (5! + T(4! + F(9))) \times 300$$

$$5493000 := (5! + T(4! + F(9))) \times 3000$$

785.

$$5493 := (5 \times \sqrt{C(C(4))} - C(9)) \times 3$$

$$54930 := (5 \times \sqrt{C(C(4))} - C(9)) \times 30$$

$$549300 := (5 \times \sqrt{C(C(4))} - C(9)) \times 300$$

$$5493000 := (5 \times \sqrt{C(C(4))} - C(9)) \times 3000$$

786.

$$5499 := (F(T(5)) + T(4) - 9) \times 9$$

$$54990 := (F(T(5)) + T(4) - 9) \times 90$$

$$549900 := (F(T(5)) + T(4) - 9) \times 900$$

$$5499000 := (F(T(5)) + T(4) - 9) \times 9000$$

787.

$$5528 := (5! - 5 + Q(Q(2!))) \times 8$$

$$55280 := (5! - 5 + Q(Q(2!))) \times 80$$

$$552800 := (5! - 5 + Q(Q(2!))) \times 800$$

$$5528000 := (5! - 5 + Q(Q(2!))) \times 8000$$

788.

$$5528 := (5 \times 5 + T(T(C(2)))) \times 8$$

$$55280 := (5 \times 5 + T(T(C(2)))) \times 80$$

$$552800 := (5 \times 5 + T(T(C(2)))) \times 800$$

$$5528000 := (5 \times 5 + T(T(C(2)))) \times 8000$$

789.

$$5528 := (5 \times 5 + T(T(F(T(T(2))))) \times 8$$

$$55280 := (5 \times 5 + T(T(F(T(T(2))))) \times 80$$

$$552800 := (5 \times 5 + T(T(F(T(T(2))))) \times 800$$

$$5528000 := (5 \times 5 + T(T(F(T(T(2))))) \times 8000$$

790.

$$5528 := (Q(Q(5)) + T(T(5) - Q(2))) \times 8$$

$$55280 := (Q(Q(5)) + T(T(5) - Q(2))) \times 80$$

$$552800 := (Q(Q(5)) + T(T(5) - Q(2))) \times 800$$

$$5528000 := (Q(Q(5)) + T(T(5) - Q(2))) \times 8000$$

791.

$$\begin{aligned}5535 &:= (5! + F(-5 + F(C(F(3)))))) \times 5 \\55350 &:= (5! + F(-5 + F(C(F(3)))))) \times 50 \\553500 &:= (5! + F(-5 + F(C(F(3)))))) \times 500 \\5535000 &:= (5! + F(-5 + F(C(F(3)))))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

792.

$$\begin{aligned}5535 &:= (5! + F(-5 + F(F(3!)))) \times 5 \\55350 &:= (5! + F(-5 + F(F(3!)))) \times 50 \\553500 &:= (5! + F(-5 + F(F(3!)))) \times 500 \\5535000 &:= (5! + F(-5 + F(F(3!)))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

793.

$$\begin{aligned}5535 &:= (5! + F(Q(5) - Q(3))) \times 5 \\55350 &:= (5! + F(Q(5) - Q(3))) \times 50 \\553500 &:= (5! + F(Q(5) - Q(3))) \times 500 \\5535000 &:= (5! + F(Q(5) - Q(3))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

794.

$$\begin{aligned}5564 &:= (5! - Q(5) + Q(Q(6))) \times 4 \\55640 &:= (5! - Q(5) + Q(Q(6))) \times 40 \\556400 &:= (5! - Q(5) + Q(Q(6))) \times 400 \\5564000 &:= (5! - Q(5) + Q(Q(6))) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

795.

$$\begin{aligned}5568 &:= (-5!/5 + 6!) \times 8 \\55680 &:= (-5!/5 + 6!) \times 80 \\556800 &:= (-5!/5 + 6!) \times 800 \\5568000 &:= (-5!/5 + 6!) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

796.

$$\begin{aligned}5568 &:= (Q(5) - Q(Q(5)) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 \\55680 &:= (Q(5) - Q(Q(5)) + Q(Q(6))) \times 80 \\556800 &:= (Q(5) - Q(Q(5)) + Q(Q(6))) \times 800 \\5568000 &:= (Q(5) - Q(Q(5)) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

797.

$$\begin{aligned}5568 &:= (T(T(5) + T(5)) + T(T(6))) \times 8 \\55680 &:= (T(T(5) + T(5)) + T(T(6))) \times 80 \\556800 &:= (T(T(5) + T(5)) + T(T(6))) \times 800 \\5568000 &:= (T(T(5) + T(5)) + T(T(6))) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

798.

$$\begin{aligned}5584 &:= (F(T(5)) + 5! + T(T(8))) \times 4 \\55840 &:= (F(T(5)) + 5! + T(T(8))) \times 40 \\558400 &:= (F(T(5)) + 5! + T(T(8))) \times 400 \\5584000 &:= (F(T(5)) + 5! + T(T(8))) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

799.

$$\begin{aligned}5584 &:= (F(T(5)) + T(T(5)) + T(T(8))) \times 4 \\55840 &:= (F(T(5)) + T(T(5)) + T(T(8))) \times 40 \\558400 &:= (F(T(5)) + T(T(5)) + T(T(8))) \times 400 \\5584000 &:= (F(T(5)) + T(T(5)) + T(T(8))) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

800.

$$\begin{aligned}5589 &:= (5 \times 5! + F(8)) \times 9 \\55890 &:= (5 \times 5! + F(8)) \times 90 \\558900 &:= (5 \times 5! + F(8)) \times 900 \\5589000 &:= (5 \times 5! + F(8)) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

801.

$$5589 := (5 \times 5! + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 9$$

$$55890 := (5 \times 5! + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 90$$

$$558900 := (5 \times 5! + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 900$$

$$5589000 := (5 \times 5! + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 9000$$

802.

$$5589 := (5 \times T(T(5)) + F(8)) \times 9$$

$$55890 := (5 \times T(T(5)) + F(8)) \times 90$$

$$558900 := (5 \times T(T(5)) + F(8)) \times 900$$

$$5589000 := (5 \times T(T(5)) + F(8)) \times 9000$$

803.

$$5589 := (5 \times T(T(5)) + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 9$$

$$55890 := (5 \times T(T(5)) + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 90$$

$$558900 := (5 \times T(T(5)) + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 900$$

$$5589000 := (5 \times T(T(5)) + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 9000$$

804.

$$5608 := (F(T(5)) + T(F(F(6) - 0!))) \times 8$$

$$56080 := (F(T(5)) + T(F(F(6) - 0!))) \times 80$$

$$560800 := (F(T(5)) + T(F(F(6) - 0!))) \times 800$$

$$5608000 := (F(T(5)) + T(F(F(6) - 0!))) \times 8000$$

805.

$$5610 := (5! + Q(T(6))) \times 10$$

$$56100 := (5! + Q(T(6))) \times 100$$

$$561000 := (5! + Q(T(6))) \times 1000$$

$$5610000 := (5! + Q(T(6))) \times 10000$$

806.

$$5610 := (Q(Q(5)) - Q(F(6))) \times 10$$

$$56100 := (Q(Q(5)) - Q(F(6))) \times 100$$

$$561000 := (Q(Q(5)) - Q(F(6))) \times 1000$$

$$5610000 := (Q(Q(5)) - Q(F(6))) \times 10000$$

807.

$$5616 := T(5 + T(6)) \times 16$$

$$56160 := T(5 + T(6)) \times 160$$

$$561600 := T(5 + T(6)) \times 1600$$

$$5616000 := T(5 + T(6)) \times 16000$$

808.

$$5624 := (-F(T(5)) + T(T(6) \times T(2))) \times 4$$

$$56240 := (-F(T(5)) + T(T(6) \times T(2))) \times 40$$

$$562400 := (-F(T(5)) + T(T(6) \times T(2))) \times 400$$

$$5624000 := (-F(T(5)) + T(T(6) \times T(2))) \times 4000$$

809.

$$5625 := 5 \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(2))) \times 5$$

$$56250 := 5 \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(2))) \times 50$$

$$562500 := 5 \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(2))) \times 500$$

$$5625000 := 5 \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(2))) \times 5000$$

810.

$$5635 := (C(5) + Q(6)) \times 35$$

$$56350 := (C(5) + Q(6)) \times 350$$

$$563500 := (C(5) + Q(6)) \times 3500$$

$$5635000 := (C(5) + Q(6)) \times 35000$$

811.

$$\begin{aligned}5640 &:= (5! + F(F(6))) \times 40 \\56400 &:= (5! + F(F(6))) \times 400 \\564000 &:= (5! + F(F(6))) \times 4000 \\5640000 &:= (5! + F(F(6))) \times 40000\end{aligned}$$

812.

$$\begin{aligned}5640 &:= (5! + T(6)) \times 40 \\56400 &:= (5! + T(6)) \times 400 \\564000 &:= (5! + T(6)) \times 4000 \\5640000 &:= (5! + T(6)) \times 40000\end{aligned}$$

813.

$$\begin{aligned}5640 &:= (T(T(5)) + T(6)) \times 40 \\56400 &:= (T(T(5)) + T(6)) \times 400 \\564000 &:= (T(T(5)) + T(6)) \times 4000 \\5640000 &:= (T(T(5)) + T(6)) \times 40000\end{aligned}$$

814.

$$\begin{aligned}5644 &:= (5 \times T(T(6)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 4 \\56440 &:= (5 \times T(T(6)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 40 \\564400 &:= (5 \times T(T(6)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 400 \\5644000 &:= (5 \times T(T(6)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

815.

$$\begin{aligned}5646 &:= (-Q(5) - F(F(6)) + F(Q(4))) \times 6 \\56460 &:= (-Q(5) - F(F(6)) + F(Q(4))) \times 60 \\564600 &:= (-Q(5) - F(F(6)) + F(Q(4))) \times 600 \\5646000 &:= (-Q(5) - F(F(6)) + F(Q(4))) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

816.

$$\begin{aligned}5648 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + Q(Q(6)/4)) \times 8 \\56480 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + Q(Q(6)/4)) \times 80 \\564800 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + Q(Q(6)/4)) \times 800 \\5648000 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + Q(Q(6)/4)) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

817.

$$\begin{aligned}5648 &:= (-T(5) + 6! + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 8 \\56480 &:= (-T(5) + 6! + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 80 \\564800 &:= (-T(5) + 6! + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 800 \\5648000 &:= (-T(5) + 6! + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

818.

$$\begin{aligned}5664 &:= (5! + Q(6 \times 6)) \times 4 \\56640 &:= (5! + Q(6 \times 6)) \times 40 \\566400 &:= (5! + Q(6 \times 6)) \times 400 \\5664000 &:= (5! + Q(6 \times 6)) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

819.

$$\begin{aligned}5673 &:= T(F(5 + 6) - T(7)) \times 3 \\56730 &:= T(F(5 + 6) - T(7)) \times 30 \\567300 &:= T(F(5 + 6) - T(7)) \times 300 \\5673000 &:= T(F(5 + 6) - T(7)) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

820.

$$\begin{aligned}5675 &:= (C(-6 + T(5)) + T(T(7))) \times 5 \\56750 &:= (C(-6 + T(5)) + T(T(7))) \times 50 \\567500 &:= (C(-6 + T(5)) + T(T(7))) \times 500 \\5675000 &:= (C(-6 + T(5)) + T(T(7))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

821.

$$5675 := 5 \times (-6 + F(F(7))) \times 5$$

$$56750 := 5 \times (-6 + F(F(7))) \times 50$$

$$567500 := 5 \times (-6 + F(F(7))) \times 500$$

$$5675000 := 5 \times (-6 + F(F(7))) \times 5000$$

822.

$$5676 := T(5 \times 6 + F(7)) \times 6$$

$$56760 := T(5 \times 6 + F(7)) \times 60$$

$$567600 := T(5 \times 6 + F(7)) \times 600$$

$$5676000 := T(5 \times 6 + F(7)) \times 6000$$

823.

$$5676 := T(T(5) + T(6) + 7) \times 6$$

$$56760 := T(T(5) + T(6) + 7) \times 60$$

$$567600 := T(T(5) + T(6) + 7) \times 600$$

$$5676000 := T(T(5) + T(6) + 7) \times 6000$$

824.

$$5677 := (T(T(5)) \times 6 + T(F(7))) \times 7$$

$$56770 := (T(T(5)) \times 6 + T(F(7))) \times 70$$

$$567700 := (T(T(5)) \times 6 + T(F(7))) \times 700$$

$$5677000 := (T(T(5)) \times 6 + T(F(7))) \times 7000$$

825.

$$5679 := (F(T(5)) + F(6) + F(7)) \times 9$$

$$56790 := (F(T(5)) + F(6) + F(7)) \times 90$$

$$567900 := (F(T(5)) + F(6) + F(7)) \times 900$$

$$5679000 := (F(T(5)) + F(6) + F(7)) \times 9000$$

826.

$$5682 := (C(5) \times T(6) + C(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 2$$

$$56820 := (C(5) \times T(6) + C(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 20$$

$$568200 := (C(5) \times T(6) + C(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 200$$

$$5682000 := (C(5) \times T(6) + C(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 2000$$

827.

$$5684 := (\sqrt{5^6} + Q(T(8))) \times 4$$

$$56840 := (\sqrt{5^6} + Q(T(8))) \times 40$$

$$568400 := (\sqrt{5^6} + Q(T(8))) \times 400$$

$$5684000 := (\sqrt{5^6} + Q(T(8))) \times 4000$$

828.

$$5685 := (Q(Q(5)) + F(6) \times Q(8)) \times 5$$

$$56850 := (Q(Q(5)) + F(6) \times Q(8)) \times 50$$

$$568500 := (Q(Q(5)) + F(6) \times Q(8)) \times 500$$

$$5685000 := (Q(Q(5)) + F(6) \times Q(8)) \times 5000$$

829.

$$5685 := (\sqrt{5^{F(6)}} + C(8)) \times 5$$

$$56850 := (\sqrt{5^{F(6)}} + C(8)) \times 50$$

$$568500 := (\sqrt{5^{F(6)}} + C(8)) \times 500$$

$$5685000 := (\sqrt{5^{F(6)}} + C(8)) \times 5000$$

830.

$$5688 := (T(-6 + T(5)) + T(T(8))) \times 8$$

$$56880 := (T(-6 + T(5)) + T(T(8))) \times 80$$

$$568800 := (T(-6 + T(5)) + T(T(8))) \times 800$$

$$5688000 := (T(-6 + T(5)) + T(T(8))) \times 8000$$

831.

$$\begin{aligned} 5695 &:= (C(5) - T(6) + T(T(9))) \times 5 \\ 56950 &:= (C(5) - T(6) + T(T(9))) \times 50 \\ 569500 &:= (C(5) - T(6) + T(T(9))) \times 500 \\ 5695000 &:= (C(5) - T(6) + T(T(9))) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

832.

$$\begin{aligned} 5705 &:= (-T(5) + Q(\sqrt{T(Q(7)) - 0!})) \times 5 \\ 57050 &:= (-T(5) + Q(\sqrt{T(Q(7)) - 0!})) \times 50 \\ 570500 &:= (-T(5) + Q(\sqrt{T(Q(7)) - 0!})) \times 500 \\ 5705000 &:= (-T(5) + Q(\sqrt{T(Q(7)) - 0!})) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

833.

$$\begin{aligned} 5715 &:= (-Q(5) + T(T(7))) \times 15 \\ 57150 &:= (-Q(5) + T(T(7))) \times 150 \\ 571500 &:= (-Q(5) + T(T(7))) \times 1500 \\ 5715000 &:= (-Q(5) + T(T(7))) \times 15000 \end{aligned}$$

834.

$$\begin{aligned} 5724 &:= T(C(5) - 72) \times 4 \\ 57240 &:= T(C(5) - 72) \times 40 \\ 572400 &:= T(C(5) - 72) \times 400 \\ 5724000 &:= T(C(5) - 72) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

835.

$$\begin{aligned} 5728 &:= (Q(5) \times T(7) + Q(Q(2))) \times 8 \\ 57280 &:= (Q(5) \times T(7) + Q(Q(2))) \times 80 \\ 572800 &:= (Q(5) \times T(7) + Q(Q(2))) \times 800 \\ 5728000 &:= (Q(5) \times T(7) + Q(Q(2))) \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

836.

$$\begin{aligned} 5742 &:= (-Q(5 \times 7) + Q(C(4))) \times 2 \\ 57420 &:= (-Q(5 \times 7) + Q(C(4))) \times 20 \\ 574200 &:= (-Q(5 \times 7) + Q(C(4))) \times 200 \\ 5742000 &:= (-Q(5 \times 7) + Q(C(4))) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

837.

$$\begin{aligned} 5747 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + 4 \times Q(7)) \times 7 \\ 57470 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + 4 \times Q(7)) \times 70 \\ 574700 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + 4 \times Q(7)) \times 700 \\ 5747000 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + 4 \times Q(7)) \times 7000 \end{aligned}$$

838.

$$\begin{aligned} 5760 &:= (5 + T(F(7))) \times 60 \\ 57600 &:= (5 + T(F(7))) \times 600 \\ 576000 &:= (5 + T(F(7))) \times 6000 \\ 5760000 &:= (5 + T(F(7))) \times 60000 \end{aligned}$$

839.

$$\begin{aligned} 5764 &:= (Q(5 \times 7) + C(6)) \times 4 \\ 57640 &:= (Q(5 \times 7) + C(6)) \times 40 \\ 576400 &:= (Q(5 \times 7) + C(6)) \times 400 \\ 5764000 &:= (Q(5 \times 7) + C(6)) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

840.

$$\begin{aligned} 5766 &:= (5! + Q(-7 + Q(6))) \times 6 \\ 57660 &:= (5! + Q(-7 + Q(6))) \times 60 \\ 576600 &:= (5! + Q(-7 + Q(6))) \times 600 \\ 5766000 &:= (5! + Q(-7 + Q(6))) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

841.

$$\begin{aligned}5766 &:= (T(5) + T(7 + T(F(6)))) \times 6 \\57660 &:= (T(5) + T(7 + T(F(6)))) \times 60 \\576600 &:= (T(5) + T(7 + T(F(6)))) \times 600 \\5766000 &:= (T(5) + T(7 + T(F(6)))) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

842.

$$\begin{aligned}5768 &:= (-5! + Q(-7 + Q(6))) \times 8 \\57680 &:= (-5! + Q(-7 + Q(6))) \times 80 \\576800 &:= (-5! + Q(-7 + Q(6))) \times 800 \\5768000 &:= (-5! + Q(-7 + Q(6))) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

843.

$$\begin{aligned}5768 &:= (Q(5) \times T(7) + T(6)) \times 8 \\57680 &:= (Q(5) \times T(7) + T(6)) \times 80 \\576800 &:= (Q(5) \times T(7) + T(6)) \times 800 \\5768000 &:= (Q(5) \times T(7) + T(6)) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

844.

$$\begin{aligned}5776 &:= (-T(5) + T(F(7))) \times 76 \\57760 &:= (-T(5) + T(F(7))) \times 760 \\577600 &:= (-T(5) + T(F(7))) \times 7600 \\5776000 &:= (-T(5) + T(F(7))) \times 76000\end{aligned}$$

845.

$$\begin{aligned}5782 &:= (C(T(5)) + T(7) - C(8)) \times 2 \\57820 &:= (C(T(5)) + T(7) - C(8)) \times 20 \\578200 &:= (C(T(5)) + T(7) - C(8)) \times 200 \\5782000 &:= (C(T(5)) + T(7) - C(8)) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

846.

$$\begin{aligned}5785 &:= (5 \times F(F(7)) - 8) \times 5 \\57850 &:= (5 \times F(F(7)) - 8) \times 50 \\578500 &:= (5 \times F(F(7)) - 8) \times 500 \\5785000 &:= (5 \times F(F(7)) - 8) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

847.

$$\begin{aligned}5793 &:= (5 \times C(7) + C((\sqrt{9})!)) \times 3 \\57930 &:= (5 \times C(7) + C((\sqrt{9})!)) \times 30 \\579300 &:= (5 \times C(7) + C((\sqrt{9})!)) \times 300 \\5793000 &:= (5 \times C(7) + C((\sqrt{9})!)) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

848.

$$\begin{aligned}5795 &:= (5 \times F(F(7)) - (\sqrt{9})!) \times 5 \\57950 &:= (5 \times F(F(7)) - (\sqrt{9})!) \times 50 \\579500 &:= (5 \times F(F(7)) - (\sqrt{9})!) \times 500 \\5795000 &:= (5 \times F(F(7)) - (\sqrt{9})!) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

849.

$$\begin{aligned}5795 &:= (5 \times F(F(7)) - T(\sqrt{9})) \times 5 \\57950 &:= (5 \times F(F(7)) - T(\sqrt{9})) \times 50 \\579500 &:= (5 \times F(F(7)) - T(\sqrt{9})) \times 500 \\5795000 &:= (5 \times F(F(7)) - T(\sqrt{9})) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

850.

$$\begin{aligned}5795 &:= (T(5) + T(Q(7)) - Q(9)) \times 5 \\57950 &:= (T(5) + T(Q(7)) - Q(9)) \times 50 \\579500 &:= (T(5) + T(Q(7)) - Q(9)) \times 500 \\5795000 &:= (T(5) + T(Q(7)) - Q(9)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

851.

$$5808 := (5 + (\sqrt{T(8)})! + 0!) \times 8$$

$$58080 := (5 + (\sqrt{T(8)})! + 0!) \times 80$$

$$580800 := (5 + (\sqrt{T(8)})! + 0!) \times 800$$

$$5808000 := (5 + (\sqrt{T(8)})! + 0!) \times 8000$$

852.

$$5826 := (F(-5 + F(8)) - Q(Q(2))) \times 6$$

$$58260 := (F(-5 + F(8)) - Q(Q(2))) \times 60$$

$$582600 := (F(-5 + F(8)) - Q(Q(2))) \times 600$$

$$5826000 := (F(-5 + F(8)) - Q(Q(2))) \times 6000$$

853.

$$5826 := (Q(-5 + T(8)) + T(Q(2))) \times 6$$

$$58260 := (Q(-5 + T(8)) + T(Q(2))) \times 60$$

$$582600 := (Q(-5 + T(8)) + T(Q(2))) \times 600$$

$$5826000 := (Q(-5 + T(8)) + T(Q(2))) \times 6000$$

854.

$$5840 := (C(5) + F(8)) \times 40$$

$$58400 := (C(5) + F(8)) \times 400$$

$$584000 := (C(5) + F(8)) \times 4000$$

$$5840000 := (C(5) + F(8)) \times 40000$$

855.

$$5840 := (C(5) + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 40$$

$$58400 := (C(5) + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 400$$

$$584000 := (C(5) + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 4000$$

$$5840000 := (C(5) + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 40000$$

856.

$$5842 := (5 + Q(Q(8) - T(4))) \times 2$$

$$58420 := (5 + Q(Q(8) - T(4))) \times 20$$

$$584200 := (5 + Q(Q(8) - T(4))) \times 200$$

$$5842000 := (5 + Q(Q(8) - T(4))) \times 2000$$

857.

$$5842 := (-5 + T(F(8) + F(T(4)))) \times 2$$

$$58420 := (-5 + T(F(8) + F(T(4)))) \times 20$$

$$584200 := (-5 + T(F(8) + F(T(4)))) \times 200$$

$$5842000 := (-5 + T(F(8) + F(T(4)))) \times 2000$$

858.

$$5842 := (-5 + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)} + T(T(4)))) \times 2$$

$$58420 := (-5 + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)} + T(T(4)))) \times 20$$

$$584200 := (-5 + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)} + T(T(4)))) \times 200$$

$$5842000 := (-5 + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)} + T(T(4)))) \times 2000$$

859.

$$5848 := (5! + T(T(8)) - F(T(4))) \times 8$$

$$58480 := (5! + T(T(8)) - F(T(4))) \times 80$$

$$584800 := (5! + T(T(8)) - F(T(4))) \times 800$$

$$5848000 := (5! + T(T(8)) - F(T(4))) \times 8000$$

860.

$$5848 := (5! + T(T(8)) - T(T(4))) \times 8$$

$$58480 := (5! + T(T(8)) - T(T(4))) \times 80$$

$$584800 := (5! + T(T(8)) - T(T(4))) \times 800$$

$$5848000 := (5! + T(T(8)) - T(T(4))) \times 8000$$

861.

$$\begin{aligned} 5848 &:= (C(Q(-5+8)) + \sqrt{4}) \times 8 \\ 58480 &:= (C(Q(-5+8)) + \sqrt{4}) \times 80 \\ 584800 &:= (C(Q(-5+8)) + \sqrt{4}) \times 800 \\ 5848000 &:= (C(Q(-5+8)) + \sqrt{4}) \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

862.

$$\begin{aligned} 5848 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + \sqrt{T(8)} + Q(T(4))) \times 8 \\ 58480 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + \sqrt{T(8)} + Q(T(4))) \times 80 \\ 584800 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + \sqrt{T(8)} + Q(T(4))) \times 800 \\ 5848000 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + \sqrt{T(8)} + Q(T(4))) \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

863.

$$\begin{aligned} 5848 &:= (T(T(5)) + T(T(8)) - F(T(4))) \times 8 \\ 58480 &:= (T(T(5)) + T(T(8)) - F(T(4))) \times 80 \\ 584800 &:= (T(T(5)) + T(T(8)) - F(T(4))) \times 800 \\ 5848000 &:= (T(T(5)) + T(T(8)) - F(T(4))) \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

864.

$$\begin{aligned} 5848 &:= (T(T(5)) + T(T(8)) - T(T(4))) \times 8 \\ 58480 &:= (T(T(5)) + T(T(8)) - T(T(4))) \times 80 \\ 584800 &:= (T(T(5)) + T(T(8)) - T(T(4))) \times 800 \\ 5848000 &:= (T(T(5)) + T(T(8)) - T(T(4))) \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

865.

$$\begin{aligned} 5850 &:= (C(5) - 8) \times 50 \\ 58500 &:= (C(5) - 8) \times 500 \\ 585000 &:= (C(5) - 8) \times 5000 \\ 5850000 &:= (C(5) - 8) \times 50000 \end{aligned}$$

866.

$$\begin{aligned} 5852 &:= T(T(5+8) - T(5)) \times 2 \\ 58520 &:= T(T(5+8) - T(5)) \times 20 \\ 585200 &:= T(T(5+8) - T(5)) \times 200 \\ 5852000 &:= T(T(5+8) - T(5)) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

867.

$$\begin{aligned} 5853 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + T(T(8) + T(5))) \times 3 \\ 58530 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + T(T(8) + T(5))) \times 30 \\ 585300 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + T(T(8) + T(5))) \times 300 \\ 5853000 &:= (Q(Q(5)) + T(T(8) + T(5))) \times 3000 \end{aligned}$$

868.

$$\begin{aligned} 5855 &:= (-5 + T((\sqrt{T(8)})!/T(5))) \times 5 \\ 58550 &:= (-5 + T((\sqrt{T(8)})!/T(5))) \times 50 \\ 585500 &:= (-5 + T((\sqrt{T(8)})!/T(5))) \times 500 \\ 5855000 &:= (-5 + T((\sqrt{T(8)})!/T(5))) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

869.

$$\begin{aligned} 5855 &:= (-C(5) + Q(Q((8-5)!))) \times 5 \\ 58550 &:= (-C(5) + Q(Q((8-5)!))) \times 50 \\ 585500 &:= (-C(5) + Q(Q((8-5)!))) \times 500 \\ 5855000 &:= (-C(5) + Q(Q((8-5)!))) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

870.

$$\begin{aligned} 5856 &:= (T(5) + Q(-5 + T(8))) \times 6 \\ 58560 &:= (T(5) + Q(-5 + T(8))) \times 60 \\ 585600 &:= (T(5) + Q(-5 + T(8))) \times 600 \\ 5856000 &:= (T(5) + Q(-5 + T(8))) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

871.

$$5856 := F(T(5)) \times 8/5 \times 6$$

$$58560 := F(T(5)) \times 8/5 \times 60$$

$$585600 := F(T(5)) \times 8/5 \times 600$$

$$5856000 := F(T(5)) \times 8/5 \times 6000$$

872.

$$5856 := F(T(5)) \times 8/5 \times 6$$

$$58560 := F(T(5)) \times 8/5 \times 60$$

$$585600 := F(T(5)) \times 8/5 \times 600$$

$$5856000 := F(T(5)) \times 8/5 \times 6000$$

873.

$$5859 := (F(T(5)) + T(8) + 5) \times 9$$

$$58590 := (F(T(5)) + T(8) + 5) \times 90$$

$$585900 := (F(T(5)) + T(8) + 5) \times 900$$

$$5859000 := (F(T(5)) + T(8) + 5) \times 9000$$

874.

$$5862 := (T(T(5 + \sqrt{T(8)})) + 6!) \times 2$$

$$58620 := (T(T(5 + \sqrt{T(8)})) + 6!) \times 20$$

$$586200 := (T(T(5 + \sqrt{T(8)})) + 6!) \times 200$$

$$5862000 := (T(T(5 + \sqrt{T(8)})) + 6!) \times 2000$$

875.

$$5865 := (Q(Q(5)) + C(8) + Q(6)) \times 5$$

$$58650 := (Q(Q(5)) + C(8) + Q(6)) \times 50$$

$$586500 := (Q(Q(5)) + C(8) + Q(6)) \times 500$$

$$5865000 := (Q(Q(5)) + C(8) + Q(6)) \times 5000$$

876.

$$5883 := (Q(5) + Q(8 + T(8))) \times 3$$

$$58830 := (Q(5) + Q(8 + T(8))) \times 30$$

$$588300 := (Q(5) + Q(8 + T(8))) \times 300$$

$$5883000 := (Q(5) + Q(8 + T(8))) \times 3000$$

877.

$$5886 := (5! \times 8 + F(8)) \times 6$$

$$58860 := (5! \times 8 + F(8)) \times 60$$

$$588600 := (5! \times 8 + F(8)) \times 600$$

$$5886000 := (5! \times 8 + F(8)) \times 6000$$

878.

$$5886 := (T(5) \times F(8) + T(T(8))) \times 6$$

$$58860 := (T(5) \times F(8) + T(T(8))) \times 60$$

$$588600 := (T(5) \times F(8) + T(T(8))) \times 600$$

$$5886000 := (T(5) \times F(8) + T(T(8))) \times 6000$$

879.

$$5886 := (T(5) \times T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + T(T(8))) \times 6$$

$$58860 := (T(5) \times T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + T(T(8))) \times 60$$

$$588600 := (T(5) \times T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + T(T(8))) \times 600$$

$$5886000 := (T(5) \times T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + T(T(8))) \times 6000$$

880.

$$5887 := (\sqrt{5^8} + C(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 7$$

$$58870 := (\sqrt{5^8} + C(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 70$$

$$588700 := (\sqrt{5^8} + C(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 700$$

$$5887000 := (\sqrt{5^8} + C(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 7000$$

881.

$$\begin{aligned} 5887 &:= (T(5 \times 8) + F(8)) \times 7 \\ 58870 &:= (T(5 \times 8) + F(8)) \times 70 \\ 588700 &:= (T(5 \times 8) + F(8)) \times 700 \\ 5887000 &:= (T(5 \times 8) + F(8)) \times 7000 \end{aligned}$$

882.

$$\begin{aligned} 5887 &:= (T(5 \times 8) + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 7 \\ 58870 &:= (T(5 \times 8) + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 70 \\ 588700 &:= (T(5 \times 8) + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 700 \\ 5887000 &:= (T(5 \times 8) + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 7000 \end{aligned}$$

883.

$$\begin{aligned} 5887 &:= Q(Q(5) + \sqrt{8+8}) \times 7 \\ 58870 &:= Q(Q(5) + \sqrt{8+8}) \times 70 \\ 588700 &:= Q(Q(5) + \sqrt{8+8}) \times 700 \\ 5887000 &:= Q(Q(5) + \sqrt{8+8}) \times 7000 \end{aligned}$$

884.

$$\begin{aligned} 5888 &:= (F(T(5)) + \sqrt{T(8)} \times F(8)) \times 8 \\ 58880 &:= (F(T(5)) + \sqrt{T(8)} \times F(8)) \times 80 \\ 588800 &:= (F(T(5)) + \sqrt{T(8)} \times F(8)) \times 800 \\ 5888000 &:= (F(T(5)) + \sqrt{T(8)} \times F(8)) \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

885.

$$\begin{aligned} 5905 &:= (Q(5) + Q(F(9))) \times 5 \\ 59050 &:= (Q(5) + Q(F(9))) \times 50 \\ 590500 &:= (Q(5) + Q(F(9))) \times 500 \\ 5905000 &:= (Q(5) + Q(F(9))) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

886.

$$\begin{aligned} 5910 &:= (Q(Q(5)) - F(9)) \times 10 \\ 59100 &:= (Q(Q(5)) - F(9)) \times 100 \\ 591000 &:= (Q(Q(5)) - F(9)) \times 1000 \\ 5910000 &:= (Q(Q(5)) - F(9)) \times 10000 \end{aligned}$$

887.

$$\begin{aligned} 5916 &:= (F(Q(5) - 9) - 1) \times 6 \\ 59160 &:= (F(Q(5) - 9) - 1) \times 60 \\ 591600 &:= (F(Q(5) - 9) - 1) \times 600 \\ 5916000 &:= (F(Q(5) - 9) - 1) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

888.

$$\begin{aligned} 5916 &:= (F(T(5) + F(F(\sqrt{9}))) - 1) \times 6 \\ 59160 &:= (F(T(5) + F(F(\sqrt{9}))) - 1) \times 60 \\ 591600 &:= (F(T(5) + F(F(\sqrt{9}))) - 1) \times 600 \\ 5916000 &:= (F(T(5) + F(F(\sqrt{9}))) - 1) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

889.

$$\begin{aligned} 5922 &:= (-5! + T(T(9 + T(2)))) \times 2 \\ 59220 &:= (-5! + T(T(9 + T(2)))) \times 20 \\ 592200 &:= (-5! + T(T(9 + T(2)))) \times 200 \\ 5922000 &:= (-5! + T(T(9 + T(2)))) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

890.

$$\begin{aligned} 5922 &:= (-T(T(5)) + T(T(9 + T(2)))) \times 2 \\ 59220 &:= (-T(T(5)) + T(T(9 + T(2)))) \times 20 \\ 592200 &:= (-T(T(5)) + T(T(9 + T(2)))) \times 200 \\ 5922000 &:= (-T(T(5)) + T(T(9 + T(2)))) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

891.

$$5928 := (5! \times (\sqrt{9})! + F(C(2))) \times 8$$

$$59280 := (5! \times (\sqrt{9})! + F(C(2))) \times 80$$

$$592800 := (5! \times (\sqrt{9})! + F(C(2))) \times 800$$

$$5928000 := (5! \times (\sqrt{9})! + F(C(2))) \times 8000$$

892.

$$5928 := (T(5) + C(9) - T(2)) \times 8$$

$$59280 := (T(5) + C(9) - T(2)) \times 80$$

$$592800 := (T(5) + C(9) - T(2)) \times 800$$

$$5928000 := (T(5) + C(9) - T(2)) \times 8000$$

893.

$$5928 := T(5 + F(9) - F(2)) \times 8$$

$$59280 := T(5 + F(9) - F(2)) \times 80$$

$$592800 := T(5 + F(9) - F(2)) \times 800$$

$$5928000 := T(5 + F(9) - F(2)) \times 8000$$

894.

$$5928 := T(-5 + T(9) - 2) \times 8$$

$$59280 := T(-5 + T(9) - 2) \times 80$$

$$592800 := T(-5 + T(9) - 2) \times 800$$

$$5928000 := T(-5 + T(9) - 2) \times 8000$$

895.

$$5935 := (-5 + Q(F(9)) + Q(3!)) \times 5$$

$$59350 := (-5 + Q(F(9)) + Q(3!)) \times 50$$

$$593500 := (-5 + Q(F(9)) + Q(3!)) \times 500$$

$$5935000 := (-5 + Q(F(9)) + Q(3!)) \times 5000$$

896.

$$5935 := (C(5) + T(T(9)) + C(3)) \times 5$$

$$59350 := (C(5) + T(T(9)) + C(3)) \times 50$$

$$593500 := (C(5) + T(T(9)) + C(3)) \times 500$$

$$5935000 := (C(5) + T(T(9)) + C(3)) \times 5000$$

897.

$$5942 := (5 \times T(F(9)) - 4) \times 2$$

$$59420 := (5 \times T(F(9)) - 4) \times 20$$

$$594200 := (5 \times T(F(9)) - 4) \times 200$$

$$5942000 := (5 \times T(F(9)) - 4) \times 2000$$

898.

$$5942 := (-C(5) \times 9 + Q(C(4))) \times 2$$

$$59420 := (-C(5) \times 9 + Q(C(4))) \times 20$$

$$594200 := (-C(5) \times 9 + Q(C(4))) \times 200$$

$$5942000 := (-C(5) \times 9 + Q(C(4))) \times 2000$$

899.

$$5945 := (-5! - T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5$$

$$59450 := (-5! - T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 50$$

$$594500 := (-5! - T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 500$$

$$5945000 := (-5! - T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5000$$

900.

$$5945 := (C(5) \times 9 + C(4)) \times 5$$

$$59450 := (C(5) \times 9 + C(4)) \times 50$$

$$594500 := (C(5) \times 9 + C(4)) \times 500$$

$$5945000 := (C(5) \times 9 + C(4)) \times 5000$$

901.

$$\begin{aligned} 5945 &:= (-T(T(5)) - T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5 \\ 59450 &:= (-T(T(5)) - T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 50 \\ 594500 &:= (-T(T(5)) - T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 500 \\ 5945000 &:= (-T(T(5)) - T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

902.

$$\begin{aligned} 5946 &:= -(5 - 9) + F(Q(4)) \times 6 \\ 59460 &:= -(5 - 9) + F(Q(4)) \times 60 \\ 594600 &:= -(5 - 9) + F(Q(4)) \times 600 \\ 5946000 &:= -(5 - 9) + F(Q(4)) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

903.

$$\begin{aligned} 5946 &:= (T(Q(5)) + T(9 \times 4)) \times 6 \\ 59460 &:= (T(Q(5)) + T(9 \times 4)) \times 60 \\ 594600 &:= (T(Q(5)) + T(9 \times 4)) \times 600 \\ 5946000 &:= (T(Q(5)) + T(9 \times 4)) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

904.

$$\begin{aligned} 5949 &:= (-5 + T(9 \times 4)) \times 9 \\ 59490 &:= (-5 + T(9 \times 4)) \times 90 \\ 594900 &:= (-5 + T(9 \times 4)) \times 900 \\ 5949000 &:= (-5 + T(9 \times 4)) \times 9000 \end{aligned}$$

905.

$$\begin{aligned} 5949 &:= (-59 + F(4)!) \times 9 \\ 59490 &:= (-59 + F(4)!) \times 90 \\ 594900 &:= (-59 + F(4)!) \times 900 \\ 5949000 &:= (-59 + F(4)!) \times 9000 \end{aligned}$$

906.

$$\begin{aligned} 5950 &:= (5! - F(F(\sqrt{9}))) \times 50 \\ 59500 &:= (5! - F(F(\sqrt{9}))) \times 500 \\ 595000 &:= (5! - F(F(\sqrt{9}))) \times 5000 \\ 5950000 &:= (5! - F(F(\sqrt{9}))) \times 50000 \end{aligned}$$

907.

$$\begin{aligned} 5950 &:= (C(5) - (\sqrt{9})!) \times 50 \\ 59500 &:= (C(5) - (\sqrt{9})!) \times 500 \\ 595000 &:= (C(5) - (\sqrt{9})!) \times 5000 \\ 5950000 &:= (C(5) - (\sqrt{9})!) \times 50000 \end{aligned}$$

908.

$$\begin{aligned} 5962 &:= (5 \times T(F(9)) + 6) \times 2 \\ 59620 &:= (5 \times T(F(9)) + 6) \times 20 \\ 596200 &:= (5 \times T(F(9)) + 6) \times 200 \\ 5962000 &:= (5 \times T(F(9)) + 6) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

909.

$$\begin{aligned} 5964 &:= (T(5 + T(9)) + C(6)) \times 4 \\ 59640 &:= (T(5 + T(9)) + C(6)) \times 40 \\ 596400 &:= (T(5 + T(9)) + C(6)) \times 400 \\ 5964000 &:= (T(5 + T(9)) + C(6)) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

910.

$$\begin{aligned} 5965 &:= 5 + (Q(F(9)) + Q(6)) \times 5 \\ 59650 &:= 5 + (Q(F(9)) + Q(6)) \times 50 \\ 596500 &:= 5 + (Q(F(9)) + Q(6)) \times 500 \\ 5965000 &:= 5 + (Q(F(9)) + Q(6)) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

911.

$$\begin{aligned}5968 &:= (5 + (\sqrt{9})!! + F(F(6))) \times 8 \\59680 &:= (5 + (\sqrt{9})!! + F(F(6))) \times 80 \\596800 &:= (5 + (\sqrt{9})!! + F(F(6))) \times 800 \\5968000 &:= (5 + (\sqrt{9})!! + F(F(6))) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

912.

$$\begin{aligned}5968 &:= (5 + T(T(\sqrt{9})) + 6!) \times 8 \\59680 &:= (5 + T(T(\sqrt{9})) + 6!) \times 80 \\596800 &:= (5 + T(T(\sqrt{9})) + 6!) \times 800 \\5968000 &:= (5 + T(T(\sqrt{9})) + 6!) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

913.

$$\begin{aligned}5968 &:= (F(T(5)) + T(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(6))) \times 8 \\59680 &:= (F(T(5)) + T(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(6))) \times 80 \\596800 &:= (F(T(5)) + T(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(6))) \times 800 \\5968000 &:= (F(T(5)) + T(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(6))) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

914.

$$\begin{aligned}5975 &:= (F(T(5)) + T(9) \times F(7)) \times 5 \\59750 &:= (F(T(5)) + T(9) \times F(7)) \times 50 \\597500 &:= (F(T(5)) + T(9) \times F(7)) \times 500 \\5975000 &:= (F(T(5)) + T(9) \times F(7)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

915.

$$\begin{aligned}6027 &:= T(6 - 0! + T(C(2))) \times 7 \\60270 &:= T(6 - 0! + T(C(2))) \times 70 \\602700 &:= T(6 - 0! + T(C(2))) \times 700 \\6027000 &:= T(6 - 0! + T(C(2))) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

916.

$$\begin{aligned}6027 &:= T(T(6) - 0! + T(T(T(2)))) \times 7 \\60270 &:= T(T(6) - 0! + T(T(T(2)))) \times 70 \\602700 &:= T(T(6) - 0! + T(T(T(2)))) \times 700 \\6027000 &:= T(T(6) - 0! + T(T(T(2)))) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

917.

$$\begin{aligned}6036 &:= (6 + C(0! + Q(3))) \times 6 \\60360 &:= (6 + C(0! + Q(3))) \times 60 \\603600 &:= (6 + C(0! + Q(3))) \times 600 \\6036000 &:= (6 + C(0! + Q(3))) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

918.

$$\begin{aligned}6039 &:= (6! - Q(0! + 3!)) \times 9 \\60390 &:= (6! - Q(0! + 3!)) \times 90 \\603900 &:= (6! - Q(0! + 3!)) \times 900 \\6039000 &:= (6! - Q(0! + 3!)) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

919.

$$\begin{aligned}6039 &:= (6! - Q(0! + T(3))) \times 9 \\60390 &:= (6! - Q(0! + T(3))) \times 90 \\603900 &:= (6! - Q(0! + T(3))) \times 900 \\6039000 &:= (6! - Q(0! + T(3))) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

920.

$$\begin{aligned}6045 &:= (Q(Q(6) - 0!) - Q(4)) \times 5 \\60450 &:= (Q(Q(6) - 0!) - Q(4)) \times 50 \\604500 &:= (Q(Q(6) - 0!) - Q(4)) \times 500 \\6045000 &:= (Q(Q(6) - 0!) - Q(4)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

921.

$$\begin{aligned}6048 &:= (Q(6) + (-0! + 4)!!) \times 8 \\60480 &:= (Q(6) + (-0! + 4)!!) \times 80 \\604800 &:= (Q(6) + (-0! + 4)!!) \times 800 \\6048000 &:= (Q(6) + (-0! + 4)!!) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

922.

$$\begin{aligned}6048 &:= (Q(6) + (0! + \sqrt{4})!!) \times 8 \\60480 &:= (Q(6) + (0! + \sqrt{4})!!) \times 80 \\604800 &:= (Q(6) + (0! + \sqrt{4})!!) \times 800 \\6048000 &:= (Q(6) + (0! + \sqrt{4})!!) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

923.

$$\begin{aligned}6052 &:= (Q(Q(6 + 0!)) + Q(Q(5))) \times 2 \\60520 &:= (Q(Q(6 + 0!)) + Q(Q(5))) \times 20 \\605200 &:= (Q(Q(6 + 0!)) + Q(Q(5))) \times 200 \\6052000 &:= (Q(Q(6 + 0!)) + Q(Q(5))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

924.

$$\begin{aligned}6052 &:= (Q(Q(F(6) - 0!)) + Q(Q(5))) \times 2 \\60520 &:= (Q(Q(F(6) - 0!)) + Q(Q(5))) \times 20 \\605200 &:= (Q(Q(F(6) - 0!)) + Q(Q(5))) \times 200 \\6052000 &:= (Q(Q(F(6) - 0!)) + Q(Q(5))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

925.

$$\begin{aligned}6075 &:= Q(F(6) + 0!) \times 75 \\60750 &:= Q(F(6) + 0!) \times 750 \\607500 &:= Q(F(6) + 0!) \times 7500 \\6075000 &:= Q(F(6) + 0!) \times 75000\end{aligned}$$

926.

$$\begin{aligned}6085 &:= (Q(Q(6) - 0!) - 8) \times 5 \\60850 &:= (Q(Q(6) - 0!) - 8) \times 50 \\608500 &:= (Q(Q(6) - 0!) - 8) \times 500 \\6085000 &:= (Q(Q(6) - 0!) - 8) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

927.

$$\begin{aligned}6092 &:= (T(6) + Q(T(9 + 0!))) \times 2 \\60920 &:= (T(6) + Q(T(9 + 0!))) \times 20 \\609200 &:= (T(6) + Q(T(9 + 0!))) \times 200 \\6092000 &:= (T(6) + Q(T(9 + 0!))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

928.

$$\begin{aligned}6093 &:= (6 + Q(T(9))) \times 3 \\60930 &:= (6 + Q(T(9))) \times 30 \\609300 &:= (6 + Q(T(9))) \times 300 \\6093000 &:= (6 + Q(T(9))) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

929.

$$\begin{aligned}6095 &:= (-6 + Q(F(9) + 0!)) \times 5 \\60950 &:= (-6 + Q(F(9) + 0!)) \times 50 \\609500 &:= (-6 + Q(F(9) + 0!)) \times 500 \\6095000 &:= (-6 + Q(F(9) + 0!)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

930.

$$\begin{aligned}6095 &:= (Q(Q(6) - 0!) - (\sqrt{9})!) \times 5 \\60950 &:= (Q(Q(6) - 0!) - (\sqrt{9})!) \times 50 \\609500 &:= (Q(Q(6) - 0!) - (\sqrt{9})!) \times 500 \\6095000 &:= (Q(Q(6) - 0!) - (\sqrt{9})!) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

931.

$$\begin{aligned}6096 &:= (F(6)! - C(F(9))) \times 6 \\60960 &:= (F(6)! - C(F(9))) \times 60 \\609600 &:= (F(6)! - C(F(9))) \times 600 \\6096000 &:= (F(6)! - C(F(9))) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

932.

$$\begin{aligned}6125 &:= (Q(6) - 1)^2 \times 5 \\61250 &:= (Q(6) - 1)^2 \times 50 \\612500 &:= (Q(6) - 1)^2 \times 500 \\6125000 &:= (Q(6) - 1)^2 \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

933.

$$\begin{aligned}6125 &:= T((6 + 1)^2) \times 5 \\61250 &:= T((6 + 1)^2) \times 50 \\612500 &:= T((6 + 1)^2) \times 500 \\6125000 &:= T((6 + 1)^2) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

934.

$$\begin{aligned}6126 &:= (F(F(6) + 1) + F(Q(Q(2)))) \times 6 \\61260 &:= (F(F(6) + 1) + F(Q(Q(2)))) \times 60 \\612600 &:= (F(F(6) + 1) + F(Q(Q(2)))) \times 600 \\6126000 &:= (F(F(6) + 1) + F(Q(Q(2)))) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

935.

$$\begin{aligned}6126 &:= (T(6) + C(T(T(2) + 1))) \times 6 \\61260 &:= (T(6) + C(T(T(2) + 1))) \times 60 \\612600 &:= (T(6) + C(T(T(2) + 1))) \times 600 \\6126000 &:= (T(6) + C(T(T(2) + 1))) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

936.

$$\begin{aligned}6129 &:= (T(Q(6)) + T(1 + Q(2))) \times 9 \\61290 &:= (T(Q(6)) + T(1 + Q(2))) \times 90 \\612900 &:= (T(Q(6)) + T(1 + Q(2))) \times 900 \\6129000 &:= (T(Q(6)) + T(1 + Q(2))) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

937.

$$\begin{aligned}6129 &:= (T(T(F(6))) + T(-1 + T(T(2)))) \times 9 \\61290 &:= (T(T(F(6))) + T(-1 + T(T(2)))) \times 90 \\612900 &:= (T(T(F(6))) + T(-1 + T(T(2)))) \times 900 \\6129000 &:= (T(T(F(6))) + T(-1 + T(T(2)))) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

938.

$$\begin{aligned}6132 &:= (C(F(6)) - 1) \times 3! \times 2 \\61320 &:= (C(F(6)) - 1) \times 3! \times 20 \\613200 &:= (C(F(6)) - 1) \times 3! \times 200 \\6132000 &:= (C(F(6)) - 1) \times 3! \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

939.

$$\begin{aligned}6132 &:= (C(F(6)) - 1) \times 3! \times 2 \\61320 &:= (C(F(6)) - 1) \times 3! \times 20 \\613200 &:= (C(F(6)) - 1) \times 3! \times 200 \\6132000 &:= (C(F(6)) - 1) \times 3! \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

940.

$$\begin{aligned}6135 &:= (Q(Q(6) - 1) + F(3)) \times 5 \\61350 &:= (Q(Q(6) - 1) + F(3)) \times 50 \\613500 &:= (Q(Q(6) - 1) + F(3)) \times 500 \\6135000 &:= (Q(Q(6) - 1) + F(3)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

941.

$$\begin{aligned}6144 &:= Q(F(6)) \times 4! \times 4 \\61440 &:= Q(F(6)) \times 4! \times 40 \\614400 &:= Q(F(6)) \times 4! \times 400 \\6144000 &:= Q(F(6)) \times 4! \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

942.

$$\begin{aligned}6144 &:= Q(F(6)) \times 4! \times 4 \\61440 &:= Q(F(6)) \times 4! \times 40 \\614400 &:= Q(F(6)) \times 4! \times 400 \\6144000 &:= Q(F(6)) \times 4! \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

943.

$$\begin{aligned}6145 &:= (Q(Q(6) - 1) + 4) \times 5 \\61450 &:= (Q(Q(6) - 1) + 4) \times 50 \\614500 &:= (Q(Q(6) - 1) + 4) \times 500 \\6145000 &:= (Q(Q(6) - 1) + 4) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

944.

$$\begin{aligned}6153 &:= (6! + C(\sqrt{1+5!})) \times 3 \\61530 &:= (6! + C(\sqrt{1+5!})) \times 30 \\615300 &:= (6! + C(\sqrt{1+5!})) \times 300 \\6153000 &:= (6! + C(\sqrt{1+5!})) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

945.

$$\begin{aligned}6153 &:= (6! + C(\sqrt{5!+1})) \times 3 \\61530 &:= (6! + C(\sqrt{5!+1})) \times 30 \\615300 &:= (6! + C(\sqrt{5!+1})) \times 300 \\6153000 &:= (6! + C(\sqrt{5!+1})) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

946.

$$\begin{aligned}6155 &:= (T(T(6)) + C(T(-1+5))) \times 5 \\61550 &:= (T(T(6)) + C(T(-1+5))) \times 50 \\615500 &:= (T(T(6)) + C(T(-1+5))) \times 500 \\6155000 &:= (T(T(6)) + C(T(-1+5))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

947.

$$\begin{aligned}6162 &:= T(T(6 \times 1 + 6)) \times 2 \\61620 &:= T(T(6 \times 1 + 6)) \times 20 \\616200 &:= T(T(6 \times 1 + 6)) \times 200 \\6162000 &:= T(T(6 \times 1 + 6)) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

948.

$$\begin{aligned}6165 &:= (6! + 1 + C(F(6))) \times 5 \\61650 &:= (6! + 1 + C(F(6))) \times 50 \\616500 &:= (6! + 1 + C(F(6))) \times 500 \\6165000 &:= (6! + 1 + C(F(6))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

949.

$$\begin{aligned}6165 &:= (F(6) + Q(Q(6) + 1)) \times 5 \\61650 &:= (F(6) + Q(Q(6) + 1)) \times 50 \\616500 &:= (F(6) + Q(Q(6) + 1)) \times 500 \\6165000 &:= (F(6) + Q(Q(6) + 1)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

950.

$$\begin{aligned}6167 &:= (Q(T(6)) - 1 + Q(T(6))) \times 7 \\61670 &:= (Q(T(6)) - 1 + Q(T(6))) \times 70 \\616700 &:= (Q(T(6)) - 1 + Q(T(6))) \times 700 \\6167000 &:= (Q(T(6)) - 1 + Q(T(6))) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

951.

$$\begin{aligned}6168 &:= (-C(6) + F(16)) \times 8 \\61680 &:= (-C(6) + F(16)) \times 80 \\616800 &:= (-C(6) + F(16)) \times 800 \\6168000 &:= (-C(6) + F(16)) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

952.

$$\begin{aligned}6205 &:= (C(F(6)) + C(0! + C(2))) \times 5 \\62050 &:= (C(F(6)) + C(0! + C(2))) \times 50 \\620500 &:= (C(F(6)) + C(0! + C(2))) \times 500 \\6205000 &:= (C(F(6)) + C(0! + C(2))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

953.

$$\begin{aligned}6205 &:= (Q(Q(6)) - F(Q(F(Q(2))) + 0!)) \times 5 \\62050 &:= (Q(Q(6)) - F(Q(F(Q(2))) + 0!)) \times 50 \\620500 &:= (Q(Q(6)) - F(Q(F(Q(2))) + 0!)) \times 500 \\6205000 &:= (Q(Q(6)) - F(Q(F(Q(2))) + 0!)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

954.

$$\begin{aligned}6216 &:= (T(T(6 + T(2))) + 1) \times 6 \\62160 &:= (T(T(6 + T(2))) + 1) \times 60 \\621600 &:= (T(T(6 + T(2))) + 1) \times 600 \\6216000 &:= (T(T(6 + T(2))) + 1) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

955.

$$\begin{aligned}6224 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + Q(2) + Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times 4 \\62240 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + Q(2) + Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times 40 \\622400 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + Q(2) + Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times 400 \\6224000 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + Q(2) + Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

956.

$$\begin{aligned}6224 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2))) + Q(2)) \times 4 \\62240 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2))) + Q(2)) \times 40 \\622400 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2))) + Q(2)) \times 400 \\6224000 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2))) + Q(2)) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

957.

$$\begin{aligned}6237 &:= (C(6) \times Q(2) + C(3)) \times 7 \\62370 &:= (C(6) \times Q(2) + C(3)) \times 70 \\623700 &:= (C(6) \times Q(2) + C(3)) \times 700 \\6237000 &:= (C(6) \times Q(2) + C(3)) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

958.

$$\begin{aligned}6237 &:= (F(6) + F(Q(2))) \times Q(Q(3)) \times 7 \\62370 &:= (F(6) + F(Q(2))) \times Q(Q(3)) \times 70 \\623700 &:= (F(6) + F(Q(2))) \times Q(Q(3)) \times 700 \\6237000 &:= (F(6) + F(Q(2))) \times Q(Q(3)) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

959.

$$\begin{aligned}6237 &:= (Q(6 + Q(2)!) - Q(3)) \times 7 \\62370 &:= (Q(6 + Q(2)!) - Q(3)) \times 70 \\623700 &:= (Q(6 + Q(2)!) - Q(3)) \times 700 \\6237000 &:= (Q(6 + Q(2)!) - Q(3)) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

960.

$$\begin{aligned}6241 &:= (T(T(6)) \times C(T(2)) + 4) \times 1 \\62410 &:= (T(T(6)) \times C(T(2)) + 4) \times 10 \\624100 &:= (T(T(6)) \times C(T(2)) + 4) \times 100 \\6241000 &:= (T(T(6)) \times C(T(2)) + 4) \times 1000\end{aligned}$$

961.

$$\begin{aligned}6243 &:= (T(F(6)^2) + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 3 \\62430 &:= (T(F(6)^2) + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 30 \\624300 &:= (T(F(6)^2) + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 300 \\6243000 &:= (T(F(6)^2) + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

962.

$$\begin{aligned}6243 &:= (T(T(6)) \times Q(T(2)) + \sqrt{4}) \times 3 \\62430 &:= (T(T(6)) \times Q(T(2)) + \sqrt{4}) \times 30 \\624300 &:= (T(T(6)) \times Q(T(2)) + \sqrt{4}) \times 300 \\6243000 &:= (T(T(6)) \times Q(T(2)) + \sqrt{4}) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

963.

$$\begin{aligned}6244 &:= (-Q(6) + F(F(2) + Q(4))) \times 4 \\62440 &:= (-Q(6) + F(F(2) + Q(4))) \times 40 \\624400 &:= (-Q(6) + F(F(2) + Q(4))) \times 400 \\6244000 &:= (-Q(6) + F(F(2) + Q(4))) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

964.

$$\begin{aligned}6244 &:= (T(T(6/2)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 4 \\62440 &:= (T(T(6/2)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 40 \\624400 &:= (T(T(6/2)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 400 \\6244000 &:= (T(T(6/2)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

965.

$$\begin{aligned}6246 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + F(2) - Q(Q(4))) \times 6 \\62460 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + F(2) - Q(Q(4))) \times 60 \\624600 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + F(2) - Q(Q(4))) \times 600 \\6246000 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + F(2) - Q(Q(4))) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

966.

$$\begin{aligned}6248 &:= (6! + T(T(2)) + F(T(4))) \times 8 \\62480 &:= (6! + T(T(2)) + F(T(4))) \times 80 \\624800 &:= (6! + T(T(2)) + F(T(4))) \times 800 \\6248000 &:= (6! + T(T(2)) + F(T(4))) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

967.

$$\begin{aligned}6248 &:= (6! + T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times 8 \\62480 &:= (6! + T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times 80 \\624800 &:= (6! + T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times 800 \\6248000 &:= (6! + T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

968.

$$\begin{aligned}6248 &:= (6! - T(2) + C(4)) \times 8 \\62480 &:= (6! - T(2) + C(4)) \times 80 \\624800 &:= (6! - T(2) + C(4)) \times 800 \\6248000 &:= (6! - T(2) + C(4)) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

969.

$$\begin{aligned}6250 &:= C(6 - F(2)) \times 50 \\62500 &:= C(6 - F(2)) \times 500 \\625000 &:= C(6 - F(2)) \times 5000 \\6250000 &:= C(6 - F(2)) \times 50000\end{aligned}$$

970.

$$\begin{aligned}6265 &:= (C(F(6)) + F(C(2)) + 6!) \times 5 \\62650 &:= (C(F(6)) + F(C(2)) + 6!) \times 50 \\626500 &:= (C(F(6)) + F(C(2)) + 6!) \times 500 \\6265000 &:= (C(F(6)) + F(C(2)) + 6!) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

971.

$$\begin{aligned}6265 &:= (T(6) + C(C(2)) + 6!) \times 5 \\62650 &:= (T(6) + C(C(2)) + 6!) \times 50 \\626500 &:= (T(6) + C(C(2)) + 6!) \times 500 \\6265000 &:= (T(6) + C(C(2)) + 6!) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

972.

$$\begin{aligned}6288 &:= (6! + 2 + Q(8)) \times 8 \\62880 &:= (6! + 2 + Q(8)) \times 80 \\628800 &:= (6! + 2 + Q(8)) \times 800 \\6288000 &:= (6! + 2 + Q(8)) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

973.

$$\begin{aligned}6288 &:= (6 + T(T(2) + T(8))) \times 8 \\62880 &:= (6 + T(T(2) + T(8))) \times 80 \\628800 &:= (6 + T(T(2) + T(8))) \times 800 \\6288000 &:= (6 + T(T(2) + T(8))) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

974.

$$\begin{aligned}6291 &:= (6! - F(C(2))) \times 9 \\62910 &:= (6! - F(C(2))) \times 90 \\629100 &:= (6! - F(C(2))) \times 900 \\6291000 &:= (6! - F(C(2))) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

975.

$$\begin{aligned}6291 &:= (-T(6) + T(T(2))!) \times 9 \\62910 &:= (-T(6) + T(T(2))!) \times 90 \\629100 &:= (-T(6) + T(T(2))!) \times 900 \\6291000 &:= (-T(6) + T(T(2))!) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

976.

$$\begin{aligned}6292 &:= (F(T(6) - 2) - T(T(9))) \times 2 \\62920 &:= (F(T(6) - 2) - T(T(9))) \times 20 \\629200 &:= (F(T(6) - 2) - T(T(9))) \times 200 \\6292000 &:= (F(T(6) - 2) - T(T(9))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

977.

$$\begin{aligned}6295 &:= (6! + C(C(2)) + \sqrt{C(9)}) \times 5 \\62950 &:= (6! + C(C(2)) + \sqrt{C(9)}) \times 50 \\629500 &:= (6! + C(C(2)) + \sqrt{C(9)}) \times 500 \\6295000 &:= (6! + C(C(2)) + \sqrt{C(9)}) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

978.

$$\begin{aligned}6295 &:= (C(6) + C(2) + T(T(9))) \times 5 \\62950 &:= (C(6) + C(2) + T(T(9))) \times 50 \\629500 &:= (C(6) + C(2) + T(T(9))) \times 500 \\6295000 &:= (C(6) + C(2) + T(T(9))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

979.

$$\begin{aligned}6295 &:= (Q(Q(6)) - Q(C(2)) + C(\sqrt{9})) \times 5 \\62950 &:= (Q(Q(6)) - Q(C(2)) + C(\sqrt{9})) \times 50 \\629500 &:= (Q(Q(6)) - Q(C(2)) + C(\sqrt{9})) \times 500 \\6295000 &:= (Q(Q(6)) - Q(C(2)) + C(\sqrt{9})) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

980.

$$\begin{aligned}6295 &:= (Q(Q(6) - F(2)) + F(9)) \times 5 \\62950 &:= (Q(Q(6) - F(2)) + F(9)) \times 50 \\629500 &:= (Q(Q(6) - F(2)) + F(9)) \times 500 \\6295000 &:= (Q(Q(6) - F(2)) + F(9)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

981.

$$\begin{aligned}6295 &:= (T(T(F(6))) - 2 + T(F(9))) \times 5 \\62950 &:= (T(T(F(6))) - 2 + T(F(9))) \times 50 \\629500 &:= (T(T(F(6))) - 2 + T(F(9))) \times 500 \\6295000 &:= (T(T(F(6))) - 2 + T(F(9))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

982.

$$\begin{aligned}6303 &:= (T(6) + T(C(3 + 0!))) \times 3 \\63030 &:= (T(6) + T(C(3 + 0!))) \times 30 \\630300 &:= (T(6) + T(C(3 + 0!))) \times 300 \\6303000 &:= (T(6) + T(C(3 + 0!))) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

983.

$$\begin{aligned}6303 &:= (T(6) + T(Q(Q(3) - 0!))) \times 3 \\63030 &:= (T(6) + T(Q(Q(3) - 0!))) \times 30 \\630300 &:= (T(6) + T(Q(Q(3) - 0!))) \times 300 \\6303000 &:= (T(6) + T(Q(Q(3) - 0!))) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

984.

$$\begin{aligned}6305 &:= (C(F(F(6))) - C(F(C(F(3))) - 0!) \times 5 \\63050 &:= (C(F(F(6))) - C(F(C(F(3))) - 0!) \times 50 \\630500 &:= (C(F(F(6))) - C(F(C(F(3))) - 0!) \times 500 \\6305000 &:= (C(F(F(6))) - C(F(C(F(3))) - 0!) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

985.

$$\begin{aligned}6305 &:= (C(T(6)) - C(T(T(3)) - 0!) \times 5 \\63050 &:= (C(T(6)) - C(T(T(3)) - 0!) \times 50 \\630500 &:= (C(T(6)) - C(T(T(3)) - 0!) \times 500 \\6305000 &:= (C(T(6)) - C(T(T(3)) - 0!) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

986.

$$\begin{aligned}6305 &:= (Q(Q(6)) - Q(3!) + 0!) \times 5 \\63050 &:= (Q(Q(6)) - Q(3!) + 0!) \times 50 \\630500 &:= (Q(Q(6)) - Q(3!) + 0!) \times 500 \\6305000 &:= (Q(Q(6)) - Q(3!) + 0!) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

987.

$$\begin{aligned}6307 &:= (Q(Q(6) - 3!) + 0!) \times 7 \\63070 &:= (Q(Q(6) - 3!) + 0!) \times 70 \\630700 &:= (Q(Q(6) - 3!) + 0!) \times 700 \\6307000 &:= (Q(Q(6) - 3!) + 0!) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

988.

$$\begin{aligned}6307 &:= (Q(Q(6) - T(3)) + 0!) \times 7 \\63070 &:= (Q(Q(6) - T(3)) + 0!) \times 70 \\630700 &:= (Q(Q(6) - T(3)) + 0!) \times 700 \\6307000 &:= (Q(Q(6) - T(3)) + 0!) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

989.

$$\begin{aligned}6309 &:= (T(Q(6)) + Q(T(3)) - 0!) \times 9 \\63090 &:= (T(Q(6)) + Q(T(3)) - 0!) \times 90 \\630900 &:= (T(Q(6)) + Q(T(3)) - 0!) \times 900 \\6309000 &:= (T(Q(6)) + Q(T(3)) - 0!) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

990.

$$\begin{aligned}6315 &:= (Q(Q(6)) - F(Q(3)) + 1) \times 5 \\63150 &:= (Q(Q(6)) - F(Q(3)) + 1) \times 50 \\631500 &:= (Q(Q(6)) - F(Q(3)) + 1) \times 500 \\6315000 &:= (Q(Q(6)) - F(Q(3)) + 1) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

991.

$$\begin{aligned}6324 &:= (F(F(6) + Q(3)) - Q(Q(2))) \times 4 \\63240 &:= (F(F(6) + Q(3)) - Q(Q(2))) \times 40 \\632400 &:= (F(F(6) + Q(3)) - Q(Q(2))) \times 400 \\6324000 &:= (F(F(6) + Q(3)) - Q(Q(2))) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

992.

$$\begin{aligned}6365 &:= (Q(Q(6)) - F(3) - F(F(6))) \times 5 \\63650 &:= (Q(Q(6)) - F(3) - F(F(6))) \times 50 \\636500 &:= (Q(Q(6)) - F(3) - F(F(6))) \times 500 \\6365000 &:= (Q(Q(6)) - F(3) - F(F(6))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

993.

$$\begin{aligned}6370 &:= T(F(T(6)/3)) \times 70 \\63700 &:= T(F(T(6)/3)) \times 700 \\637000 &:= T(F(T(6)/3)) \times 7000 \\6370000 &:= T(F(T(6)/3)) \times 70000\end{aligned}$$

994.

$$\begin{aligned}6375 &:= T(63 - F(7)) \times 5 \\63750 &:= T(63 - F(7)) \times 50 \\637500 &:= T(63 - F(7)) \times 500 \\6375000 &:= T(63 - F(7)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

995.

$$\begin{aligned}6375 &:= T(T(6 + T(3)) - T(7)) \times 5 \\63750 &:= T(T(6 + T(3)) - T(7)) \times 50 \\637500 &:= T(T(6 + T(3)) - T(7)) \times 500 \\6375000 &:= T(T(6 + T(3)) - T(7)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

996.

$$\begin{aligned}6377 &:= (F(6) + T(7 \times T(3))) \times 7 \\63770 &:= (F(6) + T(7 \times T(3))) \times 70 \\637700 &:= (F(6) + T(7 \times T(3))) \times 700 \\6377000 &:= (F(6) + T(7 \times T(3))) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

997.

$$\begin{aligned}6385 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + F(3) - F(8)) \times 5 \\63850 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + F(3) - F(8)) \times 50 \\638500 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + F(3) - F(8)) \times 500 \\6385000 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + F(3) - F(8)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

998.

$$\begin{aligned}6385 &:= (Q(Q(6)) - C(3) + 8) \times 5 \\63850 &:= (Q(Q(6)) - C(3) + 8) \times 50 \\638500 &:= (Q(Q(6)) - C(3) + 8) \times 500 \\6385000 &:= (Q(Q(6)) - C(3) + 8) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

999.

$$\begin{aligned}6399 &:= ((6 - 3)!! - 9) \times 9 \\63990 &:= ((6 - 3)!! - 9) \times 90 \\639900 &:= ((6 - 3)!! - 9) \times 900 \\6399000 &:= ((6 - 3)!! - 9) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

1000.

$$\begin{aligned}6399 &:= (6! \times F(3) - C(9)) \times 9 \\63990 &:= (6! \times F(3) - C(9)) \times 90 \\639900 &:= (6! \times F(3) - C(9)) \times 900 \\6399000 &:= (6! \times F(3) - C(9)) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

1001.

$$6399 := (6! - 3! - \sqrt{9}) \times 9$$

$$63990 := (6! - 3! - \sqrt{9}) \times 90$$

$$639900 := (6! - 3! - \sqrt{9}) \times 900$$

$$6399000 := (6! - 3! - \sqrt{9}) \times 9000$$

1002.

$$6399 := (6! - T(3) - \sqrt{9}) \times 9$$

$$63990 := (6! - T(3) - \sqrt{9}) \times 90$$

$$639900 := (6! - T(3) - \sqrt{9}) \times 900$$

$$6399000 := (6! - T(3) - \sqrt{9}) \times 9000$$

1003.

$$6399 := (-6 \times 3 + C(9)) \times 9$$

$$63990 := (-6 \times 3 + C(9)) \times 90$$

$$639900 := (-6 \times 3 + C(9)) \times 900$$

$$6399000 := (-6 \times 3 + C(9)) \times 9000$$

1004.

$$6399 := (F(6) + T(3 + F(9))) \times 9$$

$$63990 := (F(6) + T(3 + F(9))) \times 90$$

$$639900 := (F(6) + T(3 + F(9))) \times 900$$

$$6399000 := (F(6) + T(3 + F(9))) \times 9000$$

1005.

$$6399 := (T(6 \times T(3)) + T(9)) \times 9$$

$$63990 := (T(6 \times T(3)) + T(9)) \times 90$$

$$639900 := (T(6 \times T(3)) + T(9)) \times 900$$

$$6399000 := (T(6 \times T(3)) + T(9)) \times 9000$$

1006.

$$6404 := (Q(Q(6) + 4) + 0!) \times 4$$

$$64040 := (Q(Q(6) + 4) + 0!) \times 40$$

$$640400 := (Q(Q(6) + 4) + 0!) \times 400$$

$$6404000 := (Q(Q(6) + 4) + 0!) \times 4000$$

1007.

$$6405 := (Q(Q(6)) - Q(4) + 0!) \times 5$$

$$64050 := (Q(Q(6)) - Q(4) + 0!) \times 50$$

$$640500 := (Q(Q(6)) - Q(4) + 0!) \times 500$$

$$6405000 := (Q(Q(6)) - Q(4) + 0!) \times 5000$$

1008.

$$6408 := (6! + Q(Q(4 - 0!))) \times 8$$

$$64080 := (6! + Q(Q(4 - 0!))) \times 80$$

$$640800 := (6! + Q(Q(4 - 0!))) \times 800$$

$$6408000 := (6! + Q(Q(4 - 0!))) \times 8000$$

1009.

$$6408 := (6! + Q(Q(\sqrt{4} + 0!))) \times 8$$

$$64080 := (6! + Q(Q(\sqrt{4} + 0!))) \times 80$$

$$640800 := (6! + Q(Q(\sqrt{4} + 0!))) \times 800$$

$$6408000 := (6! + Q(Q(\sqrt{4} + 0!))) \times 8000$$

1010.

$$6408 := (6! + Q(T(4) - 0!)) \times 8$$

$$64080 := (6! + Q(T(4) - 0!)) \times 80$$

$$640800 := (6! + Q(T(4) - 0!)) \times 800$$

$$6408000 := (6! + Q(T(4) - 0!)) \times 8000$$

1011.

$$\begin{aligned} 6420 &:= (T(6) + T(4!)) \times 20 \\ 64200 &:= (T(6) + T(4!)) \times 200 \\ 642000 &:= (T(6) + T(4!)) \times 2000 \\ 6420000 &:= (T(6) + T(4!)) \times 20000 \end{aligned}$$

1012.

$$\begin{aligned} 6425 &:= (-T(T(F(6))) + F(T(T(F(4)))))/F(T(T(2))) \times 5 \\ 64250 &:= (-T(T(F(6))) + F(T(T(F(4)))))/F(T(T(2))) \times 50 \\ 642500 &:= (-T(T(F(6))) + F(T(T(F(4)))))/F(T(T(2))) \times 500 \\ 6425000 &:= (-T(T(F(6))) + F(T(T(F(4)))))/F(T(T(2))) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1013.

$$\begin{aligned} 6432 &:= (C(F(6)) + 4!) \times 3! \times 2 \\ 64320 &:= (C(F(6)) + 4!) \times 3! \times 20 \\ 643200 &:= (C(F(6)) + 4!) \times 3! \times 200 \\ 6432000 &:= (C(F(6)) + 4!) \times 3! \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1014.

$$\begin{aligned} 6432 &:= (C(F(6)) + 4!) \times 3! \times 2 \\ 64320 &:= (C(F(6)) + 4!) \times 3! \times 20 \\ 643200 &:= (C(F(6)) + 4!) \times 3! \times 200 \\ 6432000 &:= (C(F(6)) + 4!) \times 3! \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1015.

$$\begin{aligned} 6447 &:= (T(T(6)) \times 4 - F(4)) \times 7 \\ 64470 &:= (T(T(6)) \times 4 - F(4)) \times 70 \\ 644700 &:= (T(T(6)) \times 4 - F(4)) \times 700 \\ 6447000 &:= (T(T(6)) \times 4 - F(4)) \times 7000 \end{aligned}$$

1016.

$$\begin{aligned} 6447 &:= (T(T(6)) \times 4 - T(\sqrt{4})) \times 7 \\ 64470 &:= (T(T(6)) \times 4 - T(\sqrt{4})) \times 70 \\ 644700 &:= (T(T(6)) \times 4 - T(\sqrt{4})) \times 700 \\ 6447000 &:= (T(T(6)) \times 4 - T(\sqrt{4})) \times 7000 \end{aligned}$$

1017.

$$\begin{aligned} 6453 &:= (6 + T(-F(T(4)) + T(T(5)))) \times 3 \\ 64530 &:= (6 + T(-F(T(4)) + T(T(5)))) \times 30 \\ 645300 &:= (6 + T(-F(T(4)) + T(T(5)))) \times 300 \\ 6453000 &:= (6 + T(-F(T(4)) + T(T(5)))) \times 3000 \end{aligned}$$

1018.

$$\begin{aligned} 6453 &:= (6 + T(-T(T(4)) + 5!)) \times 3 \\ 64530 &:= (6 + T(-T(T(4)) + 5!)) \times 30 \\ 645300 &:= (6 + T(-T(T(4)) + 5!)) \times 300 \\ 6453000 &:= (6 + T(-T(T(4)) + 5!)) \times 3000 \end{aligned}$$

1019.

$$\begin{aligned} 6453 &:= (6 + T(-T(T(4)) + T(T(5)))) \times 3 \\ 64530 &:= (6 + T(-T(T(4)) + T(T(5)))) \times 30 \\ 645300 &:= (6 + T(-T(T(4)) + T(T(5)))) \times 300 \\ 6453000 &:= (6 + T(-T(T(4)) + T(T(5)))) \times 3000 \end{aligned}$$

1020.

$$\begin{aligned} 6455 &:= (6^4 - 5) \times 5 \\ 64550 &:= (6^4 - 5) \times 50 \\ 645500 &:= (6^4 - 5) \times 500 \\ 6455000 &:= (6^4 - 5) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1021.

$$\begin{aligned}6456 &:= (Q(F(6)) + F(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times 6 \\64560 &:= (Q(F(6)) + F(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times 60 \\645600 &:= (Q(F(6)) + F(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times 600 \\6456000 &:= (Q(F(6)) + F(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1022.

$$\begin{aligned}6465 &:= (-6/\sqrt{4} + Q(Q(6))) \times 5 \\64650 &:= (-6/\sqrt{4} + Q(Q(6))) \times 50 \\646500 &:= (-6/\sqrt{4} + Q(Q(6))) \times 500 \\6465000 &:= (-6/\sqrt{4} + Q(Q(6))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1023.

$$\begin{aligned}6475 &:= (T(T(6)) \times T(F(4)) - T(F(7))) \times 5 \\64750 &:= (T(T(6)) \times T(F(4)) - T(F(7))) \times 50 \\647500 &:= (T(T(6)) \times T(F(4)) - T(F(7))) \times 500 \\6475000 &:= (T(T(6)) \times T(F(4)) - T(F(7))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1024.

$$\begin{aligned}6485 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + F(Q(4)/8)) \times 5 \\64850 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + F(Q(4)/8)) \times 50 \\648500 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + F(Q(4)/8)) \times 500 \\6485000 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + F(Q(4)/8)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1025.

$$\begin{aligned}6489 &:= (F(6+4) + T(T(8))) \times 9 \\64890 &:= (F(6+4) + T(T(8))) \times 90 \\648900 &:= (F(6+4) + T(T(8))) \times 900 \\6489000 &:= (F(6+4) + T(T(8))) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

1026.

$$\begin{aligned}6489 &:= (T(6+4) + T(T(8))) \times 9 \\64890 &:= (T(6+4) + T(T(8))) \times 90 \\648900 &:= (T(6+4) + T(T(8))) \times 900 \\6489000 &:= (T(6+4) + T(T(8))) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

1027.

$$\begin{aligned}6492 &:= (T(T(T(6) - T(4))) + T(T(9))) \times 2 \\64920 &:= (T(T(T(6) - T(4))) + T(T(9))) \times 20 \\649200 &:= (T(T(T(6) - T(4))) + T(T(9))) \times 200 \\6492000 &:= (T(T(T(6) - T(4))) + T(T(9))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1028.

$$\begin{aligned}6505 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + 5) \times 5 \\65050 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + 5) \times 50 \\650500 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + 5) \times 500 \\6505000 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + 5) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1029.

$$\begin{aligned}6510 &:= (T(Q(6)) - T(5)) \times 10 \\65100 &:= (T(Q(6)) - T(5)) \times 100 \\651000 &:= (T(Q(6)) - T(5)) \times 1000 \\6510000 &:= (T(Q(6)) - T(5)) \times 10000\end{aligned}$$

1030.

$$\begin{aligned}6510 &:= (T(T(F(6))) - T(5)) \times 10 \\65100 &:= (T(T(F(6))) - T(5)) \times 100 \\651000 &:= (T(T(F(6))) - T(5)) \times 1000 \\6510000 &:= (T(T(F(6))) - T(5)) \times 10000\end{aligned}$$

1031.

$$\begin{aligned}6525 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 - 2)) \times 5 \\65250 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 - 2)) \times 50 \\652500 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 - 2)) \times 500 \\6525000 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 - 2)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1032.

$$\begin{aligned}6528 &:= 6 \times T(T(5) + F(2)) \times 8 \\65280 &:= 6 \times T(T(5) + F(2)) \times 80 \\652800 &:= 6 \times T(T(5) + F(2)) \times 800 \\6528000 &:= 6 \times T(T(5) + F(2)) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

1033.

$$\begin{aligned}6528 &:= T(T(6) - 5) \times T(T(2)) \times 8 \\65280 &:= T(T(6) - 5) \times T(T(2)) \times 80 \\652800 &:= T(T(6) - 5) \times T(T(2)) \times 800 \\6528000 &:= T(T(6) - 5) \times T(T(2)) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

1034.

$$\begin{aligned}6535 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 3!) \times 5 \\65350 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 3!) \times 50 \\653500 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 3!) \times 500 \\6535000 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 3!) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1035.

$$\begin{aligned}6535 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + T(3)) \times 5 \\65350 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + T(3)) \times 50 \\653500 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + T(3)) \times 500 \\6535000 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + T(3)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1036.

$$\begin{aligned}6543 &:= (T(65) + T(\sqrt{C(4)})) \times 3 \\65430 &:= (T(65) + T(\sqrt{C(4)})) \times 30 \\654300 &:= (T(65) + T(\sqrt{C(4)})) \times 300 \\6543000 &:= (T(65) + T(\sqrt{C(4)})) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

1037.

$$\begin{aligned}6545 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + F(5 + \sqrt{4})) \times 5 \\65450 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + F(5 + \sqrt{4})) \times 50 \\654500 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + F(5 + \sqrt{4})) \times 500 \\6545000 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + F(5 + \sqrt{4})) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1038.

$$\begin{aligned}6545 &:= (-T(6 + T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5 \\65450 &:= (-T(6 + T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 50 \\654500 &:= (-T(6 + T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 500 \\6545000 &:= (-T(6 + T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1039.

$$\begin{aligned}6545 &:= (-T(T(6)) + T(T(5 \times \sqrt{4}))) \times 5 \\65450 &:= (-T(T(6)) + T(T(5 \times \sqrt{4}))) \times 50 \\654500 &:= (-T(T(6)) + T(T(5 \times \sqrt{4}))) \times 500 \\6545000 &:= (-T(T(6)) + T(T(5 \times \sqrt{4}))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1040.

$$\begin{aligned}6546 &:= (C(6) - C(5) + C(T(4))) \times 6 \\65460 &:= (C(6) - C(5) + C(T(4))) \times 60 \\654600 &:= (C(6) - C(5) + C(T(4))) \times 600 \\6546000 &:= (C(6) - C(5) + C(T(4))) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1041.

$$\begin{aligned}6546 &:= (Q(F(6) + Q(5)) + \sqrt{4}) \times 6 \\65460 &:= (Q(F(6) + Q(5)) + \sqrt{4}) \times 60 \\654600 &:= (Q(F(6) + Q(5)) + \sqrt{4}) \times 600 \\6546000 &:= (Q(F(6) + Q(5)) + \sqrt{4}) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1042.

$$\begin{aligned}6550 &:= (6 + C(5)) \times 50 \\65500 &:= (6 + C(5)) \times 500 \\655000 &:= (6 + C(5)) \times 5000 \\6550000 &:= (6 + C(5)) \times 50000\end{aligned}$$

1043.

$$\begin{aligned}6555 &:= (T(T(F(6)) + T(5)) - T(5)) \times 5 \\65550 &:= (T(T(F(6)) + T(5)) - T(5)) \times 50 \\655500 &:= (T(T(F(6)) + T(5)) - T(5)) \times 500 \\6555000 &:= (T(T(F(6)) + T(5)) - T(5)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1044.

$$\begin{aligned}6565 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5) - F(6)) \times 5 \\65650 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5) - F(6)) \times 50 \\656500 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5) - F(6)) \times 500 \\6565000 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5) - F(6)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1045.

$$\begin{aligned}6585 &:= (T(T(F(6))) - T(5) + T(T(8))) \times 5 \\65850 &:= (T(T(F(6))) - T(5) + T(T(8))) \times 50 \\658500 &:= (T(T(F(6))) - T(5) + T(T(8))) \times 500 \\6585000 &:= (T(T(F(6))) - T(5) + T(T(8))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1046.

$$\begin{aligned}6595 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5) - F(\sqrt{9})) \times 5 \\65950 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5) - F(\sqrt{9})) \times 50 \\659500 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5) - F(\sqrt{9})) \times 500 \\6595000 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5) - F(\sqrt{9})) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1047.

$$\begin{aligned}6605 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + Q(6 - 0!)) \times 5 \\66050 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + Q(6 - 0!)) \times 50 \\660500 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + Q(6 - 0!)) \times 500 \\6605000 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + Q(6 - 0!)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1048.

$$\begin{aligned}6608 &:= (T(T(6)) + T(F(F(6) + 0!))) \times 8 \\66080 &:= (T(T(6)) + T(F(F(6) + 0!))) \times 80 \\660800 &:= (T(T(6)) + T(F(F(6) + 0!))) \times 800 \\6608000 &:= (T(T(6)) + T(F(F(6) + 0!))) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

1049.

$$\begin{aligned}6615 &:= (F(F(6)) \times F(F(6))) \times 15 \\66150 &:= (F(F(6)) \times F(F(6))) \times 150 \\661500 &:= (F(F(6)) \times F(F(6))) \times 1500 \\6615000 &:= (F(F(6)) \times F(F(6))) \times 15000\end{aligned}$$

1050.

$$\begin{aligned}6615 &:= (T(6) \times T(6)) \times 15 \\66150 &:= (T(6) \times T(6)) \times 150 \\661500 &:= (T(6) \times T(6)) \times 1500 \\6615000 &:= (T(6) \times T(6)) \times 15000\end{aligned}$$

1051.

$$\begin{aligned}6624 &:= (C(6) + 2 \times 6!) \times 4 \\66240 &:= (C(6) + 2 \times 6!) \times 40 \\662400 &:= (C(6) + 2 \times 6!) \times 400 \\6624000 &:= (C(6) + 2 \times 6!) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

1052.

$$\begin{aligned}6642 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + Q(6!/Q(4))) \times 2 \\66420 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + Q(6!/Q(4))) \times 20 \\664200 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + Q(6!/Q(4))) \times 200 \\6642000 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + Q(6!/Q(4))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1053.

$$\begin{aligned}6642 &:= T(T(6) + 6 \times T(4)) \times 2 \\66420 &:= T(T(6) + 6 \times T(4)) \times 20 \\664200 &:= T(T(6) + 6 \times T(4)) \times 200 \\6642000 &:= T(T(6) + 6 \times T(4)) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1054.

$$\begin{aligned}6644 &:= (T(T(F(6)) + T(6)) + F(T(F(4)))) \times 4 \\66440 &:= (T(T(F(6)) + T(6)) + F(T(F(4)))) \times 40 \\664400 &:= (T(T(F(6)) + T(6)) + F(T(F(4)))) \times 400 \\6644000 &:= (T(T(F(6)) + T(6)) + F(T(F(4)))) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

1055.

$$\begin{aligned}6648 &:= (Q(Q(6)) - T(6!/4!)) \times 8 \\66480 &:= (Q(Q(6)) - T(6!/4!)) \times 80 \\664800 &:= (Q(Q(6)) - T(6!/4!)) \times 800 \\6648000 &:= (Q(Q(6)) - T(6!/4!)) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

1056.

$$\begin{aligned}6655 &:= C(\sqrt{6 \times 6} + 5) \times 5 \\66550 &:= C(\sqrt{6 \times 6} + 5) \times 50 \\665500 &:= C(\sqrt{6 \times 6} + 5) \times 500 \\6655000 &:= C(\sqrt{6 \times 6} + 5) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1057.

$$\begin{aligned}6657 &:= (C(6) + 6! + T(5)) \times 7 \\66570 &:= (C(6) + 6! + T(5)) \times 70 \\665700 &:= (C(6) + 6! + T(5)) \times 700 \\6657000 &:= (C(6) + 6! + T(5)) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

1058.

$$\begin{aligned}6657 &:= (T(T(6)) + 6 \times 5!) \times 7 \\66570 &:= (T(T(6)) + 6 \times 5!) \times 70 \\665700 &:= (T(T(6)) + 6 \times 5!) \times 700 \\6657000 &:= (T(T(6)) + 6 \times 5!) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

1059.

$$\begin{aligned}6657 &:= (T(T(6)) + 6 \times T(T(5))) \times 7 \\66570 &:= (T(T(6)) + 6 \times T(T(5))) \times 70 \\665700 &:= (T(T(6)) + 6 \times T(T(5))) \times 700 \\6657000 &:= (T(T(6)) + 6 \times T(T(5))) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

1060.

$$\begin{aligned}6660 &:= T(T(F(6)))/6 \times 60 \\66600 &:= T(T(F(6)))/6 \times 600 \\666000 &:= T(T(F(6)))/6 \times 6000 \\6660000 &:= T(T(F(6)))/6 \times 60000\end{aligned}$$

1061.

$$\begin{aligned}6669 &:= T(T(F(6)) + F(6) - 6) \times 9 \\66690 &:= T(T(F(6)) + F(6) - 6) \times 90 \\666900 &:= T(T(F(6)) + F(6) - 6) \times 900 \\6669000 &:= T(T(F(6)) + F(6) - 6) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

1062.

$$\begin{aligned}6675 &:= F(T(T(6))/T(6)) \times 75 \\66750 &:= F(T(T(6))/T(6)) \times 750 \\667500 &:= F(T(T(6))/T(6)) \times 7500 \\6675000 &:= F(T(T(6))/T(6)) \times 75000\end{aligned}$$

1063.

$$\begin{aligned}6684 &:= (6! + 6! + T(F(8))) \times 4 \\66840 &:= (6! + 6! + T(F(8))) \times 40 \\668400 &:= (6! + 6! + T(F(8))) \times 400 \\6684000 &:= (6! + 6! + T(F(8))) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

1064.

$$\begin{aligned}6684 &:= (T(T(6)) + 6! + (\sqrt{T(8)})!) \times 4 \\66840 &:= (T(T(6)) + 6! + (\sqrt{T(8)})!) \times 40 \\668400 &:= (T(T(6)) + 6! + (\sqrt{T(8)})!) \times 400 \\6684000 &:= (T(T(6)) + 6! + (\sqrt{T(8)})!) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

1065.

$$\begin{aligned}6685 &:= (C(T(T(6))/T(6)) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 5 \\66850 &:= (C(T(T(6))/T(6)) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 50 \\668500 &:= (C(T(T(6))/T(6)) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 500 \\6685000 &:= (C(T(T(6))/T(6)) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1066.

$$\begin{aligned}6695 &:= (F(6) + C(F(6) + \sqrt{9})) \times 5 \\66950 &:= (F(6) + C(F(6) + \sqrt{9})) \times 50 \\669500 &:= (F(6) + C(F(6) + \sqrt{9})) \times 500 \\6695000 &:= (F(6) + C(F(6) + \sqrt{9})) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1067.

$$\begin{aligned}6710 &:= (6! - Q(7)) \times 10 \\67100 &:= (6! - Q(7)) \times 100 \\671000 &:= (6! - Q(7)) \times 1000 \\6710000 &:= (6! - Q(7)) \times 10000\end{aligned}$$

1068.

$$\begin{aligned}6725 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + 7^2) \times 5 \\67250 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + 7^2) \times 50 \\672500 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + 7^2) \times 500 \\6725000 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + 7^2) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1069.

$$\begin{aligned}6725 &:= (T(F(6)) + F(F(7))) \times 25 \\67250 &:= (T(F(6)) + F(F(7))) \times 250 \\672500 &:= (T(F(6)) + F(F(7))) \times 2500 \\6725000 &:= (T(F(6)) + F(F(7))) \times 25000\end{aligned}$$

1070.

$$\begin{aligned}6727 &:= Q(Q(6) - 7 + 2) \times 7 \\67270 &:= Q(Q(6) - 7 + 2) \times 70 \\672700 &:= Q(Q(6) - 7 + 2) \times 700 \\6727000 &:= Q(Q(6) - 7 + 2) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

1071.

$$\begin{aligned}6728 &:= (Q(6) - 7)^2 \times 8 \\67280 &:= (Q(6) - 7)^2 \times 80 \\672800 &:= (Q(6) - 7)^2 \times 800 \\6728000 &:= (Q(6) - 7)^2 \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

1072.

$$\begin{aligned}6728 &:= (T(F(6)) - 7)^2 \times 8 \\67280 &:= (T(F(6)) - 7)^2 \times 80 \\672800 &:= (T(F(6)) - 7)^2 \times 800 \\6728000 &:= (T(F(6)) - 7)^2 \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

1073.

$$\begin{aligned}6732 &:= T(T(T(6))/7) \times T(3) \times 2 \\67320 &:= T(T(T(6))/7) \times T(3) \times 20 \\673200 &:= T(T(T(6))/7) \times T(3) \times 200 \\6732000 &:= T(T(T(6))/7) \times T(3) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1074.

$$\begin{aligned}6735 &:= (C(6) + F(F(7))) \times 3 \times 5 \\67350 &:= (C(6) + F(F(7))) \times 3 \times 50 \\673500 &:= (C(6) + F(F(7))) \times 3 \times 500 \\6735000 &:= (C(6) + F(F(7))) \times 3 \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1075.

$$\begin{aligned}6735 &:= (C(6) + F(F(7))) \times 3 \times 5 \\67350 &:= (C(6) + F(F(7))) \times 3 \times 50 \\673500 &:= (C(6) + F(F(7))) \times 3 \times 500 \\6735000 &:= (C(6) + F(F(7))) \times 3 \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1076.

$$\begin{aligned}6742 &:= (C(F(6) + 7) - 4) \times 2 \\67420 &:= (C(F(6) + 7) - 4) \times 20 \\674200 &:= (C(F(6) + 7) - 4) \times 200 \\6742000 &:= (C(F(6) + 7) - 4) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1077.

$$\begin{aligned}6745 &:= (6 + C(7) + C(T(4))) \times 5 \\67450 &:= (6 + C(7) + C(T(4))) \times 50 \\674500 &:= (6 + C(7) + C(T(4))) \times 500 \\6745000 &:= (6 + C(7) + C(T(4))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1078.

$$\begin{aligned}6745 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + Q(7) + 4) \times 5 \\67450 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + Q(7) + 4) \times 50 \\674500 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + Q(7) + 4) \times 500 \\6745000 &:= (Q(Q(6)) + Q(7) + 4) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1079.

$$\begin{aligned}6752 &:= (-(6 - 7) + C(T(5))) \times 2 \\67520 &:= (-(6 - 7) + C(T(5))) \times 20 \\675200 &:= (-(6 - 7) + C(T(5))) \times 200 \\6752000 &:= (-(6 - 7) + C(T(5))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1080.

$$\begin{aligned}6768 &:= (6 + 7!/6) \times 8 \\67680 &:= (6 + 7!/6) \times 80 \\676800 &:= (6 + 7!/6) \times 800 \\6768000 &:= (6 + 7!/6) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

1081.

$$6768 := (Q(6) + 7!)/6 \times 8$$

$$67680 := (Q(6) + 7!)/6 \times 80$$

$$676800 := (Q(6) + 7!)/6 \times 800$$

$$6768000 := (Q(6) + 7!)/6 \times 8000$$

1082.

$$6775 := (F(F(F(6)))/(-F(7)) + C(F(7))) \times 5$$

$$67750 := (F(F(F(6)))/(-F(7)) + C(F(7))) \times 50$$

$$677500 := (F(F(F(6)))/(-F(7)) + C(F(7))) \times 500$$

$$6775000 := (F(F(F(6)))/(-F(7)) + C(F(7))) \times 5000$$

1083.

$$6783 := (C(6 + 7) + Q(8)) \times 3$$

$$67830 := (C(6 + 7) + Q(8)) \times 30$$

$$678300 := (C(6 + 7) + Q(8)) \times 300$$

$$6783000 := (C(6 + 7) + Q(8)) \times 3000$$

1084.

$$6785 := (6! + T(T(7)) + T(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$67850 := (6! + T(T(7)) + T(F(8))) \times 50$$

$$678500 := (6! + T(T(7)) + T(F(8))) \times 500$$

$$6785000 := (6! + T(T(7)) + T(F(8))) \times 5000$$

1085.

$$6785 := (T(T(6)) + T(T(7)) + (\sqrt{T(8)!}) \times 5$$

$$67850 := (T(T(6)) + T(T(7)) + (\sqrt{T(8)!}) \times 50$$

$$678500 := (T(T(6)) + T(T(7)) + (\sqrt{T(8)!}) \times 500$$

$$6785000 := (T(T(6)) + T(T(7)) + (\sqrt{T(8)!}) \times 5000$$

1086.

$$6795 := (Q(Q(6)) + 7 \times 9) \times 5$$

$$67950 := (Q(Q(6)) + 7 \times 9) \times 50$$

$$679500 := (Q(Q(6)) + 7 \times 9) \times 500$$

$$6795000 := (Q(Q(6)) + 7 \times 9) \times 5000$$

1087.

$$6795 := (T(T(6)) + T(F(7) + F(9))) \times 5$$

$$67950 := (T(T(6)) + T(F(7) + F(9))) \times 50$$

$$679500 := (T(T(6)) + T(F(7) + F(9))) \times 500$$

$$6795000 := (T(T(6)) + T(F(7) + F(9))) \times 5000$$

1088.

$$6805 := (Q(Q(6)) + Q(8) + 0!) \times 5$$

$$68050 := (Q(Q(6)) + Q(8) + 0!) \times 50$$

$$680500 := (Q(Q(6)) + Q(8) + 0!) \times 500$$

$$6805000 := (Q(Q(6)) + Q(8) + 0!) \times 5000$$

1089.

$$6815 := (-6 + Q(T(8) + 1)) \times 5$$

$$68150 := (-6 + Q(T(8) + 1)) \times 50$$

$$681500 := (-6 + Q(T(8) + 1)) \times 500$$

$$6815000 := (-6 + Q(T(8) + 1)) \times 5000$$

1090.

$$6822 := (F(6) + T(82)) \times 2$$

$$68220 := (F(6) + T(82)) \times 20$$

$$682200 := (F(6) + T(82)) \times 200$$

$$6822000 := (F(6) + T(82)) \times 2000$$

1091.

$$6844 := T(6 \times 8 + T(4)) \times 4$$

$$68440 := T(6 \times 8 + T(4)) \times 40$$

$$684400 := T(6 \times 8 + T(4)) \times 400$$

$$6844000 := T(6 \times 8 + T(4)) \times 4000$$

1092.

$$6844 := T(-6 + \sqrt{8^4}) \times 4$$

$$68440 := T(-6 + \sqrt{8^4}) \times 40$$

$$684400 := T(-6 + \sqrt{8^4}) \times 400$$

$$6844000 := T(-6 + \sqrt{8^4}) \times 4000$$

1093.

$$6845 := Q(Q(6) + F(8/4)) \times 5$$

$$68450 := Q(Q(6) + F(8/4)) \times 50$$

$$684500 := Q(Q(6) + F(8/4)) \times 500$$

$$6845000 := Q(Q(6) + F(8/4)) \times 5000$$

1094.

$$6848 := (T(F(6)) + T(T(8) + 4)) \times 8$$

$$68480 := (T(F(6)) + T(T(8) + 4)) \times 80$$

$$684800 := (T(F(6)) + T(T(8) + 4)) \times 800$$

$$6848000 := (T(F(6)) + T(T(8) + 4)) \times 8000$$

1095.

$$6867 := (-6 + F(F(6) + 8)) \times 7$$

$$68670 := (-6 + F(F(6) + 8)) \times 70$$

$$686700 := (-6 + F(F(6) + 8)) \times 700$$

$$6867000 := (-6 + F(F(6) + 8)) \times 7000$$

1096.

$$6873 := (Q(6 \times 8) - F(7)) \times 3$$

$$68730 := (Q(6 \times 8) - F(7)) \times 30$$

$$687300 := (Q(6 \times 8) - F(7)) \times 300$$

$$6873000 := (Q(6 \times 8) - F(7)) \times 3000$$

1097.

$$6888 := (-F(F(6)) + Q(F(8)) + Q(F(8))) \times 8$$

$$68880 := (-F(F(6)) + Q(F(8)) + Q(F(8))) \times 80$$

$$688800 := (-F(F(6)) + Q(F(8)) + Q(F(8))) \times 800$$

$$6888000 := (-F(F(6)) + Q(F(8)) + Q(F(8))) \times 8000$$

1098.

$$6888 := (T(T(6)) + T(T(8)) - T(8)) \times 8$$

$$68880 := (T(T(6)) + T(T(8)) - T(8)) \times 80$$

$$688800 := (T(T(6)) + T(T(8)) - T(8)) \times 800$$

$$6888000 := (T(T(6)) + T(T(8)) - T(8)) \times 8000$$

1099.

$$6906 := (-6 + Q(F(9)) + 0!) \times 6$$

$$69060 := (-6 + Q(F(9)) + 0!) \times 60$$

$$690600 := (-6 + Q(F(9)) + 0!) \times 600$$

$$6906000 := (-6 + Q(F(9)) + 0!) \times 6000$$

1100.

$$6922 := (-6! + F(F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) - 2)) \times 2$$

$$69220 := (-6! + F(F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) - 2)) \times 20$$

$$692200 := (-6! + F(F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) - 2)) \times 200$$

$$6922000 := (-6! + F(F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) - 2)) \times 2000$$

1101.

$$\begin{aligned} 6922 &:= (F(T(6) - F(\sqrt{9})) - T(T(2)))! \times 2 \\ 69220 &:= (F(T(6) - F(\sqrt{9})) - T(T(2)))! \times 20 \\ 692200 &:= (F(T(6) - F(\sqrt{9})) - T(T(2)))! \times 200 \\ 6922000 &:= (F(T(6) - F(\sqrt{9})) - T(T(2)))! \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1102.

$$\begin{aligned} 6924 &:= (C(T(6) - 9) + T(2)) \times 4 \\ 69240 &:= (C(T(6) - 9) + T(2)) \times 40 \\ 692400 &:= (C(T(6) - 9) + T(2)) \times 400 \\ 6924000 &:= (C(T(6) - 9) + T(2)) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

1103.

$$\begin{aligned} 6925 &:= (T(T(6)) \times T(\sqrt{9}) - F(2)) \times 5 \\ 69250 &:= (T(T(6)) \times T(\sqrt{9}) - F(2)) \times 50 \\ 692500 &:= (T(T(6)) \times T(\sqrt{9}) - F(2)) \times 500 \\ 6925000 &:= (T(T(6)) \times T(\sqrt{9}) - F(2)) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1104.

$$\begin{aligned} 6935 &:= (-C(F(F(6))) + C(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + F(C(F(3)))) \times 5 \\ 69350 &:= (-C(F(F(6))) + C(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + F(C(F(3)))) \times 50 \\ 693500 &:= (-C(F(F(6))) + C(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + F(C(F(3)))) \times 500 \\ 6935000 &:= (-C(F(F(6))) + C(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + F(C(F(3)))) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1105.

$$\begin{aligned} 6935 &:= (T(T(6)) + F(9)^{F(3)}) \times 5 \\ 69350 &:= (T(T(6)) + F(9)^{F(3)}) \times 50 \\ 693500 &:= (T(T(6)) + F(9)^{F(3)}) \times 500 \\ 6935000 &:= (T(T(6)) + F(9)^{F(3)}) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1106.

$$\begin{aligned} 6937 &:= (-T(F(6)) + T(T(9)) - F(T(3))) \times 7 \\ 69370 &:= (-T(F(6)) + T(T(9)) - F(T(3))) \times 70 \\ 693700 &:= (-T(F(6)) + T(T(9)) - F(T(3))) \times 700 \\ 6937000 &:= (-T(F(6)) + T(T(9)) - F(T(3))) \times 7000 \end{aligned}$$

1107.

$$\begin{aligned} 6939 &:= (6! + T(9) + T(3)) \times 9 \\ 69390 &:= (6! + T(9) + T(3)) \times 90 \\ 693900 &:= (6! + T(9) + T(3)) \times 900 \\ 6939000 &:= (6! + T(9) + T(3)) \times 9000 \end{aligned}$$

1108.

$$\begin{aligned} 6939 &:= (Q(6) + C(9) + 3!) \times 9 \\ 69390 &:= (Q(6) + C(9) + 3!) \times 90 \\ 693900 &:= (Q(6) + C(9) + 3!) \times 900 \\ 6939000 &:= (Q(6) + C(9) + 3!) \times 9000 \end{aligned}$$

1109.

$$\begin{aligned} 6955 &:= (T(T(6)) \times T(\sqrt{9}) + 5) \times 5 \\ 69550 &:= (T(T(6)) \times T(\sqrt{9}) + 5) \times 50 \\ 695500 &:= (T(T(6)) \times T(\sqrt{9}) + 5) \times 500 \\ 6955000 &:= (T(T(6)) \times T(\sqrt{9}) + 5) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1110.

$$\begin{aligned} 6966 &:= (F(F(6))^{F(\sqrt{9})} + 6!) \times 6 \\ 69660 &:= (F(F(6))^{F(\sqrt{9})} + 6!) \times 60 \\ 696600 &:= (F(F(6))^{F(\sqrt{9})} + 6!) \times 600 \\ 6966000 &:= (F(F(6))^{F(\sqrt{9})} + 6!) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

1111.

$$\begin{aligned} 6966 &:= (T(6)^{F(\sqrt{9})} + 6!) \times 6 \\ 69660 &:= (T(6)^{F(\sqrt{9})} + 6!) \times 60 \\ 696600 &:= (T(6)^{F(\sqrt{9})} + 6!) \times 600 \\ 6966000 &:= (T(6)^{F(\sqrt{9})} + 6!) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

1112.

$$\begin{aligned} 6996 &:= (F(6) + F(\sqrt{9}) + Q(F(9))) \times 6 \\ 69960 &:= (F(6) + F(\sqrt{9}) + Q(F(9))) \times 60 \\ 699600 &:= (F(6) + F(\sqrt{9}) + Q(F(9))) \times 600 \\ 6996000 &:= (F(6) + F(\sqrt{9}) + Q(F(9))) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

1113.

$$\begin{aligned} 7042 &:= (T(T(F(7))) + 0! - T(T(F(T(F(4)))))) \times 2 \\ 70420 &:= (T(T(F(7))) + 0! - T(T(F(T(F(4)))))) \times 20 \\ 704200 &:= (T(T(F(7))) + 0! - T(T(F(T(F(4)))))) \times 200 \\ 7042000 &:= (T(T(F(7))) + 0! - T(T(F(T(F(4)))))) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1114.

$$\begin{aligned} 7045 &:= (Q(T(7)) + Q(0! + 4!)) \times 5 \\ 70450 &:= (Q(T(7)) + Q(0! + 4!)) \times 50 \\ 704500 &:= (Q(T(7)) + Q(0! + 4!)) \times 500 \\ 7045000 &:= (Q(T(7)) + Q(0! + 4!)) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1115.

$$\begin{aligned} 7084 &:= 7 \times T(0! + F(8)) \times 4 \\ 70840 &:= 7 \times T(0! + F(8)) \times 40 \\ 708400 &:= 7 \times T(0! + F(8)) \times 400 \\ 7084000 &:= 7 \times T(0! + F(8)) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

1116.

$$\begin{aligned} 7152 &:= (T(T(F(7))) - F(15)) \times 2 \\ 71520 &:= (T(T(F(7))) - F(15)) \times 20 \\ 715200 &:= (T(T(F(7))) - F(15)) \times 200 \\ 7152000 &:= (T(T(F(7))) - F(15)) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1117.

$$\begin{aligned} 7155 &:= T(-F(7) + T(\sqrt{1 + 5!})) \times 5 \\ 71550 &:= T(-F(7) + T(\sqrt{1 + 5!})) \times 50 \\ 715500 &:= T(-F(7) + T(\sqrt{1 + 5!})) \times 500 \\ 7155000 &:= T(-F(7) + T(\sqrt{1 + 5!})) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1118.

$$\begin{aligned} 7155 &:= T(-F(7) + T(\sqrt{1 + T(T(5))})) \times 5 \\ 71550 &:= T(-F(7) + T(\sqrt{1 + T(T(5))})) \times 50 \\ 715500 &:= T(-F(7) + T(\sqrt{1 + T(T(5))})) \times 500 \\ 7155000 &:= T(-F(7) + T(\sqrt{1 + T(T(5))})) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1119.

$$\begin{aligned} 7155 &:= T(Q(7) - 1 + 5) \times 5 \\ 71550 &:= T(Q(7) - 1 + 5) \times 50 \\ 715500 &:= T(Q(7) - 1 + 5) \times 500 \\ 7155000 &:= T(Q(7) - 1 + 5) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1120.

$$\begin{aligned} 7176 &:= (T(F(7)) + 1) \times F(7) \times 6 \\ 71760 &:= (T(F(7)) + 1) \times F(7) \times 60 \\ 717600 &:= (T(F(7)) + 1) \times F(7) \times 600 \\ 7176000 &:= (T(F(7)) + 1) \times F(7) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

1121.

$$7203 := 7^{T(2)+0!} \times 3$$

$$72030 := 7^{T(2)+0!} \times 30$$

$$720300 := 7^{T(2)+0!} \times 300$$

$$7203000 := 7^{T(2)+0!} \times 3000$$

1122.

$$7203 := Q(7^2) \times 3$$

$$72030 := Q(7^2) \times 30$$

$$720300 := Q(7^2) \times 300$$

$$7203000 := Q(7^2) \times 3000$$

1123.

$$7205 := (T(T(7)) + T(T(F(T(T(2)))) + 0!)) \times 5$$

$$72050 := (T(T(7)) + T(T(F(T(T(2)))) + 0!)) \times 50$$

$$720500 := (T(T(7)) + T(T(F(T(T(2)))) + 0!)) \times 500$$

$$7205000 := (T(T(7)) + T(T(F(T(T(2)))) + 0!)) \times 5000$$

1124.

$$7206 := (T(Q(7)) - Q(2)!) \times 6$$

$$72060 := (T(Q(7)) - Q(2)!) \times 60$$

$$720600 := (T(Q(7)) - Q(2)!) \times 600$$

$$7206000 := (T(Q(7)) - Q(2)!) \times 6000$$

1125.

$$7208 := (Q(T(7) + 2) + 0!) \times 8$$

$$72080 := (Q(T(7) + 2) + 0!) \times 80$$

$$720800 := (Q(T(7) + 2) + 0!) \times 800$$

$$7208000 := (Q(T(7) + 2) + 0!) \times 8000$$

1126.

$$7210 := (C(7) + T(C(T(2)))) \times 10$$

$$72100 := (C(7) + T(C(T(2)))) \times 100$$

$$721000 := (C(7) + T(C(T(2)))) \times 1000$$

$$7210000 := (C(7) + T(C(T(2)))) \times 10000$$

1127.

$$7222 := (7 \times C(C(2)) + C(T(2))) \times 2$$

$$72220 := (7 \times C(C(2)) + C(T(2))) \times 20$$

$$722200 := (7 \times C(C(2)) + C(T(2))) \times 200$$

$$7222000 := (7 \times C(C(2)) + C(T(2))) \times 2000$$

1128.

$$7230 := (F(F(7)) + F(T(T(2)))) \times 30$$

$$72300 := (F(F(7)) + F(T(T(2)))) \times 300$$

$$723000 := (F(F(7)) + F(T(T(2)))) \times 3000$$

$$7230000 := (F(F(7)) + F(T(T(2)))) \times 30000$$

1129.

$$7233 := (Q(Q(7)) + F(2) + Q(3)) \times 3$$

$$72330 := (Q(Q(7)) + F(2) + Q(3)) \times 30$$

$$723300 := (Q(Q(7)) + F(2) + Q(3)) \times 300$$

$$7233000 := (Q(Q(7)) + F(2) + Q(3)) \times 3000$$

1130.

$$7233 := (Q(Q(7)) + Q(2) + 3!) \times 3$$

$$72330 := (Q(Q(7)) + Q(2) + 3!) \times 30$$

$$723300 := (Q(Q(7)) + Q(2) + 3!) \times 300$$

$$7233000 := (Q(Q(7)) + Q(2) + 3!) \times 3000$$

1131.

$$\begin{aligned}7235 &:= (7 + 2 \times T(3)!) \times 5 \\72350 &:= (7 + 2 \times T(3)!) \times 50 \\723500 &:= (7 + 2 \times T(3)!) \times 500 \\7235000 &:= (7 + 2 \times T(3)!) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1132.

$$\begin{aligned}7244 &:= (T(Q(7)) + T(Q(2)) + Q(4!)) \times 4 \\72440 &:= (T(Q(7)) + T(Q(2)) + Q(4!)) \times 40 \\724400 &:= (T(Q(7)) + T(Q(2)) + Q(4!)) \times 400 \\7244000 &:= (T(Q(7)) + T(Q(2)) + Q(4!)) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

1133.

$$\begin{aligned}7245 &:= (Q(Q(7) - Q(2)) - Q(4!)) \times 5 \\72450 &:= (Q(Q(7) - Q(2)) - Q(4!)) \times 50 \\724500 &:= (Q(Q(7) - Q(2)) - Q(4!)) \times 500 \\7245000 &:= (Q(Q(7) - Q(2)) - Q(4!)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1134.

$$\begin{aligned}7250 &:= (Q(F(7)) - Q(2)!) \times 50 \\72500 &:= (Q(F(7)) - Q(2)!) \times 500 \\725000 &:= (Q(F(7)) - Q(2)!) \times 5000 \\7250000 &:= (Q(F(7)) - Q(2)!) \times 50000\end{aligned}$$

1135.

$$\begin{aligned}7255 &:= (C(7 + Q(2)) + 5!) \times 5 \\72550 &:= (C(7 + Q(2)) + 5!) \times 50 \\725500 &:= (C(7 + Q(2)) + 5!) \times 500 \\7255000 &:= (C(7 + Q(2)) + 5!) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1136.

$$\begin{aligned}7255 &:= (C(F(7) - 2) + 5!) \times 5 \\72550 &:= (C(F(7) - 2) + 5!) \times 50 \\725500 &:= (C(F(7) - 2) + 5!) \times 500 \\7255000 &:= (C(F(7) - 2) + 5!) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1137.

$$\begin{aligned}7260 &:= Q(7 + Q(2)) \times 60 \\72600 &:= Q(7 + Q(2)) \times 600 \\726000 &:= Q(7 + Q(2)) \times 6000 \\7260000 &:= Q(7 + Q(2)) \times 60000\end{aligned}$$

1138.

$$\begin{aligned}7260 &:= Q(F(7) - 2) \times 60 \\72600 &:= Q(F(7) - 2) \times 600 \\726000 &:= Q(F(7) - 2) \times 6000 \\7260000 &:= Q(F(7) - 2) \times 60000\end{aligned}$$

1139.

$$\begin{aligned}7263 &:= (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(2)) + Q(6)) \times 3 \\72630 &:= (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(2)) + Q(6)) \times 30 \\726300 &:= (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(2)) + Q(6)) \times 300 \\7263000 &:= (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(2)) + Q(6)) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

1140.

$$\begin{aligned}7264 &:= (F(F(7)) - T(T(2))) \times F(6) \times 4 \\72640 &:= (F(F(7)) - T(T(2))) \times F(6) \times 40 \\726400 &:= (F(F(7)) - T(T(2))) \times F(6) \times 400 \\7264000 &:= (F(F(7)) - T(T(2))) \times F(6) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

1141.

$$\begin{aligned}7265 &:= (F(7) + 2 \times 6!) \times 5 \\72650 &:= (F(7) + 2 \times 6!) \times 50 \\726500 &:= (F(7) + 2 \times 6!) \times 500 \\7265000 &:= (F(7) + 2 \times 6!) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1142.

$$\begin{aligned}7265 &:= (Q(T(7)) + T(2) + T(Q(6))) \times 5 \\72650 &:= (Q(T(7)) + T(2) + T(Q(6))) \times 50 \\726500 &:= (Q(T(7)) + T(2) + T(Q(6))) \times 500 \\7265000 &:= (Q(T(7)) + T(2) + T(Q(6))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1143.

$$\begin{aligned}7275 &:= (T(F(7)) + T(T(2))) \times 75 \\72750 &:= (T(F(7)) + T(T(2))) \times 750 \\727500 &:= (T(F(7)) + T(T(2))) \times 7500 \\7275000 &:= (T(F(7)) + T(T(2))) \times 75000\end{aligned}$$

1144.

$$\begin{aligned}7280 &:= T(7 + T(T(2))) \times 80 \\72800 &:= T(7 + T(T(2))) \times 800 \\728000 &:= T(7 + T(T(2))) \times 8000 \\7280000 &:= T(7 + T(T(2))) \times 80000\end{aligned}$$

1145.

$$\begin{aligned}7280 &:= T(F(7)) \times F(2) \times 80 \\72800 &:= T(F(7)) \times F(2) \times 800 \\728000 &:= T(F(7)) \times F(2) \times 8000 \\7280000 &:= T(F(7)) \times F(2) \times 80000\end{aligned}$$

1146.

$$\begin{aligned}7285 &:= (Q(F(7) \times F(Q(2))) - Q(8)) \times 5 \\72850 &:= (Q(F(7) \times F(Q(2))) - Q(8)) \times 50 \\728500 &:= (Q(F(7) \times F(Q(2))) - Q(8)) \times 500 \\7285000 &:= (Q(F(7) \times F(Q(2))) - Q(8)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1147.

$$\begin{aligned}7285 &:= (-T(7) + T(T(T(2)))! - T(T(8))) \times 5 \\72850 &:= (-T(7) + T(T(T(2)))! - T(T(8))) \times 50 \\728500 &:= (-T(7) + T(T(T(2)))! - T(T(8))) \times 500 \\7285000 &:= (-T(7) + T(T(T(2)))! - T(T(8))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1148.

$$\begin{aligned}7287 &:= (Q(Q(Q(2)) + 7) + C(8)) \times 7 \\72870 &:= (Q(Q(Q(2)) + 7) + C(8)) \times 70 \\728700 &:= (Q(Q(Q(2)) + 7) + C(8)) \times 700 \\7287000 &:= (Q(Q(Q(2)) + 7) + C(8)) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

1149.

$$\begin{aligned}7287 &:= (T(T(7 + 2)) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 7 \\72870 &:= (T(T(7 + 2)) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 70 \\728700 &:= (T(T(7 + 2)) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 700 \\7287000 &:= (T(T(7 + 2)) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

1150.

$$\begin{aligned}7288 &:= (T(7 \times T(T(2))) + 8) \times 8 \\72880 &:= (T(7 \times T(T(2))) + 8) \times 80 \\728800 &:= (T(7 \times T(T(2))) + 8) \times 800 \\7288000 &:= (T(7 \times T(T(2))) + 8) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

1151.

$$\begin{aligned}7290 &:= Q(7 + 2) \times 90 \\72900 &:= Q(7 + 2) \times 900 \\729000 &:= Q(7 + 2) \times 9000 \\7290000 &:= Q(7 + 2) \times 90000\end{aligned}$$

1152.

$$\begin{aligned}7293 &:= (Q(Q(7)) + Q(2)! + (\sqrt{9})!) \times 3 \\72930 &:= (Q(Q(7)) + Q(2)! + (\sqrt{9})!) \times 30 \\729300 &:= (Q(Q(7)) + Q(2)! + (\sqrt{9})!) \times 300 \\7293000 &:= (Q(Q(7)) + Q(2)! + (\sqrt{9})!) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

1153.

$$\begin{aligned}7295 &:= (T(7) + T(F(T(T(2)))) + T(9)) \times 5 \\72950 &:= (T(7) + T(F(T(T(2)))) + T(9)) \times 50 \\729500 &:= (T(7) + T(F(T(T(2)))) + T(9)) \times 500 \\7295000 &:= (T(7) + T(F(T(T(2)))) + T(9)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1154.

$$\begin{aligned}7296 &:= (T(7^2) - 9) \times 6 \\72960 &:= (T(7^2) - 9) \times 60 \\729600 &:= (T(7^2) - 9) \times 600 \\7296000 &:= (T(7^2) - 9) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1155.

$$\begin{aligned}7299 &:= (T(F(7)) + (2 \times \sqrt{9})!) \times 9 \\72990 &:= (T(F(7)) + (2 \times \sqrt{9})!) \times 90 \\729900 &:= (T(F(7)) + (2 \times \sqrt{9})!) \times 900 \\7299000 &:= (T(F(7)) + (2 \times \sqrt{9})!) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

1156.

$$\begin{aligned}7312 &:= (T(T(F(7)) - T(3)) + 1) \times 2 \\73120 &:= (T(T(F(7)) - T(3)) + 1) \times 20 \\731200 &:= (T(T(F(7)) - T(3)) + 1) \times 200 \\7312000 &:= (T(T(F(7)) - T(3)) + 1) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1157.

$$\begin{aligned}7322 &:= (T(T(F(7)) - T(3)) + T(T(2))) \times 2 \\73220 &:= (T(T(F(7)) - T(3)) + T(T(2))) \times 20 \\732200 &:= (T(T(F(7)) - T(3)) + T(T(2))) \times 200 \\7322000 &:= (T(T(F(7)) - T(3)) + T(T(2))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1158.

$$\begin{aligned}7324 &:= (Q(Q(7)) + 3! - Q(Q(2)!)) \times 4 \\73240 &:= (Q(Q(7)) + 3! - Q(Q(2)!)) \times 40 \\732400 &:= (Q(Q(7)) + 3! - Q(Q(2)!)) \times 400 \\7324000 &:= (Q(Q(7)) + 3! - Q(Q(2)!)) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

1159.

$$\begin{aligned}7325 &:= (F(F(7)) + 3!! + C(C(2))) \times 5 \\73250 &:= (F(F(7)) + 3!! + C(C(2))) \times 50 \\732500 &:= (F(F(7)) + 3!! + C(C(2))) \times 500 \\7325000 &:= (F(F(7)) + 3!! + C(C(2))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1160.

$$\begin{aligned}7326 &:= (T(T(7)) \times 3 + T(2)) \times 6 \\73260 &:= (T(T(7)) \times 3 + T(2)) \times 60 \\732600 &:= (T(T(7)) \times 3 + T(2)) \times 600 \\7326000 &:= (T(T(7)) \times 3 + T(2)) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1161.

$$\begin{aligned} 7328 &:= (F(7) + T(2 \times T(T(3)))) \times 8 \\ 73280 &:= (F(7) + T(2 \times T(T(3)))) \times 80 \\ 732800 &:= (F(7) + T(2 \times T(T(3)))) \times 800 \\ 7328000 &:= (F(7) + T(2 \times T(T(3)))) \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

1162.

$$\begin{aligned} 7328 &:= (F(F(7)) - Q(F(3))) \times Q(2) \times 8 \\ 73280 &:= (F(F(7)) - Q(F(3))) \times Q(2) \times 80 \\ 732800 &:= (F(F(7)) - Q(F(3))) \times Q(2) \times 800 \\ 7328000 &:= (F(F(7)) - Q(F(3))) \times Q(2) \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

1163.

$$\begin{aligned} 7350 &:= 7 \times F(C(F(3))) \times 50 \\ 73500 &:= 7 \times F(C(F(3))) \times 500 \\ 735000 &:= 7 \times F(C(F(3))) \times 5000 \\ 7350000 &:= 7 \times F(C(F(3))) \times 50000 \end{aligned}$$

1164.

$$\begin{aligned} 7350 &:= 7 \times T(T(3)) \times 50 \\ 73500 &:= 7 \times T(T(3)) \times 500 \\ 735000 &:= 7 \times T(T(3)) \times 5000 \\ 7350000 &:= 7 \times T(T(3)) \times 50000 \end{aligned}$$

1165.

$$\begin{aligned} 7353 &:= (T(T(7)) \times T(3) + T(5)) \times 3 \\ 73530 &:= (T(T(7)) \times T(3) + T(5)) \times 30 \\ 735300 &:= (T(T(7)) \times T(3) + T(5)) \times 300 \\ 7353000 &:= (T(T(7)) \times T(3) + T(5)) \times 3000 \end{aligned}$$

1166.

$$\begin{aligned} 7365 &:= (Q(F(7)) + F(3!) + Q(Q(6))) \times 5 \\ 73650 &:= (Q(F(7)) + F(3!) + Q(Q(6))) \times 50 \\ 736500 &:= (Q(F(7)) + F(3!) + Q(Q(6))) \times 500 \\ 7365000 &:= (Q(F(7)) + F(3!) + Q(Q(6))) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1167.

$$\begin{aligned} 7384 &:= (T(T(7)) + T(3)! + (\sqrt{T(8)!}) \times 4 \\ 73840 &:= (T(T(7)) + T(3)! + (\sqrt{T(8)!}) \times 40 \\ 738400 &:= (T(T(7)) + T(3)! + (\sqrt{T(8)!}) \times 400 \\ 7384000 &:= (T(T(7)) + T(3)! + (\sqrt{T(8)!}) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

1168.

$$\begin{aligned} 7385 &:= (C(F(7)) - (C(3) - F(8))!) \times 5 \\ 73850 &:= (C(F(7)) - (C(3) - F(8))!) \times 50 \\ 738500 &:= (C(F(7)) - (C(3) - F(8))!) \times 500 \\ 7385000 &:= (C(F(7)) - (C(3) - F(8))!) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1169.

$$\begin{aligned} 7385 &:= (T(F(7)) + T(3)! + T(T(8))) \times 5 \\ 73850 &:= (T(F(7)) + T(3)! + T(T(8))) \times 50 \\ 738500 &:= (T(F(7)) + T(3)! + T(T(8))) \times 500 \\ 7385000 &:= (T(F(7)) + T(3)! + T(T(8))) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1170.

$$\begin{aligned} 7385 &:= (T(F(7)) + T(3) \times T(F(8))) \times 5 \\ 73850 &:= (T(F(7)) + T(3) \times T(F(8))) \times 50 \\ 738500 &:= (T(F(7)) + T(3) \times T(F(8))) \times 500 \\ 7385000 &:= (T(F(7)) + T(3) \times T(F(8))) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1171.

$$\begin{aligned}7386 &:= (T(7^{F(3)}) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 6 \\73860 &:= (T(7^{F(3)}) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 60 \\738600 &:= (T(7^{F(3)}) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 600 \\7386000 &:= (T(7^{F(3)}) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1172.

$$\begin{aligned}7386 &:= (T(T(7) + T(T(3))) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 6 \\73860 &:= (T(T(7) + T(T(3))) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 60 \\738600 &:= (T(T(7) + T(T(3))) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 600 \\7386000 &:= (T(T(7) + T(T(3))) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1173.

$$\begin{aligned}7395 &:= (C(F(7)) - 3!! + F(\sqrt{9})) \times 5 \\73950 &:= (C(F(7)) - 3!! + F(\sqrt{9})) \times 50 \\739500 &:= (C(F(7)) - 3!! + F(\sqrt{9})) \times 500 \\7395000 &:= (C(F(7)) - 3!! + F(\sqrt{9})) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1174.

$$\begin{aligned}7405 &:= (T(Q(7)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 5 \\74050 &:= (T(Q(7)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 50 \\740500 &:= (T(Q(7)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 500 \\7405000 &:= (T(Q(7)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1175.

$$\begin{aligned}7408 &:= (T(Q(7)) - T(4!) + 0!) \times 8 \\74080 &:= (T(Q(7)) - T(4!) + 0!) \times 80 \\740800 &:= (T(Q(7)) - T(4!) + 0!) \times 800 \\7408000 &:= (T(Q(7)) - T(4!) + 0!) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

1176.

$$\begin{aligned}7410 &:= T(T(7) + T(4)) \times 10 \\74100 &:= T(T(7) + T(4)) \times 100 \\741000 &:= T(T(7) + T(4)) \times 1000 \\7410000 &:= T(T(7) + T(4)) \times 10000\end{aligned}$$

1177.

$$\begin{aligned}7416 &:= (T(Q(7)) + T(4) + 1) \times 6 \\74160 &:= (T(Q(7)) + T(4) + 1) \times 60 \\741600 &:= (T(Q(7)) + T(4) + 1) \times 600 \\7416000 &:= (T(Q(7)) + T(4) + 1) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1178.

$$\begin{aligned}7425 &:= (F(F(7)) + C(4)) \times 25 \\74250 &:= (F(F(7)) + C(4)) \times 250 \\742500 &:= (F(F(7)) + C(4)) \times 2500 \\7425000 &:= (F(F(7)) + C(4)) \times 25000\end{aligned}$$

1179.

$$\begin{aligned}7425 &:= T((T(7) - T(4)) \times T(2)) \times 5 \\74250 &:= T((T(7) - T(4)) \times T(2)) \times 50 \\742500 &:= T((T(7) - T(4)) \times T(2)) \times 500 \\7425000 &:= T((T(7) - T(4)) \times T(2)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1180.

$$\begin{aligned}7435 &:= (-Q(7) + Q(Q(4)) \times 3!) \times 5 \\74350 &:= (-Q(7) + Q(Q(4)) \times 3!) \times 50 \\743500 &:= (-Q(7) + Q(Q(4)) \times 3!) \times 500 \\7435000 &:= (-Q(7) + Q(Q(4)) \times 3!) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1181.

$$\begin{aligned}7435 &:= (T(Q(7)) + Q(Q(4)) + T(3)) \times 5 \\74350 &:= (T(Q(7)) + Q(Q(4)) + T(3)) \times 50 \\743500 &:= (T(Q(7)) + Q(Q(4)) + T(3)) \times 500 \\7435000 &:= (T(Q(7)) + Q(Q(4)) + T(3)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1182.

$$\begin{aligned}7442 &:= Q(Q(7) - 4 + Q(4)) \times 2 \\74420 &:= Q(Q(7) - 4 + Q(4)) \times 20 \\744200 &:= Q(Q(7) - 4 + Q(4)) \times 200 \\7442000 &:= Q(Q(7) - 4 + Q(4)) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1183.

$$\begin{aligned}7443 &:= (T(7 \times T(4)) - 4) \times 3 \\74430 &:= (T(7 \times T(4)) - 4) \times 30 \\744300 &:= (T(7 \times T(4)) - 4) \times 300 \\7443000 &:= (T(7 \times T(4)) - 4) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

1184.

$$\begin{aligned}7444 &:= (F(F(7)) \times F(F(4)!) - F(4)) \times 4 \\74440 &:= (F(F(7)) \times F(F(4)!) - F(4)) \times 40 \\744400 &:= (F(F(7)) \times F(F(4)!) - F(4)) \times 400 \\7444000 &:= (F(F(7)) \times F(F(4)!) - F(4)) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

1185.

$$\begin{aligned}7446 &:= (C(7 + \sqrt{4}) + \sqrt{C(C(4))}) \times 6 \\74460 &:= (C(7 + \sqrt{4}) + \sqrt{C(C(4))}) \times 60 \\744600 &:= (C(7 + \sqrt{4}) + \sqrt{C(C(4))}) \times 600 \\7446000 &:= (C(7 + \sqrt{4}) + \sqrt{C(C(4))}) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1186.

$$\begin{aligned}7446 &:= (C(Q(7 - 4)) + \sqrt{C(C(4))}) \times 6 \\74460 &:= (C(Q(7 - 4)) + \sqrt{C(C(4))}) \times 60 \\744600 &:= (C(Q(7 - 4)) + \sqrt{C(C(4))}) \times 600 \\7446000 &:= (C(Q(7 - 4)) + \sqrt{C(C(4))}) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1187.

$$\begin{aligned}7448 &:= (F(F(7)) \times 4 - F(F(F(4)))) \times 8 \\74480 &:= (F(F(7)) \times 4 - F(F(F(4)))) \times 80 \\744800 &:= (F(F(7)) \times 4 - F(F(F(4)))) \times 800 \\7448000 &:= (F(F(7)) \times 4 - F(F(F(4)))) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

1188.

$$\begin{aligned}7448 &:= (F(F(7)) \times 4 - F(\sqrt{4})) \times 8 \\74480 &:= (F(F(7)) \times 4 - F(\sqrt{4})) \times 80 \\744800 &:= (F(F(7)) \times 4 - F(\sqrt{4})) \times 800 \\7448000 &:= (F(F(7)) \times 4 - F(\sqrt{4})) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

1189.

$$\begin{aligned}7450 &:= (Q(7) + Q(T(4))) \times 50 \\74500 &:= (Q(7) + Q(T(4))) \times 500 \\745000 &:= (Q(7) + Q(T(4))) \times 5000 \\7450000 &:= (Q(7) + Q(T(4))) \times 50000\end{aligned}$$

1190.

$$\begin{aligned}7455 &:= (Q(Q(7) - F(4)) - Q(Q(5))) \times 5 \\74550 &:= (Q(Q(7) - F(4)) - Q(Q(5))) \times 50 \\745500 &:= (Q(Q(7) - F(4)) - Q(Q(5))) \times 500 \\7455000 &:= (Q(Q(7) - F(4)) - Q(Q(5))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1191.

$$\begin{aligned}7465 &:= (Q(7) + Q(\sqrt{4} + Q(6))) \times 5 \\74650 &:= (Q(7) + Q(\sqrt{4} + Q(6))) \times 50 \\746500 &:= (Q(7) + Q(\sqrt{4} + Q(6))) \times 500 \\7465000 &:= (Q(7) + Q(\sqrt{4} + Q(6))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1192.

$$\begin{aligned}7474 &:= (T(F(7)) + T(4)) \times 74 \\74740 &:= (T(F(7)) + T(4)) \times 740 \\747400 &:= (T(F(7)) + T(4)) \times 7400 \\7474000 &:= (T(F(7)) + T(4)) \times 74000\end{aligned}$$

1193.

$$\begin{aligned}7476 &:= (Q(F(7)) + Q(F(4))) \times 7 \times 6 \\74760 &:= (Q(F(7)) + Q(F(4))) \times 7 \times 60 \\747600 &:= (Q(F(7)) + Q(F(4))) \times 7 \times 600 \\7476000 &:= (Q(F(7)) + Q(F(4))) \times 7 \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1194.

$$\begin{aligned}7476 &:= (Q(F(7)) + Q(F(4))) \times 7 \times 6 \\74760 &:= (Q(F(7)) + Q(F(4))) \times 7 \times 60 \\747600 &:= (Q(F(7)) + Q(F(4))) \times 7 \times 600 \\7476000 &:= (Q(F(7)) + Q(F(4))) \times 7 \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1195.

$$\begin{aligned}7476 &:= (T(T(7)) \times T(\sqrt{4}) + T(7)) \times 6 \\74760 &:= (T(T(7)) \times T(\sqrt{4}) + T(7)) \times 60 \\747600 &:= (T(T(7)) \times T(\sqrt{4}) + T(7)) \times 600 \\7476000 &:= (T(T(7)) \times T(\sqrt{4}) + T(7)) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1196.

$$\begin{aligned}7482 &:= (7! - T(\sqrt{4}) - Q(T(8))) \times 2 \\74820 &:= (7! - T(\sqrt{4}) - Q(T(8))) \times 20 \\748200 &:= (7! - T(\sqrt{4}) - Q(T(8))) \times 200 \\7482000 &:= (7! - T(\sqrt{4}) - Q(T(8))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1197.

$$\begin{aligned}7485 &:= (-7 + T(F(T(4))) - T(8)) \times 5 \\74850 &:= (-7 + T(F(T(4))) - T(8)) \times 50 \\748500 &:= (-7 + T(F(T(4))) - T(8)) \times 500 \\7485000 &:= (-7 + T(F(T(4))) - T(8)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1198.

$$\begin{aligned}7485 &:= (-7 + T(T(T(4))) - T(8)) \times 5 \\74850 &:= (-7 + T(T(T(4))) - T(8)) \times 50 \\748500 &:= (-7 + T(T(T(4))) - T(8)) \times 500 \\7485000 &:= (-7 + T(T(T(4))) - T(8)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1199.

$$\begin{aligned}7485 &:= (-7 - Q(4!) + T(Q(8))) \times 5 \\74850 &:= (-7 - Q(4!) + T(Q(8))) \times 50 \\748500 &:= (-7 - Q(4!) + T(Q(8))) \times 500 \\7485000 &:= (-7 - Q(4!) + T(Q(8))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1200.

$$\begin{aligned}7488 &:= F(7) \times F(F(4)) \times T(8) \times 8 \\74880 &:= F(7) \times F(F(4)) \times T(8) \times 80 \\748800 &:= F(7) \times F(F(4)) \times T(8) \times 800 \\7488000 &:= F(7) \times F(F(4)) \times T(8) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

1201.

$$\begin{aligned} 7492 &:= (C(7) + T(T(T(4)) + C(\sqrt{9}))) \times 2 \\ 74920 &:= (C(7) + T(T(T(4)) + C(\sqrt{9}))) \times 20 \\ 749200 &:= (C(7) + T(T(T(4)) + C(\sqrt{9}))) \times 200 \\ 7492000 &:= (C(7) + T(T(T(4)) + C(\sqrt{9}))) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1202.

$$\begin{aligned} 7495 &:= (7^{F(4)} + Q(F(9))) \times 5 \\ 74950 &:= (7^{F(4)} + Q(F(9))) \times 50 \\ 749500 &:= (7^{F(4)} + Q(F(9))) \times 500 \\ 7495000 &:= (7^{F(4)} + Q(F(9))) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1203.

$$\begin{aligned} 7497 &:= (C(7) + \sqrt{C(C(4)) + C((\sqrt{9})!)}) \times 7 \\ 74970 &:= (C(7) + \sqrt{C(C(4)) + C((\sqrt{9})!)}) \times 70 \\ 749700 &:= (C(7) + \sqrt{C(C(4)) + C((\sqrt{9})!)}) \times 700 \\ 7497000 &:= (C(7) + \sqrt{C(C(4)) + C((\sqrt{9})!)}) \times 7000 \end{aligned}$$

1204.

$$\begin{aligned} 7497 &:= (C(7) - F(\sqrt{4}) + C(9)) \times 7 \\ 74970 &:= (C(7) - F(\sqrt{4}) + C(9)) \times 70 \\ 749700 &:= (C(7) - F(\sqrt{4}) + C(9)) \times 700 \\ 7497000 &:= (C(7) - F(\sqrt{4}) + C(9)) \times 7000 \end{aligned}$$

1205.

$$\begin{aligned} 7506 &:= (T(Q(7)) + Q(5) + 0!) \times 6 \\ 75060 &:= (T(Q(7)) + Q(5) + 0!) \times 60 \\ 750600 &:= (T(Q(7)) + Q(5) + 0!) \times 600 \\ 7506000 &:= (T(Q(7)) + Q(5) + 0!) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

1206.

$$\begin{aligned} 7536 &:= (T(Q(7)) + Q(5) + T(3)) \times 6 \\ 75360 &:= (T(Q(7)) + Q(5) + T(3)) \times 60 \\ 753600 &:= (T(Q(7)) + Q(5) + T(3)) \times 600 \\ 7536000 &:= (T(Q(7)) + Q(5) + T(3)) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

1207.

$$\begin{aligned} 7563 &:= (Q(7 \times 5) + Q(Q(6))) \times 3 \\ 75630 &:= (Q(7 \times 5) + Q(Q(6))) \times 30 \\ 756300 &:= (Q(7 \times 5) + Q(Q(6))) \times 300 \\ 7563000 &:= (Q(7 \times 5) + Q(Q(6))) \times 3000 \end{aligned}$$

1208.

$$\begin{aligned} 7566 &:= (Q(7 \times 5) + Q(6)) \times 6 \\ 75660 &:= (Q(7 \times 5) + Q(6)) \times 60 \\ 756600 &:= (Q(7 \times 5) + Q(6)) \times 600 \\ 7566000 &:= (Q(7 \times 5) + Q(6)) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

1209.

$$\begin{aligned} 7567 &:= T(T(F(7)) - T(T(5) - 6)) \times 7 \\ 75670 &:= T(T(F(7)) - T(T(5) - 6)) \times 70 \\ 756700 &:= T(T(F(7)) - T(T(5) - 6)) \times 700 \\ 7567000 &:= T(T(F(7)) - T(T(5) - 6)) \times 7000 \end{aligned}$$

1210.

$$\begin{aligned} 7567 &:= T(T(T(7) - 5)/6) \times 7 \\ 75670 &:= T(T(T(7) - 5)/6) \times 70 \\ 756700 &:= T(T(T(7) - 5)/6) \times 700 \\ 7567000 &:= T(T(T(7) - 5)/6) \times 7000 \end{aligned}$$

1211.

$$\begin{aligned}7568 &:= T(7 + T(5) + T(6)) \times 8 \\75680 &:= T(7 + T(5) + T(6)) \times 80 \\756800 &:= T(7 + T(5) + T(6)) \times 800 \\7568000 &:= T(7 + T(5) + T(6)) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

1212.

$$\begin{aligned}7568 &:= T(F(7) + 5 \times 6) \times 8 \\75680 &:= T(F(7) + 5 \times 6) \times 80 \\756800 &:= T(F(7) + 5 \times 6) \times 800 \\7568000 &:= T(F(7) + 5 \times 6) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

1213.

$$\begin{aligned}7569 &:= Q(7 \times 5 - 6) \times 9 \\75690 &:= Q(7 \times 5 - 6) \times 90 \\756900 &:= Q(7 \times 5 - 6) \times 900 \\7569000 &:= Q(7 \times 5 - 6) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

1214.

$$\begin{aligned}7626 &:= (-Q(7) + Q(Q(6)) + Q(2!)) \times 6 \\76260 &:= (-Q(7) + Q(Q(6)) + Q(2!)) \times 60 \\762600 &:= (-Q(7) + Q(Q(6)) + Q(2!)) \times 600 \\7626000 &:= (-Q(7) + Q(Q(6)) + Q(2!)) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1215.

$$\begin{aligned}7635 &:= (F(F(7)) + Q(Q(6)) - F(3)) \times 5 \\76350 &:= (F(F(7)) + Q(Q(6)) - F(3)) \times 50 \\763500 &:= (F(F(7)) + Q(Q(6)) - F(3)) \times 500 \\7635000 &:= (F(F(7)) + Q(Q(6)) - F(3)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1216.

$$\begin{aligned}7637 &:= (-7 + 6! + T(C(3))) \times 7 \\76370 &:= (-7 + 6! + T(C(3))) \times 70 \\763700 &:= (-7 + 6! + T(C(3))) \times 700 \\7637000 &:= (-7 + 6! + T(C(3))) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

1217.

$$\begin{aligned}7645 &:= (-7 + 6 \times Q(Q(4))) \times 5 \\76450 &:= (-7 + 6 \times Q(Q(4))) \times 50 \\764500 &:= (-7 + 6 \times Q(Q(4))) \times 500 \\7645000 &:= (-7 + 6 \times Q(Q(4))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1218.

$$\begin{aligned}7645 &:= (-C(7) + Q(Q(6)) + Q(4!)) \times 5 \\76450 &:= (-C(7) + Q(Q(6)) + Q(4!)) \times 50 \\764500 &:= (-C(7) + Q(Q(6)) + Q(4!)) \times 500 \\7645000 &:= (-C(7) + Q(Q(6)) + Q(4!)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1219.

$$\begin{aligned}7645 &:= (F(F(7)) + 6^4) \times 5 \\76450 &:= (F(F(7)) + 6^4) \times 50 \\764500 &:= (F(F(7)) + 6^4) \times 500 \\7645000 &:= (F(F(7)) + 6^4) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1220.

$$\begin{aligned}7648 &:= (Q(T(7)) + Q(6) + T(Q(4))) \times 8 \\76480 &:= (Q(T(7)) + Q(6) + T(Q(4))) \times 80 \\764800 &:= (Q(T(7)) + Q(6) + T(Q(4))) \times 800 \\7648000 &:= (Q(T(7)) + Q(6) + T(Q(4))) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

1221.

$$\begin{aligned}7652 &:= (T(Q(7)) + Q(Q(6) + T(5))) \times 2 \\76520 &:= (T(Q(7)) + Q(Q(6) + T(5))) \times 20 \\765200 &:= (T(Q(7)) + Q(Q(6) + T(5))) \times 200 \\7652000 &:= (T(Q(7)) + Q(Q(6) + T(5))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1222.

$$\begin{aligned}7653 &:= (Q(Q(7)) + 6 \times Q(5)) \times 3 \\76530 &:= (Q(Q(7)) + 6 \times Q(5)) \times 30 \\765300 &:= (Q(Q(7)) + 6 \times Q(5)) \times 300 \\7653000 &:= (Q(Q(7)) + 6 \times Q(5)) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

1223.

$$\begin{aligned}7653 &:= (T(T(7)) + T(65)) \times 3 \\76530 &:= (T(T(7)) + T(65)) \times 30 \\765300 &:= (T(T(7)) + T(65)) \times 300 \\7653000 &:= (T(T(7)) + T(65)) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

1224.

$$\begin{aligned}7656 &:= (T(Q(7)) + Q(6) + T(5)) \times 6 \\76560 &:= (T(Q(7)) + Q(6) + T(5)) \times 60 \\765600 &:= (T(Q(7)) + Q(6) + T(5)) \times 600 \\7656000 &:= (T(Q(7)) + Q(6) + T(5)) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1225.

$$\begin{aligned}7656 &:= (T(T(7) + F(6)) + F(T(5))) \times 6 \\76560 &:= (T(T(7) + F(6)) + F(T(5))) \times 60 \\765600 &:= (T(T(7) + F(6)) + F(T(5))) \times 600 \\7656000 &:= (T(T(7) + F(6)) + F(T(5))) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1226.

$$\begin{aligned}7659 &:= (F(F(7)) + F(6) + F(T(5))) \times 9 \\76590 &:= (F(F(7)) + F(6) + F(T(5))) \times 90 \\765900 &:= (F(F(7)) + F(6) + F(T(5))) \times 900 \\7659000 &:= (F(F(7)) + F(6) + F(T(5))) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

1227.

$$\begin{aligned}7665 &:= (7 \times C(6) + F(F(6))) \times 5 \\76650 &:= (7 \times C(6) + F(F(6))) \times 50 \\766500 &:= (7 \times C(6) + F(F(6))) \times 500 \\7665000 &:= (7 \times C(6) + F(F(6))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1228.

$$\begin{aligned}7686 &:= (Q(7) + 6! + C(8)) \times 6 \\76860 &:= (Q(7) + 6! + C(8)) \times 60 \\768600 &:= (Q(7) + 6! + C(8)) \times 600 \\7686000 &:= (Q(7) + 6! + C(8)) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1229.

$$\begin{aligned}7688 &:= (-C(7) + Q(Q(6)) + 8) \times 8 \\76880 &:= (-C(7) + Q(Q(6)) + 8) \times 80 \\768800 &:= (-C(7) + Q(Q(6)) + 8) \times 800 \\7688000 &:= (-C(7) + Q(Q(6)) + 8) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

1230.

$$\begin{aligned}7688 &:= (F(F(7)) + 6! + 8) \times 8 \\76880 &:= (F(F(7)) + 6! + 8) \times 80 \\768800 &:= (F(F(7)) + 6! + 8) \times 800 \\7688000 &:= (F(F(7)) + 6! + 8) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

1231.

$$\begin{aligned}7688 &:= Q(7 + Q(-6 + 8!)) \times 8 \\76880 &:= Q(7 + Q(-6 + 8!)) \times 80 \\768800 &:= Q(7 + Q(-6 + 8!)) \times 800 \\7688000 &:= Q(7 + Q(-6 + 8!)) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

1232.

$$\begin{aligned}7695 &:= (F(7) + 6) \times Q(9) \times 5 \\76950 &:= (F(7) + 6) \times Q(9) \times 50 \\769500 &:= (F(7) + 6) \times Q(9) \times 500 \\7695000 &:= (F(7) + 6) \times Q(9) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1233.

$$\begin{aligned}7705 &:= (T(F(T(T(7)/7))) + 0!) \times 5 \\77050 &:= (T(F(T(T(7)/7))) + 0!) \times 50 \\770500 &:= (T(F(T(T(7)/7))) + 0!) \times 500 \\7705000 &:= (T(F(T(T(7)/7))) + 0!) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1234.

$$\begin{aligned}7705 &:= (T(T(T(T(7)/7))) + 0!) \times 5 \\77050 &:= (T(T(T(T(7)/7))) + 0!) \times 50 \\770500 &:= (T(T(T(T(7)/7))) + 0!) \times 500 \\7705000 &:= (T(T(T(T(7)/7))) + 0!) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1235.

$$\begin{aligned}7713 &:= (Q(F(7)) + Q(Q(7)) + 1) \times 3 \\77130 &:= (Q(F(7)) + Q(Q(7)) + 1) \times 30 \\771300 &:= (Q(F(7)) + Q(Q(7)) + 1) \times 300 \\7713000 &:= (Q(F(7)) + Q(Q(7)) + 1) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

1236.

$$\begin{aligned}7735 &:= (7 + T(T(7 + 3))) \times 5 \\77350 &:= (7 + T(T(7 + 3))) \times 50 \\773500 &:= (7 + T(T(7 + 3))) \times 500 \\7735000 &:= (7 + T(T(7 + 3))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1237.

$$\begin{aligned}7745 &:= (T(Q(7)) + Q(T(7) - T(4))) \times 5 \\77450 &:= (T(Q(7)) + Q(T(7) - T(4))) \times 50 \\774500 &:= (T(Q(7)) + Q(T(7) - T(4))) \times 500 \\7745000 &:= (T(Q(7)) + Q(T(7) - T(4))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1238.

$$\begin{aligned}7746 &:= (T(Q(7)) + T(7 + 4)) \times 6 \\77460 &:= (T(Q(7)) + T(7 + 4)) \times 60 \\774600 &:= (T(Q(7)) + T(7 + 4)) \times 600 \\7746000 &:= (T(Q(7)) + T(7 + 4)) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1239.

$$\begin{aligned}7749 &:= T(-7 - 7 + T(T(4))) \times 9 \\77490 &:= T(-7 - 7 + T(T(4))) \times 90 \\774900 &:= T(-7 - 7 + T(T(4))) \times 900 \\7749000 &:= T(-7 - 7 + T(T(4))) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

1240.

$$\begin{aligned}7749 &:= T(F(7) + 7 \times 4) \times 9 \\77490 &:= T(F(7) + 7 \times 4) \times 90 \\774900 &:= T(F(7) + 7 \times 4) \times 900 \\7749000 &:= T(F(7) + 7 \times 4) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

1241.

$$\begin{aligned} 7765 &:= (Q(T(7)) + Q(7) + 6!) \times 5 \\ 77650 &:= (Q(T(7)) + Q(7) + 6!) \times 50 \\ 776500 &:= (Q(T(7)) + Q(7) + 6!) \times 500 \\ 7765000 &:= (Q(T(7)) + Q(7) + 6!) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1242.

$$\begin{aligned} 7772 &:= (T(T(F(7))) - T((T(7)/7!)) \times 2 \\ 77720 &:= (T(T(F(7))) - T((T(7)/7!)) \times 20 \\ 777200 &:= (T(T(F(7))) - T((T(7)/7!)) \times 200 \\ 7772000 &:= (T(T(F(7))) - T((T(7)/7!)) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1243.

$$\begin{aligned} 7803 &:= Q(-F(7) + Q(8)) \times 03 \\ 78030 &:= Q(-F(7) + Q(8)) \times 030 \\ 780300 &:= Q(-F(7) + Q(8)) \times 0300 \\ 7803000 &:= Q(-F(7) + Q(8)) \times 03000 \end{aligned}$$

1244.

$$\begin{aligned} 7832 &:= T(Q(7) + T(8) + 3) \times 2 \\ 78320 &:= T(Q(7) + T(8) + 3) \times 20 \\ 783200 &:= T(Q(7) + T(8) + 3) \times 200 \\ 7832000 &:= T(Q(7) + T(8) + 3) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1245.

$$\begin{aligned} 7832 &:= T(T(7 + \sqrt{T(8)}) - 3) \times 2 \\ 78320 &:= T(T(7 + \sqrt{T(8)}) - 3) \times 20 \\ 783200 &:= T(T(7 + \sqrt{T(8)}) - 3) \times 200 \\ 7832000 &:= T(T(7 + \sqrt{T(8)}) - 3) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1246.

$$\begin{aligned} 7836 &:= (-F(7) + T(T(8))) \times F(3) \times 6 \\ 78360 &:= (-F(7) + T(T(8))) \times F(3) \times 60 \\ 783600 &:= (-F(7) + T(T(8))) \times F(3) \times 600 \\ 7836000 &:= (-F(7) + T(T(8))) \times F(3) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

1247.

$$\begin{aligned} 7836 &:= (T(T(7)) + Q(T(8) - T(3))) \times 6 \\ 78360 &:= (T(T(7)) + Q(T(8) - T(3))) \times 60 \\ 783600 &:= (T(T(7)) + Q(T(8) - T(3))) \times 600 \\ 7836000 &:= (T(T(7)) + Q(T(8) - T(3))) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

1248.

$$\begin{aligned} 7839 &:= (T(T(7)) + T(T(8) - T(3))) \times 9 \\ 78390 &:= (T(T(7)) + T(T(8) - T(3))) \times 90 \\ 783900 &:= (T(T(7)) + T(T(8) - T(3))) \times 900 \\ 7839000 &:= (T(T(7)) + T(T(8) - T(3))) \times 9000 \end{aligned}$$

1249.

$$\begin{aligned} 7844 &:= (-C(7) + Q(Q(8) - Q(4))) \times 4 \\ 78440 &:= (-C(7) + Q(Q(8) - Q(4))) \times 40 \\ 784400 &:= (-C(7) + Q(Q(8) - Q(4))) \times 400 \\ 7844000 &:= (-C(7) + Q(Q(8) - Q(4))) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

1250.

$$\begin{aligned} 7844 &:= (F(F(7)) + C(8 + 4)) \times 4 \\ 78440 &:= (F(F(7)) + C(8 + 4)) \times 40 \\ 784400 &:= (F(F(7)) + C(8 + 4)) \times 400 \\ 7844000 &:= (F(F(7)) + C(8 + 4)) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

1251.

$$7844 := (Q(Q(7)) - Q(F(8)) + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 4$$

$$78440 := (Q(Q(7)) - Q(F(8)) + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 40$$

$$784400 := (Q(Q(7)) - Q(F(8)) + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 400$$

$$7844000 := (Q(Q(7)) - Q(F(8)) + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 4000$$

1252.

$$7845 := (-7 + T(8) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5$$

$$78450 := (-7 + T(8) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 50$$

$$784500 := (-7 + T(8) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 500$$

$$7845000 := (-7 + T(8) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5000$$

1253.

$$7845 := (-T(7) + F(F(8) - 4)) \times 5$$

$$78450 := (-T(7) + F(F(8) - 4)) \times 50$$

$$784500 := (-T(7) + F(F(8) - 4)) \times 500$$

$$7845000 := (-T(7) + F(F(8) - 4)) \times 5000$$

1254.

$$7847 := (-7 + T(-8 + T(T(4)))) \times 7$$

$$78470 := (-7 + T(-8 + T(T(4)))) \times 70$$

$$784700 := (-7 + T(-8 + T(T(4)))) \times 700$$

$$7847000 := (-7 + T(-8 + T(T(4)))) \times 7000$$

1255.

$$7855 := (T(7 \times 8) - Q(5)) \times 5$$

$$78550 := (T(7 \times 8) - Q(5)) \times 50$$

$$785500 := (T(7 \times 8) - Q(5)) \times 500$$

$$7855000 := (T(7 \times 8) - Q(5)) \times 5000$$

1256.

$$7863 := (-7 + T(T(8) + Q(6))) \times 3$$

$$78630 := (-7 + T(T(8) + Q(6))) \times 30$$

$$786300 := (-7 + T(T(8) + Q(6))) \times 300$$

$$7863000 := (-7 + T(T(8) + Q(6))) \times 3000$$

1257.

$$7866 := (7 + 8 + Q(Q(6))) \times 6$$

$$78660 := (7 + 8 + Q(Q(6))) \times 60$$

$$786600 := (7 + 8 + Q(Q(6))) \times 600$$

$$7866000 := (7 + 8 + Q(Q(6))) \times 6000$$

1258.

$$7866 := (T(Q(7)) + 86) \times 6$$

$$78660 := (T(Q(7)) + 86) \times 60$$

$$786600 := (T(Q(7)) + 86) \times 600$$

$$7866000 := (T(Q(7)) + 86) \times 6000$$

1259.

$$7885 := (-C(7) + 8!/T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 5$$

$$78850 := (-C(7) + 8!/T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 50$$

$$788500 := (-C(7) + 8!/T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 500$$

$$7885000 := (-C(7) + 8!/T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 5000$$

1260.

$$7885 := (F(F(7)) + Q(8) \times F(8)) \times 5$$

$$78850 := (F(F(7)) + Q(8) \times F(8)) \times 50$$

$$788500 := (F(F(7)) + Q(8) \times F(8)) \times 500$$

$$7885000 := (F(F(7)) + Q(8) \times F(8)) \times 5000$$

1261.

$$\begin{aligned}7893 &:= (T(7 \times 8) + T(T(9))) \times 3 \\78930 &:= (T(7 \times 8) + T(T(9))) \times 30 \\789300 &:= (T(7 \times 8) + T(T(9))) \times 300 \\7893000 &:= (T(7 \times 8) + T(T(9))) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

1262.

$$\begin{aligned}7896 &:= (T(F(7)) \times F(8) - T(F(9))) \times 6 \\78960 &:= (T(F(7)) \times F(8) - T(F(9))) \times 60 \\789600 &:= (T(F(7)) \times F(8) - T(F(9))) \times 600 \\7896000 &:= (T(F(7)) \times F(8) - T(F(9))) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1263.

$$\begin{aligned}7902 &:= (7! - Q(F(9) - 0!)) \times 2 \\79020 &:= (7! - Q(F(9) - 0!)) \times 20 \\790200 &:= (7! - Q(F(9) - 0!)) \times 200 \\7902000 &:= (7! - Q(F(9) - 0!)) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1264.

$$\begin{aligned}7922 &:= (Q(7 \times 9) - C(2)) \times 2 \\79220 &:= (Q(7 \times 9) - C(2)) \times 20 \\792200 &:= (Q(7 \times 9) - C(2)) \times 200 \\7922000 &:= (Q(7 \times 9) - C(2)) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1265.

$$\begin{aligned}7924 &:= (-T(7) + Q(T(9)) - Q(Q(2))) \times 4 \\79240 &:= (-T(7) + Q(T(9)) - Q(Q(2))) \times 40 \\792400 &:= (-T(7) + Q(T(9)) - Q(Q(2))) \times 400 \\7924000 &:= (-T(7) + Q(T(9)) - Q(Q(2))) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

1266.

$$\begin{aligned}7932 &:= (Q(7 \times 9) - 3) \times 2 \\79320 &:= (Q(7 \times 9) - 3) \times 20 \\793200 &:= (Q(7 \times 9) - 3) \times 200 \\7932000 &:= (Q(7 \times 9) - 3) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1267.

$$\begin{aligned}7942 &:= (Q(7 \times 9) + \sqrt{4}) \times 2 \\79420 &:= (Q(7 \times 9) + \sqrt{4}) \times 20 \\794200 &:= (Q(7 \times 9) + \sqrt{4}) \times 200 \\7942000 &:= (Q(7 \times 9) + \sqrt{4}) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1268.

$$\begin{aligned}7945 &:= (T(7) + T(T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5 \\79450 &:= (T(7) + T(T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 50 \\794500 &:= (T(7) + T(T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 500 \\7945000 &:= (T(7) + T(T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1269.

$$\begin{aligned}7952 &:= (C(7 + 9) - 5!) \times 2 \\79520 &:= (C(7 + 9) - 5!) \times 20 \\795200 &:= (C(7 + 9) - 5!) \times 200 \\7952000 &:= (C(7 + 9) - 5!) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1270.

$$\begin{aligned}7955 &:= (Q(Q(7)) - T(T(9)) + Q(T(5))) \times 5 \\79550 &:= (Q(Q(7)) - T(T(9)) + Q(T(5))) \times 50 \\795500 &:= (Q(Q(7)) - T(T(9)) + Q(T(5))) \times 500 \\7955000 &:= (Q(Q(7)) - T(T(9)) + Q(T(5))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1271.

$$\begin{aligned}7955 &:= (T(F(7) + T(9)) - 5!) \times 5 \\79550 &:= (T(F(7) + T(9)) - 5!) \times 50 \\795500 &:= (T(F(7) + T(9)) - 5!) \times 500 \\7955000 &:= (T(F(7) + T(9)) - 5!) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1272.

$$\begin{aligned}7955 &:= (T(F(7) + T(9)) - T(T(5))) \times 5 \\79550 &:= (T(F(7) + T(9)) - T(T(5))) \times 50 \\795500 &:= (T(F(7) + T(9)) - T(T(5))) \times 500 \\7955000 &:= (T(F(7) + T(9)) - T(T(5))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1273.

$$\begin{aligned}7985 &:= F(-7 + \sqrt{9} + F(8)) \times 5 \\79850 &:= F(-7 + \sqrt{9} + F(8)) \times 50 \\798500 &:= F(-7 + \sqrt{9} + F(8)) \times 500 \\7985000 &:= F(-7 + \sqrt{9} + F(8)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1274.

$$\begin{aligned}7985 &:= F(-F(7) + 9 + F(8)) \times 5 \\79850 &:= F(-F(7) + 9 + F(8)) \times 50 \\798500 &:= F(-F(7) + 9 + F(8)) \times 500 \\7985000 &:= F(-F(7) + 9 + F(8)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1275.

$$\begin{aligned}7985 &:= F(T(7 + 9)/8) \times 5 \\79850 &:= F(T(7 + 9)/8) \times 50 \\798500 &:= F(T(7 + 9)/8) \times 500 \\7985000 &:= F(T(7 + 9)/8) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1276.

$$\begin{aligned}7986 &:= (-T(7) + Q(T(9)) - T(T(8))) \times 6 \\79860 &:= (-T(7) + Q(T(9)) - T(T(8))) \times 60 \\798600 &:= (-T(7) + Q(T(9)) - T(T(8))) \times 600 \\7986000 &:= (-T(7) + Q(T(9)) - T(T(8))) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1277.

$$\begin{aligned}7986 &:= C((7 + Q(9))/8) \times 6 \\79860 &:= C((7 + Q(9))/8) \times 60 \\798600 &:= C((7 + Q(9))/8) \times 600 \\7986000 &:= C((7 + Q(9))/8) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1278.

$$\begin{aligned}7986 &:= C(T(7) - (9 + 8)) \times 6 \\79860 &:= C(T(7) - (9 + 8)) \times 60 \\798600 &:= C(T(7) - (9 + 8)) \times 600 \\7986000 &:= C(T(7) - (9 + 8)) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1279.

$$\begin{aligned}7992 &:= (7! - 9 - T(T(9))) \times 2 \\79920 &:= (7! - 9 - T(T(9))) \times 20 \\799200 &:= (7! - 9 - T(T(9))) \times 200 \\7992000 &:= (7! - 9 - T(T(9))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1280.

$$\begin{aligned}7992 &:= (7! - T(T(9)) - 9) \times 2 \\79920 &:= (7! - T(T(9)) - 9) \times 20 \\799200 &:= (7! - T(T(9)) - 9) \times 200 \\7992000 &:= (7! - T(T(9)) - 9) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1281.

$$\begin{aligned} 7995 &:= (7!/\sqrt{9} - Q(9)) \times 5 \\ 79950 &:= (7!/\sqrt{9} - Q(9)) \times 50 \\ 799500 &:= (7!/\sqrt{9} - Q(9)) \times 500 \\ 7995000 &:= (7!/\sqrt{9} - Q(9)) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1282.

$$\begin{aligned} 8032 &:= (Q(Q(8)) + 0! - Q(Q(3))) \times 2 \\ 80320 &:= (Q(Q(8)) + 0! - Q(Q(3))) \times 20 \\ 803200 &:= (Q(Q(8)) + 0! - Q(Q(3))) \times 200 \\ 8032000 &:= (Q(Q(8)) + 0! - Q(Q(3))) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1283.

$$\begin{aligned} 8048 &:= (\sqrt{T(8)} + C(T(4))) \times 8 \\ 80480 &:= (\sqrt{T(8)} + C(T(4))) \times 80 \\ 804800 &:= (\sqrt{T(8)} + C(T(4))) \times 800 \\ 8048000 &:= (\sqrt{T(8)} + C(T(4))) \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

1284.

$$\begin{aligned} 8052 &:= (F(8) + T(F(\sqrt{0! + 5!}))) \times 2 \\ 80520 &:= (F(8) + T(F(\sqrt{0! + 5!}))) \times 20 \\ 805200 &:= (F(8) + T(F(\sqrt{0! + 5!}))) \times 200 \\ 8052000 &:= (F(8) + T(F(\sqrt{0! + 5!}))) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1285.

$$\begin{aligned} 8076 &:= (Q(T(8)) + 0! + Q(7)) \times 6 \\ 80760 &:= (Q(T(8)) + 0! + Q(7)) \times 60 \\ 807600 &:= (Q(T(8)) + 0! + Q(7)) \times 600 \\ 8076000 &:= (Q(T(8)) + 0! + Q(7)) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

1286.

$$\begin{aligned} 8102 &:= (Q(Q(8)) - T(Q(T(1 + 0!)))) \times 2 \\ 81020 &:= (Q(Q(8)) - T(Q(T(1 + 0!)))) \times 20 \\ 810200 &:= (Q(Q(8)) - T(Q(T(1 + 0!)))) \times 200 \\ 8102000 &:= (Q(Q(8)) - T(Q(T(1 + 0!)))) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1287.

$$\begin{aligned} 8103 &:= T(Q(8) + Q(T(1 + 0!))) \times 3 \\ 81030 &:= T(Q(8) + Q(T(1 + 0!))) \times 30 \\ 810300 &:= T(Q(8) + Q(T(1 + 0!))) \times 300 \\ 8103000 &:= T(Q(8) + Q(T(1 + 0!))) \times 3000 \end{aligned}$$

1288.

$$\begin{aligned} 8104 &:= (Q(T(8 + 1)) + 0!) \times 4 \\ 81040 &:= (Q(T(8 + 1)) + 0!) \times 40 \\ 810400 &:= (Q(T(8 + 1)) + 0!) \times 400 \\ 8104000 &:= (Q(T(8 + 1)) + 0!) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

1289.

$$\begin{aligned} 8106 &:= (Q(T(8)) + T(10)) \times 6 \\ 81060 &:= (Q(T(8)) + T(10)) \times 60 \\ 810600 &:= (Q(T(8)) + T(10)) \times 600 \\ 8106000 &:= (Q(T(8)) + T(10)) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

1290.

$$\begin{aligned} 8122 &:= (Q(Q(8)) - 1 - F(Q(F(Q(2)))) \times 2 \\ 81220 &:= (Q(Q(8)) - 1 - F(Q(F(Q(2)))) \times 20 \\ 812200 &:= (Q(Q(8)) - 1 - F(Q(F(Q(2)))) \times 200 \\ 8122000 &:= (Q(Q(8)) - 1 - F(Q(F(Q(2)))) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1291.

$$8124 := (Q(T(8+1)) + T(T(2))) \times 4$$

$$81240 := (Q(T(8+1)) + T(T(2))) \times 40$$

$$812400 := (Q(T(8+1)) + T(T(2))) \times 400$$

$$8124000 := (Q(T(8+1)) + T(T(2))) \times 4000$$

1292.

$$8142 := (Q(Q(8)) - Q(1+4)) \times 2$$

$$81420 := (Q(Q(8)) - Q(1+4)) \times 20$$

$$814200 := (Q(Q(8)) - Q(1+4)) \times 200$$

$$8142000 := (Q(Q(8)) - Q(1+4)) \times 2000$$

1293.

$$8162 := (Q(Q(8)) - T(-1+6)) \times 2$$

$$81620 := (Q(Q(8)) - T(-1+6)) \times 20$$

$$816200 := (Q(Q(8)) - T(-1+6)) \times 200$$

$$8162000 := (Q(Q(8)) - T(-1+6)) \times 2000$$

1294.

$$8166 := (-8 + Q(1 + Q(6))) \times 6$$

$$81660 := (-8 + Q(1 + Q(6))) \times 60$$

$$816600 := (-8 + Q(1 + Q(6))) \times 600$$

$$8166000 := (-8 + Q(1 + Q(6))) \times 6000$$

1295.

$$8168 := (T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + C(T(\sqrt{16}))) \times 8$$

$$81680 := (T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + C(T(\sqrt{16}))) \times 80$$

$$816800 := (T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + C(T(\sqrt{16}))) \times 800$$

$$8168000 := (T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + C(T(\sqrt{16}))) \times 8000$$

1296.

$$8190 := T(F(8-1)) \times 90$$

$$81900 := T(F(8-1)) \times 900$$

$$819000 := T(F(8-1)) \times 9000$$

$$8190000 := T(F(8-1)) \times 90000$$

1297.

$$8192 := Q(8 \times (-1+9)) \times 2$$

$$81920 := Q(8 \times (-1+9)) \times 20$$

$$819200 := Q(8 \times (-1+9)) \times 200$$

$$8192000 := Q(8 \times (-1+9)) \times 2000$$

1298.

$$8192 := Q(Q(8)) \times 1^9 \times 2$$

$$81920 := Q(Q(8)) \times 1^9 \times 20$$

$$819200 := Q(Q(8)) \times 1^9 \times 200$$

$$8192000 := Q(Q(8)) \times 1^9 \times 2000$$

1299.

$$8192 := Q(Q(8)) \times 1^9 \times 2$$

$$81920 := Q(Q(8)) \times 1^9 \times 20$$

$$819200 := Q(Q(8)) \times 1^9 \times 200$$

$$8192000 := Q(Q(8)) \times 1^9 \times 2000$$

1300.

$$8195 := (C(8-1) + Q(Q((\sqrt{9}!))) \times 5$$

$$81950 := (C(8-1) + Q(Q((\sqrt{9}!))) \times 50$$

$$819500 := (C(8-1) + Q(Q((\sqrt{9}!))) \times 500$$

$$8195000 := (C(8-1) + Q(Q((\sqrt{9}!))) \times 5000$$

1301.

$$8196 := (Q(Q(8-1)) - T(T(9))) \times 6$$

$$81960 := (Q(Q(8-1)) - T(T(9))) \times 60$$

$$819600 := (Q(Q(8-1)) - T(T(9))) \times 600$$

$$8196000 := (Q(Q(8-1)) - T(T(9))) \times 6000$$

1302.

$$8202 := (Q(Q(8)) + Q(2) + 0!) \times 2$$

$$82020 := (Q(Q(8)) + Q(2) + 0!) \times 20$$

$$820200 := (Q(Q(8)) + Q(2) + 0!) \times 200$$

$$8202000 := (Q(Q(8)) + Q(2) + 0!) \times 2000$$

1303.

$$8212 := (Q(Q(8)) + T(Q(2))) \times 2$$

$$82120 := (Q(Q(8)) + T(Q(2))) \times 20$$

$$821200 := (Q(Q(8)) + T(Q(2))) \times 200$$

$$8212000 := (Q(Q(8)) + T(Q(2))) \times 2000$$

1304.

$$8222 := (Q(Q(8)) + T(2 + T(2))) \times 2$$

$$82220 := (Q(Q(8)) + T(2 + T(2))) \times 20$$

$$822200 := (Q(Q(8)) + T(2 + T(2))) \times 200$$

$$8222000 := (Q(Q(8)) + T(2 + T(2))) \times 2000$$

1305.

$$8223 := (C(\sqrt{T(8)} + C(2)) - T(2)) \times 3$$

$$82230 := (C(\sqrt{T(8)} + C(2)) - T(2)) \times 30$$

$$822300 := (C(\sqrt{T(8)} + C(2)) - T(2)) \times 300$$

$$8223000 := (C(\sqrt{T(8)} + C(2)) - T(2)) \times 3000$$

1306.

$$8235 := (C(8 + Q(2)) - Q(Q(3))) \times 5$$

$$82350 := (C(8 + Q(2)) - Q(Q(3))) \times 50$$

$$823500 := (C(8 + Q(2)) - Q(Q(3))) \times 500$$

$$8235000 := (C(8 + Q(2)) - Q(Q(3))) \times 5000$$

1307.

$$8244 := (T(Q(8)) - T(2) - Q(4)) \times 4$$

$$82440 := (T(Q(8)) - T(2) - Q(4)) \times 40$$

$$824400 := (T(Q(8)) - T(2) - Q(4)) \times 400$$

$$8244000 := (T(Q(8)) - T(2) - Q(4)) \times 4000$$

1308.

$$8245 := (T(T(8) + T(T(T(2)))) - 4) \times 5$$

$$82450 := (T(T(8) + T(T(T(2)))) - 4) \times 50$$

$$824500 := (T(T(8) + T(T(T(2)))) - 4) \times 500$$

$$8245000 := (T(T(8) + T(T(T(2)))) - 4) \times 5000$$

1309.

$$8248 := (C(8 + T(2)) - T(4!)) \times 8$$

$$82480 := (C(8 + T(2)) - T(4!)) \times 80$$

$$824800 := (C(8 + T(2)) - T(4!)) \times 800$$

$$8248000 := (C(8 + T(2)) - T(4!)) \times 8000$$

1310.

$$8248 := (T(T(8 + F(2))) - 4) \times 8$$

$$82480 := (T(T(8 + F(2))) - 4) \times 80$$

$$824800 := (T(T(8 + F(2))) - 4) \times 800$$

$$8248000 := (T(T(8 + F(2))) - 4) \times 8000$$

1311.

$$8248 := (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)} + T(2))) - 4) \times 8$$

$$82480 := (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)} + T(2))) - 4) \times 80$$

$$824800 := (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)} + T(2))) - 4) \times 800$$

$$8248000 := (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)} + T(2))) - 4) \times 8000$$

1312.

$$8262 := (Q(Q(8)) - F(2) + Q(6)) \times 2$$

$$82620 := (Q(Q(8)) - F(2) + Q(6)) \times 20$$

$$826200 := (Q(Q(8)) - F(2) + Q(6)) \times 200$$

$$8262000 := (Q(Q(8)) - F(2) + Q(6)) \times 2000$$

1313.

$$8262 := (T(F(8)) \times T(T(T(2))) - 6!) \times 2$$

$$82620 := (T(F(8)) \times T(T(T(2))) - 6!) \times 20$$

$$826200 := (T(F(8)) \times T(T(T(2))) - 6!) \times 200$$

$$8262000 := (T(F(8)) \times T(T(T(2))) - 6!) \times 2000$$

1314.

$$8265 := T(T(8) + F(2 + 6)) \times 5$$

$$82650 := T(T(8) + F(2 + 6)) \times 50$$

$$826500 := T(T(8) + F(2 + 6)) \times 500$$

$$8265000 := T(T(8) + F(2 + 6)) \times 5000$$

1315.

$$8265 := T(T(8 - 2) + Q(6)) \times 5$$

$$82650 := T(T(8 - 2) + Q(6)) \times 50$$

$$826500 := T(T(8 - 2) + Q(6)) \times 500$$

$$8265000 := T(T(8 - 2) + Q(6)) \times 5000$$

1316.

$$8282 := (Q(Q(8)) + Q(2)! + F(8)) \times 2$$

$$82820 := (Q(Q(8)) + Q(2)! + F(8)) \times 20$$

$$828200 := (Q(Q(8)) + Q(2)! + F(8)) \times 200$$

$$8282000 := (Q(Q(8)) + Q(2)! + F(8)) \times 2000$$

1317.

$$8286 := (F(8) + Q(Q(F(Q(2)!))) + Q(8)) \times 6$$

$$82860 := (F(8) + Q(Q(F(Q(2)!))) + Q(8)) \times 60$$

$$828600 := (F(8) + Q(Q(F(Q(2)!))) + Q(8)) \times 600$$

$$8286000 := (F(8) + Q(Q(F(Q(2)!))) + Q(8)) \times 6000$$

1318.

$$8288 := (T(8) + C(2 + 8)) \times 8$$

$$82880 := (T(8) + C(2 + 8)) \times 80$$

$$828800 := (T(8) + C(2 + 8)) \times 800$$

$$8288000 := (T(8) + C(2 + 8)) \times 8000$$

1319.

$$8302 := (Q(Q(8)) + F(Q(3) + 0!)) \times 2$$

$$83020 := (Q(Q(8)) + F(Q(3) + 0!)) \times 20$$

$$830200 := (Q(Q(8)) + F(Q(3) + 0!)) \times 200$$

$$8302000 := (Q(Q(8)) + F(Q(3) + 0!)) \times 2000$$

1320.

$$8302 := (Q(Q(8)) + T(Q(3) + 0!)) \times 2$$

$$83020 := (Q(Q(8)) + T(Q(3) + 0!)) \times 20$$

$$830200 := (Q(Q(8)) + T(Q(3) + 0!)) \times 200$$

$$8302000 := (Q(Q(8)) + T(Q(3) + 0!)) \times 2000$$

1321.

$$\begin{aligned} 8322 &:= (Q(Q(8)) + Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(2))) \times 2 \\ 83220 &:= (Q(Q(8)) + Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(2))) \times 20 \\ 832200 &:= (Q(Q(8)) + Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(2))) \times 200 \\ 8322000 &:= (Q(Q(8)) + Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(2))) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1322.

$$\begin{aligned} 8324 &:= (T(8^{F(3)}) + F(2)) \times 4 \\ 83240 &:= (T(8^{F(3)}) + F(2)) \times 40 \\ 832400 &:= (T(8^{F(3)}) + F(2)) \times 400 \\ 8324000 &:= (T(8^{F(3)}) + F(2)) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

1323.

$$\begin{aligned} 8324 &:= (T(Q(8)) + 3 - 2) \times 4 \\ 83240 &:= (T(Q(8)) + 3 - 2) \times 40 \\ 832400 &:= (T(Q(8)) + 3 - 2) \times 400 \\ 8324000 &:= (T(Q(8)) + 3 - 2) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

1324.

$$\begin{aligned} 8325 &:= -T(T(8))/(-F(3)) \times 25 \\ 83250 &:= -T(T(8))/(-F(3)) \times 250 \\ 832500 &:= -T(T(8))/(-F(3)) \times 2500 \\ 8325000 &:= -T(T(8))/(-F(3)) \times 25000 \end{aligned}$$

1325.

$$\begin{aligned} 8325 &:= T(T(8))/F(3) \times 25 \\ 83250 &:= T(T(8))/F(3) \times 250 \\ 832500 &:= T(T(8))/F(3) \times 2500 \\ 8325000 &:= T(T(8))/F(3) \times 25000 \end{aligned}$$

1326.

$$\begin{aligned} 8328 &:= (C(8) + Q(C(3) - Q(2))) \times 8 \\ 83280 &:= (C(8) + Q(C(3) - Q(2))) \times 80 \\ 832800 &:= (C(8) + Q(C(3) - Q(2))) \times 800 \\ 8328000 &:= (C(8) + Q(C(3) - Q(2))) \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

1327.

$$\begin{aligned} 8328 &:= (\sqrt{T(8)} + T(T(3^2))) \times 8 \\ 83280 &:= (\sqrt{T(8)} + T(T(3^2))) \times 80 \\ 832800 &:= (\sqrt{T(8)} + T(T(3^2))) \times 800 \\ 8328000 &:= (\sqrt{T(8)} + T(T(3^2))) \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

1328.

$$\begin{aligned} 8332 &:= (Q(Q(8)) + F(Q(3)) + Q(3!)) \times 2 \\ 83320 &:= (Q(Q(8)) + F(Q(3)) + Q(3!)) \times 20 \\ 833200 &:= (Q(Q(8)) + F(Q(3)) + Q(3!)) \times 200 \\ 8332000 &:= (Q(Q(8)) + F(Q(3)) + Q(3!)) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1329.

$$\begin{aligned} 8335 &:= (F(8) \times Q(Q(3)) - F(Q(3))) \times 5 \\ 83350 &:= (F(8) \times Q(Q(3)) - F(Q(3))) \times 50 \\ 833500 &:= (F(8) \times Q(Q(3)) - F(Q(3))) \times 500 \\ 8335000 &:= (F(8) \times Q(Q(3)) - F(Q(3))) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1330.

$$\begin{aligned} 8342 &:= (F(F(8) - F(3)) - T(4)) \times 2 \\ 83420 &:= (F(F(8) - F(3)) - T(4)) \times 20 \\ 834200 &:= (F(F(8) - F(3)) - T(4)) \times 200 \\ 8342000 &:= (F(F(8) - F(3)) - T(4)) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1331.

$$\begin{aligned}8342 &:= (Q(Q(8)) + Q(Q(3)) - F(4)!) \times 2 \\83420 &:= (Q(Q(8)) + Q(Q(3)) - F(4)!) \times 20 \\834200 &:= (Q(Q(8)) + Q(Q(3)) - F(4)!) \times 200 \\8342000 &:= (Q(Q(8)) + Q(Q(3)) - F(4)!) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1332.

$$\begin{aligned}8344 &:= (T(8^{F(3)}) + T(F(4))) \times 4 \\83440 &:= (T(8^{F(3)}) + T(F(4))) \times 40 \\834400 &:= (T(8^{F(3)}) + T(F(4))) \times 400 \\8344000 &:= (T(8^{F(3)}) + T(F(4))) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

1333.

$$\begin{aligned}8345 &:= (T(T(8)) + 3 + C(T(4))) \times 5 \\83450 &:= (T(T(8)) + 3 + C(T(4))) \times 50 \\834500 &:= (T(T(8)) + 3 + C(T(4))) \times 500 \\8345000 &:= (T(T(8)) + 3 + C(T(4))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1334.

$$\begin{aligned}8350 &:= (-Q(8) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 50 \\83500 &:= (-Q(8) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 500 \\835000 &:= (-Q(8) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 5000 \\8350000 &:= (-Q(8) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 50000\end{aligned}$$

1335.

$$\begin{aligned}8352 &:= (F(-8 + C(3)) - 5) \times 2 \\83520 &:= (F(-8 + C(3)) - 5) \times 20 \\835200 &:= (F(-8 + C(3)) - 5) \times 200 \\8352000 &:= (F(-8 + C(3)) - 5) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1336.

$$\begin{aligned}8352 &:= (F(F(8) - F(3)) - 5) \times 2 \\83520 &:= (F(F(8) - F(3)) - 5) \times 20 \\835200 &:= (F(F(8) - F(3)) - 5) \times 200 \\8352000 &:= (F(F(8) - F(3)) - 5) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1337.

$$\begin{aligned}8372 &:= T(T(8) + F(3 + 7)) \times 2 \\83720 &:= T(T(8) + F(3 + 7)) \times 20 \\837200 &:= T(T(8) + F(3 + 7)) \times 200 \\8372000 &:= T(T(8) + F(3 + 7)) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1338.

$$\begin{aligned}8372 &:= T(T(8) + T(3 + 7)) \times 2 \\83720 &:= T(T(8) + T(3 + 7)) \times 20 \\837200 &:= T(T(8) + T(3 + 7)) \times 200 \\8372000 &:= T(T(8) + T(3 + 7)) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1339.

$$\begin{aligned}8376 &:= (Q(T(8)) + Q(3 + 7)) \times 6 \\83760 &:= (Q(T(8)) + Q(3 + 7)) \times 60 \\837600 &:= (Q(T(8)) + Q(3 + 7)) \times 600 \\8376000 &:= (Q(T(8)) + Q(3 + 7)) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1340.

$$\begin{aligned}8379 &:= (-8 + C(3)) \times Q(7) \times 9 \\83790 &:= (-8 + C(3)) \times Q(7) \times 90 \\837900 &:= (-8 + C(3)) \times Q(7) \times 900 \\8379000 &:= (-8 + C(3)) \times Q(7) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

1341.

$$8379 := (F(8) - F(3)) \times Q(7) \times 9$$

$$83790 := (F(8) - F(3)) \times Q(7) \times 90$$

$$837900 := (F(8) - F(3)) \times Q(7) \times 900$$

$$8379000 := (F(8) - F(3)) \times Q(7) \times 9000$$

1342.

$$8379 := (Q(8) - T(Q(3))) \times Q(7) \times 9$$

$$83790 := (Q(8) - T(Q(3))) \times Q(7) \times 90$$

$$837900 := (Q(8) - T(Q(3))) \times Q(7) \times 900$$

$$8379000 := (Q(8) - T(Q(3))) \times Q(7) \times 9000$$

1343.

$$8379 := (T(T(8) + T(3)) + T(7)) \times 9$$

$$83790 := (T(T(8) + T(3)) + T(7)) \times 90$$

$$837900 := (T(T(8) + T(3)) + T(7)) \times 900$$

$$8379000 := (T(T(8) + T(3)) + T(7)) \times 9000$$

1344.

$$8403 := ((\sqrt{T(8)})! + T(C(4)) + 0!) \times 3$$

$$84030 := ((\sqrt{T(8)})! + T(C(4)) + 0!) \times 30$$

$$840300 := ((\sqrt{T(8)})! + T(C(4)) + 0!) \times 300$$

$$8403000 := ((\sqrt{T(8)})! + T(C(4)) + 0!) \times 3000$$

1345.

$$8403 := (Q(Q(8)) - Q(Q(F(4)!)) + 0!) \times 3$$

$$84030 := (Q(Q(8)) - Q(Q(F(4)!)) + 0!) \times 30$$

$$840300 := (Q(Q(8)) - Q(Q(F(4)!)) + 0!) \times 300$$

$$8403000 := (Q(Q(8)) - Q(Q(F(4)!)) + 0!) \times 3000$$

1346.

$$8403 := (T(Q(8)) + T(T(\sqrt{4}))! + 0!) \times 3$$

$$84030 := (T(Q(8)) + T(T(\sqrt{4}))! + 0!) \times 30$$

$$840300 := (T(Q(8)) + T(T(\sqrt{4}))! + 0!) \times 300$$

$$8403000 := (T(Q(8)) + T(T(\sqrt{4}))! + 0!) \times 3000$$

1347.

$$8404 := (T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + T(C(4))) \times 4$$

$$84040 := (T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + T(C(4))) \times 40$$

$$840400 := (T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + T(C(4))) \times 400$$

$$8404000 := (T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + T(C(4))) \times 4000$$

1348.

$$8405 := (8!/4! + 0!) \times 5$$

$$84050 := (8!/4! + 0!) \times 50$$

$$840500 := (8!/4! + 0!) \times 500$$

$$8405000 := (8!/4! + 0!) \times 5000$$

1349.

$$8408 := (T(F(8)) + T(40)) \times 8$$

$$84080 := (T(F(8)) + T(40)) \times 80$$

$$840800 := (T(F(8)) + T(40)) \times 800$$

$$8408000 := (T(F(8)) + T(40)) \times 8000$$

1350.

$$8408 := (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + T(40)) \times 8$$

$$84080 := (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + T(40)) \times 80$$

$$840800 := (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + T(40)) \times 800$$

$$8408000 := (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + T(40)) \times 8000$$

1351.

$$8410 := Q(8 + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) \times 10$$

$$84100 := Q(8 + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) \times 100$$

$$841000 := Q(8 + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) \times 1000$$

$$8410000 := Q(8 + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) \times 10000$$

1352.

$$8410 := Q(F(8) + F(F(4)!)) \times 10$$

$$84100 := Q(F(8) + F(F(4)!)) \times 100$$

$$841000 := Q(F(8) + F(F(4)!)) \times 1000$$

$$8410000 := Q(F(8) + F(F(4)!)) \times 10000$$

1353.

$$8425 := (-C(8) + C(T(4) + T(2))) \times 5$$

$$84250 := (-C(8) + C(T(4) + T(2))) \times 50$$

$$842500 := (-C(8) + C(T(4) + T(2))) \times 500$$

$$8425000 := (-C(8) + C(T(4) + T(2))) \times 5000$$

1354.

$$8425 := (F(F(8)) - C(F(4 \times 2))) \times 5$$

$$84250 := (F(F(8)) - C(F(4 \times 2))) \times 50$$

$$842500 := (F(F(8)) - C(F(4 \times 2))) \times 500$$

$$8425000 := (F(F(8)) - C(F(4 \times 2))) \times 5000$$

1355.

$$8432 := (Q(Q(8)) + (-4 + Q(3)!)) \times 2$$

$$84320 := (Q(Q(8)) + (-4 + Q(3)!)) \times 20$$

$$843200 := (Q(Q(8)) + (-4 + Q(3)!)) \times 200$$

$$8432000 := (Q(Q(8)) + (-4 + Q(3)!)) \times 2000$$

1356.

$$8435 := (T(F(8)) + T(4)) \times 35$$

$$84350 := (T(F(8)) + T(4)) \times 350$$

$$843500 := (T(F(8)) + T(4)) \times 3500$$

$$8435000 := (T(F(8)) + T(4)) \times 35000$$

1357.

$$8435 := (T(T(8)) + C(T(4)) + T(T(3))) \times 5$$

$$84350 := (T(T(8)) + C(T(4)) + T(T(3))) \times 50$$

$$843500 := (T(T(8)) + C(T(4)) + T(T(3))) \times 500$$

$$8435000 := (T(T(8)) + C(T(4)) + T(T(3))) \times 5000$$

1358.

$$8435 := (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + T(4)) \times 35$$

$$84350 := (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + T(4)) \times 350$$

$$843500 := (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + T(4)) \times 3500$$

$$8435000 := (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + T(4)) \times 35000$$

1359.

$$8442 := (C(F(8)) - (F(4) + 4)!) \times 2$$

$$84420 := (C(F(8)) - (F(4) + 4)!) \times 20$$

$$844200 := (C(F(8)) - (F(4) + 4)!) \times 200$$

$$8442000 := (C(F(8)) - (F(4) + 4)!) \times 2000$$

1360.

$$8448 := (T(F(8)) - F(T(4))) \times 48$$

$$84480 := (T(F(8)) - F(T(4))) \times 480$$

$$844800 := (T(F(8)) - F(T(4))) \times 4800$$

$$8448000 := (T(F(8)) - F(T(4))) \times 48000$$

1361.

$$8455 := (T(T(8) + T(4)) + F(T(5))) \times 5$$

$$84550 := (T(T(8) + T(4)) + F(T(5))) \times 50$$

$$845500 := (T(T(8) + T(4)) + F(T(5))) \times 500$$

$$8455000 := (T(T(8) + T(4)) + F(T(5))) \times 5000$$

1362.

$$8465 := (F(F(8)) + \sqrt{C(4) - C(F(F(6)))}) \times 5$$

$$84650 := (F(F(8)) + \sqrt{C(4) - C(F(F(6)))}) \times 50$$

$$846500 := (F(F(8)) + \sqrt{C(4) - C(F(F(6)))}) \times 500$$

$$8465000 := (F(F(8)) + \sqrt{C(4) - C(F(F(6)))}) \times 5000$$

1363.

$$8466 := (T(Q(8)) - T(\sqrt{4}) - T(Q(6))) \times 6$$

$$84660 := (T(Q(8)) - T(\sqrt{4}) - T(Q(6))) \times 60$$

$$846600 := (T(Q(8)) - T(\sqrt{4}) - T(Q(6))) \times 600$$

$$8466000 := (T(Q(8)) - T(\sqrt{4}) - T(Q(6))) \times 6000$$

1364.

$$8469 := (T(F(8)) - T(4) + 6!) \times 9$$

$$84690 := (T(F(8)) - T(4) + 6!) \times 90$$

$$846900 := (T(F(8)) - T(4) + 6!) \times 900$$

$$8469000 := (T(F(8)) - T(4) + 6!) \times 9000$$

1365.

$$8471 := (Q(-8 + Q(T(4))) + 7) \times 1$$

$$84710 := (Q(-8 + Q(T(4))) + 7) \times 10$$

$$847100 := (Q(-8 + Q(T(4))) + 7) \times 100$$

$$8471000 := (Q(-8 + Q(T(4))) + 7) \times 1000$$

1366.

$$8470 := Q(8 + F(4)) \times 70$$

$$84700 := Q(8 + F(4)) \times 700$$

$$847000 := Q(8 + F(4)) \times 7000$$

$$8470000 := Q(8 + F(4)) \times 70000$$

1367.

$$8472 := (T(F(8)) + T(F(4 + 7))) \times 2$$

$$84720 := (T(F(8)) + T(F(4 + 7))) \times 20$$

$$847200 := (T(F(8)) + T(F(4 + 7))) \times 200$$

$$8472000 := (T(F(8)) + T(F(4 + 7))) \times 2000$$

1368.

$$8472 := (T(T(8)) + T(T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(7))) \times 2$$

$$84720 := (T(T(8)) + T(T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(7))) \times 20$$

$$847200 := (T(T(8)) + T(T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(7))) \times 200$$

$$8472000 := (T(T(8)) + T(T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(7))) \times 2000$$

1369.

$$8475 := (8^4 - Q(Q(7))) \times 5$$

$$84750 := (8^4 - Q(Q(7))) \times 50$$

$$847500 := (8^4 - Q(Q(7))) \times 500$$

$$8475000 := (8^4 - Q(Q(7))) \times 5000$$

1370.

$$8482 := (Q(8) + Q(Q(F(4))) + Q(Q(8))) \times 2$$

$$84820 := (Q(8) + Q(Q(F(4))) + Q(Q(8))) \times 20$$

$$848200 := (Q(8) + Q(Q(F(4))) + Q(Q(8))) \times 200$$

$$8482000 := (Q(8) + Q(Q(F(4))) + Q(Q(8))) \times 2000$$

1371.

$$\begin{aligned}8495 &:= (T(Q(8)) - T(4!) - Q(9)) \times 5 \\84950 &:= (T(Q(8)) - T(4!) - Q(9)) \times 50 \\849500 &:= (T(Q(8)) - T(4!) - Q(9)) \times 500 \\8495000 &:= (T(Q(8)) - T(4!) - Q(9)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1372.

$$\begin{aligned}8495 &:= (T(T(8)) - F(F(4)) + T(T(9))) \times 5 \\84950 &:= (T(T(8)) - F(F(4)) + T(T(9))) \times 50 \\849500 &:= (T(T(8)) - F(F(4)) + T(T(9))) \times 500 \\8495000 &:= (T(T(8)) - F(F(4)) + T(T(9))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1373.

$$\begin{aligned}8495 &:= (T(T(8)) - \sqrt{4} + T(T(9))) \times 5 \\84950 &:= (T(T(8)) - \sqrt{4} + T(T(9))) \times 50 \\849500 &:= (T(T(8)) - \sqrt{4} + T(T(9))) \times 500 \\8495000 &:= (T(T(8)) - \sqrt{4} + T(T(9))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1374.

$$\begin{aligned}8525 &:= (T(T(8)) - T(Q(5))) \times 25 \\85250 &:= (T(T(8)) - T(Q(5))) \times 250 \\852500 &:= (T(T(8)) - T(Q(5))) \times 2500 \\8525000 &:= (T(T(8)) - T(Q(5))) \times 25000\end{aligned}$$

1375.

$$\begin{aligned}8535 &:= (F(F(8)) - 5 + 3!) \times 5 \\85350 &:= (F(F(8)) - 5 + 3!) \times 50 \\853500 &:= (F(F(8)) - 5 + 3!) \times 500 \\8535000 &:= (F(F(8)) - 5 + 3!) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1376.

$$\begin{aligned}8535 &:= (F(F(8)) - 5 + T(3!)) \times 5 \\85350 &:= (F(F(8)) - 5 + T(3!)) \times 50 \\853500 &:= (F(F(8)) - 5 + T(3!)) \times 500 \\8535000 &:= (F(F(8)) - 5 + T(3!)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1377.

$$\begin{aligned}8542 &:= (Q(Q(8)) + 5! + T(T(4))) \times 2 \\85420 &:= (Q(Q(8)) + 5! + T(T(4))) \times 20 \\854200 &:= (Q(Q(8)) + 5! + T(T(4))) \times 200 \\8542000 &:= (Q(Q(8)) + 5! + T(T(4))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1378.

$$\begin{aligned}8544 &:= (Q(8) + Q(5)) \times 4! \times 4 \\85440 &:= (Q(8) + Q(5)) \times 4! \times 40 \\854400 &:= (Q(8) + Q(5)) \times 4! \times 400 \\8544000 &:= (Q(8) + Q(5)) \times 4! \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

1379.

$$\begin{aligned}8544 &:= (Q(8) + Q(5)) \times 4! \times 4 \\85440 &:= (Q(8) + Q(5)) \times 4! \times 40 \\854400 &:= (Q(8) + Q(5)) \times 4! \times 400 \\8544000 &:= (Q(8) + Q(5)) \times 4! \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

1380.

$$\begin{aligned}8544 &:= (-T(8) + C(5)) \times 4! \times 4 \\85440 &:= (-T(8) + C(5)) \times 4! \times 40 \\854400 &:= (-T(8) + C(5)) \times 4! \times 400 \\8544000 &:= (-T(8) + C(5)) \times 4! \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

1381.

$$8544 := (-T(8) + C(5)) \times 4! \times 4$$

$$85440 := (-T(8) + C(5)) \times 4! \times 40$$

$$854400 := (-T(8) + C(5)) \times 4! \times 400$$

$$8544000 := (-T(8) + C(5)) \times 4! \times 4000$$

1382.

$$8547 := (F(8) + 5! \times T(4)) \times 7$$

$$85470 := (F(8) + 5! \times T(4)) \times 70$$

$$854700 := (F(8) + 5! \times T(4)) \times 700$$

$$8547000 := (F(8) + 5! \times T(4)) \times 7000$$

1383.

$$8547 := (T(Q(8) - T(5)) - 4) \times 7$$

$$85470 := (T(Q(8) - T(5)) - 4) \times 70$$

$$854700 := (T(Q(8) - T(5)) - 4) \times 700$$

$$8547000 := (T(Q(8) - T(5)) - 4) \times 7000$$

1384.

$$8555 := T(\sqrt{-\sqrt{T(8)} - 5 + C(T(5))}) \times 5$$

$$85550 := T(\sqrt{-\sqrt{T(8)} - 5 + C(T(5))}) \times 50$$

$$855500 := T(\sqrt{-\sqrt{T(8)} - 5 + C(T(5))}) \times 500$$

$$8555000 := T(\sqrt{-\sqrt{T(8)} - 5 + C(T(5))}) \times 5000$$

1385.

$$8559 := (T(F(8)) + T(T(5)/5!)) \times 9$$

$$85590 := (T(F(8)) + T(T(5)/5!)) \times 90$$

$$855900 := (T(F(8)) + T(T(5)/5!)) \times 900$$

$$8559000 := (T(F(8)) + T(T(5)/5!)) \times 9000$$

1386.

$$8559 := (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + T(T(5)/5!)) \times 9$$

$$85590 := (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + T(T(5)/5!)) \times 90$$

$$855900 := (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + T(T(5)/5!)) \times 900$$

$$8559000 := (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + T(T(5)/5!)) \times 9000$$

1387.

$$8564 := (Q(F(8)) \times 5 - Q(F(6))) \times 4$$

$$85640 := (Q(F(8)) \times 5 - Q(F(6))) \times 40$$

$$856400 := (Q(F(8)) \times 5 - Q(F(6))) \times 400$$

$$8564000 := (Q(F(8)) \times 5 - Q(F(6))) \times 4000$$

1388.

$$8564 := (T(Q(8)) + Q(5) + Q(6)) \times 4$$

$$85640 := (T(Q(8)) + Q(5) + Q(6)) \times 40$$

$$856400 := (T(Q(8)) + Q(5) + Q(6)) \times 400$$

$$8564000 := (T(Q(8)) + Q(5) + Q(6)) \times 4000$$

1389.

$$8584 := (T(T(8) - Q(5)) + T(Q(8))) \times 4$$

$$85840 := (T(T(8) - Q(5)) + T(Q(8))) \times 40$$

$$858400 := (T(T(8) - Q(5)) + T(Q(8))) \times 400$$

$$8584000 := (T(T(8) - Q(5)) + T(Q(8))) \times 4000$$

1390.

$$8585 := (\sqrt{T(8)} + T(58)) \times 5$$

$$85850 := (\sqrt{T(8)} + T(58)) \times 50$$

$$858500 := (\sqrt{T(8)} + T(58)) \times 500$$

$$8585000 := (\sqrt{T(8)} + T(58)) \times 5000$$

1391.

$$\begin{aligned}8585 &:= (T(8) + Q(5 + T(8))) \times 5 \\85850 &:= (T(8) + Q(5 + T(8))) \times 50 \\858500 &:= (T(8) + Q(5 + T(8))) \times 500 \\8585000 &:= (T(8) + Q(5 + T(8))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1392.

$$\begin{aligned}8595 &:= ((-8 + T(5))! - T(Q(9))) \times 5 \\85950 &:= ((-8 + T(5))! - T(Q(9))) \times 50 \\859500 &:= ((-8 + T(5))! - T(Q(9))) \times 500 \\8595000 &:= ((-8 + T(5))! - T(Q(9))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1393.

$$\begin{aligned}8612 &:= (Q(Q(8)) + T(T(6) - 1)) \times 2 \\86120 &:= (Q(Q(8)) + T(T(6) - 1)) \times 20 \\861200 &:= (Q(Q(8)) + T(T(6) - 1)) \times 200 \\8612000 &:= (Q(Q(8)) + T(T(6) - 1)) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1394.

$$\begin{aligned}8613 &:= (Q(Q(8)) - Q(Q(6) - 1)) \times 3 \\86130 &:= (Q(Q(8)) - Q(Q(6) - 1)) \times 30 \\861300 &:= (Q(Q(8)) - Q(Q(6) - 1)) \times 300 \\8613000 &:= (Q(Q(8)) - Q(Q(6) - 1)) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

1395.

$$\begin{aligned}8617 &:= (C(8) + 6! - 1) \times 7 \\86170 &:= (C(8) + 6! - 1) \times 70 \\861700 &:= (C(8) + 6! - 1) \times 700 \\8617000 &:= (C(8) + 6! - 1) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

1396.

$$\begin{aligned}8617 &:= (-Q(8) + Q(Q(6)) - 1) \times 7 \\86170 &:= (-Q(8) + Q(Q(6)) - 1) \times 70 \\861700 &:= (-Q(8) + Q(Q(6)) - 1) \times 700 \\8617000 &:= (-Q(8) + Q(Q(6)) - 1) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

1397.

$$\begin{aligned}8635 &:= (C(8) + Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(3))) \times 5 \\86350 &:= (C(8) + Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(3))) \times 50 \\863500 &:= (C(8) + Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(3))) \times 500 \\8635000 &:= (C(8) + Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(3))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1398.

$$\begin{aligned}8642 &:= (Q(T(8)) + Q(T(6 + 4))) \times 2 \\86420 &:= (Q(T(8)) + Q(T(6 + 4))) \times 20 \\864200 &:= (Q(T(8)) + Q(T(6 + 4))) \times 200 \\8642000 &:= (Q(T(8)) + Q(T(6 + 4))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1399.

$$\begin{aligned}8646 &:= (\sqrt{T(8)} \times T(T(6)) + F(T(4))) \times 6 \\86460 &:= (\sqrt{T(8)} \times T(T(6)) + F(T(4))) \times 60 \\864600 &:= (\sqrt{T(8)} \times T(T(6)) + F(T(4))) \times 600 \\8646000 &:= (\sqrt{T(8)} \times T(T(6)) + F(T(4))) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1400.

$$\begin{aligned}8646 &:= (\sqrt{T(8)} \times T(T(6)) + T(T(4))) \times 6 \\86460 &:= (\sqrt{T(8)} \times T(T(6)) + T(T(4))) \times 60 \\864600 &:= (\sqrt{T(8)} \times T(T(6)) + T(T(4))) \times 600 \\8646000 &:= (\sqrt{T(8)} \times T(T(6)) + T(T(4))) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1401.

$$\begin{aligned} 8646 &:= (T(F(8)) \times 6 + F(T(4))) \times 6 \\ 86460 &:= (T(F(8)) \times 6 + F(T(4))) \times 60 \\ 864600 &:= (T(F(8)) \times 6 + F(T(4))) \times 600 \\ 8646000 &:= (T(F(8)) \times 6 + F(T(4))) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

1402.

$$\begin{aligned} 8646 &:= (T(T(8)) + 6! + T(T(4))) \times 6 \\ 86460 &:= (T(T(8)) + 6! + T(T(4))) \times 60 \\ 864600 &:= (T(T(8)) + 6! + T(T(4))) \times 600 \\ 8646000 &:= (T(T(8)) + 6! + T(T(4))) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

1403.

$$\begin{aligned} 8652 &:= (\sqrt{T(8)} + Q(6) \times 5!) \times 2 \\ 86520 &:= (\sqrt{T(8)} + Q(6) \times 5!) \times 20 \\ 865200 &:= (\sqrt{T(8)} + Q(6) \times 5!) \times 200 \\ 8652000 &:= (\sqrt{T(8)} + Q(6) \times 5!) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1404.

$$\begin{aligned} 8652 &:= (T(F(8)) + T(6 \times T(5))) \times 2 \\ 86520 &:= (T(F(8)) + T(6 \times T(5))) \times 20 \\ 865200 &:= (T(F(8)) + T(6 \times T(5))) \times 200 \\ 8652000 &:= (T(F(8)) + T(6 \times T(5))) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1405.

$$\begin{aligned} 8682 &:= (\sqrt{T(8)} \times 6! + F(8)) \times 2 \\ 86820 &:= (\sqrt{T(8)} \times 6! + F(8)) \times 20 \\ 868200 &:= (\sqrt{T(8)} \times 6! + F(8)) \times 200 \\ 8682000 &:= (\sqrt{T(8)} \times 6! + F(8)) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1406.

$$\begin{aligned} 8688 &:= (Q(T(8)) - T(6!/T(8))) \times 8 \\ 86880 &:= (Q(T(8)) - T(6!/T(8))) \times 80 \\ 868800 &:= (Q(T(8)) - T(6!/T(8))) \times 800 \\ 8688000 &:= (Q(T(8)) - T(6!/T(8))) \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

1407.

$$\begin{aligned} 8695 &:= (Q(F(8)) + Q(Q(6)) + F(\sqrt{9})) \times 5 \\ 86950 &:= (Q(F(8)) + Q(Q(6)) + F(\sqrt{9})) \times 50 \\ 869500 &:= (Q(F(8)) + Q(Q(6)) + F(\sqrt{9})) \times 500 \\ 8695000 &:= (Q(F(8)) + Q(Q(6)) + F(\sqrt{9})) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1408.

$$\begin{aligned} 8706 &:= (T(T(8)) + Q(T(7)) + 0!) \times 6 \\ 87060 &:= (T(T(8)) + Q(T(7)) + 0!) \times 60 \\ 870600 &:= (T(T(8)) + Q(T(7)) + 0!) \times 600 \\ 8706000 &:= (T(T(8)) + Q(T(7)) + 0!) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

1409.

$$\begin{aligned} 8725 &:= (\sqrt{T(8)} + C(7)) \times 25 \\ 87250 &:= (\sqrt{T(8)} + C(7)) \times 250 \\ 872500 &:= (\sqrt{T(8)} + C(7)) \times 2500 \\ 8725000 &:= (\sqrt{T(8)} + C(7)) \times 25000 \end{aligned}$$

1410.

$$\begin{aligned} 8732 &:= (-8 + 7! - T(Q(T(3)))) \times 2 \\ 87320 &:= (-8 + 7! - T(Q(T(3)))) \times 20 \\ 873200 &:= (-8 + 7! - T(Q(T(3)))) \times 200 \\ 8732000 &:= (-8 + 7! - T(Q(T(3)))) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1411.

$$\begin{aligned}8735 &:= (T(8) + T(Q(7) + Q(3))) \times 5 \\87350 &:= (T(8) + T(Q(7) + Q(3))) \times 50 \\873500 &:= (T(8) + T(Q(7) + Q(3))) \times 500 \\8735000 &:= (T(8) + T(Q(7) + Q(3))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1412.

$$\begin{aligned}8739 &:= (Q(T(8)) - T(T(7) - 3)) \times 9 \\87390 &:= (Q(T(8)) - T(T(7) - 3)) \times 90 \\873900 &:= (Q(T(8)) - T(T(7) - 3)) \times 900 \\8739000 &:= (Q(T(8)) - T(T(7) - 3)) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

1413.

$$\begin{aligned}8742 &:= -(T(T(8)) - 7! + F(4)) \times 2 \\87420 &:= -(T(T(8)) - 7! + F(4)) \times 20 \\874200 &:= -(T(T(8)) - 7! + F(4)) \times 200 \\8742000 &:= -(T(T(8)) - 7! + F(4)) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1414.

$$\begin{aligned}8744 &:= (C(8) - T(T(7)) + T(C(4))) \times 4 \\87440 &:= (C(8) - T(T(7)) + T(C(4))) \times 40 \\874400 &:= (C(8) - T(T(7)) + T(C(4))) \times 400 \\8744000 &:= (C(8) - T(T(7)) + T(C(4))) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

1415.

$$\begin{aligned}8745 &:= (F(8) \times Q(7) + F(4)!!) \times 5 \\87450 &:= (F(8) \times Q(7) + F(4)!!) \times 50 \\874500 &:= (F(8) \times Q(7) + F(4)!!) \times 500 \\8745000 &:= (F(8) \times Q(7) + F(4)!!) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1416.

$$\begin{aligned}8755 &:= (T(8) + 5 \times C(7)) \times 5 \\87550 &:= (T(8) + 5 \times C(7)) \times 50 \\875500 &:= (T(8) + 5 \times C(7)) \times 500 \\8755000 &:= (T(8) + 5 \times C(7)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1417.

$$\begin{aligned}8757 &:= ((\sqrt{T(8)})! + T(T(7)) + C(5)) \times 7 \\87570 &:= ((\sqrt{T(8)})! + T(T(7)) + C(5)) \times 70 \\875700 &:= ((\sqrt{T(8)})! + T(T(7)) + C(5)) \times 700 \\8757000 &:= ((\sqrt{T(8)})! + T(T(7)) + C(5)) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

1418.

$$\begin{aligned}8763 &:= (T(Q(8)) + Q(-7 + Q(6))) \times 3 \\87630 &:= (T(Q(8)) + Q(-7 + Q(6))) \times 30 \\876300 &:= (T(Q(8)) + Q(-7 + Q(6))) \times 300 \\8763000 &:= (T(Q(8)) + Q(-7 + Q(6))) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

1419.

$$\begin{aligned}8764 &:= (C(\sqrt{C(8) - C(7)}) - 6) \times 4 \\87640 &:= (C(\sqrt{C(8) - C(7)}) - 6) \times 40 \\876400 &:= (C(\sqrt{C(8) - C(7)}) - 6) \times 400 \\8764000 &:= (C(\sqrt{C(8) - C(7)}) - 6) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

1420.

$$\begin{aligned}8766 &:= (8!/T(7) + T(6)) \times 6 \\87660 &:= (8!/T(7) + T(6)) \times 60 \\876600 &:= (8!/T(7) + T(6)) \times 600 \\8766000 &:= (8!/T(7) + T(6)) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1421.

$$8772 := (-8 + C(F(7)) + C(F(7))) \times 2$$

$$87720 := (-8 + C(F(7)) + C(F(7))) \times 20$$

$$877200 := (-8 + C(F(7)) + C(F(7))) \times 200$$

$$8772000 := (-8 + C(F(7)) + C(F(7))) \times 2000$$

1422.

$$8792 := (T(F(8)) + 7 \times T(F(9))) \times 2$$

$$87920 := (T(F(8)) + 7 \times T(F(9))) \times 20$$

$$879200 := (T(F(8)) + 7 \times T(F(9))) \times 200$$

$$8792000 := (T(F(8)) + 7 \times T(F(9))) \times 2000$$

1423.

$$8796 := (T(T(8)) - T(Q(7)) + Q(T(9))) \times 6$$

$$87960 := (T(T(8)) - T(Q(7)) + Q(T(9))) \times 60$$

$$879600 := (T(T(8)) - T(Q(7)) + Q(T(9))) \times 600$$

$$8796000 := (T(T(8)) - T(Q(7)) + Q(T(9))) \times 6000$$

1424.

$$8815 := (Q(T(8) + \sqrt{T(8)}) - 1) \times 5$$

$$88150 := (Q(T(8) + \sqrt{T(8)}) - 1) \times 50$$

$$881500 := (Q(T(8) + \sqrt{T(8)}) - 1) \times 500$$

$$8815000 := (Q(T(8) + \sqrt{T(8)}) - 1) \times 5000$$

1425.

$$8824 := (T(T(8)) + T(F(8+2))) \times 4$$

$$88240 := (T(T(8)) + T(F(8+2))) \times 40$$

$$882400 := (T(T(8)) + T(F(8+2))) \times 400$$

$$8824000 := (T(T(8)) + T(F(8+2))) \times 4000$$

1426.

$$8824 := (T(T(8)) + T(T(8+2))) \times 4$$

$$88240 := (T(T(8)) + T(T(8+2))) \times 40$$

$$882400 := (T(T(8)) + T(T(8+2))) \times 400$$

$$8824000 := (T(T(8)) + T(T(8+2))) \times 4000$$

1427.

$$8827 := (T(T(8)) + T(T(8) - 2)) \times 7$$

$$88270 := (T(T(8)) + T(T(8) - 2)) \times 70$$

$$882700 := (T(T(8)) + T(T(8) - 2)) \times 700$$

$$8827000 := (T(T(8)) + T(T(8) - 2)) \times 7000$$

1428.

$$8829 := (F(8+8) - T(T(2))) \times 9$$

$$88290 := (F(8+8) - T(T(2))) \times 90$$

$$882900 := (F(8+8) - T(T(2))) \times 900$$

$$8829000 := (F(8+8) - T(T(2))) \times 9000$$

1429.

$$8835 := (Q(F(8) + F(8)) + 3) \times 5$$

$$88350 := (Q(F(8) + F(8)) + 3) \times 50$$

$$883500 := (Q(F(8) + F(8)) + 3) \times 500$$

$$8835000 := (Q(F(8) + F(8)) + 3) \times 5000$$

1430.

$$8844 := (T(F(8)) + T(8) \times F(T(4))) \times 4$$

$$88440 := (T(F(8)) + T(8) \times F(T(4))) \times 40$$

$$884400 := (T(F(8)) + T(8) \times F(T(4))) \times 400$$

$$8844000 := (T(F(8)) + T(8) \times F(T(4))) \times 4000$$

1431.

$$\begin{aligned} 8844 &:= T(8 \times 8 + \sqrt{4}) \times 4 \\ 88440 &:= T(8 \times 8 + \sqrt{4}) \times 40 \\ 884400 &:= T(8 \times 8 + \sqrt{4}) \times 400 \\ 8844000 &:= T(8 \times 8 + \sqrt{4}) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

1432.

$$\begin{aligned} 8844 &:= T(F(8) + F(8) + 4!) \times 4 \\ 88440 &:= T(F(8) + F(8) + 4!) \times 40 \\ 884400 &:= T(F(8) + F(8) + 4!) \times 400 \\ 8844000 &:= T(F(8) + F(8) + 4!) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

1433.

$$\begin{aligned} 8844 &:= T(T(8 + T(8/4))) \times 4 \\ 88440 &:= T(T(8 + T(8/4))) \times 40 \\ 884400 &:= T(T(8 + T(8/4))) \times 400 \\ 8844000 &:= T(T(8 + T(8/4))) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

1434.

$$\begin{aligned} 8855 &:= (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + T(T(T(\sqrt{T(\sqrt{T(8)} - 5))))) \times 5 \\ 88550 &:= (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + T(T(T(\sqrt{T(\sqrt{T(8)} - 5))))) \times 50 \\ 885500 &:= (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + T(T(T(\sqrt{T(\sqrt{T(8)} - 5))))) \times 500 \\ 8855000 &:= (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + T(T(T(\sqrt{T(\sqrt{T(8)} - 5))))) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1435.

$$\begin{aligned} 8916 &:= (T(9 \times \sqrt{T(8)}) + 1) \times 6 \\ 89160 &:= (T(9 \times \sqrt{T(8)}) + 1) \times 60 \\ 891600 &:= (T(9 \times \sqrt{T(8)}) + 1) \times 600 \\ 8916000 &:= (T(9 \times \sqrt{T(8)}) + 1) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

1436.

$$\begin{aligned} 8916 &:= (T(\sqrt{T(8) \times Q(9)}) + 1) \times 6 \\ 89160 &:= (T(\sqrt{T(8) \times Q(9)}) + 1) \times 60 \\ 891600 &:= (T(\sqrt{T(8) \times Q(9)}) + 1) \times 600 \\ 8916000 &:= (T(\sqrt{T(8) \times Q(9)}) + 1) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

MMM

$$\begin{aligned} 8919 &:= (T(T(8)) + T(Q(T(\sqrt{9}) - 1))) \times 9 \\ 89190 &:= (T(T(8)) + T(Q(T(\sqrt{9}) - 1))) \times 90 \\ 891900 &:= (T(T(8)) + T(Q(T(\sqrt{9}) - 1))) \times 900 \\ 8919000 &:= (T(T(8)) + T(Q(T(\sqrt{9}) - 1))) \times 9000 \end{aligned}$$

1437.

$$\begin{aligned} 8932 &:= (F(F(8)) - 9 \times 3!!) \times 2 \\ 89320 &:= (F(F(8)) - 9 \times 3!!) \times 20 \\ 893200 &:= (F(F(8)) - 9 \times 3!!) \times 200 \\ 8932000 &:= (F(F(8)) - 9 \times 3!!) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

$$8932 := (F(F(8)) - 9 \times T(3)!) \times 2$$

$$89320 := (F(F(8)) - 9 \times T(3)!) \times 20$$

$$893200 := (F(F(8)) - 9 \times T(3)!) \times 200$$

$$8932000 := (F(F(8)) - 9 \times T(3)!) \times 2000$$

1439.

$$\begin{aligned} 8932 &:= (F(F(8)) - Q(Q(9)) + Q(Q(3))) \times 2 \\ 89320 &:= (F(F(8)) - Q(Q(9)) + Q(Q(3))) \times 20 \\ 893200 &:= (F(F(8)) - Q(Q(9)) + Q(Q(3))) \times 200 \\ 8932000 &:= (F(F(8)) - Q(Q(9)) + Q(Q(3))) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1440.

$$8942 := (8! - Q(9))/Q(F(4)) \times 2$$

$$89420 := (8! - Q(9))/Q(F(4)) \times 20$$

$$894200 := (8! - Q(9))/Q(F(4)) \times 200$$

$$8942000 := (8! - Q(9))/Q(F(4)) \times 2000$$

1441.

$$8942 := (\sqrt{T(8)} + T(94)) \times 2$$

$$89420 := (\sqrt{T(8)} + T(94)) \times 20$$

$$894200 := (\sqrt{T(8)} + T(94)) \times 200$$

$$8942000 := (\sqrt{T(8)} + T(94)) \times 2000$$

1442.

$$8944 := (-T(8) + T(F(9))) \times 4 \times 4$$

$$89440 := (-T(8) + T(F(9))) \times 4 \times 40$$

$$894400 := (-T(8) + T(F(9))) \times 4 \times 400$$

$$8944000 := (-T(8) + T(F(9))) \times 4 \times 4000$$

1443.

$$8944 := (-T(8) + T(F(9))) \times 4 \times 4$$

$$89440 := (-T(8) + T(F(9))) \times 4 \times 40$$

$$894400 := (-T(8) + T(F(9))) \times 4 \times 400$$

$$8944000 := (-T(8) + T(F(9))) \times 4 \times 4000$$

1444.

$$8952 := (Q(Q(8) + F(\sqrt{9})) + 5!) \times 2$$

$$89520 := (Q(Q(8) + F(\sqrt{9})) + 5!) \times 20$$

$$895200 := (Q(Q(8) + F(\sqrt{9})) + 5!) \times 200$$

$$8952000 := (Q(Q(8) + F(\sqrt{9})) + 5!) \times 2000$$

1445.

$$8955 := (T(T(8)) + 9 \times C(5)) \times 5$$

$$89550 := (T(T(8)) + 9 \times C(5)) \times 50$$

$$895500 := (T(T(8)) + 9 \times C(5)) \times 500$$

$$8955000 := (T(T(8)) + 9 \times C(5)) \times 5000$$

1446.

$$8967 := (Q(8) - \sqrt{9}) \times T(6) \times 7$$

$$89670 := (Q(8) - \sqrt{9}) \times T(6) \times 70$$

$$896700 := (Q(8) - \sqrt{9}) \times T(6) \times 700$$

$$8967000 := (Q(8) - \sqrt{9}) \times T(6) \times 7000$$

1447.

$$8992 := -(Q(T(8)) + 9!)/(-Q(9)) \times 2$$

$$89920 := -(Q(T(8)) + 9!)/(-Q(9)) \times 20$$

$$899200 := -(Q(T(8)) + 9!)/(-Q(9)) \times 200$$

$$8992000 := -(Q(T(8)) + 9!)/(-Q(9)) \times 2000$$

1448.

$$8995 := (C(8) - 9 + Q(Q((\sqrt{9}!))) \times 5$$

$$89950 := (C(8) - 9 + Q(Q((\sqrt{9}!))) \times 50$$

$$899500 := (C(8) - 9 + Q(Q((\sqrt{9}!))) \times 500$$

$$8995000 := (C(8) - 9 + Q(Q((\sqrt{9}!))) \times 5000$$

1449.

$$9009 := (C(9 + 0!) + 0!) \times 9$$

$$90090 := (C(9 + 0!) + 0!) \times 90$$

$$900900 := (C(9 + 0!) + 0!) \times 900$$

$$9009000 := (C(9 + 0!) + 0!) \times 9000$$

1450.

$$\begin{aligned}9037 &:= (-\sqrt{9})! + 0! + Q(Q(3!)) \times 7 \\90370 &:= (-\sqrt{9})! + 0! + Q(Q(3!)) \times 70 \\903700 &:= (-\sqrt{9})! + 0! + Q(Q(3!)) \times 700 \\9037000 &:= (-\sqrt{9})! + 0! + Q(Q(3!)) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

1451.

$$\begin{aligned}9037 &:= (T(T(9)) + Q(Q(0! + 3))) \times 7 \\90370 &:= (T(T(9)) + Q(Q(0! + 3))) \times 70 \\903700 &:= (T(T(9)) + Q(Q(0! + 3))) \times 700 \\9037000 &:= (T(T(9)) + Q(Q(0! + 3))) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

1452.

$$\begin{aligned}9044 &:= (T(\sqrt{9})! + 0! + T(T(T(4)))) \times 4 \\90440 &:= (T(\sqrt{9})! + 0! + T(T(T(4)))) \times 40 \\904400 &:= (T(\sqrt{9})! + 0! + T(T(T(4)))) \times 400 \\9044000 &:= (T(\sqrt{9})! + 0! + T(T(T(4)))) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

1453.

$$\begin{aligned}9045 &:= (Q(F(9) - 0!) + F(4)!) \times 5 \\90450 &:= (Q(F(9) - 0!) + F(4)!) \times 50 \\904500 &:= (Q(F(9) - 0!) + F(4)!) \times 500 \\9045000 &:= (Q(F(9) - 0!) + F(4)!) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1454.

$$\begin{aligned}9048 &:= (Q(F(9)) - 0! - 4!) \times 8 \\90480 &:= (Q(F(9)) - 0! - 4!) \times 80 \\904800 &:= (Q(F(9)) - 0! - 4!) \times 800 \\9048000 &:= (Q(F(9)) - 0! - 4!) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

1455.

$$\begin{aligned}9088 &:= (Q(F(9)) + 0! - F(8)) \times 8 \\90880 &:= (Q(F(9)) + 0! - F(8)) \times 80 \\908800 &:= (Q(F(9)) + 0! - F(8)) \times 800 \\9088000 &:= (Q(F(9)) + 0! - F(8)) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

1456.

$$\begin{aligned}9123 &:= (Q(F(9 + 1)) + Q(Q(2))) \times 3 \\91230 &:= (Q(F(9 + 1)) + Q(Q(2))) \times 30 \\912300 &:= (Q(F(9 + 1)) + Q(Q(2))) \times 300 \\9123000 &:= (Q(F(9 + 1)) + Q(Q(2))) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

1457.

$$\begin{aligned}9123 &:= (Q(T(9 + 1)) + Q(Q(2))) \times 3 \\91230 &:= (Q(T(9 + 1)) + Q(Q(2))) \times 30 \\912300 &:= (Q(T(9 + 1)) + Q(Q(2))) \times 300 \\9123000 &:= (Q(T(9 + 1)) + Q(Q(2))) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

1458.

$$\begin{aligned}9126 &:= Q(-Q(9) + (1 + Q(2))!) \times 6 \\91260 &:= Q(-Q(9) + (1 + Q(2))!) \times 60 \\912600 &:= Q(-Q(9) + (1 + Q(2))!) \times 600 \\9126000 &:= Q(-Q(9) + (1 + Q(2))!) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1459.

$$\begin{aligned}9128 &:= (Q(F(9)) + 1 - Q(Q(2))) \times 8 \\91280 &:= (Q(F(9)) + 1 - Q(Q(2))) \times 80 \\912800 &:= (Q(F(9)) + 1 - Q(Q(2))) \times 800 \\9128000 &:= (Q(F(9)) + 1 - Q(Q(2))) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

1460.

$$\begin{aligned} 9183 &:= (-T(T(9)) + Q(Q(8))) \times 3 \\ 91830 &:= (-T(T(9)) + Q(Q(8))) \times 30 \\ 918300 &:= (-T(T(9)) + Q(Q(8))) \times 300 \\ 9183000 &:= (-T(T(9)) + Q(Q(8))) \times 3000 \end{aligned}$$

1461.

$$\begin{aligned} 9184 &:= (T(C(\sqrt{9} + 1)) + C(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 4 \\ 91840 &:= (T(C(\sqrt{9} + 1)) + C(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 40 \\ 918400 &:= (T(C(\sqrt{9} + 1)) + C(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 400 \\ 9184000 &:= (T(C(\sqrt{9} + 1)) + C(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

1462.

$$\begin{aligned} 9189 &:= (C(9 + 1) + F(8)) \times 9 \\ 91890 &:= (C(9 + 1) + F(8)) \times 90 \\ 918900 &:= (C(9 + 1) + F(8)) \times 900 \\ 9189000 &:= (C(9 + 1) + F(8)) \times 9000 \end{aligned}$$

1463.

$$\begin{aligned} 9208 &:= (Q(F(9)) - Q(2) - 0!) \times 8 \\ 92080 &:= (Q(F(9)) - Q(2) - 0!) \times 80 \\ 920800 &:= (Q(F(9)) - Q(2) - 0!) \times 800 \\ 9208000 &:= (Q(F(9)) - Q(2) - 0!) \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

1464.

$$\begin{aligned} 9213 &:= ((\sqrt{9})! \times C(C(2)) - 1) \times 3 \\ 92130 &:= ((\sqrt{9})! \times C(C(2)) - 1) \times 30 \\ 921300 &:= ((\sqrt{9})! \times C(C(2)) - 1) \times 300 \\ 9213000 &:= ((\sqrt{9})! \times C(C(2)) - 1) \times 3000 \end{aligned}$$

1465.

$$\begin{aligned} 9216 &:= \sqrt{9} \times C(C(2 \times 1)) \times 6 \\ 92160 &:= \sqrt{9} \times C(C(2 \times 1)) \times 60 \\ 921600 &:= \sqrt{9} \times C(C(2 \times 1)) \times 600 \\ 9216000 &:= \sqrt{9} \times C(C(2 \times 1)) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

1466.

$$\begin{aligned} 9224 &:= (9 \times Q(Q(Q(2))) + 2) \times 4 \\ 92240 &:= (9 \times Q(Q(Q(2))) + 2) \times 40 \\ 922400 &:= (9 \times Q(Q(Q(2))) + 2) \times 400 \\ 9224000 &:= (9 \times Q(Q(Q(2))) + 2) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

1467.

$$\begin{aligned} 9242 &:= (-\sqrt{9} + Q(Q(2) + C(4))) \times 2 \\ 92420 &:= (-\sqrt{9} + Q(Q(2) + C(4))) \times 20 \\ 924200 &:= (-\sqrt{9} + Q(Q(2) + C(4))) \times 200 \\ 9242000 &:= (-\sqrt{9} + Q(Q(2) + C(4))) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1468.

$$\begin{aligned} 9242 &:= (T(T(9 + T(2))) + T(F(T(4)))) \times 2 \\ 92420 &:= (T(T(9 + T(2))) + T(F(T(4)))) \times 20 \\ 924200 &:= (T(T(9 + T(2))) + T(F(T(4)))) \times 200 \\ 9242000 &:= (T(T(9 + T(2))) + T(F(T(4)))) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1469.

$$\begin{aligned} 9244 &:= (Q(F(9)) \times 2 - F(\sqrt{4})) \times 4 \\ 92440 &:= (Q(F(9)) \times 2 - F(\sqrt{4})) \times 40 \\ 924400 &:= (Q(F(9)) \times 2 - F(\sqrt{4})) \times 400 \\ 9244000 &:= (Q(F(9)) \times 2 - F(\sqrt{4})) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

1470.

$$\begin{aligned} 9245 &:= (C(\sqrt{9}) + Q(Q(2)))^{\sqrt{4}} \times 5 \\ 92450 &:= (C(\sqrt{9}) + Q(Q(2)))^{\sqrt{4}} \times 50 \\ 924500 &:= (C(\sqrt{9}) + Q(Q(2)))^{\sqrt{4}} \times 500 \\ 9245000 &:= (C(\sqrt{9}) + Q(Q(2)))^{\sqrt{4}} \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1471.

$$\begin{aligned} 9245 &:= (T(9) - 2)^{F(F(4))} \times 5 \\ 92450 &:= (T(9) - 2)^{F(F(4))} \times 50 \\ 924500 &:= (T(9) - 2)^{F(F(4))} \times 500 \\ 9245000 &:= (T(9) - 2)^{F(F(4))} \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1472.

$$\begin{aligned} 9245 &:= (T(9) - 2)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 5 \\ 92450 &:= (T(9) - 2)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 50 \\ 924500 &:= (T(9) - 2)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 500 \\ 9245000 &:= (T(9) - 2)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1473.

$$\begin{aligned} 9246 &:= (C(9) + C(C(2)) + T(4!)) \times 6 \\ 92460 &:= (C(9) + C(C(2)) + T(4!)) \times 60 \\ 924600 &:= (C(9) + C(C(2)) + T(4!)) \times 600 \\ 9246000 &:= (C(9) + C(C(2)) + T(4!)) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

1474.

$$\begin{aligned} 9246 &:= (F(F(9/T(2))) + T(F(T(4)))) \times 6 \\ 92460 &:= (F(F(9/T(2))) + T(F(T(4)))) \times 60 \\ 924600 &:= (F(F(9/T(2))) + T(F(T(4)))) \times 600 \\ 9246000 &:= (F(F(9/T(2))) + T(F(T(4)))) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

1475.

$$\begin{aligned} 9247 &:= (C(9) + Q(Q(2)) + Q(4!)) \times 7 \\ 92470 &:= (C(9) + Q(Q(2)) + Q(4!)) \times 70 \\ 924700 &:= (C(9) + Q(Q(2)) + Q(4!)) \times 700 \\ 9247000 &:= (C(9) + Q(Q(2)) + Q(4!)) \times 7000 \end{aligned}$$

1476.

$$\begin{aligned} 9247 &:= (C(9 + 2) - T(4)) \times 7 \\ 92470 &:= (C(9 + 2) - T(4)) \times 70 \\ 924700 &:= (C(9 + 2) - T(4)) \times 700 \\ 9247000 &:= (C(9 + 2) - T(4)) \times 7000 \end{aligned}$$

1477.

$$\begin{aligned} 9247 &:= (T(F(9)) + T(T(2)) + T(F(4)!)) \times 7 \\ 92470 &:= (T(F(9)) + T(T(2)) + T(F(4)!)) \times 70 \\ 924700 &:= (T(F(9)) + T(T(2)) + T(F(4)!)) \times 700 \\ 9247000 &:= (T(F(9)) + T(T(2)) + T(F(4)!)) \times 7000 \end{aligned}$$

1478.

$$\begin{aligned} 9248 &:= (-T(\sqrt{9}) - T(C(T(2))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 8 \\ 92480 &:= (-T(\sqrt{9}) - T(C(T(2))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 80 \\ 924800 &:= (-T(\sqrt{9}) - T(C(T(2))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 800 \\ 9248000 &:= (-T(\sqrt{9}) - T(C(T(2))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

1479.

$$\begin{aligned} 9248 &:= F(9)^{-2+4} \times 8 \\ 92480 &:= F(9)^{-2+4} \times 80 \\ 924800 &:= F(9)^{-2+4} \times 800 \\ 9248000 &:= F(9)^{-2+4} \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

1480.

$$\begin{aligned} 9248 &:= Q(9 \times 2 + Q(4)) \times 8 \\ 92480 &:= Q(9 \times 2 + Q(4)) \times 80 \\ 924800 &:= Q(9 \times 2 + Q(4)) \times 800 \\ 9248000 &:= Q(9 \times 2 + Q(4)) \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

1481.

$$\begin{aligned} 9275 &:= (9 + Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times 7 \times 5 \\ 92750 &:= (9 + Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times 7 \times 50 \\ 927500 &:= (9 + Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times 7 \times 500 \\ 9275000 &:= (9 + Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times 7 \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1482.

$$\begin{aligned} 9275 &:= (9 + Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times 7 \times 5 \\ 92750 &:= (9 + Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times 7 \times 50 \\ 927500 &:= (9 + Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times 7 \times 500 \\ 9275000 &:= (9 + Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times 7 \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1483.

$$\begin{aligned} 9276 &:= (T(\sqrt{9}) + T(T(T(2) + 7))) \times 6 \\ 92760 &:= (T(\sqrt{9}) + T(T(T(2) + 7))) \times 60 \\ 927600 &:= (T(\sqrt{9}) + T(T(T(2) + 7))) \times 600 \\ 9276000 &:= (T(\sqrt{9}) + T(T(T(2) + 7))) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

1484.

$$\begin{aligned} 9279 &:= (Q(F(9) - 2) + 7) \times 9 \\ 92790 &:= (Q(F(9) - 2) + 7) \times 90 \\ 927900 &:= (Q(F(9) - 2) + 7) \times 900 \\ 9279000 &:= (Q(F(9) - 2) + 7) \times 9000 \end{aligned}$$

1485.

$$\begin{aligned} 9279 &:= (T(T(9)) + T(2) - 7) \times 9 \\ 92790 &:= (T(T(9)) + T(2) - 7) \times 90 \\ 927900 &:= (T(T(9)) + T(2) - 7) \times 900 \\ 9279000 &:= (T(T(9)) + T(2) - 7) \times 9000 \end{aligned}$$

1486.

$$\begin{aligned} 9279 &:= (T(T(9)) - \sqrt{T(2) + F(7)}) \times 9 \\ 92790 &:= (T(T(9)) - \sqrt{T(2) + F(7)}) \times 90 \\ 927900 &:= (T(T(9)) - \sqrt{T(2) + F(7)}) \times 900 \\ 9279000 &:= (T(T(9)) - \sqrt{T(2) + F(7)}) \times 9000 \end{aligned}$$

1487.

$$\begin{aligned} 9317 &:= (F(\sqrt{9}) \times T(T(F(T(3)))) - 1) \times 7 \\ 93170 &:= (F(\sqrt{9}) \times T(T(F(T(3)))) - 1) \times 70 \\ 931700 &:= (F(\sqrt{9}) \times T(T(F(T(3)))) - 1) \times 700 \\ 9317000 &:= (F(\sqrt{9}) \times T(T(F(T(3)))) - 1) \times 7000 \end{aligned}$$

1488.

$$\begin{aligned} 9317 &:= (Q((\sqrt{9})!) + Q(Q(3!)) - 1) \times 7 \\ 93170 &:= (Q((\sqrt{9})!) + Q(Q(3!)) - 1) \times 70 \\ 931700 &:= (Q((\sqrt{9})!) + Q(Q(3!)) - 1) \times 700 \\ 9317000 &:= (Q((\sqrt{9})!) + Q(Q(3!)) - 1) \times 7000 \end{aligned}$$

1489.

$$\begin{aligned} 9317 &:= (Q(T(\sqrt{9})) + Q(Q(T(3))) - 1) \times 7 \\ 93170 &:= (Q(T(\sqrt{9})) + Q(Q(T(3))) - 1) \times 70 \\ 931700 &:= (Q(T(\sqrt{9})) + Q(Q(T(3))) - 1) \times 700 \\ 9317000 &:= (Q(T(\sqrt{9})) + Q(Q(T(3))) - 1) \times 7000 \end{aligned}$$

1490.

$$\begin{aligned} 9317 &:= C(9 + 3 - 1) \times 7 \\ 93170 &:= C(9 + 3 - 1) \times 70 \\ 931700 &:= C(9 + 3 - 1) \times 700 \\ 9317000 &:= C(9 + 3 - 1) \times 7000 \end{aligned}$$

1491.

$$\begin{aligned} 9333 &:= (T(T(9)) \times 3 + T(3)) \times 3 \\ 93330 &:= (T(T(9)) \times 3 + T(3)) \times 30 \\ 933300 &:= (T(T(9)) \times 3 + T(3)) \times 300 \\ 9333000 &:= (T(T(9)) \times 3 + T(3)) \times 3000 \end{aligned}$$

1492.

$$\begin{aligned} 9333 &:= (T(T(9)) + F(3)) \times 3 \times 3 \\ 93330 &:= (T(T(9)) + F(3)) \times 3 \times 30 \\ 933300 &:= (T(T(9)) + F(3)) \times 3 \times 300 \\ 9333000 &:= (T(T(9)) + F(3)) \times 3 \times 3000 \end{aligned}$$

1493.

$$\begin{aligned} 9333 &:= (T(T(9)) + F(3)) \times 3 \times 3 \\ 93330 &:= (T(T(9)) + F(3)) \times 3 \times 30 \\ 933300 &:= (T(T(9)) + F(3)) \times 3 \times 300 \\ 9333000 &:= (T(T(9)) + F(3)) \times 3 \times 3000 \end{aligned}$$

1494.

$$\begin{aligned} 9335 &:= (Q(F(9)) - Q(3) + 3!) \times 5 \\ 93350 &:= (Q(F(9)) - Q(3) + 3!) \times 50 \\ 933500 &:= (Q(F(9)) - Q(3) + 3!) \times 500 \\ 9335000 &:= (Q(F(9)) - Q(3) + 3!) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1495.

$$\begin{aligned} 9344 &:= (Q(Q(9)) - Q(Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) \times 4 \\ 93440 &:= (Q(Q(9)) - Q(Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) \times 40 \\ 934400 &:= (Q(Q(9)) - Q(Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) \times 400 \\ 9344000 &:= (Q(Q(9)) - Q(Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

1496.

$$\begin{aligned} 9344 &:= (T(F(9) \times F(3)) - T(4)) \times 4 \\ 93440 &:= (T(F(9) \times F(3)) - T(4)) \times 40 \\ 934400 &:= (T(F(9) \times F(3)) - T(4)) \times 400 \\ 9344000 &:= (T(F(9) \times F(3)) - T(4)) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

1497.

$$\begin{aligned} 9345 &:= F(9 + F(3)) \times F(F(F(4)!)) \times 5 \\ 93450 &:= F(9 + F(3)) \times F(F(F(4)!)) \times 50 \\ 934500 &:= F(9 + F(3)) \times F(F(F(4)!)) \times 500 \\ 9345000 &:= F(9 + F(3)) \times F(F(F(4)!)) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1498.

$$\begin{aligned} 9345 &:= F(9 + F(3)) \times F(\sqrt{C(4)}) \times 5 \\ 93450 &:= F(9 + F(3)) \times F(\sqrt{C(4)}) \times 50 \\ 934500 &:= F(9 + F(3)) \times F(\sqrt{C(4)}) \times 500 \\ 9345000 &:= F(9 + F(3)) \times F(\sqrt{C(4)}) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1499.

$$\begin{aligned} 9345 &:= F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \times F(F(3!) + F(4)) \times 5 \\ 93450 &:= F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \times F(F(3!) + F(4)) \times 50 \\ 934500 &:= F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \times F(F(3!) + F(4)) \times 500 \\ 9345000 &:= F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \times F(F(3!) + F(4)) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1500.

$$\begin{aligned}9366 &:= (F(F(9)/F(3)) - T(F(6))) \times 6 \\93660 &:= (F(F(9)/F(3)) - T(F(6))) \times 60 \\936600 &:= (F(F(9)/F(3)) - T(F(6))) \times 600 \\9366000 &:= (F(F(9)/F(3)) - T(F(6))) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1501.

$$\begin{aligned}9368 &:= (T(T(9)) + T(F(3) \times F(6))) \times 8 \\93680 &:= (T(T(9)) + T(F(3) \times F(6))) \times 80 \\936800 &:= (T(T(9)) + T(F(3) \times F(6))) \times 800 \\9368000 &:= (T(T(9)) + T(F(3) \times F(6))) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

1502.

$$\begin{aligned}9369 &:= (T(T(9)) + T(-(3 - 6))) \times 9 \\93690 &:= (T(T(9)) + T(-(3 - 6))) \times 90 \\936900 &:= (T(T(9)) + T(-(3 - 6))) \times 900 \\9369000 &:= (T(T(9)) + T(-(3 - 6))) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

1503.

$$\begin{aligned}9387 &:= (-T(9) + T(3)! + T(T(8))) \times 7 \\93870 &:= (-T(9) + T(3)! + T(T(8))) \times 70 \\938700 &:= (-T(9) + T(3)! + T(T(8))) \times 700 \\9387000 &:= (-T(9) + T(3)! + T(T(8))) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

1504.

$$\begin{aligned}9387 &:= (-T(9) + T(3) \times T(F(8))) \times 7 \\93870 &:= (-T(9) + T(3) \times T(F(8))) \times 70 \\938700 &:= (-T(9) + T(3) \times T(F(8))) \times 700 \\9387000 &:= (-T(9) + T(3) \times T(F(8))) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

1505.

$$\begin{aligned}9387 &:= (T(Q(9/3)) + Q(T(8))) \times 7 \\93870 &:= (T(Q(9/3)) + Q(T(8))) \times 70 \\938700 &:= (T(Q(9/3)) + Q(T(8))) \times 700 \\9387000 &:= (T(Q(9/3)) + Q(T(8))) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

1506.

$$\begin{aligned}9392 &:= (C((\sqrt{9})!) + Q(3)!/Q(9)) \times 2 \\93920 &:= (C((\sqrt{9})!) + Q(3)!/Q(9)) \times 20 \\939200 &:= (C((\sqrt{9})!) + Q(3)!/Q(9)) \times 200 \\9392000 &:= (C((\sqrt{9})!) + Q(3)!/Q(9)) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1507.

$$\begin{aligned}9395 &:= (\sqrt{9} + 3!! + Q(F(9))) \times 5 \\93950 &:= (\sqrt{9} + 3!! + Q(F(9))) \times 50 \\939500 &:= (\sqrt{9} + 3!! + Q(F(9))) \times 500 \\9395000 &:= (\sqrt{9} + 3!! + Q(F(9))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1508.

$$\begin{aligned}9408 &:= T(\sqrt{9} \times Q(4)) \times 08 \\94080 &:= T(\sqrt{9} \times Q(4)) \times 080 \\940800 &:= T(\sqrt{9} \times Q(4)) \times 0800 \\9408000 &:= T(\sqrt{9} \times Q(4)) \times 08000\end{aligned}$$

1509.

$$\begin{aligned}9408 &:= T(T(9) + 4 - 0!) \times 8 \\94080 &:= T(T(9) + 4 - 0!) \times 80 \\940800 &:= T(T(9) + 4 - 0!) \times 800 \\9408000 &:= T(T(9) + 4 - 0!) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

1510.

$$\begin{aligned}9408 &:= T(T(9) + F(4)) \times 08 \\94080 &:= T(T(9) + F(4)) \times 080 \\940800 &:= T(T(9) + F(4)) \times 0800 \\9408000 &:= T(T(9) + F(4)) \times 08000\end{aligned}$$

1511.

$$\begin{aligned}9408 &:= T(T(9) + \sqrt{4} + 0!) \times 8 \\94080 &:= T(T(9) + \sqrt{4} + 0!) \times 80 \\940800 &:= T(T(9) + \sqrt{4} + 0!) \times 800 \\9408000 &:= T(T(9) + \sqrt{4} + 0!) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

1512.

$$\begin{aligned}9408 &:= T(T(9) + T(\sqrt{4})) \times 08 \\94080 &:= T(T(9) + T(\sqrt{4})) \times 080 \\940800 &:= T(T(9) + T(\sqrt{4})) \times 0800 \\9408000 &:= T(T(9) + T(\sqrt{4})) \times 08000\end{aligned}$$

1513.

$$\begin{aligned}9425 &:= (-T(\sqrt{9}) + T(T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))) \times 5 \\94250 &:= (-T(\sqrt{9}) + T(T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))) \times 50 \\942500 &:= (-T(\sqrt{9}) + T(T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))) \times 500 \\9425000 &:= (-T(\sqrt{9}) + T(T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1514.

$$\begin{aligned}9426 &:= (F(9) + T(F(T(4))) - T(2)) \times 6 \\94260 &:= (F(9) + T(F(T(4))) - T(2)) \times 60 \\942600 &:= (F(9) + T(F(T(4))) - T(2)) \times 600 \\9426000 &:= (F(9) + T(F(T(4))) - T(2)) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1515.

$$\begin{aligned}9442 &:= (Q(Q(9 - 4)) + Q(C(4))) \times 2 \\94420 &:= (Q(Q(9 - 4)) + Q(C(4))) \times 20 \\944200 &:= (Q(Q(9 - 4)) + Q(C(4))) \times 200 \\9442000 &:= (Q(Q(9 - 4)) + Q(C(4))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1516.

$$\begin{aligned}9442 &:= (T(94) + Q(Q(4))) \times 2 \\94420 &:= (T(94) + Q(Q(4))) \times 20 \\944200 &:= (T(94) + Q(Q(4))) \times 200 \\9442000 &:= (T(94) + Q(Q(4))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1517.

$$\begin{aligned}9444 &:= (T(T(9)) + T(-4 + T(T(4)))) \times 4 \\94440 &:= (T(T(9)) + T(-4 + T(T(4)))) \times 40 \\944400 &:= (T(T(9)) + T(-4 + T(T(4)))) \times 400 \\9444000 &:= (T(T(9)) + T(-4 + T(T(4)))) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

1518.

$$\begin{aligned}9448 &:= (Q(F(9)) + Q(\sqrt{4} + F(4))) \times 8 \\94480 &:= (Q(F(9)) + Q(\sqrt{4} + F(4))) \times 80 \\944800 &:= (Q(F(9)) + Q(\sqrt{4} + F(4))) \times 800 \\9448000 &:= (Q(F(9)) + Q(\sqrt{4} + F(4))) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

1519.

$$\begin{aligned}9448 &:= (T(T(9)) + T(4) + T(Q(4))) \times 8 \\94480 &:= (T(T(9)) + T(4) + T(Q(4))) \times 80 \\944800 &:= (T(T(9)) + T(4) + T(Q(4))) \times 800 \\9448000 &:= (T(T(9)) + T(4) + T(Q(4))) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

1520.

$$9450 := 9 \times F(F(F(4)!)) \times 50$$

$$94500 := 9 \times F(F(F(4)!)) \times 500$$

$$945000 := 9 \times F(F(F(4)!)) \times 5000$$

$$9450000 := 9 \times F(F(F(4)!)) \times 50000$$

1521.

$$9450 := 9 \times F(\sqrt{C(4)}) \times 50$$

$$94500 := 9 \times F(\sqrt{C(4)}) \times 500$$

$$945000 := 9 \times F(\sqrt{C(4)}) \times 5000$$

$$9450000 := 9 \times F(\sqrt{C(4)}) \times 50000$$

1522.

$$9450 := F(F((\sqrt{9}!)) \times 450$$

$$94500 := F(F((\sqrt{9}!)) \times 4500$$

$$945000 := F(F((\sqrt{9}!)) \times 45000$$

$$9450000 := F(F((\sqrt{9}!)) \times 450000$$

1523.

$$9459 := (C(\sqrt{9}) + 4^5) \times 9$$

$$94590 := (C(\sqrt{9}) + 4^5) \times 90$$

$$945900 := (C(\sqrt{9}) + 4^5) \times 900$$

$$9459000 := (C(\sqrt{9}) + 4^5) \times 9000$$

1524.

$$9459 := (\sqrt{C(9)} + 4^5) \times 9$$

$$94590 := (\sqrt{C(9)} + 4^5) \times 90$$

$$945900 := (\sqrt{C(9)} + 4^5) \times 900$$

$$9459000 := (\sqrt{C(9)} + 4^5) \times 9000$$

1525.

$$9462 := (Q(Q(9)) - T(6 \times T(4))) \times 2$$

$$94620 := (Q(Q(9)) - T(6 \times T(4))) \times 20$$

$$946200 := (Q(Q(9)) - T(6 \times T(4))) \times 200$$

$$9462000 := (Q(Q(9)) - T(6 \times T(4))) \times 2000$$

1526.

$$9464 := (-F(9) + T(4!) \times F(6)) \times 4$$

$$94640 := (-F(9) + T(4!) \times F(6)) \times 40$$

$$946400 := (-F(9) + T(4!) \times F(6)) \times 400$$

$$9464000 := (-F(9) + T(4!) \times F(6)) \times 4000$$

1527.

$$9464 := (T(F(9)) + T(F(T(4))) + T(T(6))) \times 4$$

$$94640 := (T(F(9)) + T(F(T(4))) + T(T(6))) \times 40$$

$$946400 := (T(F(9)) + T(F(T(4))) + T(T(6))) \times 400$$

$$9464000 := (T(F(9)) + T(F(T(4))) + T(T(6))) \times 4000$$

1528.

$$9465 := (-C(\sqrt{9}) - (\sqrt{C(4)!}/(-F(F(6)))) \times 5$$

$$94650 := (-C(\sqrt{9}) - (\sqrt{C(4)!}/(-F(F(6)))) \times 50$$

$$946500 := (-C(\sqrt{9}) - (\sqrt{C(4)!}/(-F(F(6)))) \times 500$$

$$9465000 := (-C(\sqrt{9}) - (\sqrt{C(4)!}/(-F(F(6)))) \times 5000$$

1529.

$$9475 := (Q(9) \times 4! - Q(7)) \times 5$$

$$94750 := (Q(9) \times 4! - Q(7)) \times 50$$

$$947500 := (Q(9) \times 4! - Q(7)) \times 500$$

$$9475000 := (Q(9) \times 4! - Q(7)) \times 5000$$

1530.

$$\begin{aligned} 9484 &:= (-9 + T(4!) + T(Q(8))) \times 4 \\ 94840 &:= (-9 + T(4!) + T(Q(8))) \times 40 \\ 948400 &:= (-9 + T(4!) + T(Q(8))) \times 400 \\ 9484000 &:= (-9 + T(4!) + T(Q(8))) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

1531.

$$\begin{aligned} 9485 &:= (Q(F(9)) + F(4)!! + F(8)) \times 5 \\ 94850 &:= (Q(F(9)) + F(4)!! + F(8)) \times 50 \\ 948500 &:= (Q(F(9)) + F(4)!! + F(8)) \times 500 \\ 9485000 &:= (Q(F(9)) + F(4)!! + F(8)) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1532.

$$\begin{aligned} 9485 &:= (Q(T(9)) - \sqrt{4} \times Q(8)) \times 5 \\ 94850 &:= (Q(T(9)) - \sqrt{4} \times Q(8)) \times 50 \\ 948500 &:= (Q(T(9)) - \sqrt{4} \times Q(8)) \times 500 \\ 9485000 &:= (Q(T(9)) - \sqrt{4} \times Q(8)) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1533.

$$\begin{aligned} 9486 &:= (Q(F(9)) - Q(4) + Q(F(8))) \times 6 \\ 94860 &:= (Q(F(9)) - Q(4) + Q(F(8))) \times 60 \\ 948600 &:= (Q(F(9)) - Q(4) + Q(F(8))) \times 600 \\ 9486000 &:= (Q(F(9)) - Q(4) + Q(F(8))) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

1534.

$$\begin{aligned} 9486 &:= (T(9) + 4! \times Q(8)) \times 6 \\ 94860 &:= (T(9) + 4! \times Q(8)) \times 60 \\ 948600 &:= (T(9) + 4! \times Q(8)) \times 600 \\ 9486000 &:= (T(9) + 4! \times Q(8)) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

1535.

$$\begin{aligned} 9488 &:= (C(9) - T(T(4)) + C(8)) \times 8 \\ 94880 &:= (C(9) - T(T(4)) + C(8)) \times 80 \\ 948800 &:= (C(9) - T(T(4)) + C(8)) \times 800 \\ 9488000 &:= (C(9) - T(T(4)) + C(8)) \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

1536.

$$\begin{aligned} 9488 &:= (T(Q(9)) - T(T(4)) - T(Q(8))) \times 8 \\ 94880 &:= (T(Q(9)) - T(T(4)) - T(Q(8))) \times 80 \\ 948800 &:= (T(Q(9)) - T(T(4)) - T(Q(8))) \times 800 \\ 9488000 &:= (T(Q(9)) - T(T(4)) - T(Q(8))) \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

1537.

$$\begin{aligned} 9495 &:= (F((\sqrt{9})!) / F(F(F(4)!)) - F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) \times 5 \\ 94950 &:= (F((\sqrt{9})!) / F(F(F(4)!)) - F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) \times 50 \\ 949500 &:= (F((\sqrt{9})!) / F(F(F(4)!)) - F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) \times 500 \\ 9495000 &:= (F((\sqrt{9})!) / F(F(F(4)!)) - F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1538.

$$\begin{aligned} 9495 &:= (Q(9) \times 4! - T(9)) \times 5 \\ 94950 &:= (Q(9) \times 4! - T(9)) \times 50 \\ 949500 &:= (Q(9) \times 4! - T(9)) \times 500 \\ 9495000 &:= (Q(9) \times 4! - T(9)) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1539.

$$\begin{aligned} 9522 &:= (9 \times Q(Q(5) - 2)) \times 2 \\ 95220 &:= (9 \times Q(Q(5) - 2)) \times 20 \\ 952200 &:= (9 \times Q(Q(5) - 2)) \times 200 \\ 9522000 &:= (9 \times Q(Q(5) - 2)) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1540.

$$\begin{aligned}9522 &:= (9 \times Q(Q(5) - 2)) \times 2 \\95220 &:= (9 \times Q(Q(5) - 2)) \times 20 \\952200 &:= (9 \times Q(Q(5) - 2)) \times 200 \\9522000 &:= (9 \times Q(Q(5) - 2)) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1541.

$$\begin{aligned}9522 &:= (T(T(9))/T(5))^2 \times 2 \\95220 &:= (T(T(9))/T(5))^2 \times 20 \\952200 &:= (T(T(9))/T(5))^2 \times 200 \\9522000 &:= (T(T(9))/T(5))^2 \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1542.

$$\begin{aligned}9527 &:= ((\sqrt{9})!! + Q(Q(5)) + Q(Q(2))) \times 7 \\95270 &:= ((\sqrt{9})!! + Q(Q(5)) + Q(Q(2))) \times 70 \\952700 &:= ((\sqrt{9})!! + Q(Q(5)) + Q(Q(2))) \times 700 \\9527000 &:= ((\sqrt{9})!! + Q(Q(5)) + Q(Q(2))) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

1543.

$$\begin{aligned}9527 &:= (C(9) + 5! + C(C(2))) \times 7 \\95270 &:= (C(9) + 5! + C(C(2))) \times 70 \\952700 &:= (C(9) + 5! + C(C(2))) \times 700 \\9527000 &:= (C(9) + 5! + C(C(2))) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

1544.

$$\begin{aligned}9527 &:= (Q(9) + 5 \times Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times 7 \\95270 &:= (Q(9) + 5 \times Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times 70 \\952700 &:= (Q(9) + 5 \times Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times 700 \\9527000 &:= (Q(9) + 5 \times Q(Q(Q(2)))) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

1545.

$$\begin{aligned}9528 &:= (T(T(9)) + 5! + T(C(2))) \times 8 \\95280 &:= (T(T(9)) + 5! + T(C(2))) \times 80 \\952800 &:= (T(T(9)) + 5! + T(C(2))) \times 800 \\9528000 &:= (T(T(9)) + 5! + T(C(2))) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

1546.

$$\begin{aligned}9543 &:= (9 \times T(Q(5)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 3 \\95430 &:= (9 \times T(Q(5)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 30 \\954300 &:= (9 \times T(Q(5)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 300 \\9543000 &:= (9 \times T(Q(5)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

1547.

$$\begin{aligned}9543 &:= (Q(F(9)) + Q(5 \times Q(F(4)))) \times 3 \\95430 &:= (Q(F(9)) + Q(5 \times Q(F(4)))) \times 30 \\954300 &:= (Q(F(9)) + Q(5 \times Q(F(4)))) \times 300 \\9543000 &:= (Q(F(9)) + Q(5 \times Q(F(4)))) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

1548.

$$\begin{aligned}9545 &:= (F(9) + Q(Q(5)) \times F(4)) \times 5 \\95450 &:= (F(9) + Q(Q(5)) \times F(4)) \times 50 \\954500 &:= (F(9) + Q(Q(5)) \times F(4)) \times 500 \\9545000 &:= (F(9) + Q(Q(5)) \times F(4)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1549.

$$\begin{aligned}9545 &:= (Q(T(9)) - 5! + 4) \times 5 \\95450 &:= (Q(T(9)) - 5! + 4) \times 50 \\954500 &:= (Q(T(9)) - 5! + 4) \times 500 \\9545000 &:= (Q(T(9)) - 5! + 4) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1550.

$$\begin{aligned}9546 &:= (-9 + Q(5!/F(4))) \times 6 \\95460 &:= (-9 + Q(5!/F(4))) \times 60 \\954600 &:= (-9 + Q(5!/F(4))) \times 600 \\9546000 &:= (-9 + Q(5!/F(4))) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1551.

$$\begin{aligned}9546 &:= (-9 + Q(5) \times C(4)) \times 6 \\95460 &:= (-9 + Q(5) \times C(4)) \times 60 \\954600 &:= (-9 + Q(5) \times C(4)) \times 600 \\9546000 &:= (-9 + Q(5) \times C(4)) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1552.

$$\begin{aligned}9549 &:= (9 \times C(5) - C(4)) \times 9 \\95490 &:= (9 \times C(5) - C(4)) \times 90 \\954900 &:= (9 \times C(5) - C(4)) \times 900 \\9549000 &:= (9 \times C(5) - C(4)) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

1553.

$$\begin{aligned}9549 &:= (T(T(9)) + 5 + T(T(F(4)))) \times 9 \\95490 &:= (T(T(9)) + 5 + T(T(F(4)))) \times 90 \\954900 &:= (T(T(9)) + 5 + T(T(F(4)))) \times 900 \\9549000 &:= (T(T(9)) + 5 + T(T(F(4)))) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

1554.

$$\begin{aligned}9549 &:= (T(T(9)) + 5 + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) \times 9 \\95490 &:= (T(T(9)) + 5 + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) \times 90 \\954900 &:= (T(T(9)) + 5 + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) \times 900 \\9549000 &:= (T(T(9)) + 5 + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

1555.

$$\begin{aligned}9550 &:= (C((\sqrt{9})!) - Q(5)) \times 50 \\95500 &:= (C((\sqrt{9})!) - Q(5)) \times 500 \\955000 &:= (C((\sqrt{9})!) - Q(5)) \times 5000 \\9550000 &:= (C((\sqrt{9})!) - Q(5)) \times 50000\end{aligned}$$

1556.

$$\begin{aligned}9562 &:= (T(F(9)) + T(T(5 + F(6)))) \times 2 \\95620 &:= (T(F(9)) + T(T(5 + F(6)))) \times 20 \\956200 &:= (T(F(9)) + T(T(5 + F(6)))) \times 200 \\9562000 &:= (T(F(9)) + T(T(5 + F(6)))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1557.

$$\begin{aligned}9565 &:= (-F((\sqrt{9})!) + Q(Q(5)) + Q(Q(6))) \times 5 \\95650 &:= (-F((\sqrt{9})!) + Q(Q(5)) + Q(Q(6))) \times 50 \\956500 &:= (-F((\sqrt{9})!) + Q(Q(5)) + Q(Q(6))) \times 500 \\9565000 &:= (-F((\sqrt{9})!) + Q(Q(5)) + Q(Q(6))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1558.

$$\begin{aligned}9568 &:= (Q(F(9)) + 5 \times F(6)) \times 8 \\95680 &:= (Q(F(9)) + 5 \times F(6)) \times 80 \\956800 &:= (Q(F(9)) + 5 \times F(6)) \times 800 \\9568000 &:= (Q(F(9)) + 5 \times F(6)) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

1559.

$$\begin{aligned}9572 &:= (T(F(9)) + 5 + T(T(F(7)))) \times 2 \\95720 &:= (T(F(9)) + 5 + T(T(F(7)))) \times 20 \\957200 &:= (T(F(9)) + 5 + T(T(F(7)))) \times 200 \\9572000 &:= (T(F(9)) + 5 + T(T(F(7)))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1560.

$$\begin{aligned} 9576 &:= ((\sqrt{9})! + 5!) \times 76 \\ 95760 &:= ((\sqrt{9})! + 5!) \times 760 \\ 957600 &:= ((\sqrt{9})! + 5!) \times 7600 \\ 9576000 &:= ((\sqrt{9})! + 5!) \times 76000 \end{aligned}$$

1561.

$$\begin{aligned} 9582 &:= ((\sqrt{9})!! - Q(5) + Q(Q(8))) \times 2 \\ 95820 &:= ((\sqrt{9})!! - Q(5) + Q(Q(8))) \times 20 \\ 958200 &:= ((\sqrt{9})!! - Q(5) + Q(Q(8))) \times 200 \\ 9582000 &:= ((\sqrt{9})!! - Q(5) + Q(Q(8))) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1562.

$$\begin{aligned} 9582 &:= (T(95) + T(F(8))) \times 2 \\ 95820 &:= (T(95) + T(F(8))) \times 20 \\ 958200 &:= (T(95) + T(F(8))) \times 200 \\ 9582000 &:= (T(95) + T(F(8))) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1563.

$$\begin{aligned} 9582 &:= (T(95) + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times 2 \\ 95820 &:= (T(95) + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times 20 \\ 958200 &:= (T(95) + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times 200 \\ 9582000 &:= (T(95) + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1564.

$$\begin{aligned} 9603 &:= (T(Q(9)) - (6 - 0!)!) \times 3 \\ 96030 &:= (T(Q(9)) - (6 - 0!)!) \times 30 \\ 960300 &:= (T(Q(9)) - (6 - 0!)!) \times 300 \\ 9603000 &:= (T(Q(9)) - (6 - 0!)!) \times 3000 \end{aligned}$$

1565.

$$\begin{aligned} 9605 &:= (F((\sqrt{9})!)/F(F(6)) + 0!) \times 5 \\ 96050 &:= (F((\sqrt{9})!)/F(F(6)) + 0!) \times 50 \\ 960500 &:= (F((\sqrt{9})!)/F(F(6)) + 0!) \times 500 \\ 9605000 &:= (F((\sqrt{9})!)/F(F(6)) + 0!) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1566.

$$\begin{aligned} 9605 &:= (F(T(\sqrt{9}))!/T(6) + 0!) \times 5 \\ 96050 &:= (F(T(\sqrt{9}))!/T(6) + 0!) \times 50 \\ 960500 &:= (F(T(\sqrt{9}))!/T(6) + 0!) \times 500 \\ 9605000 &:= (F(T(\sqrt{9}))!/T(6) + 0!) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1567.

$$\begin{aligned} 9605 &:= (Q(Q((\sqrt{9})!)) + Q(Q(6 - 0!))) \times 5 \\ 96050 &:= (Q(Q((\sqrt{9})!)) + Q(Q(6 - 0!))) \times 50 \\ 960500 &:= (Q(Q((\sqrt{9})!)) + Q(Q(6 - 0!))) \times 500 \\ 9605000 &:= (Q(Q((\sqrt{9})!)) + Q(Q(6 - 0!))) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1568.

$$\begin{aligned} 9605 &:= (Q(Q(T(\sqrt{9}))) + Q(Q(6 - 0!))) \times 5 \\ 96050 &:= (Q(Q(T(\sqrt{9}))) + Q(Q(6 - 0!))) \times 50 \\ 960500 &:= (Q(Q(T(\sqrt{9}))) + Q(Q(6 - 0!))) \times 500 \\ 9605000 &:= (Q(Q(T(\sqrt{9}))) + Q(Q(6 - 0!))) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1569.

$$\begin{aligned} 9606 &:= (Q(F(9) + 6) + 0!) \times 6 \\ 96060 &:= (Q(F(9) + 6) + 0!) \times 60 \\ 960600 &:= (Q(F(9) + 6) + 0!) \times 600 \\ 9606000 &:= (Q(F(9) + 6) + 0!) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

1570.

$$\begin{aligned}9612 &:= (Q(9) + 6!) \times 12 \\96120 &:= (Q(9) + 6!) \times 120 \\961200 &:= (Q(9) + 6!) \times 1200 \\9612000 &:= (Q(9) + 6!) \times 12000\end{aligned}$$

1571.

$$\begin{aligned}9616 &:= (T(F(9)) + 6) \times 16 \\96160 &:= (T(F(9)) + 6) \times 160 \\961600 &:= (T(F(9)) + 6) \times 1600 \\9616000 &:= (T(F(9)) + 6) \times 16000\end{aligned}$$

1572.

$$\begin{aligned}9621 &:= (C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!)))) + 6!/2) \times 1 \\96210 &:= (C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!)))) + 6!/2) \times 10 \\962100 &:= (C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!)))) + 6!/2) \times 100 \\9621000 &:= (C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!)))) + 6!/2) \times 1000\end{aligned}$$

1573.

$$\begin{aligned}9632 &:= ((\sqrt{9}!! + C(Q(Q(6/3)))) \times 2 \\96320 &:= ((\sqrt{9}!! + C(Q(Q(6/3)))) \times 20 \\963200 &:= ((\sqrt{9}!! + C(Q(Q(6/3)))) \times 200 \\9632000 &:= ((\sqrt{9}!! + C(Q(Q(6/3)))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1574.

$$\begin{aligned}9636 &:= (9 + F(F(6) + Q(3))) \times 6 \\96360 &:= (9 + F(F(6) + Q(3))) \times 60 \\963600 &:= (9 + F(F(6) + Q(3))) \times 600 \\9636000 &:= (9 + F(F(6) + Q(3))) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1575.

$$\begin{aligned}9644 &:= (Q(T(9)) + Q(T(6)) - T(T(4))) \times 4 \\96440 &:= (Q(T(9)) + Q(T(6)) - T(T(4))) \times 40 \\964400 &:= (Q(T(9)) + Q(T(6)) - T(T(4))) \times 400 \\9644000 &:= (Q(T(9)) + Q(T(6)) - T(T(4))) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

1576.

$$\begin{aligned}9645 &:= (9 + F(6)!/F(F(F(4!)))) \times 5 \\96450 &:= (9 + F(6)!/F(F(F(4!)))) \times 50 \\964500 &:= (9 + F(6)!/F(F(F(4!)))) \times 500 \\9645000 &:= (9 + F(6)!/F(F(F(4!)))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1577.

$$\begin{aligned}9645 &:= (Q(9 \times 6) - F(Q(4))) \times 5 \\96450 &:= (Q(9 \times 6) - F(Q(4))) \times 50 \\964500 &:= (Q(9 \times 6) - F(Q(4))) \times 500 \\9645000 &:= (Q(9 \times 6) - F(Q(4))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1578.

$$\begin{aligned}9652 &:= (T(T(\sqrt{9})) \times T(T(6)) - Q(5)) \times 2 \\96520 &:= (T(T(\sqrt{9})) \times T(T(6)) - Q(5)) \times 20 \\965200 &:= (T(T(\sqrt{9})) \times T(T(6)) - Q(5)) \times 200 \\9652000 &:= (T(T(\sqrt{9})) \times T(T(6)) - Q(5)) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1579.

$$\begin{aligned}9655 &:= (Q(T(9)) + T(T(6)) - T(Q(5))) \times 5 \\96550 &:= (Q(T(9)) + T(T(6)) - T(Q(5))) \times 50 \\965500 &:= (Q(T(9)) + T(T(6)) - T(Q(5))) \times 500 \\9655000 &:= (Q(T(9)) + T(T(6)) - T(Q(5))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1580.

$$\begin{aligned}9665 &:= (-\sqrt{9} + Q(F(6) + Q(6))) \times 5 \\96650 &:= (-\sqrt{9} + Q(F(6) + Q(6))) \times 50 \\966500 &:= (-\sqrt{9} + Q(F(6) + Q(6))) \times 500 \\9665000 &:= (-\sqrt{9} + Q(F(6) + Q(6))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1581.

$$\begin{aligned}9667 &:= (F(9 + F(6)) - C(6)) \times 7 \\96670 &:= (F(9 + F(6)) - C(6)) \times 70 \\966700 &:= (F(9 + F(6)) - C(6)) \times 700 \\9667000 &:= (F(9 + F(6)) - C(6)) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

1582.

$$\begin{aligned}9672 &:= (C(\sqrt{9}) - T(T(6)) + 7!) \times 2 \\96720 &:= (C(\sqrt{9}) - T(T(6)) + 7!) \times 20 \\967200 &:= (C(\sqrt{9}) - T(T(6)) + 7!) \times 200 \\9672000 &:= (C(\sqrt{9}) - T(T(6)) + 7!) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1583.

$$\begin{aligned}9672 &:= (-F(9) \times 6 + 7!) \times 2 \\96720 &:= (-F(9) \times 6 + 7!) \times 20 \\967200 &:= (-F(9) \times 6 + 7!) \times 200 \\9672000 &:= (-F(9) \times 6 + 7!) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1584.

$$\begin{aligned}9680 &:= Q(\sqrt{9} + F(6)) \times 80 \\96800 &:= Q(\sqrt{9} + F(6)) \times 800 \\968000 &:= Q(\sqrt{9} + F(6)) \times 8000 \\9680000 &:= Q(\sqrt{9} + F(6)) \times 80000\end{aligned}$$

1585.

$$\begin{aligned}9684 &:= (T(T(9)) + 6! + T(T(8))) \times 4 \\96840 &:= (T(T(9)) + 6! + T(T(8))) \times 40 \\968400 &:= (T(T(9)) + 6! + T(T(8))) \times 400 \\9684000 &:= (T(T(9)) + 6! + T(T(8))) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

1586.

$$\begin{aligned}9684 &:= (T(T(9)) + T(T(6)) \times \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 4 \\96840 &:= (T(T(9)) + T(T(6)) \times \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 40 \\968400 &:= (T(T(9)) + T(T(6)) \times \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 400 \\9684000 &:= (T(T(9)) + T(T(6)) \times \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

1587.

$$\begin{aligned}9685 &:= (F(C(\sqrt{9})) - F(F(6)) \times C(F(8))) \times 5 \\96850 &:= (F(C(\sqrt{9})) - F(F(6)) \times C(F(8))) \times 50 \\968500 &:= (F(C(\sqrt{9})) - F(F(6)) \times C(F(8))) \times 500 \\9685000 &:= (F(C(\sqrt{9})) - F(F(6)) \times C(F(8))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1588.

$$\begin{aligned}9685 &:= (Q(Q(9)) - Q(68)) \times 5 \\96850 &:= (Q(Q(9)) - Q(68)) \times 50 \\968500 &:= (Q(Q(9)) - Q(68)) \times 500 \\9685000 &:= (Q(Q(9)) - Q(68)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1589.

$$\begin{aligned}9693 &:= (-9 + T(6!/9)) \times 3 \\96930 &:= (-9 + T(6!/9)) \times 30 \\969300 &:= (-9 + T(6!/9)) \times 300 \\9693000 &:= (-9 + T(6!/9)) \times 3000\end{aligned}$$

1590.

$$\begin{aligned}9696 &:= (T(T(9) + T(6)) - T(F(9))) \times 6 \\96960 &:= (T(T(9) + T(6)) - T(F(9))) \times 60 \\969600 &:= (T(T(9) + T(6)) - T(F(9))) \times 600 \\9696000 &:= (T(T(9) + T(6)) - T(F(9))) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1591.

$$\begin{aligned}9702 &:= T(97 + 0!) \times 2 \\97020 &:= T(97 + 0!) \times 20 \\970200 &:= T(97 + 0!) \times 200 \\9702000 &:= T(97 + 0!) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1592.

$$\begin{aligned}9725 &:= (T(F(9) + T(7)) - F(T(T(2)))) \times 5 \\97250 &:= (T(F(9) + T(7)) - F(T(T(2)))) \times 50 \\972500 &:= (T(F(9) + T(7)) - F(T(T(2)))) \times 500 \\9725000 &:= (T(F(9) + T(7)) - F(T(T(2)))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1593.

$$\begin{aligned}9725 &:= (T(\sqrt{9})! + T(7^2)) \times 5 \\97250 &:= (T(\sqrt{9})! + T(7^2)) \times 50 \\972500 &:= (T(\sqrt{9})! + T(7^2)) \times 500 \\9725000 &:= (T(\sqrt{9})! + T(7^2)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1594.

$$\begin{aligned}9735 &:= (-F(9) + C(F(7)) - C(3!)) \times 5 \\97350 &:= (-F(9) + C(F(7)) - C(3!)) \times 50 \\973500 &:= (-F(9) + C(F(7)) - C(3!)) \times 500 \\9735000 &:= (-F(9) + C(F(7)) - C(3!)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1595.

$$\begin{aligned}9735 &:= (T(F(9) + T(7)) - T(3)) \times 5 \\97350 &:= (T(F(9) + T(7)) - T(3)) \times 50 \\973500 &:= (T(F(9) + T(7)) - T(3)) \times 500 \\9735000 &:= (T(F(9) + T(7)) - T(3)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1596.

$$\begin{aligned}9737 &:= ((\sqrt{9})!! - Q(7) + 3!!) \times 7 \\97370 &:= ((\sqrt{9})!! - Q(7) + 3!!) \times 70 \\973700 &:= ((\sqrt{9})!! - Q(7) + 3!!) \times 700 \\9737000 &:= ((\sqrt{9})!! - Q(7) + 3!!) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

1597.

$$\begin{aligned}9737 &:= (Q(F(9)) + F(F(7)) + F(3)) \times 7 \\97370 &:= (Q(F(9)) + F(F(7)) + F(3)) \times 70 \\973700 &:= (Q(F(9)) + F(F(7)) + F(3)) \times 700 \\9737000 &:= (Q(F(9)) + F(F(7)) + F(3)) \times 7000\end{aligned}$$

1598.

$$\begin{aligned}9744 &:= T(\sqrt{9}) \times T(7 \times 4) \times 4 \\97440 &:= T(\sqrt{9}) \times T(7 \times 4) \times 40 \\974400 &:= T(\sqrt{9}) \times T(7 \times 4) \times 400 \\9744000 &:= T(\sqrt{9}) \times T(7 \times 4) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

1599.

$$\begin{aligned}9745 &:= (\sqrt{9} + T(T(7)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5 \\97450 &:= (\sqrt{9} + T(T(7)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 50 \\974500 &:= (\sqrt{9} + T(T(7)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 500 \\9745000 &:= (\sqrt{9} + T(T(7)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1600.

$$\begin{aligned}9745 &:= (T(F(9) + T(7)) - 4) \times 5 \\97450 &:= (T(F(9) + T(7)) - 4) \times 50 \\974500 &:= (T(F(9) + T(7)) - 4) \times 500 \\9745000 &:= (T(F(9) + T(7)) - 4) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1601.

$$\begin{aligned}9755 &:= (Q(T(9)) - Q(7) - Q(5)) \times 5 \\97550 &:= (Q(T(9)) - Q(7) - Q(5)) \times 50 \\975500 &:= (Q(T(9)) - Q(7) - Q(5)) \times 500 \\9755000 &:= (Q(T(9)) - Q(7) - Q(5)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1602.

$$\begin{aligned}9764 &:= (F(9) + Q(Q(7)) + 6) \times 4 \\97640 &:= (F(9) + Q(Q(7)) + 6) \times 40 \\976400 &:= (F(9) + Q(Q(7)) + 6) \times 400 \\9764000 &:= (F(9) + Q(Q(7)) + 6) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

1603.

$$\begin{aligned}9772 &:= (F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) \times F(F(7)) - 7) \times 2 \\97720 &:= (F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) \times F(F(7)) - 7) \times 20 \\977200 &:= (F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) \times F(F(7)) - 7) \times 200 \\9772000 &:= (F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) \times F(F(7)) - 7) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1604.

$$\begin{aligned}9775 &:= (-9 + C(F(7)) - F(F(7))) \times 5 \\97750 &:= (-9 + C(F(7)) - F(F(7))) \times 50 \\977500 &:= (-9 + C(F(7)) - F(F(7))) \times 500 \\9775000 &:= (-9 + C(F(7)) - F(F(7))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1605.

$$\begin{aligned}9785 &:= (-\sqrt{9} + Q(Q(7)) - Q(F(8))) \times 5 \\97850 &:= (-\sqrt{9} + Q(Q(7)) - Q(F(8))) \times 50 \\978500 &:= (-\sqrt{9} + Q(Q(7)) - Q(F(8))) \times 500 \\9785000 &:= (-\sqrt{9} + Q(Q(7)) - Q(F(8))) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1606.

$$\begin{aligned}9802 &:= (Q((\sqrt{9})! + Q(8)) + 0!) \times 2 \\98020 &:= (Q((\sqrt{9})! + Q(8)) + 0!) \times 20 \\980200 &:= (Q((\sqrt{9})! + Q(8)) + 0!) \times 200 \\9802000 &:= (Q((\sqrt{9})! + Q(8)) + 0!) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1607.

$$\begin{aligned}9805 &:= (Q(T(9)) - Q(8)) \times 5 \\98050 &:= (Q(T(9)) - Q(8)) \times 50 \\980500 &:= (Q(T(9)) - Q(8)) \times 500 \\9805000 &:= (Q(T(9)) - Q(8)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1608.

$$\begin{aligned}9808 &:= (Q(C(\sqrt{9}) + 8) + 0!) \times 8 \\98080 &:= (Q(C(\sqrt{9}) + 8) + 0!) \times 80 \\980800 &:= (Q(C(\sqrt{9}) + 8) + 0!) \times 800 \\9808000 &:= (Q(C(\sqrt{9}) + 8) + 0!) \times 8000\end{aligned}$$

1609.

$$\begin{aligned}9812 &:= (T(\sqrt{9})! + T(T(F(8 - 1)))) \times 2 \\98120 &:= (T(\sqrt{9})! + T(T(F(8 - 1)))) \times 20 \\981200 &:= (T(\sqrt{9})! + T(T(F(8 - 1)))) \times 200 \\9812000 &:= (T(\sqrt{9})! + T(T(F(8 - 1)))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1610.

$$\begin{aligned} 9815 &:= (Q(Q(T(\sqrt{9}))) + T(T(8)) + 1) \times 5 \\ 98150 &:= (Q(Q(T(\sqrt{9}))) + T(T(8)) + 1) \times 50 \\ 981500 &:= (Q(Q(T(\sqrt{9}))) + T(T(8)) + 1) \times 500 \\ 9815000 &:= (Q(Q(T(\sqrt{9}))) + T(T(8)) + 1) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1611.

$$\begin{aligned} 9822 &:= (C(9 + 8) - 2) \times 2 \\ 98220 &:= (C(9 + 8) - 2) \times 20 \\ 982200 &:= (C(9 + 8) - 2) \times 200 \\ 9822000 &:= (C(9 + 8) - 2) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1612.

$$\begin{aligned} 9832 &:= (C(9 + 8) + 3) \times 2 \\ 98320 &:= (C(9 + 8) + 3) \times 20 \\ 983200 &:= (C(9 + 8) + 3) \times 200 \\ 9832000 &:= (C(9 + 8) + 3) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1613.

$$\begin{aligned} 9842 &:= (C(9 + 8) + \sqrt{C(4)}) \times 2 \\ 98420 &:= (C(9 + 8) + \sqrt{C(4)}) \times 20 \\ 984200 &:= (C(9 + 8) + \sqrt{C(4)}) \times 200 \\ 9842000 &:= (C(9 + 8) + \sqrt{C(4)}) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1614.

$$\begin{aligned} 9843 &:= (Q(-9 + Q(8)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 3 \\ 98430 &:= (Q(-9 + Q(8)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 30 \\ 984300 &:= (Q(-9 + Q(8)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 300 \\ 9843000 &:= (Q(-9 + Q(8)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 3000 \end{aligned}$$

1615.

$$\begin{aligned} 9843 &:= (Q(F(9) + F(8)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 3 \\ 98430 &:= (Q(F(9) + F(8)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 30 \\ 984300 &:= (Q(F(9) + F(8)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 300 \\ 9843000 &:= (Q(F(9) + F(8)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 3000 \end{aligned}$$

1616.

$$\begin{aligned} 9843 &:= (T(Q(9)) - Q(8) + 4!) \times 3 \\ 98430 &:= (T(Q(9)) - Q(8) + 4!) \times 30 \\ 984300 &:= (T(Q(9)) - Q(8) + 4!) \times 300 \\ 9843000 &:= (T(Q(9)) - Q(8) + 4!) \times 3000 \end{aligned}$$

1617.

$$\begin{aligned} 9844 &:= (Q(Q(9)) - Q(Q(8)) - 4) \times 4 \\ 98440 &:= (Q(Q(9)) - Q(Q(8)) - 4) \times 40 \\ 984400 &:= (Q(Q(9)) - Q(Q(8)) - 4) \times 400 \\ 9844000 &:= (Q(Q(9)) - Q(Q(8)) - 4) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

1618.

$$\begin{aligned} 9844 &:= (T(F(9) + T(8)) - 4!) \times 4 \\ 98440 &:= (T(F(9) + T(8)) - 4!) \times 40 \\ 984400 &:= (T(F(9) + T(8)) - 4!) \times 400 \\ 9844000 &:= (T(F(9) + T(8)) - 4!) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

1619.

$$\begin{aligned} 9846 &:= (T(9) \times T(8) + T(T(F(4)))) \times 6 \\ 98460 &:= (T(9) \times T(8) + T(T(F(4)))) \times 60 \\ 984600 &:= (T(9) \times T(8) + T(T(F(4)))) \times 600 \\ 9846000 &:= (T(9) \times T(8) + T(T(F(4)))) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

1620.

$$\begin{aligned} 9846 &:= (T(9) \times T(8) + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) \times 6 \\ 98460 &:= (T(9) \times T(8) + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) \times 60 \\ 984600 &:= (T(9) \times T(8) + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) \times 600 \\ 9846000 &:= (T(9) \times T(8) + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

1621.

$$\begin{aligned} 9848 &:= (C(9) + C(8) - T(4)) \times 8 \\ 98480 &:= (C(9) + C(8) - T(4)) \times 80 \\ 984800 &:= (C(9) + C(8) - T(4)) \times 800 \\ 9848000 &:= (C(9) + C(8) - T(4)) \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

1622.

$$\begin{aligned} 9848 &:= (-Q(9) + Q(T(8)) + Q(4)) \times 8 \\ 98480 &:= (-Q(9) + Q(T(8)) + Q(4)) \times 80 \\ 984800 &:= (-Q(9) + Q(T(8)) + Q(4)) \times 800 \\ 9848000 &:= (-Q(9) + Q(T(8)) + Q(4)) \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

1623.

$$\begin{aligned} 9848 &:= (T(8 \times T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(4))) \times 8 \\ 98480 &:= (T(8 \times T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(4))) \times 80 \\ 984800 &:= (T(8 \times T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(4))) \times 800 \\ 9848000 &:= (T(8 \times T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(4))) \times 8000 \end{aligned}$$

1624.

$$\begin{aligned} 9850 &:= (-F(9) + T(F(8))) \times 50 \\ 98500 &:= (-F(9) + T(F(8))) \times 500 \\ 985000 &:= (-F(9) + T(F(8))) \times 5000 \\ 9850000 &:= (-F(9) + T(F(8))) \times 50000 \end{aligned}$$

1625.

$$\begin{aligned} 9876 &:= (F(9 + 8) + Q(7)) \times 6 \\ 98760 &:= (F(9 + 8) + Q(7)) \times 60 \\ 987600 &:= (F(9 + 8) + Q(7)) \times 600 \\ 9876000 &:= (F(9 + 8) + Q(7)) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

1626.

$$\begin{aligned} 9876 &:= (T(T(T(\sqrt{9})) + T(8)) - 7) \times 6 \\ 98760 &:= (T(T(T(\sqrt{9})) + T(8)) - 7) \times 60 \\ 987600 &:= (T(T(T(\sqrt{9})) + T(8)) - 7) \times 600 \\ 9876000 &:= (T(T(T(\sqrt{9})) + T(8)) - 7) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

1627.

$$\begin{aligned} 9884 &:= (Q(Q(9)) - Q(Q(8)) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 4 \\ 98840 &:= (Q(Q(9)) - Q(Q(8)) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 40 \\ 988400 &:= (Q(Q(9)) - Q(Q(8)) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 400 \\ 9884000 &:= (Q(Q(9)) - Q(Q(8)) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 4000 \end{aligned}$$

1628.

$$\begin{aligned} 9885 &:= (Q(T(9)) - \sqrt{Q(8) \times T(8)}) \times 5 \\ 98850 &:= (Q(T(9)) - \sqrt{Q(8) \times T(8)}) \times 50 \\ 988500 &:= (Q(T(9)) - \sqrt{Q(8) \times T(8)}) \times 500 \\ 9885000 &:= (Q(T(9)) - \sqrt{Q(8) \times T(8)}) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1629.

$$\begin{aligned} 9885 &:= (\sqrt{9} \times T(T(8)) - T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 5 \\ 98850 &:= (\sqrt{9} \times T(T(8)) - T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 50 \\ 988500 &:= (\sqrt{9} \times T(T(8)) - T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 500 \\ 9885000 &:= (\sqrt{9} \times T(T(8)) - T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1630.

$$\begin{aligned} 9891 &:= (T(T(9)) + Q(8)) \times 9 \\ 98910 &:= (T(T(9)) + Q(8)) \times 90 \\ 989100 &:= (T(T(9)) + Q(8)) \times 900 \\ 9891000 &:= (T(T(9)) + Q(8)) \times 9000 \end{aligned}$$

1631.

$$\begin{aligned} 9902 &:= (T(99) + 0!) \times 2 \\ 99020 &:= (T(99) + 0!) \times 20 \\ 990200 &:= (T(99) + 0!) \times 200 \\ 9902000 &:= (T(99) + 0!) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1632.

$$\begin{aligned} 9905 &:= (-C((\sqrt{9})!) + C(F((\sqrt{9})! + 0!))) \times 5 \\ 99050 &:= (-C((\sqrt{9})!) + C(F((\sqrt{9})! + 0!))) \times 50 \\ 990500 &:= (-C((\sqrt{9})!) + C(F((\sqrt{9})! + 0!))) \times 500 \\ 9905000 &:= (-C((\sqrt{9})!) + C(F((\sqrt{9})! + 0!))) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1633.

$$\begin{aligned} 9905 &:= (T(9) + Q(T(9) - 0!)) \times 5 \\ 99050 &:= (T(9) + Q(T(9) - 0!)) \times 50 \\ 990500 &:= (T(9) + Q(T(9) - 0!)) \times 500 \\ 9905000 &:= (T(9) + Q(T(9) - 0!)) \times 5000 \end{aligned}$$

1634.

$$\begin{aligned} 9909 &:= (Q(F(9)) - F(9 + 0!)) \times 9 \\ 99090 &:= (Q(F(9)) - F(9 + 0!)) \times 90 \\ 990900 &:= (Q(F(9)) - F(9 + 0!)) \times 900 \\ 9909000 &:= (Q(F(9)) - F(9 + 0!)) \times 9000 \end{aligned}$$

1635.

$$\begin{aligned} 9912 &:= (F(Q(Q(F(\sqrt{9})))) + Q(Q(F((\sqrt{9})!)) - 1)) \times 2 \\ 99120 &:= (F(Q(Q(F(\sqrt{9})))) + Q(Q(F((\sqrt{9})!)) - 1)) \times 20 \\ 991200 &:= (F(Q(Q(F(\sqrt{9})))) + Q(Q(F((\sqrt{9})!)) - 1)) \times 200 \\ 9912000 &:= (F(Q(Q(F(\sqrt{9})))) + Q(Q(F((\sqrt{9})!)) - 1)) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1636.

$$\begin{aligned} 9932 &:= (T(F(9)) + T(93)) \times 2 \\ 99320 &:= (T(F(9)) + T(93)) \times 20 \\ 993200 &:= (T(F(9)) + T(93)) \times 200 \\ 9932000 &:= (T(F(9)) + T(93)) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1637.

$$\begin{aligned} 9936 &:= ((\sqrt{9})!! + (\sqrt{9})!! + C(3!)) \times 6 \\ 99360 &:= ((\sqrt{9})!! + (\sqrt{9})!! + C(3!)) \times 60 \\ 993600 &:= ((\sqrt{9})!! + (\sqrt{9})!! + C(3!)) \times 600 \\ 9936000 &:= ((\sqrt{9})!! + (\sqrt{9})!! + C(3!)) \times 6000 \end{aligned}$$

1638.

$$\begin{aligned} 9936 &:= T(T(T(9))/T(9)) \times 36 \\ 99360 &:= T(T(T(9))/T(9)) \times 360 \\ 993600 &:= T(T(T(9))/T(9)) \times 3600 \\ 9936000 &:= T(T(T(9))/T(9)) \times 36000 \end{aligned}$$

1639.

$$\begin{aligned} 9942 &:= (T(99) + T(T(F(4)))) \times 2 \\ 99420 &:= (T(99) + T(T(F(4)))) \times 20 \\ 994200 &:= (T(99) + T(T(F(4)))) \times 200 \\ 9942000 &:= (T(99) + T(T(F(4)))) \times 2000 \end{aligned}$$

1640.

$$\begin{aligned}9944 &:= (-T(F(9)) + T(T(4 \times \sqrt{9}))) \times 4 \\99440 &:= (-T(F(9)) + T(T(4 \times \sqrt{9}))) \times 40 \\994400 &:= (-T(F(9)) + T(T(4 \times \sqrt{9}))) \times 400 \\9944000 &:= (-T(F(9)) + T(T(4 \times \sqrt{9}))) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

1641.

$$\begin{aligned}9944 &:= (-T(F(9)) + T(T(9 + F(4)))) \times 4 \\99440 &:= (-T(F(9)) + T(T(9 + F(4)))) \times 40 \\994400 &:= (-T(F(9)) + T(T(9 + F(4)))) \times 400 \\9944000 &:= (-T(F(9)) + T(T(9 + F(4)))) \times 4000\end{aligned}$$

1642.

$$\begin{aligned}9962 &:= (Q(9) + Q(F(9) + Q(6))) \times 2 \\99620 &:= (Q(9) + Q(F(9) + Q(6))) \times 20 \\996200 &:= (Q(9) + Q(F(9) + Q(6))) \times 200 \\9962000 &:= (Q(9) + Q(F(9) + Q(6))) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1643.

$$\begin{aligned}9966 &:= (Q(Q(9)) - Q(F(9) + Q(6))) \times 6 \\99660 &:= (Q(Q(9)) - Q(F(9) + Q(6))) \times 60 \\996600 &:= (Q(Q(9)) - Q(F(9) + Q(6))) \times 600 \\9966000 &:= (Q(Q(9)) - Q(F(9) + Q(6))) \times 6000\end{aligned}$$

1644.

$$\begin{aligned}9972 &:= (-9 \times (\sqrt{9})! + 7!) \times 2 \\99720 &:= (-9 \times (\sqrt{9})! + 7!) \times 20 \\997200 &:= (-9 \times (\sqrt{9})! + 7!) \times 200 \\9972000 &:= (-9 \times (\sqrt{9})! + 7!) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1645.

$$\begin{aligned}9972 &:= (-9 - T(9) + 7!) \times 2 \\99720 &:= (-9 - T(9) + 7!) \times 20 \\997200 &:= (-9 - T(9) + 7!) \times 200 \\9972000 &:= (-9 - T(9) + 7!) \times 2000\end{aligned}$$

1646.

$$\begin{aligned}9985 &:= (T(9 + T(9)) + C(8)) \times 5 \\99850 &:= (T(9 + T(9)) + C(8)) \times 50 \\998500 &:= (T(9 + T(9)) + C(8)) \times 500 \\9985000 &:= (T(9 + T(9)) + C(8)) \times 5000\end{aligned}$$

1647.

$$\begin{aligned}9999 &:= (F(9) \times F(9) - T(9)) \times 9 \\99990 &:= (F(9) \times F(9) - T(9)) \times 90 \\999900 &:= (F(9) \times F(9) - T(9)) \times 900 \\9999000 &:= (F(9) \times F(9) - T(9)) \times 9000\end{aligned}$$

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